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Economic Sciences

PERSONNEL POLICY AND QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF KAZAKHSTAN

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The relevance of research. In order to improve the efficiency of universities, the issue of personnel development is one of the most significant in their activities. Accordingly, the importance of forming a personnel development system is growing. In the context of the development of competitiveness in the education system, universities have to pay attention to the professional skills of employees. The professionalism of employees is reflected in the current tasks they perform and the results that affect the effectiveness of the university.

In the context of the development of innovative technologies, the market requires the availability of qualified specialists. Employees need to improve in their field of activity. To do this, universities should form an optimal system of personnel development. The development of personnel in the long-term plan is reflected in its strategic objectives. HR management influences the solution of long-term and large-scale tasks and corporate culture. Universities, determining the need for new personnel and assessing the potential of existing ones, invest in their development. Investments in personnel development form high productivity and increase the value of human capital. As a result, universities have highly professional specialists and increase their competitiveness. The quality and productivity of labor is growing. The formation of a personnel development system contributes to the preservation of the necessary personnel and the growth of profitability of the enterprise. Highly qualified staff is the best asset of any university. In modern conditions, many organizations pay attention to the motivation of employees, which encourages them to be loyal and innovate in their work.

The starting point in the personnel planning process is the tasks facing the enterprise, as well as the quantitative and qualitative composition of the staff. The discrepancy between these two values indicates that there is a need for personnel, which is covered in quantitative terms by attracting personnel, and in qualitative terms by developing personnel. [1]

The HR policy of an organization is a set of internal documents that define work with personnel.

Universities are characterized by openness in the recruitment and selection of personnel, transparency of all procedures for potential employees at any level of personnel selection, objectivity of competitions in the selection of applicants for scientific and pedagogical positions, as well as compliance with corporate requirements that have developed in this organization to its personnel.

Mistakes made during the selection of personnel and during the procedures of its certification are sometimes too expensive for the university.

KP is reflected in the charter of the organization, the mission of the organization, the

collective agreement, the rules of internal labor regulations, the employee contract, the regulations on remuneration, the regulations on personnel certification.

The purpose of the personnel policy is the formation of a team (human potential) of the university that effectively ensures the achievement of the strategic goals of the university and is attractive to a person focused on professional development and self-realization in the interests of the organization.

The object of personnel policy is the staff of the university, including administrative and managerial personnel, scientific and pedagogical workers, educational and auxiliary and administrative and economic personnel, as well as the personnel reserve.

Figure 1 - Basic principles of personnel policy

A source: [2]

The main tasks of the personnel policy include:

- stimulating the innovative activity of the teaching staff;
- preserving the continuity of generations, maintaining the professional activity of the older generation of teachers;
- support of collective decision-making culture of scientific and educational problems;
- ensuring the openness of the rights and obligations of subjects of the higher education system, methods of planning and monitoring their activities, which are embedded in the management cycle of the institute of higher education at various levels;
- preservation of the rights of autonomy of higher educational institutions in solving personnel issues.

Figure 2. The main directions of personnel policy
A source: [2]

According to the report on the implementation of the national project "Quality Education "Educated Nation" in 2022, one of the main tasks is to increase the competitiveness of Kazakhstani universities. In Kazakhstan, out of 104 civil universities, 35% (36) universities implement joint educational programs and double-degree programs. During the reporting period, 202 foreign experts were involved in 29 universities of the country. [2].

Table 1. Strategy for improving the quality of universities in Kazakhstan

	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Number of universities in Kazakhstan in the QS-WUR ranking, TOP 200, units.	1	2	2	2	3
A source: [3]					

According to the annual report on the implementation of the national project "Quality Education "Educated Nation", one of the strategic objectives of quality education is to increase the competitiveness of Kazakhstani universities. The project provides for the entry of domestic universities into the top 200 in the QS-WUR rating.

Out of 104 civil universities, 36 universities implement joint educational programs (hereinafter referred to as SOP) and double-degree programs (hereinafter referred to as DDP). There are contracts for 65 SOP between the OVPO of the Republic of Kazakhstan and partner universities. Of these, the SOP in English is 30 (46%).

The training is carried out both with the departure of Kazakhstani students and with the use of distance technologies.

The SOP training is carried out in 7 languages: Kazakh, Russian, English, French, Chinese, German, Turkish.

The largest number of implemented SOPs are universities such as Almaty Management University – 12 units, KazNPU im. Abaya – 8 units, M.Kozybayev SKU – 7 units, ASUE - 4 units.

The largest contingent of students have such universities as Almaty Management University – 497 people, KazNPU im. Abaya – 155 people, AUES – 111 people, KazNMU named after S.D. Asfendiyarov – 72 people. E.A. Buketov KarU – 60 people.

The largest number of implemented DDPS are universities such as KazNU named after al-Farabi – 47 units, ENU named after L.N.Gumilev – 42 units, KazNPU named after. Abaya – 8 units, ATU – 7 units.

At the same time, such universities as Al-Farabi KazNU – 278 people, Gumilev ENU – 257 people, KBTU – 170 students, KazNPU named after al-Farabi have the largest contingent of students in the framework of the DDP. Abaya – 122 people.[3]

Measures have been taken to expand the range of short-term courses in partnership with companies in the real sector. Structural divisions have been created in universities, contracts have been concluded with enterprises of the regions, courses have been developed aimed at implementing the requests and needs of enterprises of the regions, online platforms operate.

Measures have been taken to develop "Silver Universities". Silver universities exist in 72 OVPO RK. In the first half of 2022-2023, 28 OVPO out of 72 (39%) implemented 234 courses within the framework of silver education.

List of OVPO implementing silver education courses:

L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University; Al-Farabi Kazakh National University; Kazakh National Women's Pedagogical University; K. I. Satpayev Kazakh National Research Technical University; Kurmangazy Kazakh National Conservatory; Atyrau University named after X.Dosmukhamedov ; D.Serikbayev EKTU; East Kazakhstan University named after

S.Amanzholov; Zhangir Khan State Technical University; Saginov Karaganda Technical University; Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University; Semey Medical University; Pavlodar Pedagogical University; Rudna Industrial Institute; Toraigyrov University; M.H. Dulati Taraz Regional University; Shakarim Semey University; M.Auezov South Kazakhstan State University; Almaty University of Energy and Communications Gumarbek Daukeev; O.A.Baikonurov Zhezkazgan University; International Educational Corporation; International University of Information Technologies; Alikhan Bokeikhan University; Innovative Eurasian University; Karaganda University of Kazpotrebsoyuz; Kazakhstan Medical University "HSE"; Caspian Public University; International University of Tourism and Hospitality

The total number of students was 2,087.[3]

The number of foreign experts involved in teaching.

According to the order of the Acting Minister of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated July 19, 2021 No. 349 "On approval of the Distribution Plan for the number of foreign scientists to attract higher and postgraduate education organizations to teaching activities", it was planned to attract 200 foreign experts to 29 universities of the country within the republican budget.

Due to the increase in prices for air tickets and accommodation in Kazakhstan, the payment of labor allocated for foreign specialists, the arrival of 18 foreign experts funded under the RB did not take place.

Thus, 182 foreign scientists were attracted at the expense of the Republic of Belarus. 30,600 thousand tenge of undeveloped funds were returned to the budget.

At the same time, 20 scientists were attracted by universities at their own expense, the contract period of which ranged from 3 to 6 months.

Thus, the number of foreign scientists involved in teaching is 202 people or 100%.

To participate in the program of attracting 200 foreign specialists to teaching in 2022, 29 OVPO were selected (national – 5, NAO – 23, international - 1). The amount of financing is 340,000 thousand tenge (Order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 155 dated April 19, 2022). In 2022, 202 foreign specialists were involved. The duration of stay of foreign

specialists at the expense of the republican budget in the OVPO RK is 4 weeks, at the expense of the university – from 3 to 6 months. Foreign specialists conducted lectures (5962 hours), seminars (3674 hours), master classes (1408 hours) and trainings (295 hours) for students. 168 people conducted training sessions and seminars for university employees. Students and teaching staff of universities rated the level of teaching quality of foreign specialists by 91% out of 100% (according to the results of the survey).

The number of branches of leading foreign universities.

According to this indicator, no value is planned for 2022. However, the Ministry has carried out work on opening 3 foreign branches. The resolutions of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On some issues of the non-profit joint-stock company "North Kazakhstan University named after Manash Kozybayev" dated April 15, 2022 No. 225 were adopted; "On the establishment of a branch of the Federal State Autonomous Educational Institution of Higher Education "National Research Nuclear University "MEPhI" and a branch of the Federal State Autonomous Educational Institution of Higher Education "Gubkin Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University)" dated August 5, 2022 No. 539.

Within the framework of cooperation on the implementation of double-degree programs, Kazakh universities have established partnerships with 97 universities from 23 countries of the world. Compared to 2021, the geography has expanded almost 2 times. (2021 – universities from 13 countries). Measures have been taken to increase the number of educational grants in the direction of this program. A roadmap has been developed for the preparation of a joint OP at all levels.

Ensuring management is carried out through the understanding that the human resources of the University are its strategic resource.

One of the main tasks is the development and implementation of human resource management models (selection, recruitment, adaptation, evaluation, motivation, creation of a personnel Reserve). The University prioritizes the quality of teaching staff and administrative staff. This is ensured by the presence of a personnel policy and an open system for measuring the results of activities through the development of a system of incentives and increasing the efficiency of university personnel. The university must provide: the presence of experienced and qualified teaching staff to ensure the quality of training, evaluation and educational programs; continuous staff improvement to ensure the continuous personal development of academic and administrative staff.

Table 2. Personnel quality management of the University

No	Al-Farabi Kazakh National University	Narxoz University	ALMA University
1	2	3	4
1	The system of quality assurance in education at kaznu. Al-Farabi is based on the European standards and directives of the European Higher Education Quality Assurance Association (ENQA).	"Quality assurance guidelines" with changes and additions from 05.12.2022	Policy in the field of quality management system" Almaty Management University " dated 25.04.2022
2	The university has a policy of guaranteeing the quality of education and documented procedures for a quality management system that determines the required level of quality of educational services provided and ensures its achievement.	The main documents governing the personnel management of the University are personnel policy and qualification requirements.	The university forms a new generation of leaders with entrepreneurial thinking and contributes to the development of the knowledge economy of dynamically developing societies.
3	To ensure the quality of the educational process, quality committees are created at each faculty, monitoring the quality of development and implementation of educational programs	One of the main tasks of personnel policy is to employ professional scientists from abroad through various internet platforms (LinkedIn, Acadeus, etc.).	According to the legislative and regulatory requirements regarding the quality of services provided, accreditation bodies, students and work
	their competence includes conducting education and making recommendations to the graduating departments and the Academic Council of the faculty.	access to posts through publications	implementation of activities in accordance with the requirements of suppliers.
4	The university administration, teaching staff, employees and students are obliged to comply with the requirements of academic policy and the standards, rules, procedures and regulations established in all types of activities related to the selection and recruitment of teaching staff and staff	Rejuvenation of personnel through cooperation with JSC" Center for International Programs "under the international program" Bolashak "and state bodies under the programs" youth practice". Creation of the University's personnel Reserve and adaptation of new employees.	Continuous improvement of the quality of services provided and the performance of the university management system
Source-compiled by the authors [4, 5, 6]			

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University provides for the formation of a personnel resource of teaching staff capable of ensuring the quality of training: the level of scientific qualifications; the

formation of conceptual views on the essence of modern professional education; the ability to apply modern teaching methods within the framework of their specialty; the ability to generate and transfer new teaching technologies to a separate field of professional activity.

So, the quality management of the University's personnel:

- based on the European standards and directives of the European Association for quality assurance in higher education (ENQA) at Al-Farabi Kazakh National University;
- Personnel Quality Management at Narxoz University is based on quality assurance guidelines;
- At ALMA University, he applies to the University's policy in the field of quality management system.

The quality assessment systems of all universities take into account the assessment of the teacher by students, the assessment of attendance by colleagues, as well as scientific publications and directly affect their wages.

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Жобалардағы қаржылық емес тәуекелдерді анықтау әдістері мен құралдары: заманауи тәжірибелер мен инновациялық тәсілдер

Методы и инструменты идентификации нефинансовых рисков в проектах: современные практики и инновационные подходы

Methods and tools for identifying non-financial risks in projects: modern practices and innovative approaches

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Аннотация. Зерттеу барысында қаржылық емес тәуекелдерді анықтау әдістеріне арналған классикалық және заманауи жұмыстар қарастырылды. Қаржылық емес тәуекелдерді сәйкестендіру саласындағы құралдар мен әдістер де зерттелді. Saudi Aramco компаниясының мысалында сценарий әдісімен экологиялық және геосаяси тәуекелдерді бағалау көрсетілген. Қаржылық емес тәуекелдерді анықтау әдістері сипатталған, олар әлі кеңінен танымал емес немесе шектеулі сарапшылар шеңберінде қолданылады.

Аннотация. В рамках исследования рассмотрены классические и современные работы, посвященные методам идентификации нефинансовых рисков. Также изучены инструменты и методики в области идентификации нефинансовых рисков. На примере компании Saudi Aramco показана оценка экологических и геополитических рисков сценарным методом. Охарактеризованы методы идентификации нефинансовых рисков, которые еще не стали широко известными или используются в ограниченных кругах экспертов.

Annotation. Within the framework of the study, classical and modern works devoted to methods of identifying non-financial risks are considered. Tools and techniques in the field of identification of non-financial risks have also been studied. Using the example of Saudi Aramco, the assessment of environmental and geopolitical risks by the scenario method is shown. The methods of identifying non-financial risks that have not yet become widely known or are used in limited circles of experts are characterized.

Түйінді сөздер: тәуекел, жоба, қаржылық емес тәуекел, экологиялық тәуекел, геосаяси тәуекел.

Ключевые слова: риск, проект, нефинансовый риск, экологический риск, геополитический риск.

Keywords: risk, project, non-financial risk, environmental risk, geopolitical risk.

Введение. Одним из ключевых элементов успешной реализации проектов является умение адекватно идентифицировать, анализировать и управлять рисками. При этом риски, которые рассматриваются, далеко не всегда связаны только с финансами. Нефинансовые риски, такие как репутационные, социальные, экологические и многие другие, становятся всё более актуальными для компаний различных отраслей.

В последние годы внимание к нефинансовым рискам в проектах значительно возросло. Это обусловлено рядом факторов: усилением общественного контроля, стремлением к устойчивому развитию, возрастающими требованиями к корпоративной социальной ответственности, а также постоянным развитием и изменением рыночной среды. Нередко именно нефинансовые риски могут стать причиной существенных потерь или даже краха проектов. Тем не менее, пока ещё далеко не все организации обладают необходимыми инструментами и методиками для их идентификации и управления. В этом контексте изучение современных практик и инновационных подходов к идентификации нефинансовых рисков в проектах становится крайне актуальным и востребованным. Такое исследование может служить основой для формирования новых методик, инструментов и практик, которые помогут организациям быть более готовыми к вызовам современного мира.

Цель исследования - исследовать и анализировать современные методы и инструменты для идентификации нефинансовых рисков в проектах, а также выявить инновационные подходы, используемые в практике.

Задачи исследования:

- изучить классические и современные работы, посвященные методам идентификации нефинансовых рисков;
- оценить современные инструменты и методики в области идентификации нефинансовых рисков:
- выявить новые и эффективные методы идентификации нефинансовых рисков, которые еще не стали широко известными или используются в ограниченных кругах экспертов.

Литературный обзор. Мадера А.Г. отмечает, что «риск — это потенциальная возможность возникновения нежелательных или непредвиденных событий, которые могут повлиять на достижение поставленных целей» [1, с.27]. Эти события могут быть как отрицательными, так и положительными. На практике, как указывает Никсон Д., термин «риск» чаще всего ассоциируется с возможностью потерь или ущерба [2, с.63]. Риски могут быть финансовыми, операционными, юридическими, репутационными и многими другими, в зависимости от контекста, в котором они рассматриваются.

Важным аспектом понимания риска является его вероятностная природа. По утверждению Пфлегинга Н., - риск не гарантирует наступления определенного события, но указывает на возможность его происхождения [3, с.54]. Эта вероятность может быть измерена или оценена на основе статистических данных, анализа прошлых событий или экспертных оценок.

Нефинансовый риск проекта относится к потенциальным угрозам или проблемам, которые могут возникнуть в ходе реализации проекта и которые не связаны напрямую с финансовыми показателями или потерями. В то время как финансовые риски часто измеряются и анализируются в денежных единицах, по замечанию Цоя Л.Н., нефинансовые риски могут иметь более широкий спектр последствий и могут оказывать влияние на различные аспекты проекта [4, с.27]. Например, нефинансовые риски могут включать в себя риски, связанные с человеческими ресурсами (потеря ключевых сотрудников),

технологические риски (устаревание технологий или неудачное внедрение новых), юридические риски (изменения в законодательстве или возможные судебные иски), экологические риски или риски, связанные с репутацией (негативное восприятие проекта общественностью или потеря доверия клиентов).

Основная сложность управления нефинансовыми рисками заключается в том, что они могут быть менее очевидными и труднее для количественной оценки по сравнению с финансовыми рисками. Тем не менее, как указывает Гроув Э.В., игнорирование или недооценка нефинансовых рисков может привести к серьезным проблемам в реализации проекта и даже к его неудаче [5, с.103].

Для успешного управления нефинансовыми рисками проекта необходим систематический подход, который начинается с идентификации этих рисков, затем их оценки, выбора стратегий управления рисками и, наконец, мониторинга и контроля за их реализацией. Это поможет обеспечить, что проект будет подготовлен к возможным препятствиям и способен справиться с непредвиденными обстоятельствами [6, с.34].

Идентификация риска — это процесс выявления и описания потенциальных рисков, которые могут повлиять на достижение целей проекта, предприятия или любой другой деятельности. Это ключевой этап в управлении рисками, согласно исследованию Каплан Р., так как без определения и понимания рисков невозможно их адекватно управлять [7, с.24]. Процесс идентификации риска начинается с понимания целей и задач, а также контекста, в котором они реализуются. Как указывает Гриффин Э., это может включать в себя анализ внутренних и внешних факторов, которые могут воздействовать на проект или организацию [8, с.39].

Важным аспектом идентификации риска является участие всех заинтересованных сторон. Это может включать в себя специалистов различных профилей, руководителей, клиентов и других участников проекта или деятельности [9, с.97]. Их опыт и знания помогут выявить потенциальные риски из различных точек зрения. После идентификации рисков их детально анализируют, классифицируют и оценивают, чтобы определить, какие из них требуют принятия мер по управлению или снижению.

Воронцовский А.В. рассматривает один из широко используемых методов — анализ заинтересованных сторон [10, с.64]. Этот метод предполагает выявление и анализ потенциальных интересов и проблем различных групп либо индивидов, которые могут оказать влияние на проект. Вяткин В.Н. отмечает, что понимание ожиданий и опасений заинтересованных сторон может помочь предвидеть риски, связанные, например, с репутацией проекта или сопротивлением изменениям [11, с.59].

Метод экспертных оценок также широко применяется для идентификации нефинансовых рисков. Эксперты в определенной области или со знанием конкретной темы проекта могут предоставить ценные инсайты о потенциальных угрозах, которые могут быть упущены в ходе стандартного анализа.

Анализ сценариев предполагает создание различных вариантов развития событий, которые могут произойти в ходе реализации проекта. Каждый сценарий основывается на определенном наборе предположений, что позволяет команде проекта оценить возможные последствия и реакцию на различные угрозы [12, с.34].

Важно отметить, что успешная идентификация нефинансовых рисков требует комбинированного подхода, включающего в себя использование различных методов и инструментов, чтобы обеспечить полноту и точность анализа.

Методы. Метод сравнения в контексте исследования на тему методов и инструментов идентификации нефинансовых рисков позволяет выявить различия и сходства между разными подходами. Используя этот метод, можно определить, какие методы или

инструменты являются более эффективными в определенных условиях или как они развивались со временем. Например, сравнивая классический метод анализа рисков с новым инновационным подходом, можно определить их относительные преимущества и недостатки, а также контексты, в которых один метод может быть предпочтительнее другого.

Метод сопоставления фокусируется на соотношении различных характеристик, элементов или аспектов изучаемых методов и инструментов. Это может включать в себя сопоставление функциональных возможностей инструментов, степени их сложности или соответствия определенным критериям. В контексте исследования на указанную тему сопоставление может помочь определить, какие инструменты или методы лучше всего подходят для решения конкретных задач идентификации рисков в различных проектах.

Метод систематизации направлен на упорядочивание и структурирование информации о различных методах и инструментах. Это может включать в себя группировку методов по определенным категориям, таким как их применимость, степень новизны или основные принципы работы. Систематизация помогает создать ясную и логичную структуру, которая упрощает понимание и анализ широкого спектра методов и инструментов. В рамках данного исследования метод систематизации может быть использован для создания категорий или классификаций методов идентификации нефинансовых рисков, что облегчит их последующий анализ и сравнение.

Используя эти методы в комплексе, можно получить глубокое понимание существующих и новых методов и инструментов идентификации нефинансовых рисков, их сильных и слабых сторон, а также контекстов, в которых они могут быть наиболее эффективными.

Результаты, выводы и обсуждение. Доктор Питер Бернштейн является одним из ведущих исследователей в области риска. Его книга «Против богов: неудачная история риска» является фундаментальным исследованием истории риска. В этой работе Бернштейн рассматривает исторические аспекты восприятия риска и развитие методов его управления [14, с.89].

Профессор Даниэль Канеман, нобелевский лауреат по экономике, в своей книге «Быстрое и медленное мышление» исследует психологические аспекты принятия решений в условиях неопределенности и риска. Хотя книга не целиком посвящена нефинансовым рискам, она предоставляет ценные инсайты о том, как люди воспринимают и оценивают риски [15, с.97].

Рассмотрим на примере компании Saudi Aramco оценку нефинансовых рисков проектов. Saudi Aramco – одна из крупнейших нефтяных компаний в мире – сталкивается с различными видами нефинансовых рисков, как и любая другая крупная многонациональная корпорация. В контексте этой компании примеры оценки нефинансовых рисков могут включать следующие аспекты:

Учитывая экологическое воздействие добычи и переработки нефти, Saudi Aramco активно оценивает риски, связанные с возможными авариями, загрязнениями или инцидентами, которые могут негативно повлиять на окружающую среду. Оценка таких рисков включает в себя мониторинг технологических процессов, регулярные проверки оборудования и оценку влияния на окружающую среду в рамках различных проектов.

В условиях все большего внимания к вопросам климата и экологии компаниям, работающим в нефтяной промышленности, необходимо внимательно следить за своей репутацией. Saudi Aramco активно участвует в проектах, направленных на сокращение выбросов углекислого газа, внедрение чистых технологий и поддержание имиджа экологически ответственной компании. Оценка экологического риска проекта в компании Saudi Aramco может быть проведена на основе различных параметров, чтобы убедиться в

минимизации негативного воздействия на окружающую среду. Для иллюстрации создадим таблицу 1 оценки экологического риска для проекта по бурению новой нефтяной скважины.

Таблица 1. Оценка экологического риска для проекта по бурению новой нефтяной скважины Saudi Aramco

№	Параметр	Описание потенциального риска	Вероятность возникновения	Потенциальное воздействие	Стратегия управления риском
1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Водные ресурсы	Загрязнение подземных и поверхностных вод	Средняя	Высокое	Применение высококачественных уплотнений, мониторинг качества воды
2	Атмосфера	Выбросы вредных газов при бурении	Низкая	Среднее	Использование современных очистных установок, мониторинг состава воздуха
3	Биологическое разнообразие	Воздействие на местные экосистемы, нарушение местообитаний животных	Средняя	Высокое	Проведение экологической оценки, восстановление местообитаний после завершения работ
4	Отходы и отходные воды	Накопление опасных отходов и их обезвреживание	Высокая	Высокое	Использование технологий переработки, строгое соблюдение нормативов по обращению с отходами
5	Шумовые и вибрационные загрязнения	Шум и вибрации от работающего оборудования	Средняя	Низкая	Применение шумоподавляющего оборудования, соблюдение времени работы
Примечание – составлено автором на основе источника []					

Операционные риски связаны с возможными неполадками в операционной деятельности, такими как технические сбои, аварии или другие непредвиденные ситуации. Оценка таких рисков требует тщательного анализа рабочих процессов, использования новейших технологий и проведения регулярных тренировок для персонала.

Saudi Aramco работает в многих странах мира, и ей приходится соблюдать различные местные законы и нормативы. Риски, связанные с изменениями в законодательстве, могут оказывать влияние на операционную деятельность, финансовые показатели или репутацию

компании. Для минимизации таких рисков компания активно отслеживает изменения в законодательстве и участвует в диалоге с регуляторами.

Учитывая геополитическое положение Саудовской Аравии и масштабы деятельности Saudi Aramco, риски безопасности являются ключевым фактором. Это может включать в себя вопросы физической безопасности объектов, защиты от террористических угроз и кибербезопасности. Оценка таких рисков требует комплексного подхода и сотрудничества с местными и международными структурами безопасности.

Для демонстрации рассмотрим оценку геополитического риска сценарным методом для проекта Saudi Aramco по разработке нового месторождения нефти в третьей стране в таблице 2.

Таблица 2. Оценка геополитического риска сценарным методом для проекта Saudi Aramco по разработке нового месторождения нефти в третьей стране

№	Сценарий	Описание событий	Вероятность	Потенциальное воздействие	Стратегия минимизации риска
1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Стабильное политическое развитие	Страна поддерживает стабильное политическое и экономическое развитие без значимых потрясений.	Высокая	Позитивное	Усилить инвестиции, активное взаимодействие с местным правительством
2	Экономический кризис	Страна сталкивается с экономическим кризисом, возможны национализация активов.	Средняя	Негативное	Заключение долгосрочных договоров, страхование инвестиций
3	Политические потрясения	Переворот, нестабильность, рост антизападных настроений.	Низкая	Очень негативное	Диверсификация активов, стратегия быстрого выхода из проекта
4	Внешнее вмешательство	Возможное вмешательство соседних государств или крупных держав во внутренние дела страны.	Низкая	Негативное	Поддержание диалога с ключевыми международными акторами, создание "запасных" маршрутов поставок

Примечание – составлено автором на основе источника []

Эта таблица представляет собой лишь один из возможных способов оценки геополитического риска сценарным методом для компании Saudi Aramco. Главная цель такой оценки - представить различные потенциальные геополитические сценарии, которые могут возникнуть в процессе реализации проекта, и разработать соответствующие стратегии управления или минимизации риска.

Оценка нефинансовых рисков в Saudi Aramco представляет собой сложный процесс, который требует интеграции различных методов и подходов, чтобы обеспечить устойчивость и успешное функционирование компании в меняющемся мире.

Исследование и разработка новых методов идентификации нефинансовых рисков — это постоянно развивающаяся область, поскольку организации и исследователи ищут способы адаптации к меняющемуся окружению и новым вызовам. Использование больших данных и машинного обучения может предоставить компаниям уникальные возможности для идентификации рисков на основе анализа огромного объема информации. Например, анализ социальных медиа может помочь в выявлении изменений в общественном мнении или потребительском поведении, что может указывать на потенциальные риски репутации.

В условиях глобализации и все большей взаимосвязанности рынков сетевой анализ позволяет оценить, как изменения в одной части системы могут повлиять на другие ее части. Это особенно полезно для выявления «скрытых» рисков в сложных цепочках поставок или финансовых системах. Интегративные модели объединяют различные методы идентификации рисков, создавая картину потенциальных угроз. Это может включать в себя как качественные, так и количественные методы, и позволяет лучше понимать взаимосвязи между различными рисками.

Имитационное моделирование позволяет создавать компьютерные модели реальных систем или процессов и «имитировать» различные сценарии для выявления потенциальных рисков. Это может быть особенно полезно для оценки рисков в новых или неизведанных областях, где традиционные методы могут быть менее эффективными. Когнитивное картографирование основано на создании «карт» ментальных моделей экспертов или ключевых лиц в организации. Это помогает выявить скрытые убеждения, предположения и взгляды, которые могут влиять на восприятие и оценку рисков.

Пока что эти методы могут использоваться в ограниченных кругах экспертов или в крупных организациях с доступом к необходимым ресурсам и экспертизе. Однако по мере их дальнейшего развития и демонстрации эффективности они могут стать более доступными и широко применяемыми.

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THE ART OF MARKETING: HOW THE BARBIE MOVIE BECAME A BRAND AND CULTURAL EVENT

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ABSTRACT

The film industry has long been recognized as one of the most competitive and dynamic sectors in the world of entertainment. The entire process of filmmaking, from script development to screen distribution, is subject to significant external and internal influences. However, one of the most captivating and critically important aspects of this industry is its marketing strategy. It is precisely this component that shapes the perception of the film in the eyes of the audience and determines its commercial success. This aspect becomes particularly intriguing when it comes to films based on popular brands, such as "Barbie." In this article, we will explore the marketing history of the "Barbie" movie and examine the contribution marketing has made to the success of this franchise.

FEATURES OF THE BARBIE FRANCHISE

The "Barbie" franchise is not just the story of a doll, it is a story of a style and culture icon that has had a profound impact on millions of girls and women worldwide. The characteristics of this franchise can be divided into several key aspects.

Firstly, it is the long history and legacy: Barbie was first introduced in 1959, and since then, she has become an icon in the world of toys. Her long history instills a sense of trust among consumers and adds cultural significance to the franchise.

Secondly, it is the diversity of characters and accessories: One of Barbie's key features is her ability to take on a multitude of different roles and personas. From a nurse to an astronaut, from a princess to a businesswoman, Barbie can always reinvent herself. This allows the franchise to appeal to a diverse audience and create various doll collections and accessories.

The third aspect is the positive message: The "Barbie" franchise aims to instill positive values and teach girls about self-respect, friendship, and the possibility of being anything they want to be. This message makes Barbie not just a toy but also a role model.

Of course, there are other important aspects within the franchise, such as:

Fashion and style: Barbie has always been associated with fashion and style. Her clothing, accessories, and even homes set trends and inspire girls and women to care about their own style.

Media and entertainment: In addition to toys, the "Barbie" franchise also encompasses the media and entertainment industry. There are animated series, movies, music albums, and even video games associated with Barbie.

Global presence: Barbie is widely recognized worldwide and has many local adaptations and versions, allowing the franchise to adapt to various cultural contexts.

THE EMERGENCE OF THE BARBIE FRANCHISE IN MOVIE INDUSTRY

In the 2000s, Barbie entered the digital era, and Mattel's President, Richard Dickson, spearheaded the creation of Barbie Entertainment. In 2001, the first full-length film featuring Barbie was released—an animated movie titled "Barbie and the Nutcracker." Barbie.com, her inaugural website, also made its debut in the same year. It is important to note that producing a

film based on such a popular brand necessitated a meticulous and well-thought-out marketing plan.

Following the successful release of the animated film "Barbie and the Nutcracker" in 2001, the Barbie franchise in cinema embarked on a robust development trajectory. Mattel and Barbie Entertainment capitalized on the brand's popularity and continued to create new films that resonated with children and families.

In 2002, the next film, "Barbie in the Nutcracker," was released. Subsequently, numerous animated films followed, including "Barbie in the 12 Dancing Princesses" (2006), "Barbie: Starlight Adventure" (2008), and many others. These films often emphasized themes of fashion, friendship, and family values, making them popular among girls and teenagers.

In addition to animated films, Barbie also ventured into live-action cinema. In 2009, the film "Barbie and the Three Musketeers" was released, with actress Tiffany Thornton portraying Barbie. This experience proved successful, prompting the franchise to further experiment with live-action films.

An integral part of the marketing strategy was the promotion of national and international tours dedicated to "Barbie," where children and their parents could meet their beloved character in person and immerse themselves in the world of Barbie.

Over time, the Barbie franchise remained relevant and popular, continuously releasing new products, animated films, and collaborating with partners to create enchanting narratives. This allowed Barbie to maintain its status as one of the most recognizable and successful franchises in the world of toys and entertainment.

MARKETING CAMPAIGN FOR THE FULL-SCALE MOVIE BARBIE (2023)

1. Audience Engagement

Certainly, one of the pivotal and foundational elements in the comprehensive marketing campaign for the film "Barbie" revolved around the critical concept of audience engagement. This multifaceted strategy was not merely about advertising; it was about forging a deep and lasting connection with an array of diverse audiences.

Foremost among the considerations for the marketing team was the acknowledgment of the mature and devoted fan base of the "Barbie" brand. These individuals had grown up alongside Barbie dolls, animated series, and interactive games, forming an emotional attachment to the brand that spanned generations. Recognizing the potential of this dedicated audience segment was essential, as their nostalgia and affinity for Barbie provided a unique opportunity to create buzz and anticipation around the film.

To effectively engage this adult demographic, the marketing team embarked on a journey of nostalgia-driven marketing. They tapped into the sentiments of those who had fond memories of playing with Barbie dolls, watching Barbie cartoons, and immersing themselves in the imaginative world of Barbie games during their formative years. By evoking these cherished memories, the team aimed to rekindle the enthusiasm of adult fans, offering them a chance to relive the magic of Barbie on the big screen.

Moreover, the marketing campaign strategically appealed to the inner child of these adult fans. It emphasized that, regardless of age, the allure of Barbie's world, filled with glamour, fashion, and adventure, was still as captivating as ever. This approach not only engaged the nostalgia of the audience but also stirred a sense of excitement about experiencing Barbie's timeless charm in a new and cinematic dimension.

In addition to targeting the nostalgic sentiments of adult fans, the marketing team also recognized the potential for cross-generational appeal. They understood that many parents who had grown up with Barbie themselves would be keen to introduce their children to the beloved character, creating a shared experience that bridged generations. This insight led to a multifaceted

marketing approach that emphasized the enduring and universal appeal of Barbie, positioning the film as an event that could be enjoyed by both parents and their children, thereby fostering family engagement.

2. Collaborations with Popular Brands

To garner attention for the "Barbie" film, the marketing team employed a strategy of collaboration with well-known brands. Mattel orchestrated a multitude of collaborations. Xbox released limited-edition pink consoles with a Barbie-themed stand, ALDO designed pink shoes in classic Barbie packaging, one of the largest clothing retailers, Forever 21, created a clothing collection, and cosmetic brand NYX launched a Barbie-themed makeup line. Barbie Crocs and many other brands also took part in collaborations with Mattel.

3. Involvement of the Lead Actress Margot Robbie in the Marketing Campaign

Right from the inception of the project, the cast and crew fully immersed themselves in the captivating world of the "Barbie" movie. This dedication extended even to the set assistants, who enthusiastically donned vibrant pink attire, becoming an integral part of the film's vibrant and colorful production. This commitment to bringing the essence of Barbie to life on and off the screen underscored the passion and attention to detail that characterized the entire filmmaking process.

As the film approached its global premieres, the commitment to the Barbie aesthetic reached new heights. Special outfits were meticulously crafted, each one an exact replica of iconic Barbie ensembles. These bespoke costumes were not just clothing; they were works of art that paid homage to the timeless and ever-fashionable Barbie doll.

For Margot Robbie, who portrayed the iconic character, these meticulously designed outfits were more than costumes; they were a transformation into the living embodiment of Barbie herself. With every premiere, Margot Robbie stepped onto the red carpet, not just as an actress but as a real-life Barbie, captivating audiences with her striking resemblance to the beloved doll and adding an extra layer of excitement and authenticity to the film's promotion.

The dedication to recreating Barbie's iconic fashion in real life was a testament to the film's commitment to paying homage to the beloved character and bringing her vibrant personality to the forefront. It was a way of celebrating the enduring appeal of Barbie, not only as a toy but as a cultural icon whose influence transcends generations. In doing so, the film managed to bridge the gap between nostalgia and contemporary entertainment, making it a must-see for fans both young and old.

This meticulous attention to detail and commitment to authenticity in every aspect of the film's production, from the set design to the costumes, underscored the dedication of the entire team to creating a cinematic experience that would resonate with audiences and capture the essence of Barbie's enduring charm.

4. Barbiegamer

The hallmark of the marketing strategy for the 2023 "Barbie" film was undoubtedly the unconventional juxtaposition with another major cinematic project, Christopher Nolan's film "Oppenheimer." Both films were scheduled for the same release date - July 21, and despite this, neither studio saw fit to alter their premiere plans. "Barbie" presents a direct and contrasting counterpoint to the serious and conservative drama of "Oppenheimer." The bright and comedic adventures of the animated doll stand in stark contrast to the biographical film about the creator of the atomic bomb. Social media users quickly seized upon this information and began developing theories about which film to watch first: experience the dramatic depth of "Oppenheimer" and then relax with the colorful and lighthearted "Barbie," or vice versa, start with "Barbie" and then immerse themselves in the world of "Oppenheimer." This competition between the films gave rise

to a phenomenon known as "Barbiegamer," in which people created collages using frames from both films, designed posters, and even released T-shirts for the release date.

Social media indicates that quite a few viewers are indeed planning to see both films on the same day. While the marketing campaign for "Oppenheimer" adheres to a more traditional approach, considering the nature of the plot, which is less amenable to merchandise, the marketing strategy for "Barbie" focuses more on generating hype around the film, potentially boosting the box office performance of its cinematic neighbor.

The marketing campaign surrounding "Barbie" represents a unique phenomenon that combines the pleasant nostalgia of childhood, meticulous attention to detail, a high-quality film, and competition with Christopher Nolan's cinematic project. After the excitement subsides and the invested capital is recouped, this marketing strategy for "Barbie" will be etched into the annals of pop culture and will be remembered as one of the significant events of the summer of 2023.

5. Results and Success

The marketing history of the "Barbie" film influenced its success. Through well-planned campaigns and audience engagement strategies, the film had the potential to achieve favorable box office results. Furthermore, the film could have become popular among "Barbie" brand enthusiasts, contributing to the sales of associated products and merchandise.

CONCLUSION

The marketing journey of the "Barbie" film serves as a compelling case study in the realm of film marketing. It offers a fascinating exploration into how marketing strategies can be leveraged effectively within the film industry, particularly when the film is based on a well-established and beloved brand. The "Barbie" film stands as a prime example of how marketing can be harnessed to engage and captivate audiences, ultimately playing a pivotal role in the film's success.

This film underscores the indispensable role that marketing plays in the contemporary cinematic landscape. It showcases how well-executed marketing campaigns have the power to transform movies into cultural phenomena, making them more visible and commercially prosperous. The case of "Barbie" vividly illustrates how strategic marketing initiatives can transcend the traditional boundaries of filmmaking, propelling a beloved character from toy shelves and animated series into the realm of blockbuster cinema.

Moreover, the "Barbie" film exemplifies the synergy between nostalgia and innovation in marketing. By drawing upon the deep well of nostalgia that adults have for the brand while simultaneously captivating the imaginations of younger generations, the film managed to create a multi-generational fanbase. This unique blend of marketing tactics demonstrated that the resonance of a cherished brand like Barbie can extend across time, generations, and mediums.

In essence, the marketing story of the "Barbie" film offers valuable insights into the evolving landscape of film marketing. It highlights the enduring power of established brands and their ability to inspire creativity, as well as the potential for marketing to bridge generational gaps and unite audiences of all ages. Above all, it reinforces the notion that, in the ever-evolving world of cinema, marketing remains a dynamic force capable of shaping not only the fortunes of a film but also the cultural zeitgeist.

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Research trends in digital technology in education: systematic literature review

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Relevance: What specific education system does the submission focus on?

Today sustainable development includes social well-being contingent on the level of education. Even in the last century, education has been designated as a human right (Assembly, 1948) and identified as one of the most effective tools for development. Education is the means that contributes to reducing poverty and improving health, equity, and peace (Alvarado, 2019). At the same time, information technologies that disseminate knowledge are considered the main driving force of education reforms. The importance of technology in education has also been reaffirmed during the COVID-19 pandemic which skewed the education of millions of children. As a result of the pandemic, 1.6 billion children and adolescents have moved to distance learning in 190 countries since March 2020. This change has had varying impacts in terms of their academic performance, nutritional support, and subsequent enrollment stability (UNESCO, 2020). Most governments have used digital education as a backup measure to ensure continuity of learning at all levels of education (Martin, 2022). However, the current digital divide (World Bank, 2020) has shown that digital education is very underdeveloped; in a vulnerable environment, those with fewer technical resources had more difficulty completing lessons, as more than two-thirds of children aged 3 to 17 worldwide did not have access to the Internet at home (Unicef et al., 2020).

Theory/Context:

The post-pandemic period has led to an increase in the interest of experts and scholars to explore the importance of educational technology. Many experts have identified the importance of introducing digital educational technologies, such as mobile devices, smart boards, MOOCs, tablets, laptops, simulators, dynamic visualization and virtual laboratories, to change education in schools and institutions (van de Werfhorst, Kessenich & Geven, 2022). In the current realities, traditional educational methods do not provide an immediate learning environment, faster assessment and greater engagement at the proper level. Moreover, digital learning tools and technologies can fill this gap. Also, today there are such technologies that, increasing the efficiency of the educational process, are unmatched in comparison with traditional teaching methodologies.

In fact, modern technologies, having such qualities as adaptability and unobtrusiveness, make the educational process more attractive for the next generation.

Research question: What is the submission's goal?

This study aims to understand what are the main areas of research in the field of educational technology. We pay special attention to digital educational technologies. We are interested in the main trends in the development of digital technologies in the field of education.

Research design: How precisely & in detail was/will the work (be) executed-describe the methodology/approach.

In this study, we reviewed the literature on the digital education technology therein utilizing a citation-based SLR approach. Research citations were taken from Scopus. Several other databases such as the Web of Science (WoS) and Google Scholar provided citations. Scopus is characterized by more systematic and transparent criteria selection of citation sources and provides better content (Andersen & Nielsen, 2018). The methodology of this study is a unique SLR, based on citation counts analysis that intends to provide a content analysis of a selection of top-quality, highly rated papers. This method is three-fold: (a) process of the article selection; (b) Citation analysis; and (c) Analysis of 25 most cited papers. The details of these stages are presented in the following sub-sections.

Inquiry:

The scope of existing SLRs on the economic nature of digital education technology is narrowly focused. We identified three critical gaps: (a) the application of a limited number of keywords when searching for relevant articles, (b) an inadequate number of peer-reviewed articles compared to current research, and (c) the lack of a citation-based literature review (SLR) with the keyword range in previous research. The current study aims to fill in these gaps. In addition, this study provides a detailed content analysis of the top 25 articles which are classified based on the number of citations per year. This analysis highlights the characteristics of influential research into the economic essence of digital education technology. This citation analysis provides a classification of articles, authors, and journals based on the number of citations in each article. The number of citations can be considered as an alternative criterion to ensure that the article-selection process was performed objectively (Howland et al., 2009). To search for relevant articles, keywords related to digital education technology were used and were later narrowed to social sciences. The analysed base eventually included 979 articles on digital education technology indexed by Scopus. The research offers a detailed explanation of the methodology and data collection process. The research presents a detailed analysis of citations and an analysis of the top 25 articles. Finally, we discuss the results from a broader research perspective and offer the concluding remarks.

Findings: What are/will be the main outcomes and results?

The primary purpose of this paper was to conduct a review of the literature relevant to changes in research on digital education technology. Simultaneously, the present work identified the leading journals, the most prolific authors, and the most influential articles according to bibliometric data of articles, more precisely, the average annual citation rates. Overall, 979 peer-reviewed articles were deemed pertinent in the Scopus database using a complete keyword list. In addition, by conducting a thorough SLR on digital education technology, we were able to bridge existing gaps present in current literature in this domain.

Results show that the most influential journal with regard to the number of publications is the *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning* and in total citations is the journal *Computers & Education*. According to the overall number of citations, Selwyn N. is the most cited author (244 citations), and the most cited article is "Looking beyond learning: notes towards the critical study of educational technology" (Selwyn, 2010). The current paper discusses how this 'critical' approach differs from the ways that educational technology scholarship has tended to be pursued to date.

The number of publications was growing rapidly since 2020 (36 % growth). This illustrates the global attention of the research community on digital education technology since the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Figure 1 - Annual scientific production

The analysis shows that the allocation indicates that the leading countries are the USA (494 papers), the UK (135), Australia (125), and China (86) in this scientific area. Moreover, the first paper was published in the USA in 1947 (Porterfield, 1947). So, we can see that the USA is the largest producer of digital education technology research with 494 studies. According to the results, there is a tendency that the higher the level of economic development of the country, the more active research towards digital education technology is carried out.

Contribution: What will the outcomes and results add to the current understanding or theory in the IM community?

This study is unique in several ways. First, the number of articles reviewed in this study is 979, which is higher than all previous literature reviews on the topic of digital education technology. Second, the search process used an exhaustive list of keywords chosen based on expert opinion and earlier literature. Third, this is the first occasion of a citation-based literature review being conducted, to the best of the authors' knowledge. Fourth, this study identified the most cited authors and leading journals to determine the importance of researching digital education technology for future researchers.

Practical implications: Who will practically gain what and in which way from the findings?

This study derives important recommendations for policymakers and educators. Our data indicate that digital education technology is somehow overlooked by the government. At the same time, there is an expectation that the government should support the development of digital education technology. Supporting mechanisms need to be established for the education organizations, including financial and institutional support. This should lead to the creation of favorable economic and political conditions at the national level. Furthermore, the development of digital education technologies will improve the level of education in less developed regions, thereby solving many issues of sustainable development.

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Women's Entrepreneurship and Gender Policies in Kazakhstan: Pathways to Inclusivity and Economic Sustainability

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Abstract

This research paper explores the contemporary landscape of gendered entrepreneurship policies in Kazakhstan, emphasizing the pivotal role of women's entrepreneurship within the country's economic and social development. The study examines the evolution of government policies, particularly highlighting recent initiatives aimed at empowering women entrepreneurs, including the introduction of grants for innovative business ideas, the enactment of a law on social entrepreneurship, and the establishment of women's entrepreneurship support centers. Drawing from various secondary sources and official data, this research provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of women's entrepreneurship and the measures taken to promote gender equality in the entrepreneurial sphere. It underscores the importance of these policies in fostering an inclusive and sustainable economy in Kazakhstan.

Introduction

Gender equality issues remain a salient and pressing concern in the diverse landscape of Kazakhstan today, transcending multiple sectors, from employment and education to entrepreneurship and beyond. Serving as a cornerstone of equality and opportunity is the "Law on State Guarantees of Equal Rights and Equal Opportunities for Men and Women"¹ within the Republic of Kazakhstan. Within this intricate tapestry of gender-related policies, women's entrepreneurship emerges as a pivotal force propelling the development of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). The overarching ideals of women's empowerment and gender equality are placed in a prominent position, in consonance with the grander objectives outlined in the Concept of family and gender policy until 2030 and the sustainable development framework spanning until 2030².

This paper embarks on a critical inquiry to unearth the depth and breadth of gender-based nuances embedded within Kazakhstan's current entrepreneurship policies. It achieves this by meticulously dissecting the current landscape of women's entrepreneurship, scrutinizing extant support programs targeted at women entrepreneurs, and exploring the newfound bastions of women's entrepreneurship support centers. This exploration relies on a comprehensive review of secondary sources, enriched by data derived from esteemed entities such as the Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reform, the Ministry of Social Protection and Labor, and the Ministry of National Economy. Although this report does not purport to be an exhaustive literature review, it endeavors to provide a sweeping panorama of

¹ Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 223-IV "On State Guarantees of Equal Rights and Equal Opportunities for Men and Women" dated December 8, 2009 (as amended on 03.07.2013) https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/Z090000223_#z2

² <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/U1600000384>

the multifaceted subject matter. In sum, as women entrepreneurs constitute nearly half of all SMEs quantitatively, the crux of the matter lies in qualitative support and privileges that resonate with their unique circumstances. The year 2020 marks a turning point when the government, in response to the impassioned pleas of mothers from low-income households, initiated a transformative shift in policy, offering housing and financial support. This shift reveals the burgeoning entrepreneurial spirit among Kazakhstani women, who are emerging as trailblazers of social initiatives. Notably, quotas were introduced to furnish grants for groundbreaking business ventures initiated by women with large families and children with special needs. The year 2021 witnessed the enactment of a pioneering law on social entrepreneurship, further underscoring the government's commitment to addressing the needs of mothers from large families and children with special needs. Consequently, numerous support measures were earmarked to fortify entrepreneurs within this demographic. Furthermore, the same year saw the establishment of women's entrepreneurship support centers, a laudable initiative spearheaded by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the Asian Development Bank (ADB). These centers embrace a philosophy of offering tools and knowledge, akin to providing a fishing rod, rather than proffering fish in the form of direct financial assistance. The overarching aim is to empower women to translate their business dreams into tangible realities. The culmination of these gender-focused entrepreneurship policies reflect a commitment to inclusivity, particularly for low-income and large families, by broadening the horizon of entrepreneurial opportunities. As such, the policies endeavor to enhance support for existing women entrepreneurs while nurturing an environment conducive to women with entrepreneurial aspirations, especially in rural regions and among those with substantial family responsibilities. In doing so, the country endeavors to realize its vision of an inclusive, vibrant, and sustainable economy that benefits the nation as a whole. This research thus seeks to shed light on the intricate interplay of gender and entrepreneurship policies in Kazakhstan, offering insights into the evolving landscape and highlighting the transformative potential of gender-sensitive measures on the nation's economic and social fabric.

I. Current state of women entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan

The current state of women entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan emerges as a pivotal area of examination. Data sourced from the Bureau of National Statistics provides a snapshot of this landscape. As of the onset of 2022, a total of 1,694,672 Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) stood registered in Kazakhstan, reflecting a notable uptick of 10% compared to the corresponding period in 2021, where the count stood at 1,540,592 units. Among these registered entities, 1,431,647 SMEs operated actively, marking a 5.5% increase from the previous year, where 1,357,311 units were in operation.

Of particular significance is the prominence of women-led SMEs within this dynamic context. As of January 1, 2022, a remarkable 638 thousand SMEs were spearheaded by women entrepreneurs, signifying that women's participation in SMEs constitutes a substantial 44.6% share of the total landscape. Further parsing the data, it is discerned that individual entrepreneurs command a significant majority at 77%, corresponding to 494.3 thousand units, while legal entities comprise 14% with 86.8 thousand entities. Notably, peasant farming accounts for a noteworthy 9% share, representing 57 thousand units.

A longitudinal analysis of SMEs led by women juxtaposed against the overall SME landscape from 2016 to 2022 reveals a nuanced pattern, as illustrated in Figure 1. Remarkably, this period displays a consistent equilibrium, with neither significant growth nor decline. The share of female-led SMEs, encapsulated at 44 percent, remains steadfast and unwavering throughout this temporal span.

In summation, these descriptive statistics provide a comprehensive portrayal of the contemporary landscape of women's entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan, reflecting a notable presence of women entrepreneurs within the SME ecosystem, and highlighting the stability of their share over the years.

3

In the multifaceted landscape of entrepreneurship, a closer examination reveals intriguing variations across different sectors, where the participation of women entrepreneurs assumes varying degrees of prominence. In the realms of agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, women leaders of SMEs account for 25.4% of the total, while in the manufacturing sector, this figure rises notably to 40.2%. However, when we shift our focus to the domains of construction, transport, and warehousing—typically domains where women's presence has been less pronounced—we observe a lower representation of women entrepreneurs, with 21.4% and 21% respectively. These figures underscore the challenges and opportunities that women face when seeking to apply their entrepreneurial endeavors in sectors traditionally perceived as male-dominated.

In contrast, some sectors exhibit a notably higher prevalence of women entrepreneurs. In the sphere of education, a remarkable 69% of SMEs are led by women, indicating a significant leadership role in this sector. Similarly, in real estate operations, 59% of businesses are helmed by women, underscoring their substantial contribution to this field. The accommodation and food services sector showcases a notable 55.3% representation of women entrepreneurs, while the wholesale and retail trade sector closely follows with 55%. Furthermore, the domains of health and social services witness a robust 54% share of women entrepreneurs, emphasizing their integral role in these critical sectors.

These statistics, as presented in Table 1, shed light on the sector-specific dynamics of women's entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan, offering insights into the sectors where women are making substantial inroads as well as those where gender diversity remains a challenge. Such an analysis enriches our understanding of the nuanced landscape of women's entrepreneurship within the broader SME ecosystem, paving the way for targeted policies and initiatives to further empower women entrepreneurs in all sectors of the economy.

³ https://gender.stat.gov.kz/page/frontend/detail?id=107&slug=2018-1-2&cat_id=6&lang=kk

Table 1. Distribution of operating SMEs by type of economic activity as of January 1, 2022 ⁴

	Number of SMEs - total	Number of female-led SMEs - total	Percentage of female SMEs by industry (%)
Republic of Kazakhstan	1 431 647	638 089	44,6
Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries	256 576	65 157	25,4
Manufacturing	65 119	26 173	40,2
Construction	81 328	17 405	21,4
Wholesale and retail trade; car and motorcycle repair	458 542	252 230	55,0
Transport and warehousing	78 260	16 480	21,1
Provision of accommodation and food services	39 721	21 965	55,3
Information and communication	22 975	7 025	30,6
Financial and insurance activities	5 266	2 099	39,9
Operations with real estate	77 301	45 595	59,0
Professional, scientific, and technical activities	48 980	24 274	49,6
Administrative and support services activities	41 612	17 187	41,3
Public administration and defense; compulsory social security	142	42	29,6
Education	25 551	17 652	69,1
Public health and social services	12 453	6 718	53,9
Arts, entertainment, and recreation	12 671	5 454	43,0
Provision of other types of services	205 150	112 633	54,9

Continuing our exploration of the multifaceted impact of women's entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan, it becomes evident that women's active participation in entrepreneurial endeavors not only contributes to economic growth but also plays a pivotal role in expanding women's employment opportunities, enhancing their social standing, fostering personal development, and unlocking avenues for substantial income generation. As of January 1, 2022, women entrepreneurs have assumed a significant mantle, driving the employment engine in the Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME) sector of Kazakhstan. These dynamic women entrepreneurs have paved the way for the sustenance of 1,093.4 thousand jobs, representing a substantial 31% of all jobs within the SME sector, an undeniable testament to their transformative role.

To further underscore the evolution of this transformative role, Table 2 offers a comprehensive analysis of employment trends within SMEs from 2016 to 2022. This longitudinal data reveals a consistent and robust pattern. In 2016, women-led SMEs contributed to 31.2% of total employment within the sector, a trend that persisted throughout the subsequent years. In

⁴ https://gender.stat.gov.kz/page/frontend/detail?id=109&slug=2018-1-4&cat_id=6&lang=kk

2022, this percentage remained steadfast at 31.1%, despite fluctuations in overall employment numbers, underscoring the enduring impact of women entrepreneurs in bolstering employment opportunities.

This table, while encapsulating the statistical trajectory, also paints a vivid picture of the sustained commitment of women entrepreneurs to the growth and development of the SME sector in Kazakhstan. Their tireless efforts not only fuel economic progress but also foster social inclusivity and gender equity by offering a significant proportion of the population meaningful employment and advancement opportunities. As women continue to shape the SME landscape, their multifaceted contributions bear testament to their pivotal role in steering the nation towards a more inclusive, prosperous, and equitable future.

Table 2. Number of employees in operating SMEs in the period from 2016 to 2022 ⁵

Year	Number of employees in SMEs - total	Number of employees in SMEs headed by women - total	Share of employment in female SMEs in percent (%)
2016	3 147 046	980 916	31,2
2017	3 074 777	964 958	31,4
2018	3 190 133	969 987	30,4
2019	3 312 457	1 035 107	31,2
2020	3 398 786	1 066 828	31,4
2021	3 472 606	1 078 313	31,1
2022	3 511 618	1 093 402	31,1

Table 3. Number of people employed at operating SMEs by type of economic activity as of January 1, 2022 ⁶

	Number of employees in SMEs - total	Number of employees in SMEs headed by women - total	Percentage of number of employees in female led SMEs by industry (%)
Total	3 511 618	1 093 402	31,1
Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries	448 018	73 446	16,4
Manufacturing	360 425	59 902	16,6
Construction	301 863	48 597	16,1
Wholesale and retail trade; car and motorcycle repair	1 000 898	446 409	44,6
Transport and warehousing	187 355	30 714	16,4
Provision of accommodation and food services	132 080	50 080	37,9
Information and communication	71 825	19 581	27,3
Financial and insurance activities	23 412	10 398	44,4

⁵ <https://gender.stat.gov.kz/kk/category/6>

⁶ https://gender.stat.gov.kz/page/frontend/detail?id=110&slug=2018-1-5&cat_id=6&lang=kk

Operations with real estate	165 440	67 316	40,7
Professional, scientific, and technical activities	147 239	46 510	31,6
Administrative and support services activities	164 810	37 777	22,9
Education	114 159	42 585	37,3
Public health and social services	78 522	44 347	56,5
Arts, entertainment, and recreation	30 366	4 582	15,1
Provision of other types of services	285 147	111 158	39,0

Table 3 offers a comprehensive snapshot of employment dynamics within the Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME) sector in Kazakhstan, as of January 1, 2022. It delves into the intricate interplay of the number of employees in SMEs across various economic sectors and underscores the significant role of women entrepreneurs in shaping the employment landscape.

At a national level, SMEs collectively account for a substantial workforce of 3,511,618 individuals, among which 1,093,402 are employed in businesses led by women. This signifies that women-led SMEs contribute significantly, comprising 31.1% of the overall SME employment sector.

A more granular analysis of employment distribution within specific economic activities reveals compelling insights. In sectors such as agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, manufacturing, and construction, women entrepreneurs play an essential role in providing employment opportunities, with 16.4%, 16.6%, and 16.1% of total employment, respectively.

However, the true dynamism of women's leadership in the SME sector emerges prominently in domains like wholesale and retail trade, including car and motorcycle repair, where a substantial 44.6% of employees find their livelihoods in women-led businesses. The financial and insurance activities sector also showcases a robust presence, with 44.4% of employees working in women-led SMEs. Similarly, operations with real estate feature prominently with 40.7% of the workforce employed in businesses led by women.

Furthermore, professional, scientific, and technical activities, as well as the education sector, paint a vivid picture of women entrepreneurs' contributions, with 31.6% and 37.3% of total employment, respectively. In the realm of administrative and support services activities, women-led SMEs account for 22.9% of the workforce.

The most striking finding emanates from the public health and social services sector, where women entrepreneurs hold a commanding presence, employing a substantial 56.5% of the workforce. Their contributions to this critical sector resonate deeply, signifying their dedication to societal well-being.

In sum, this table offers an in-depth portrayal of women entrepreneurs' role in generating employment opportunities across various economic sectors. It underscores the pronounced impact of women-led businesses in sectors critical for societal development and economic growth. These findings illuminate the multifaceted contributions of women entrepreneurs, reinforcing their pivotal role in shaping the labor landscape and propelling the nation towards a more inclusive, prosperous, and gender-equitable future.

Our examination of entrepreneurial policies targeting women's Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) reveals that there has been a notable consistency in policy direction from 2016 to 2022. During this period, it is discernible that there were no specific privileges or advantages accorded to women-led SMEs. Consequently, it becomes evident that the landscape of women's SMEs has evolved organically, shaped by market forces and entrepreneurial drive.

In this context, the typical women-led SMEs have found their niche in service-oriented sectors such as education services, real estate operations, accommodation and food services, as well as health and social services. These sectors are characterized by relatively lower added value and productivity levels. Furthermore, the data underscores that the average women-led SME operates with a small workforce, employing an average of 1.7 individuals. This underscores the prevalence of micro-businesses within the women-led SME landscape and raises the possibility that there is a substantial segment of self-employed and informal businesswomen who have yet to be formally recognized.

In a broader societal context, it is noteworthy that women constitute 52% of the population and boast a 66% economic activity rate. Within the able-bodied population of Kazakhstan, women comprise a substantial 7 million individuals, which is 350 thousand more than their male counterparts. Perhaps most strikingly, the female segment of society contributes significantly, accounting for 39% of the country's total Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This underscores the profound and essential role that women play in shaping the economic fabric of the nation.

In sum, this analysis illuminates the intrinsic resilience and entrepreneurial spirit of women in Kazakhstan, who have carved their niche in SMEs despite the absence of specific policy privileges. It also underscores the prevalence of micro-businesses and the potential for further empowerment of self-employed and informal businesswomen. Moreover, it serves as a powerful reminder of the pivotal role of women in shaping the economic landscape and underscores the need for continued efforts to support and harness their economic potential for the benefit of the entire nation.

II. Current women entrepreneurship support programs in Kazakhstan

The entrepreneurial journey for women in Kazakhstan often presents distinct challenges, notably in securing financing, overcoming initial investment hurdles, and finding investors. Additionally, obstacles related to limited business education and financial literacy, coupled with high administrative barriers, have been identified by the "Atameken" National Chamber of Entrepreneurs as persistent issues⁷.

Recognizing these challenges, the state has been actively engaged in assisting women entrepreneurs in overcoming these obstacles. Over the years, women's entrepreneurship has received support through initiatives such as the Enbek Program for the Development of Productive Employment and Mass Entrepreneurship for the period 2017-2021⁸, the Business Roadmap-2025⁹, and various programs sponsored by international organizations and the Entrepreneurship Development Fund "Damu." Importantly, it is worth noting that women's entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan is supported within the framework of general requirements that SMEs must meet to access state support.

A significant development in this landscape occurred in 2022 when a new national project was introduced with a focus on augmenting the income of the population. This initiative supplanted the previous "Enbek" program, which had been in operation from 2017 to 2021. Notably, within the ambit of this transition, amendments were made to the Bastau Business project, which had operated under the umbrella of the "Enbek" program. This update entailed a

⁷ <https://dknews.kz/ru/chitayte-v-nomere/254941-zhenskoe-biznes-liderstvo-to-li-eshche-budet>

⁸ <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P1800000746>

⁹ <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P1900000968>

doubling of the grant size, escalating from 612,000 to 1,225,000 tenge¹⁰, thus enhancing support for women entrepreneurs.

Thus, the evolving landscape of women's entrepreneurship support programs in Kazakhstan underscores the government's commitment to addressing the unique challenges faced by women in business. While these programs do not entail special privileges, they are designed to provide essential resources and assistance, thereby facilitating the growth and success of women-led SMEs in the country.

According to data from the Ministry of Social Protection and Labor, the Bastau Business project has played a pivotal role in equipping aspiring entrepreneurs with essential skills over the course of five years. Since its inception, the program has successfully trained 184.5 thousand individuals in fundamental entrepreneurship principles, including accounting, marketing, and the formulation and defense of business projects. Launched in December 2016, the "Enbek" program, a predecessor to Bastau Business, also demonstrated commendable outcomes during its tenure. From 2017 onwards, it reached an impressive 84 thousand individuals¹¹.

The "Enbek" program introduced a mechanism for preferential microcrediting and the issuance of gratuitous grants to support citizens' business ideas. Approximately 40% of program participants benefited from funding opportunities to realize their entrepreneurial projects, including access to microcredits and grants. Over this five-year period, approximately 62,000 individuals availed themselves of preferential microcredits, with a significant proportion embarking on their maiden entrepreneurial ventures. Notably, about 29 thousand individuals, already active entrepreneurs, leveraged these soft loans to expand their existing enterprises. This influx of microcredit recipients catalyzed the creation of an additional 60,000 job opportunities.

Beginning in 2018, the program incorporated a mechanism for the provision of state grants. In 2019, the grant size was amplified, increasing from 100 Monthly Calculation Indices (MCI) to 200. This pivotal change provided around 119 thousand Kazakhstanis with their first opportunity to bring their business ideas to fruition or advance their entrepreneurial undertakings.

These initiatives underscore the government's commitment to fostering entrepreneurship and supporting the aspirations of its citizens. Through accessible training, microcrediting, and grants, these programs have played a vital role in empowering individuals to initiate and grow their businesses, thus contributing to the economic development and employment landscape of Kazakhstan.

Furthermore, under the purview of the "National Project for the Development of Entrepreneurship for 2021-2025," an array of financial and non-financial measures has been devised to fortify entrepreneurship. Financial backing for entrepreneurship is multifaceted, encompassing interest rate subsidies aimed at reducing the borrowing costs for business development loans extended by banks. It also includes guarantees, where a partial collateral guarantee is offered for bank loans, and preferential micro-crediting facilitated through second-tier banks.

Notably, within the framework of interest rate subsidies, entrepreneurs gain access to loans with an enticing annual interest rate of 6%. The loan ceiling for a single entrepreneur extends up to 3 billion tenge. For loans ranging up to 360 million tenge, the guarantee level stands at an impressive 85%, whereas for loans up to 1 billion tenge, it remains substantial at 50%. Furthermore, the National Project facilitates unsecured microcredits at a rate of 6%. In mono, small towns, and rural settlements without sectoral constraints, these microcredits are extended

¹⁰ <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P2200000218>

¹¹ <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/enbek/press/article/details/77404?directionId=188&lang=ru>

at a highly favorable rate of 5%, with a maximum loan amount of 20 million tenge allocated for investment purposes and up to 5 million tenge for replenishing working capital.

As per the report by the Entrepreneurship Development Fund (EDF) "Damu," the outset of 2022 witnessed the subsidization of 16,961 projects initiated by women entrepreneurs under the aegis of the National Project. Remarkably, regional statistics indicate that women entrepreneurs' projects have found particular traction in the Aktobe and Kyzylorda regions, along with the cities of Astana and Almaty. The largest volumes of subsidized loan portfolios have been recorded in the cities of Almaty and Astana, as well as in the East Kazakhstan and Almaty regions. The spectrum of subsidized projects led by women entrepreneurs predominantly encompasses ventures in the manufacturing industry, trade, and services. When scrutinizing the financial institutions involved, it becomes evident that Halyk Bank of Kazakhstan JSC, Sberbank JSC, and Bank CenterCredit JSC have been the most active in subsidizing female SME representatives.

This comprehensive framework of financial support mechanisms underscores the government's unwavering commitment to nurturing entrepreneurship and, notably, empowering women entrepreneurs. Through reduced interest rates, guarantees, and favorable micro-credit terms, these initiatives serve as catalysts for the growth and prosperity of women-led SMEs in Kazakhstan, fostering economic development and gender equity in tandem.

Within the expansive framework of the National Project, a remarkable 11,517 projects led by women entrepreneurs have been fortified with loan guarantees, cumulatively amounting to 192,744 million tenge. These guarantees collectively reached an impressive total of 90,221 million tenge. When dissected regionally, the highest count of guarantees was inked in the Aktobe, Kyzylorda, Mangystau regions, and the city of Nur-Sultan. Notably, the lion's share of guaranteed loans extended to women entrepreneurs was recorded in Nur-Sultan, as well as in the Mangystau and Atyrau regions. In terms of industry sectors, women predominantly sought guarantees within the domains of trade, manufacturing, and a diverse array of services. This is mirrored in the loan portfolio amount, where projects in these sectors predominated.

Concessional lending emerges as a particularly sought-after support mechanism, constituting a significant 58% share of women's entrepreneurship within the broader scope of concessional lending. Moreover, women's entrepreneurship accounts for 39% of projects within the ambit of interest rate subsidies and 38% in the realm of loan guarantees. Astoundingly, over 46% of all projects supported by the Entrepreneurship Development Fund (EDF) "Damu" are initiatives led by women, underscoring their substantial presence and contributions to the entrepreneurial landscape.

In addition to financial support, non-financial assistance plays a pivotal role in nurturing entrepreneurship. This encompasses a spectrum of information and consulting services offered, free of charge, to SMEs across diverse economic sectors and to individuals with entrepreneurial aspirations, accessible both offline and online. These services encompass informing and advising on state support measures, including facilitating appeals. To further enhance accessibility, there are more than 189 Business Service Centers (BSC) and their branches strategically located in regional and district centers, single-industry towns, and small towns, fostering an environment conducive to entrepreneurship. Impressively, statistics reveal that nearly half, approximately 45%, of non-financial support projects are spearheaded by women entrepreneurs.

By actively supporting and closely monitoring women entrepreneurs, "Damu" has also distilled a composite profile of these dynamic individuals within the micro, small, and medium-sized business landscape it supports. This profile typifies a woman, typically aged 39-40, predominantly engaged in individual entrepreneurship, often in the realm of trade. Their businesses typically employ fewer than 10 individuals, with approximately every second entrepreneur availing themselves of state support for investments.

In sum, the multifaceted approach to entrepreneurial support within the National Project not only highlights the government's commitment to nurturing entrepreneurship but also underscores the impressive contributions of women entrepreneurs in Kazakhstan. Their substantial presence in various support programs reaffirms their integral role in driving economic development and fostering gender inclusivity within the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Furthermore, in 2015, a pivotal agreement was inked between the Ministry of National Economy (MNE) and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), giving rise to the Technical Cooperation Account under the Women in Business Program. This program represents a strategic initiative aimed at bolstering the competitiveness and growth potential of women-led enterprises through a multifaceted approach encompassing technical assistance (comprising consulting, mentoring, and training), support for second-tier banks (STBs) in developing and delivering tailored lending products, and crucially, financial support for women's entrepreneurship. The latter facet involves extending credit lines to second-tier banks from the EBRD, coupled with the coverage of their initial loss risks.

In the context of the Kazakhstani market, the proportion of SMEs under the stewardship of women remains relatively modest. Furthermore, banks have yet to comprehensively assess the risks associated with financing such SMEs. Therefore, the principal objective underpinning the coverage of initial loss risks is to incentivize partner banks to provide long-term financial backing within the sphere of women's entrepreneurship. This mechanism allows for the coverage of up to 10% of the loan portfolio extended to women-owned SMEs under the EBRD credit line, and remarkably, it can underwrite up to 70% of each sub-loan.

Within the realm of collaboration between the Ministry of National Economy and the EBRD, over 300 women-led enterprises have already benefited from consulting support delivered by local experts. This initiative has also facilitated the disbursement of 21.8 thousand loans amounting to 35.4 billion tenge. A noteworthy characteristic of this program is its emphasis on supporting more advanced and financially stable female SMEs. Over the years, this program has demonstrated its efficacy in fostering the growth and sustainability of women-led businesses, thus contributing significantly to the evolving entrepreneurial landscape.

In conclusion, the multifaceted support landscape for women's entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan reflects the government's dedicated efforts to empower women in business and foster economic growth. Through a combination of financial and non-financial support programs, as well as strategic partnerships with international organizations like the EBRD, women-led enterprises have gained access to crucial resources, mentorship, and funding opportunities. While challenges remain, these initiatives have made significant strides in boosting women's participation in entrepreneurship, promoting gender inclusivity, and advancing the economic prospects of women in Kazakhstan. However, continued efforts and innovations are essential to further enhance the impact of these programs and ensure sustainable growth in women's entrepreneurship.

III. Women's Entrepreneurship Support Centers

In 2021, a significant milestone was achieved in Kazakhstan's commitment to supporting women in entrepreneurship with the establishment of 17 Women's Entrepreneurship Support Centers¹². These centers, situated in all regions of the country, are a result of collaboration between the National Chamber of Entrepreneurs of the Republic of Kazakhstan, known as "Atameken," and international partners, particularly the Asian Development Bank, which provided

¹² <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/economy/press/news/details/287663?lang=ru>

funding through the Solidarity Fund for Kazakhstan during the COVID-19 pandemic, and the United Nations Development Program in Kazakhstan¹³.

A distinguishing characteristic of these centers lies in their dynamic approach, wherein women are encouraged to submit applications for training and other forms of support based on their specific needs. The primary mission of these centers is to foster the growth of women's entrepreneurship, ultimately augmenting the contribution of women entrepreneurs to the sustainable development of the economy. In this process, the centers play a pivotal role in job creation and reducing social inequalities, aligning with broader national and international objectives for gender equality and economic empowerment.

The Center's overarching objective is to empower women in entrepreneurship, fostering not only their business acumen but also their personal development. It strives to create an enabling environment that contributes to the development of an inclusive, viable, and sustainable economy while championing gender equality and the empowerment of women across the board. In pursuit of these goals, the Center offers a comprehensive array of non-financial services tailored to meet the needs of two distinct categories of women. Firstly, women with entrepreneurial aspirations receive support in terms of awareness-raising, access to crucial information, guidance, and advice as they embark on their entrepreneurial journeys. Secondly, the Center extends its support to current entrepreneurs, startups, and self-employed women, with a special focus on those in rural areas, facilitating their business development and growth.

The Center's primary responsibilities encompass the establishment of a nationwide institutional framework that operates across key cities and regions, delivering targeted support to women entrepreneurs. It actively promotes networking and dialogue between government entities, women entrepreneurs' associations (including unions and cooperatives), and various stakeholders to identify and eliminate barriers hindering women's entrepreneurial activities. Moreover, it conducts training sessions aimed at enhancing the business skills of women with entrepreneurial inclinations and existing women entrepreneurs. These activities are complemented by information dissemination campaigns that raise awareness among women entrepreneurs. The Center also provides invaluable mentoring support to women engaged in business, fostering their professional growth.

Diverse support services are developed and made available to women entrepreneurs and their service providers, with a particular focus on expanding market access, improving financial accessibility, and enhancing managerial and other essential skills. The Center actively mobilizes the untapped potential of women entrepreneurs, acknowledging their pivotal role in propelling the country's economic development. It is equally dedicated to promoting entrepreneurship among women, attracting female talent to existing enterprises, and nurturing women's competencies and knowledge through vocational training and mentoring initiatives. Furthermore, the Center plays a pivotal role in supporting Family Centers, providing crucial mentoring services to mothers with multiple children and rural women, thereby fortifying the fabric of society and advancing gender equality.

Within the framework of these Centers, a diverse range of weekly training sessions and masterclasses are conducted to enhance the business acumen and personal growth of women

¹³ <https://www.undp.org/ru/kazakhstan/news/%D1%86%D0%B5%D0%BD%D1%82%D1%80%D1%8B-%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B2%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%B8%D1%8F-%D0%B6%D0%B5%D0%BD%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%B3%D0%BE-%D0%BF%D1%80%D0%B5%D0%B4%D0%BF%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%BC%D0%B0%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BB%D1%8C%D1%81%D1%82%D0%B2%D0%B0-%D0%BE%D1%82%D0%BA%D1%80%D1%8B%D0%B2%D0%B0%D1%8E%D1%82%D1%81%D1%8F-%D0%B2%D0%BE-%D0%B2%D1%81%D0%B5%D1%85-%D1%80%D0%B5%D0%B3%D0%B8%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%B0%D1%85-%D0%BA%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%B0%D1%85%D1%81%D1%82%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B0>

entrepreneurs. These courses cover a broad spectrum of areas, including SMM marketing, social entrepreneurship, vegetable cultivation, and cooperative establishment.

An innovative initiative spearheaded by the Council of Businesswomen under the Presidium of the National Chamber of Entrepreneurs of the Republic of Kazakhstan, known as "Atameken," is the introduction of the Japanese project "One Village - One Product" (OVOP). OVOP represents a distinctive approach to the development of rural communities, emphasizing the engagement of local populations in creating unique regional products with market appeal. OVOP places paramount importance on criteria such as the utilization of locally available and renewable raw materials, manual labor or the use of simple tools devoid of specialized equipment, high product quality, and alignment with market demand, incorporating a robust marketing strategy to promote these products.

The overarching objective of the OVOP project is to bolster the capacity of local communities and mitigate poverty and unemployment in rural areas. This objective is realized through the facilitation of cooperation among local residents, activation of rural communities (including women and youth), and harnessing local labor resources. OVOP encourages collaboration among villagers to craft distinctive local products by leveraging regional resources and considering the unique characteristics of each locality. Since November 12, 2021, OVOP has been piloted in four regions: Zhambyl, West Kazakhstan, Kostanay, and Mangystau.

The Kazakhstan OVOP model in its pilot phase revolves around the identification of the most promising projects in these regions, which exhibit substantial export potential or offer value addition to existing regional production. It further involves identifying the educational needs of target audiences (initiative groups) in selected villages and subsequently conducting training sessions. Additionally, the program offers methodological support and mentoring by seasoned entrepreneurs to nurture the success of these initiatives.

In conclusion, Women's Entrepreneurship Support Centers in Kazakhstan, established in partnership with international organizations and governmental bodies, serve as pivotal hubs for nurturing and advancing women's participation in entrepreneurship. These centers provide invaluable non-financial services, tailored to meet the diverse needs of aspiring and current women entrepreneurs. From offering business competence development to personal growth, these centers empower women across rural and urban landscapes, fostering an environment that fuels inclusive, viable, and sustainable economic growth. Through weekly trainings, masterclasses, and innovative initiatives like the "One Village - One Product" project, these centers actively contribute to the economic development of local communities and the nation as a whole. As this research unfolds, we will delve deeper into the tangible impacts and transformations catalyzed by Women's Entrepreneurship Support Centers in Kazakhstan.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research sheds light on the dynamic landscape of women's entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan, highlighting both its quantitative significance and the need for qualitative support and privileges to foster sustainable growth. The evolving policy landscape, marked by significant changes in 2020 and 2021, reflects a growing recognition of the invaluable role played by women entrepreneurs in driving social and economic initiatives in society. Introducing quotas for grants to support women with large families and children with special needs, alongside the adoption of the law on social entrepreneurship in 2021, underscores the commitment to address the unique challenges faced by this demographic.

Moreover, the establishment of women's entrepreneurship support centers in 2021, initiated by UNDP and ADB, marks a pivotal shift towards providing comprehensive assistance that

goes beyond financial aid. These centers embody the adage of "providing a fishing rod, not a fish," empowering women to transform their entrepreneurial ideas into reality.

The introduction of gender-based entrepreneurship policies geared towards inclusivity for low-income and large families underscores a holistic approach to providing entrepreneurial opportunities. As Kazakhstan strives for an inclusive, viable, and sustainable economy, these policies not only expand opportunities for existing women entrepreneurs but also create a favorable ecosystem for aspiring women entrepreneurs, particularly in rural areas and those with large families. By harnessing the entrepreneurial potential of women, Kazakhstan is poised to achieve the broader objectives of economic inclusivity and sustainability, ultimately benefitting the entire nation. As the journey of women in entrepreneurship continues to unfold, these initiatives pave the way for a brighter, more equitable future for Kazakhstan's economy and society as a whole.

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İqtisadiyyatının qeyri – neft sektorunun inkişafına işğaldan azad olunmuş ərazilərin təsiri

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Açar sözlər: Qeyri-neft sektoru, yeni texnologiyalar, ağıllı kənd, alternativ enerji, gənc mütəxəssislər, yerli kadrlar, aqrar +sahə, azad olunmuş ərazilər.

Son zamanlar Azərbaycanda neft və qaz sahələrinin yenidən canlanmasına, yeni uğurlar gətirməsinə baxmayaraq, qeyri neft sektorunun – xüsusən də aqrar sahənin inkişaf etdirilməsi, Azərbaycan hökumətinin prioritet məsələ kimi diqqətindədir. Bu sahəyə əlverişli və münbit şərait yaratmaq, hər vasitə ilə onun inkişafına dəstək olmaq son vaxtlar xüsusi ilə önə çəkilmişdir. Aqrar sahənin dinamik inkişafı üçün, onun əhəmiyyətli sahələrinin – heyvandarlıq, quşçuluq, pambıqçılıq, ipəkçilik, üzümçülük və bir sıra başqa sahələrin inkişafı üçün dövlət proqramları, hüquqi aktlar qəbul olunmuş, güclü dövlət dəstəyi göstərilmişdir. Bütün bunlarla yanaşı aparılan məqsədyönlü işin istiqaməti ölkəmizin xammal təminatçısından, hazır məhsul istehsalçısına çevrilməsi qarşıya qoyulmuş mühüm vəzifələrdən biridir. Regionlarda yaradılan aqroparklar, iqtisadi zonalar bu istiqamətdə aparılan məqsədyönlü siyasətin bir hissəsidir. Lakin istehsal olunan kənd təsərrüfatı məhsullarının emal olunması, müasir standartlara cavab verən, əhəlinin maddi və mənəvi tələbatını ödəyən, dünya standartlarına uyğun hazır məhsul istehsalının qurulması, dövlətimiz tərəfindən qoyulan prioritet məsələlərdən biridir. Bunun üçün müasir avadanlıqların, texnologiyaların gətirilməsi, qurulması, işə salınması, idarəetmənin, iqtisadiyyatın, texnologiyanın tələblərinə cavab verə bilən yüksək səviyyəli mütəxəssis hazırlanması ali və peşə təhsili sahəsində fəaliyyət göstərən təhsil ocaqlarının da üzərinə böyük məsuliyyət qoyur. Bu günün tələbi təkəcə xammal bazasını yaratmaq, emal – istehsal sahəsini qurmaq, keyfiyyətli məhsul ərsəyə gətirmək yox, eyni zamanda dünya standartlarına cavab verən, təhlükəsiz, təbii (orqanik) məhsul istehsalını tələb olunan bazar rəqabətinə uyğun qurmaq, ixrac gücünü artırmaq, ölkənin valyuta ehtiyatlarını və əhəlinin rifah səviyyəsini qaldırmaqdır.

Azərbaycan iqtisadiyyatında aqrar sektorun öz yeri olması hər kəsə məlumdur. Ötən əsrlərdə Bakıda neft bumunun yaratdığı xarüqələrə baxmayaraq, aqrar sektor Azərbaycanın digər regionlarında yenə də öndə qalmaqda davam etmişdir. Bu sahə insanların gündəlik tələbatını ödəməklə yanaşı iqtisadiyyatın inkişafına, insanların sosial durumuna təsirini qoruyub saxlamışdır.

Azərbaycanın neft, qeyri – neft, sənaye, tikinti – quruculuq sahələrindəki uğurlarına, müzəffər Ali Baş Komandanımızın rəhbərliyi altında igid, qəhrəman oğullarımızın 44 günlük Vətən müharibəsində 30 il işğalda qalmış torpaqlarımızın azad edilməsi ilə başa çatan zəfər qələbəmiz də əlavə olundu. Bundan başqa son antiterror əməliyyatı nəticəsində vətənimiz bütövlüyünü təmin etdi. Artıq ölkəmizdə seperaqtçı quldurların qoyduqları mina və dağıntı izlərini aradan qaldırmağa və soydaşlarımızı yenidən öz doğma yurdlarına qaytarmaq üçün quruculuq işlərini sürətləndirmək ön plana gəldi. 20 faizdən çox torpaqlarımızın işğal altında olması, qədim şəhərlərimizin, kəndlərimizin məhv edilməsi, bərəkətli torpaqlarımızın ölüm saçan partladıcılarla “əkilməsi” dayandırıldı. Azad olan torpaqlarımızda ən müasir və təhlükəsiz texnologiyalar, mütərəqqi layihələrinin tətbiq olunması, ölkəmizin iqtisadiyyatının daha da yüksəlməsinə və daha sürətli inkişafına təkan verəcəkdir. Bu gün bərəkətli Qarabağımızın maddi və mənəvi nemətlərinin doğma Azərbaycanımız adından dünyaya tanıtılması və təqdim edilməsi işləri tam sürətlə gedir. Bir çox

ölkələr üçün arzu, xəyal kimi qalan layihələr, azad olunmuş ərazilərimizdə tətbiq olunacaq. Bu istiqamətdə işlərin tam sürətlə aparılması, bizə iqtisadiyyatımızın renesans dövrünü yaşadacaq, bu torpaqların əsil sahiblərinin tezliklə öz doğma yurdlarına sahib çıxmağa və dünyaya səs salmağa imkan yaradacaqdır.

Bu günün tələbi olan ekoloji məhsul istehsalı, nanotexnologiyalar, ağıllı kəndlər, təbii və bərpa olunan enerji mənbələri, elektron idarəetmə, tullantısız, ətraf mühitə zərər verməyən texnologiyaların tətbiqi, Qarabağımızın yaralarını sağaltmaqla bərabər, onun ekosistemini qurmağa, təbiətinə vurulan yaraları sağaltmağa, iqtisadiyyatını daha müasir və mütərəqqi yolla qurmağa, bu gün Azərbaycanımızın uğurlarını izləyən dünya ictimaiyyətinə əyani göstərəcəkdir.

Son 10 – 15 ildə Azərbaycanda qurulan yeni istehsal sahələri, tətbiq olunan müasir texnologiyalar, yeni biliklərə yiyələnmiş gənc mütəxəssislərimiz, innovativ yanaşmalar doğma diyarımızı öndə gedən ölkələr sırasına çıxarmışdır. Bu gün xammal kimi satılan məhsullarımızın çox hissəsi hazır məhsul kimi ixrac olunur. Qəbul olunan və icra edilən qərarların düzgünlüyü, mütəxəssislərimiz tərəfindən lazım olan məlumatların ardıcıl və planlı toplanmasından, onun düzgün analiz olunmasından və dünya iqtisadiyyatının inkişaf tendensiyasından lazımı nəticə çıxarılmasından asılıdır.

Nəticə olaraq iqtisadiyyatımızın daha sürətli və davamlı inkişafı üçün bir neçə istiqamətdə tövsiyyə göstərə bilərik:

- Aqrar sahədə xammal tədarükünü emal istiqamətində yönləndirilməsinə üstünlük verilsin;
- Müvafiq qurumlar iqtisadiyyatın yüksəldilməsində daha vacib və müasir istiqamətləri təyin edib, bu sahəyə diqqət artırsın;
- Maraqlı dairəsi uyğun olan qurumların qarşılıqlı əlaqələrinin koordinasiyasının effektiv forması tapılsın və inkişaf istiqamətdə tətbiq edilsin;
- İşğaldan azad olunmuş ərazilərin turizm potensialının yüksəldilməsinə diqqət artırılmalı;
- Ekoloji turizmin inkişafı diqqət mərkəzində saxlansın;
- Kadr potensialının yaradılmasına və təkmilləşdirilməsinə ayrılan imkan artırılmalı;
- Yerli mütəxəssislərin inkişaf etmiş ölkələrdə təcrübə toplamasına imkan və şərait yaradılsın;

Summary:

Despite the revival of the oil and gas sector in Azerbaijan, which has brought new successes, the development of the non-oil sector - especially the agricultural sector - is a priority for the Azerbaijani government. For the dynamic development of the agrarian sector, for the development of its traditional areas, state programs, legal acts have been adopted, strong state support has been provided. Today's demand is not only to create a raw material base, to build a processing plant, to produce quality products, but also to produce safe, natural (organic) products that meet world standards in accordance with the required market competition, increase export capacity, foreign exchange reserves and to raise the level of welfare of the population.

Our recommendations:

- In the agricultural sector, preference should be given to the supply of raw materials for processing;
- Relevant agencies should identify the main and important directions in the development of the economy and pay more attention to this area;
- To find an effective form of coordination of interaction between the institutions of interest and apply it in the direction of development;
- Attention should be paid to increasing the tourism potential of territories freed from occupation;
- Focus on the development of ecological tourism;
- Create all opportunities for the creation and improvement of human resources;

- Create conditions for local specialists to gain experience in developed countries

Резюме:

Несмотря на возрождение нефтегазового сектора в Азербайджане, принесшее новые успехи, развитие не нефтяного сектора, особенно сельскохозяйственного, является приоритетом для правительства Азербайджана. Для динамичного развития аграрного сектора, для развития его традиционных направлений приняты государственные программы, нормативно-правовые акты, оказана мощная государственная поддержка. Сегодняшняя потребность заключается не только в создании сырьевой базы, строительстве перерабатывающего завода, выпуске качественной продукции, но и в производстве безопасной, натуральной (органической) продукции, отвечающей мировым стандартам в соответствии с необходимой рыночной конкуренцией, увеличении экспортных мощностей, золотовалютных резервов и повысить уровень благосостояния населения.

Наши рекомендации:

- В аграрном секторе предпочтение следует отдавать поставке сырья для переработки;
- Соответствующие органы должны определить основные и важные направления в развитии экономики и уделить этому направлению больше внимания;
- найти эффективную форму координации взаимодействия между интересующими институтами и применить ее в направлении развития;
- создать все возможности для создания и совершенствования человеческих ресурсов;
- Создать условия для получения местными специалистами опыта работы в развитых странах

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Structure and principles of formation of the food supply system

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Abstract. This article delves into the food supply system, a complex and multifaceted structure that ensures the availability, quality, and safety of food for the population. The author describes various components of the food supply system, including government authorities, producers, processors, consumers, and other stakeholders. The article underscores the importance of coordinating the efforts of all participants to ensure food security and sustainable development.

Key words: food supply system, food security, food consumers, agriculture.

In economics, food encompasses food products, edible supplies, and food items that are naturally occurring on the planet or produced through the utilization of natural or artificial fertility of the land, marine resources, and other aquatic basins. Production takes place within both the agricultural sector of the economy and laboratories involved in the development of genetically modified organisms, where it is synthesized using biochemical technologies. The procurement of food constitutes an ongoing process of producing raw biologically derived products that are subject to processing or long-term storage. The provision of food to a country's population can be achieved through self-sufficiency in food production and through imports, provided there are financial resources and no external sanctions.

Food provision requires consideration of the following factors: maintaining equilibrium over an extended period among agricultural production, supply, and consumption, as well as the quality of agricultural products before and after processing. An economic state in which each individual citizen and the population as a whole are guaranteed access to food products, drinking water, and other food items in quantities, assortments, and qualities that are necessary and sufficient for the physical and social development of individuals, the preservation of health, and the expanded reproduction of the country's population, indicates that the country has achieved food security. It is considered that a country is in a state of food security when it produces at least 80% of its essential food products domestically [1]. However, if the import of a particular type of product reaches 20% of domestic production levels, this may indicate stagnation in the domestic production, and if imports account for 60%, the production of that commodity may cease [2].

There are several approaches to understanding food supply. One approach equates food supply with food security, while another considers food supply as one of the issues in the development of the agro-industrial complex (AIC). A third approach involves organizing food markets to provide the population with food products [3]. However, the concept of food supply as an economic category is not fully elucidated. There is no universally accepted definition of the term "food security." In scientific literature, besides the concept of "food security," terms such as "food independence" [4; 5], "food self-sufficiency" [6; 7] are encountered. Issues related to food supply encompass problems such as the disparity between actual dietary patterns and scientifically based medical norms, consumer demand for food products that goes unmet, and the instability in the supply of food to the population [8].

According to M.M. Tryastin, food supply is defined as "the sustainable process of satisfying the population's nutritional needs within scientifically based medical standards, taking into account their gender and age groups, and their purchasing power, based on the more efficient

use of resources within the food subcomplex and the implementation of a competitive wholesale-retail food distribution system that optimizes the distribution of regional and imported food in major cities, industrial centers, and specific territorial entities. It also ensures its availability at prices affordable to the majority of the population, with an optimal share of imports" [9].

A.I. Altukhov, G.I. Makin, and M.A. Bobkov define "food supply" as "an organizational and economic system that, at the current stage, materializes the potential of food security based on the organization of a product distribution network that deals with promoting domestic and imported food from producer to consumer. It also involves organizational and economic relationships established among the participants in this process." They further describe it as "the sustainable provision of food to all layers of the country's population in the necessary quantity, assortment, and quality, which is resilient to negative internal and external influences and hazards" [10].

Therefore, food supply can be considered both as a process and a system. Food supply as a process consists of a complex set of interconnected functional activities within the framework of social production, aimed at creating food products and services for consumers. On the other hand, when viewed as a system, it is seen as a specialized structure within the broader system of production relations. Like any system, the food supply system consists of specific elements that are related to and interact with each other, forming a unified whole, and their interaction generates new qualities not inherent to each of them individually.

Each subsystem comprises specific elements linked by various relationships based on the following principles [11]:

1) functional: where the operation of subsystems is directed toward achieving the primary goal of the system, which is the provision of food to the population.

2) hierarchy: which involves a certain subordination of the subsystem to achieve the primary goal of the system.

3) technological: wherein subsystems establish the necessary means of communication to achieve their objectives.

4) resource-based: where subsystems provide quantitative and qualitative characteristics to the entire system.

5) organizational: where independent structures of various scales and forms are the leading economic entities, and their interaction requires appropriate organization to achieve the goal.

Given the diverse interpretations of the essence of food supply, researchers have different understandings and positions regarding the definition of the essence, structure, and development factors of the food supply system. Among researchers, the term is also used to refer to the food system [12, 13].

According to I.A. Kolesnyak, the food supply system is "a relatively autonomous structured system whose goal is the reliable (uninterrupted) and sufficient (according to medical standards) provision of the population with food".

M.M. Nuyanzina defines the food supply system as "an aggregate of closely interacting scientific, production, distribution, and management structures, mechanisms, and decision-making measures aimed at consistently satisfying the solvency-driven demand of the population for food (in terms of quantity and corresponding variety) and meeting the needs for creating food reserves that facilitate the realization of planned objectives without disruptions or violations of normative standards".

G.S. Bondareva formulates it as a system "of interaction among producers, sellers, consumers, and government authorities, ensuring the population's needs for quality food products based on scientifically justified standards. It is grounded in responsibility toward the

population, promoting the economic and physical accessibility of food under stable conditions and during emergencies".

A.B. Moldashev and G.A. Nikitina regard it as "one of the primary system-forming elements of the economy, with its main tasks being to meet the population's food needs, to provide the processing industry with raw materials, and to perform coordinating and supervisory functions for the development of the agro-industrial complex. It involves the integration of various elements (segments) of the economy, affecting production and consumption levels through the mechanism of price and income changes." According to their perspective, it is a "complex system necessary for the continuous quantitative and qualitative provision of society with food".

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the food supply system encompasses the entire spectrum of entities and their interconnected activities related to adding value associated with the production, aggregation, processing, distribution, consumption, and disposal of food products derived from agriculture, forestry, or fisheries. It consists of various subsystems such as the agricultural system, waste management system, resource input system, and interacts with other key systems like the energy system, trade system, healthcare system, and more [16].

The food supply system can be classified based on two criteria [17, 18]:

- 1) by the level of organization:
 - individual (individuals);
 - local (households);
 - municipal (cities, districts, municipalities, free economic zones, biosphere territories);
 - territorial (regions);
 - regional (two or more regions);
 - national (countries);
- 2) by the type of food:
 - cereal-based (wheat, rice, grains);
 - potato-based;
 - fruits and vegetables;
 - oil and fat-based;
 - dairy;
 - meat.

As a result, among researchers, there are differing opinions not only about the definition of the system but also about the structure of its constituent elements, including the outcome, functional-objective, and supporting subsystems (see Table 1).

Table 1 - Structure of the Food Supply System

№	Authors	The main element/component/subsystem
1	R.R. Gumerov	1) Domestic production of agricultural products, raw materials, and food. 2) Foreign trade in the corresponding products.
2	A.V. Gordeev	1) Subsystem of Food Consumption and Population Nutrition. 2) Subsystem of Food Production. 3) Subsystem of Food Resource Formation and Distribution.
3	N.V. Litvinenko	1) Subsystem of Agricultural Production. 2) Subsystem of Food Resource Formation and Distribution. 3) Subsystem of Food Consumption.

		4) Subsystem for Creating Conditions for the Formation of the Food Economy.
4	A.A. Kolesnyak	1) Agricultural Production Subsystem. 2) Food Resource Formation Subsystem. 3) Food Resource Distribution Subsystem. 4) Food Consumption Subsystem. 5) Subsystem for Creating Conditions for the Formation of a Food Economy.
5	A.A. Kolesnyak, T.V. Polozova	1) Food Needs Assessment Subsystem. 2) Food Reserve Formation Subsystem. 3) Food Production Subsystem. 4) Food Resource Distribution Subsystem. 5) Consumption Subsystem. 6) Food Supply Management Subsystem.
6	I.A. Kolesnyak	1) Food demand assessment. 2) Formation of food reserves. 3) Agricultural production. 4) Processing agricultural raw materials into food products. 5) Food resource distribution. 6) Marketing and distribution. 7) Food consumption. 8) Food supply chain management.
7	O.A. Mirgorodskaya, G.A. Narozhnaya	1) Agribusiness Subsystem (personal subsistence farms, medium and large agricultural enterprises, peasant (farm) households, processing facilities). 2) Sales and Distribution Subsystem. 3) Food Import Subsystem. 4) Food Reserve Subsystem. 5) Consumption Subsystem. 6) Financial Support Subsystem. 7) Information Support Subsystem. 8) Material and Technical Supply Subsystem. 9) Human Resources Subsystem. 10) Research and Development Subsystem.
8	M.M. Nuyanzina	1) Production of food resources. 2) Exchange and distribution of food resources. 3) Direction towards the consumption of food resources. 4) Organizational and legal regulation.
9	A.B. Moldashev, G.A. Nikitina	Agriculture. Processing Industry. Trade. Infrastructure elements that support the movement of products from producers to consumers.
10	I.A. Ryabova	1) Technico-technological subsystem. 2) Socio-economic subsystem. 3) Organizational-legal subsystem. 4) Functional-industry subsystem.
Note: Compiled based on sources [19, 20, 21, 22, 23]		

The subjects of the food supply system include all its participants: government and regulatory bodies, agricultural producers, food raw material processors, consumers, intermediaries responsible for storage, transportation, and the sale of products [24]. Each participant in the system has specific functions:

- Government and regulatory bodies play a central role in setting food policy and regulating the food sector. This includes developing legislation, establishing food safety standards, supporting the agricultural sector, and ensuring food security.

- Agricultural producers play a crucial role in growing raw materials for the production of food products such as grains, vegetables, fruits, meat, and dairy products. Additionally, they may employ sustainable farming methods to protect the environment.

- Food raw material processors transform raw materials into safe, functional food products that align with consumer preferences. This includes both primary and secondary food processing.

- Consumers play a key role in shaping the demand for food products and influence food production and distribution.

- Intermediaries perform essential functions in providing storage, transportation, and the sale of products. These intermediaries can include wholesalers, distributors, importers, or brokers. They take on risks, provide financial support, organize sales, and manage complex relationships with buyers, distributors, and other stakeholders.

Based on the information presented, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The food supply system is a complex organizational and economic system that includes various levels, subsystems, and participants working with the production, distribution, and consumption of food products.

2. The goal of the food supply system is to ensure uninterrupted and sufficient provision of the population with food products that meet scientifically based consumer standards.

3. The food supply system includes various subsystems such as determining food needs, creating food reserves, resource allocation for food, consumption, and food management.

4. The roles of entities within the food supply system encompass government authorities, agricultural producers, processors, consumers, and other participants who facilitate the processes of production, distribution, and consumption of food products.

5. Maintaining a balance between food production, supply, and consumption, as well as ensuring food quality, are important aspects of food supply.

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DIGITALIZATION OF THE ECONOMY IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Annotation. The digitalization of the economy is one of the main tasks of the state and the company, and the transition to the development of digitalization makes it possible to increase competitiveness in international markets. The article addressed a vital issue in using the digital economy in the Republic of Kazakhstan, which explores the progress of use, what is needed and where there are opportunities to use this tool. It was also concluded that the digitalization of the economy is an exemplary aspect of development. Analyzing the information on the introduction of the latest technologies in the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, one can notice a lag in comparison with such states as the USA and European countries.

Keywords: digital economy, information and communication technologies, digitalization, optimization.

Nowadays, digitalization is a hot topic not only for Kazakhstan but also for other countries.

As you know, the Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 827, dated December 12, 2017, approved the State Program "Digital Kazakhstan." The Ministry of Information and Communication of the Republic of Kazakhstan developed the program. [3] This program was aimed at accelerating the development of the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, and improving the population's quality of life was a priority. In addition, it can be noted that one of the objectives of the program was to create a digital economy for the future of the country. The implementation period of the program was scheduled for 2018-2023.

Analyzing the current situation, global economic crises pose new challenges and lead the state to participate in ensuring the necessary social protection of the population. [2, p. 45]

The introduction of digitalization into the economy has led to such side effects as the unpreparedness of the population and businesses for risks. However, the digital revolution has led Kazakhstan to include digitalization as a public policy in its development plans.

In the world ranking of the development of information and communication technology (after this referred to as ICT), in 2023, Kazakhstan rose to 30th place compared to 2016, when it ranked 52d in the ranking. In the future, the Republic of Kazakhstan plans to increase from the 30th place to the 25th in 2025 and the 15th line in the ICT development ratings in 2050.

From the point of view of the current level of development of digitalization of the economy, Kazakhstan is a catching-up country in the e-intensity rating of the international company The Boston Consulting Group. [1, p. 13]

Digital transformation in industries is changing the way different sectors of the economy are.

The digitalization of the sectoral economy by the third quarter of 2023 has reached the following achievements:

1. Developed local e-commerce.
2. Reducing the share of the shadow economy.

3. Competitive export production in priority sectors.

The unsuccessful implementation of this direction by the third quarter of 2023 amounted to the following:

1. Increasing the level of labor productivity.

The dynamics of labor productivity have been lagging for the third year in a row. In other words, unemployment in Kazakhstan has grown, and such an imbalance makes it possible for prices to rise, causing inflation in the country.

The introduction of digital technology has the impetus to the development of traditional primary industries by generating productivity growth and increasing competitiveness in the international market. Thus, the digitalization of the economy will increase domestic exports to foreign markets, increasing the capitalization of the largest manufacturing companies.

To achieve the goals set by the program in the field of personnel qualification, the education system is being updated following the best world practices. New education should meet the needs of the digital economy, first of all, for skills in analyzing information and developing creative thinking rather than memorizing facts and formulas.

Increasing digital literacy occurs in secondary, technical, vocational, and higher education.

In secondary education, to develop creative and critical thinking among the younger generation, the subject "Fundamentals of Programming" was gradually introduced, starting from the second grade of education.

To bring industry and education closer together, representatives of enterprises are involved in the educational process of the country's universities at the expense of extrabudgetary funds.

In retraining personnel, local executive bodies conduct training and retraining of the population, including the unemployed, in demanded digital skills. Also, this event gradually covers representatives of small and medium-sized businesses.

To expand educational opportunities for everyone who wants to get the necessary skills, a national platform for open education, "enbek skills," was created, which makes it possible to provide online courses.

At the same time, enterprises conduct corporate training for specialists, strengthening the communication and technical skills of the profession.

Generally, the program opens up new opportunities for strengthening the interaction between educational institutions and entrepreneurs to train competitive specialists.

The implementation of digital initiatives has become an essential link for the country's further economic growth. The program has significant economic potential, which will allow achieving the country's GDP growth rates in the future.

In conclusion, digitalization provides a stage in the development of society, and production, based on the global systems of financial, economic, credit, and monetary relations and the infrastructure of the scientific and technological revolution. Digitalization impacts all sectors and should lead to a change in the economy's structure in the Republic of Kazakhstan and other countries. The degree of influence of digital technologies in different industries in different countries is not uniform. For example, in Kazakhstan, a tremendous potential for digitalization is made within traditional sectors of the economy.

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Pedagogical Sciences

THE TRAINING AND LITERATURE OF COMPUTER USE IN EDUCATION. THE POSSIBILITIES OF USING IT IN TEACHING

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Using a computer in training essentially serves to visualize the training material. Prominent educators have considered visibility as one of the main principles in teaching. The popular saying "It is better to see a hundred than to hear a hundred" also shows that it is one of the main methods of learning and understanding. This conclusion, which people have come to from their life experience for centuries, is based on the pedagogical principle, which should be followed and kept in the focus of training.

The great pedagogue Y.A.Komensky rightly called visibility the "golden rule" in education. He writes: "...let it be a golden rule for teachers to present everything possible to perception with the senses, that is, to present what is visible to the sense of sight, what has taste to the sense of taste, and what can be touched to the sense of taste. If everything can be perceived by several senses at once, let it be perceived by several senses at the same time.

As it can be seen, Y.A.Komensky with this interpretation opens the mechanism of assimilation and understanding of learning materials, considers it appropriate to transfer the presented object and event to the cognitive process through the sensory organs. Even if it is possible to use several sense organs at the same time during training, when they are used, the training material is better absorbed by the students and is not forgotten for a long time.

Y.A.Komensky's opinion about the importance of visualization in education is appreciated and developed by other classical educators. From this point of view, the views of the great Russian pedagogue K.D.Ushinsky are also interesting and are still important from a pedagogical and methodological point of view. He writes: "The child thinks in forms, colors, sounds, and in general, feelings, and he who tries to make the child think otherwise is forcing his nature in vain and to his detriment."

K.D.Ushinsky, continuing his opinion about the importance of visibility in training, says: "The nature of the child requires clear visualization. Try to teach him 5 unknown words, he will suffer for a long time and in vain, but associate 20 such words with pictures and the child will memorize them very easily. You explain a simple idea to a child, he does not understand you; explain a complex picture to that child, he understands you very quickly".

As it can be seen, well-known pedagogues who worked in the field of educational theory and performed remarkable scientific activities in different periods attached great importance to visibility in training. This means that the attitude to visibility has never been subjective, the serious and very useful Principle of training has been interpreted as a necessary principle. Over time, the essence and mechanism of the principle of visualization in training are interpreted by pedagogues and psychologists in a more fundamental way from a scientific point of view. In recent years, the book "Pedagogy" by A.K.Pashayev and F.A.Rustamov, published under the name "New Course" and used as a resource, states:

"The history of the principle of visuality is ancient. He plans to base his teaching on things and events directly perceived in connection with the child, rather than concrete abstract words. The study of the laws underlying it affects recent times. Laws are based on this principle:

- 1) a person's sensitivity to external stimuli appears sharply;
- 2) the communication channels of the central communication channels of receptors should not transmit information: optical communication channel - 1.6×10 bits/second; acoustic link - 0.32×10^6 bits/sec. The organs of vision see more than what they see, they report hearing information 13 times more visible;
- 3) The information received by the control organs of the brain (optic channel) leaves an easy, quick and strong imprint on the memory".

Of course, the numerical expression of information about sensory data appears as a result of a serious psychological experiment.

It is known from the history of the school, the training experience, and the dynamics of the development of the teaching of individual subjects that in the principal periods, during the training, based on the visual basis, various tools were used - herbarium, material of one or other items, one or another type of technical equipment - shaft inscriptions, magnetized tape recordings, epidiastroscope, diafilms are used.

Of course, each of them has played a more or less important role as a technical training tool that increases efficiency in training for a certain period, but at the current level of development of life, science and technology, in the conditions of strong information flow, none of them has the opportunity to create an effect in training. is not. In this respect, the computer has, in the true sense of the word, unmatched power and capabilities.

The computer is, so to speak, the ultimate technical achievement for now. As for its role and importance in training, it combines the possibilities of all of the above-mentioned tools, it is an indispensable tool in terms of providing a lot of information in a short time and creating originality. Approaching it from the perspective of usefulness in training, based on school experience, at least the following can be said:

- 1) the computer mode in the lesson, due to the technology of use, arouses the interest of students, separates their attention from external objects (irritations) and directs them to the topic presented as educational material;
- 2) the computer has the ability to display the content of the presented object (topic) almost in detail;
- 3) when using a computer in the learning process, it is possible to provide relatively more information about the subject (of course, in the amount that students can understand, and also by saving time);
- 4) the computer has the ability to properly combine movement with words, which facilitates learning material;
- 5) using a computer in class consolidates the learning material in the memory and accelerates the subsequent recall;
- 6) the use of different colors in accordance with the content of educational material on the computer has a very positive effect on the feelings of students, which gives a strong impetus to the development of their aesthetic education;
- 7) using a computer in the classroom provides the necessary opportunity for interactive training;
- 8) using a computer creates conditions for students to think about the topic, analyze individual details and freely express their opinions and make generalizations;
- 9) using a computer in class encourages students to work outside the classroom;
- 10) the use of the computer creates activity in the lesson, as it allows applying various methods and principles according to the content of the educational material.

Of course, all this is related to the importance of using computers in training. However, it should not be overlooked that each subject has specific characteristics. When using a computer, the specifics of the subject cannot be overlooked. Above all, the above-mentioned benefits of computers for teaching are equally useful for literature classes as a whole. There is no need to repeat them, and the above-mentioned should be kept in focus in literature classes. Moreover, the specific characteristics of literature increase and actualize the importance of computer use.

Literature reflects life events and social relations with artistic images. The main object of literature is life, it studies natural phenomena and social life, and informs about it with literary and artistic colors. From this point of view, the difference between literature and other fields of science cannot be overlooked, and the difference is in their form of reflection. Since literature reflects life events in words and figuratively, it requires a different approach to the use of computers in the classroom - it focuses on conveying the essence of the figurative word to the students.

It must be admitted that there is a certain complexity in revealing the essence of the image, which is also observed in the school experience. Opening imagery in a work of art in the right way requires the teacher's sensitivity, in-depth knowledge of art and the ability to use the computer to open it. In other words, the work of using the computer in the literature lesson does not end with showing the image of any artistic image (copy), if this is the case, the lesson will turn into fun, a toy, and will not have a significant impact on the students' literary knowledge. The use of the computer should be aimed at making the students feel the artistic effect of the word.

It is known that there are other types of art that reflect life events: painting, sculpture, music, architecture. These, including literature, are called art forms. Imagery is a common feature among the art forms shown, but there is also a certain difference between them. Among them, it is necessary to determine the position of literature and bring it to the attention of students, to provide rich material for them, and to include it in the literary knowledge of schoolchildren. In providing this important theoretical knowledge - in explaining the relationship between art forms, the use of the computer is of great importance. Artists working in other fields of art (painter, sculptor, musicologist) use literature when creating beautiful works of art, choose a certain episode, story told in the work of art as a topic, and express the idea of the writer with certain colors and artistic strokes. School experience proves the usefulness of using a computer in visually explaining and mastering the relationship between art types. It is very useful to use the computer to show certain examples of art (a work of art, a painting, a photograph of a statue, etc.), to read the color or line, if possible, and to create a connection between color and line with words.

It is known that at one time illustrations (pictures) were drawn based on the content of M.A. Sabir's works (the author of the pictures is the famous artist Azim Azimzadeh). As an example, it is very interesting to compare the picture taken in relation to the content of the poem "Goyma geldi" with the lyrical content given in the work, and it helps to understand, understand, and remember the content later. Since it is necessary to review the content of the poem as a whole, the following text of the poem, pre-compiled in the MS Word computer program, is displayed and a characteristic aspect of the type is conveyed to the student in each verse of the poem.

From the content of the poem, it is clear that a married person said, "Amandi, don't leave!" - he cries. The question arises: What is this cry for? What does the poet want to say? From the history and analysis of the creation of the work, it is clear that M.A. Sabir dedicated this satire to events that happened in real life and satirized those events. The explanation given about the date of creation of the poem says: It was first published in "Molla Nasreddin" journal (August 18, 1908 No. 33).

THE ROLE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL REFORMS IN TEACHING SPEECH CULTURE

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After gaining independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan started reconstruction and improvement of national resources in all areas. In the economy, social and political life, as well as in the mass cultural sphere, the work of innovation in science and education began to take a large scale. As the new development prospects in the country were integrated into the international world, relations with the international world began to develop in the field of education. The goal was to remove the narrow framework of Azerbaijani education and bring it closer to international standards. The old education system could no longer keep up with the developments in the world. Therefore, the development and implementation of new standards for achieving new successes in education became the need of the hour.

For this purpose, on March 30, 1998, the State Commission for the preparation of the Reform Program in the field of education was established by the Decree of the President of the country. In the "Introduction" part of the newly developed Education Reform Program of the President's Order No. 168 dated June 15, 1999, it is stated that "The formation of science and culture, which are important factors of the progress of the society, and the intellectual potential of the people is provided by its education system.

As an ancient civilization and a center of culture, Azerbaijan has formed its education system in the very ancient layers of history. Today, our country has a widely diversified education system, an excellent network of higher, secondary and secondary education, which provides the basis for passing on science, knowledge, and experience from generation to generation. Progressing through the difficult paths of independence, Azerbaijan faced the need to fulfill great tasks in the field of education as well as in all fields. It is an objective demand to implement important changes and innovations in the field of education within the framework of the broad reform movement that has started in our country.

The Reform Program also mentions the achievements of the Soviet era education system and mentions such an important issue that, firstly, education at that time lacked national qualities, and secondly, educational standards could not be integrated into the international world. It is shown here that "during the years of Soviet rule, the development of education in Azerbaijan was carried out in a centralized manner in accordance with the spirit and requirements of the educational strategy adopted in the Soviet Union as a whole. It was, of course, impossible to deviate from the established strategy and develop an educational concept that meets national characteristics in a society guided by administrative emirate management methods.

Modernization of education on national roots, democratization, creation of humanistic principles between educators and students are of special importance in the New Program. This also creates a fertile environment for better mastering of subjects, and at the same time for developing the creativity of students. The goal is that the society will be renewed, scientific discoveries and inventions will be donated from Azerbaijan to the world civilization. 2.2 of the program.

It is stated in this regard: "The reform of the content of general and professional-specialized education is the basis of the development of the education system, and as a result, by expressing its essence and importance, to consistently eliminate the character of unification in the education system, to ensure the democratization, humanization, and humanitarianization of

education, the creative opportunities of pedagogical workers means creating conditions for its realization. For this purpose, a new system of state standards of education should be created and a national education program should be developed that ensures the comprehensive development of an individual's personality.

Article 2.4, which is related to information, teaching and scientific-methodical provision of the education system, also takes into account that for the reconstruction of the content of education and training, curricula covering all levels of education, based on national traditions and universal values, in accordance with state educational standards, it has become a vital necessity to create programs and teaching aids as well as other scientific-methodical teaching literature complexes and provide the education system with them.

One of the most important issues set forth in the State Program of New Education Reforms is the basing of education on national resources, national thinking, and the ideology of national Azerbaijanism. Here, of course, applying innovations to subjects related to the mother tongue, especially speech culture, as well as other subjects related to national thought, is one of the main demands of the day. The teaching and mastering of the native language and its norms of speech culture is the basis for the correct, correct, and unhindered introduction of scientific innovations, discoveries and inventions achieved on the national level to the international world and the labor market in the native language.

At the current stage, when the integration of Azerbaijani education into world education standards is strengthening, appropriate innovations in teaching technologies should be applied. As a successful result of integration into the world education system, the introduction of innovation in national education becomes a constant demand. Important and urgent issues related to this demand are reflected in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on "Approving the State Program for Reforms in the Higher Education System of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2009-2013" signed on May 22, 2009.

In the "Introduction" part of the order, it is said that "The successful future of every country in the modern world is determined by the level of education in that country. Experience shows that the abundance of natural resources is not the main indicator of the state's development, but the main thing is to ensure the transformation of these resources into human capital, which is the driving force of society. The role of education is increasing at a time when the competition in the fields of socio-economic activities in the information society is intensifying, as well as the natural resources are gradually being depleted.

The education development strategy stimulates the improvement of the knowledge and skill qualities of national personnel, requires the historically acquired experience, achievements in separate scientific fields to be raised to the level of discoveries. It is known that throughout the centuries geniuses of thought such as Nizami Ganjavi, Izzeddin Hasanoglu, Imadaddin Nasimi, Mohammad Fuzuli, Molla Panah Vagif have grown and enriched human thought in the humanitarian field. Undoubtedly, the presence of feelings about natural sciences in their humanitarian thoughts is also undeniable.

However, it is necessary to admit that those sensations were not of a human nature, like the discovery of elements, like the discovery of electricity. In the modern era, the educational strategy of Azerbaijan is already being formed at such a level that it does not rule out looking with the hope that the intellects growing up in this country will bring innovation to the science of humanity. Like all scientific fields, of course, there is no doubt that innovations in the speech culture of the mother tongue will be integrated into world science.

As Elchin Sardarov, an employee of the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, said, "In the education development strategy, the importance of training qualified pedagogical personnel, increasing their knowledge and skills through scientists, as well as stimulating the professional and innovative activity of educators and teachers has been emphasized. In the

education system, it is intended to train high-profile teachers who effectively provide the content of education through innovative teaching methods, who know and apply new systems and other important tools that ensure the regular development of the individual skills of the students, the professional level of the students.

In the "State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan" approved by Order No. 13 of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated October 24, 2013, it is stated that "the institutional foundations of the education system for the purpose of providing a person with comprehensive knowledge and skills in accordance with the development concept of the Republic of Azerbaijan, infrastructure and human resources should be developed. The development of education lays the foundation for improving the welfare of the population in the country, as well as building a higher level of the individual's life.

The state strategy envisages large-scale measures in five strategic directions for the creation of an educational system with an infrastructure based on advanced technologies. These are the following:

The first strategic direction focuses on the creation of competency-based, personality-oriented educational content and includes the important goal of developing curricula at all levels of education, including pre-school, general, first vocational-specialization, secondary specialization and higher education.

The second strategic direction involves the modernization of human resources in the field of education.

The third strategic direction envisages the creation of transparent and efficient management mechanisms responsible for the results in education.

The fourth strategic direction envisages the creation of an educational infrastructure that meets the requirements and provides lifelong education.

The fifth strategic direction is the establishment of a financing model of the educational system in the Republic of Azerbaijan that is economically stable and at the same level as the standards of the world's leading educational systems.

As it can be seen, the strategic importance of Azerbaijani education is highly appreciated by the state, and its realization and fruitfulness become a main goal. Achieving this goal is certainly not a simple matter. This is a global issue that cannot be contained in any administration. Solving such an important issue should not be considered as an individual issue. To solve this issue, which will have a great effect on the life of the society, it is required to educate the society itself morally and ideologically. The material, moral, social, social and economic resources of the independent Republic of Azerbaijan are sufficient to achieve these goals. It is absolutely possible to overcome all the upcoming obstacles by developing faith in the future, patriotism, initiative, and loyalty to national interests in people.

Heydar Aliyev and Azerbaijan Education

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Today, when we analytically analyze the historical services of Mr. Heydar Aliyev in the path of socio-economic and cultural development of Azerbaijan in the 30 years of time, and evaluate the work done from the point of view of national and state interest, we once again witness the rapid development of Azerbaijan in these years.

Due to the injustice of history, the people of Azerbaijan, separated from their national statehood and shackled to their national feeling, embarked on the path of socio-economic and cultural progress in those years. Heydar Aliyev's contributions to education, which is an irreplaceable means of national progress, science, culture and development of meaning, his services to the education of the people and the harmonious development of the education system are immeasurable.

The historical experience of world civilization shows that heads of state who value science and education not only ensure the economic and cultural progress of their countries, but also make a great contribution to culture. In this sense, the care and attention shown by the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev to the development of national education is distinguished by his uniqueness. Thus, the historical stage that began in 1969, when the venerable Heydar Aliyev came to power, is perceived as the development period of today's Azerbaijani science.

Heydar Aliyev's services in the field of education development in Azerbaijan went in two directions:

- Heydar Aliyev's theoretical instructions on national upbringing and education.
- Heydar Aliyev's works in the construction of national education, in the way of harmonious development of various fields of education.

The Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, speaking about the role of education in the development of society, says:

"How valuable this education system is can be seen from the fact that Azerbaijan has people with high education, knowledge, qualifications, and high science, and they make up the majority of the society. If they were not there, Azerbaijan's economy could not develop. Without them, we would not be able to manage Azerbaijan as an independent state. They need to be appreciated."

Great Leader Heydar Aliyev has always emphasized that education plays an indispensable role in national progress and independent state building. The concept of national education has not yet been developed in our country. However, the suggestions and ideas put forward in speeches, speeches and reports of Mr. Heydar Aliyev determine both the content and the ways of implementation of educational work.

He emphasized that education is an important area of every state, country, and society. The analysis of the historical development of Azerbaijani education over the past 30 years shows that our national education has gone through the following stages:

- Advances in the development of Azerbaijani education (1970-1982)
- Azerbaijan education 1982-1987 years
- Azerbaijani education during the years of depression (1988-1993)
- New era of educational construction in independent Azerbaijan

The rapid rise of Azerbaijani education in our national history, the first stage of the real renaissance coincides with the first period of Heydar Aliyev's leadership in Azerbaijan.

The second stage covers the years 1982-1987, when Mr. Heydar Aliyev worked in the supreme leadership of the former USSR. These were the years when, among other areas, Heydar Aliyev was in charge of the entire education system of the state. Even in those years, he would create conditions for the youth of Azerbaijan to study not only in Azerbaijan, but also outside the borders of Azerbaijan. He even often met with Azerbaijani students, was personally interested in their concerns and problems, and used all opportunities to solve them.

The third stage includes the most complex and crisis years of our modern education history (1988-1993), the years of recession and depression. At this stage, those in charge of Azerbaijani education could not correctly assess its role in society. In 1992, they adopted the "Law of Education" in an attempt to restructure education in a "revolutionary way".

The fourth stage covers the period when Heydar Aliyev started to build a new national education on the basis of educational reforms in accordance with world standards of independent Azerbaijan.

At the end of 1982, when Heydar Aliyev led the educational reforms of the former USSR, it led to certain qualitative changes in the development of general education.

One of the great contributions of the Honorable Heydar Aliyev to the development of education in Azerbaijan in the 1970s and 1980s, thanks to his initiative and care, was the establishment of the most famous universities of the former USSR outside Azerbaijan, covering more than 80 fields of national economy, science, education and culture of our Republic and the most It is the creation of opportunities and conditions for more than 15,000 young Azerbaijanis to receive higher education and training as highly qualified specialists in more than 250 specialties. Heydar Aliyev praised highly qualified specialists who studied outside of Azerbaijan in the 70s and 80s as "students of Azerbaijan, national wealth of Azerbaijan".

After Azerbaijan gained independence, a revival and renewal began to be noticed in the field of education, as in every field of our society. As a result of the great influence of our national leader, Heydar Aliyev, progress has been made, structural changes have taken place in secondary, secondary and higher schools, serious construction works have been carried out to strengthen the material and technical base of educational institutions, and the application of effective methods and methods for solving the problem has been put forward. Heydar Aliyev always said in his speech:

"Now Azerbaijan is an independent state. As an independent state of our republic, Azerbaijan, by creating and developing its own national concept of theology, without a doubt, the field of education should also be established on the basis of national goals and interests.

At the Congress of Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev expressed the attitude of the state to the field of education as follows:

"As an independent state, we build our own education system as we want. We use the progressive practices of all countries of the world. I believe that on the foundation created so far, Azerbaijan will further improve education and school."

Curriculum is one of the new terms and topics related to education discussed in Educational Issues and Teacher Training Institutes, and in the media. The meaning of this word has been sufficiently explained in the press. Curriculum is the preparation of programs, study plans, textbooks according to new standards, and the result, in other words, skills and actions are taken as the basis. In general, the services of the national leader Heydar Aliyev were not small in reaching the current level of education in Azerbaijan that meets the development trends of the world and international standards. We mentioned at the beginning that the renaissance period of Azerbaijani education, science and culture began on June 14, 1969. A wide network of general, technical-vocational, secondary, higher and additional educational institutions operating in our country, a strong scientific-pedagogical personnel corps has its source precisely from the far-sighted and purposeful policy in the field of education carried out under the leadership of Heydar

Aliyev in the 70s of the last century. The large-scale educational construction work has laid a strong foundation for future development.

Along with all this, he made several reforms in the education system. In 2003, the State Program for the construction of new general education schools, major renovation of existing schools and providing them with modern teaching equipment, the program for the development of the creative potential of children (youths) with special talents, and other related programs and their implementation are part of the work done in connection with the development of education.

After Azerbaijan became independent, Turkey was the first to recognize the state independence of our country. It has exceptional services in creating contemporary examples of the historical brotherhood of Azerbaijan and Turkey, and in the formation of a new type of education system in our country. After Azerbaijan became independent, 15 qualified specialists from Turkey were sent to Azerbaijan and created the current "Cag Oyratim Shirkti" which meets the standards of modern education. All this is part of the work that promotes the development of Azerbaijani education.

Innovative Methods for Teaching English: The Integrated Approach

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Annotation: This article investigates the dynamic landscape of English language instructing, shedding light on innovative instructional strategies. Centering on the integrated approach, the creator dives into strategies that consistently combine different features of dialect securing. The article not as it were explains the hypothetical underpinnings but too gives down to earth experiences into the execution of these techniques. With a basic examination of their viability and real-world applications, perusers pick up important viewpoints on upgrading English dialect instruction. This comprehensive investigation serves as a important asset for teachers, advertising a new point of view on instructing hones within the domain of English dialect instruction.

Key words: role, proverbs, sayings, linguo-cultural competence, development, high school students, language learning, cultural understanding, pedagogical tools, language education, effectiveness, language proficiency, intercultural communication skills, linguistic competence, cultural competence, literature review, empirical research, educational impact, language proficiency, language learning programs, evidence-based recommendations.

I. METHODS

Role-Play Technique in Language Teaching

Role-play is a teaching technique that involves students taking on specific roles or characters in a simulated situation or scenario. It is commonly used in language teaching to provide students with opportunities to practice and improve their language skills in a more realistic and interactive context. In a role-play, students are assigned roles that require them to use the target language to communicate, solve problems, or act out various social or professional situations.

How Does Role-Play Work?

1) Scenario Development: The first step in role-play is to create a scenario or situation that students will act out. This scenario should be relevant to the language skills and objectives being taught. For example, if the goal is to improve conversational English, the scenario could be a casual conversation at a coffee shop.

2) Assigning Roles: In the scenario, each student is assigned a specific role or character. These roles can vary from simple ones, such as a customer and a waiter, to more complex roles like job interviews or doctor-patient interactions.

3) Preparation: Students are given some time to prepare for their roles. They may be provided with some background information about their character, objectives, and any specific language or phrases they should use during the role-play.

4) Performance: Students then perform the role-play in pairs or small groups. They are encouraged to stay in character and use the target language to achieve their objectives within the

scenario. This often involves listening, speaking, and sometimes even writing in the target language.

5) Feedback and Reflection: After the role-play, there is a feedback and reflection phase. Students discuss how they performed, what went well, and what could be improved. This helps in identifying areas for language improvement.

Benefits of Role-Play in Language Teaching:

1) Real-World Context: Role-play provides students with a real-world context to apply their language skills. It makes learning practical and relevant.

2) Language Practice: It encourages active use of the language, including speaking, listening, and sometimes writing, which helps in improving overall language proficiency.

3) Communication Skills: Role-play enhances students' communication skills, including fluency, pronunciation, and vocabulary usage.

4) Problem-Solving: It requires students to think on their feet, problem-solve, and adapt their language use to different situations, which is a valuable skill in language learning.

5) Increased Engagement: Role-play is engaging and fun, making language learning more enjoyable for students.

6) Cultural Awareness: Depending on the scenarios chosen, role-play can also help students understand cultural norms, etiquette, and communication styles in different contexts.

Tips for Effective Role-Play:

1) Choose scenarios that align with the learning objectives.

2) Provide clear instructions and guidelines for each role.

3) Encourage students to stay in character and speak as naturally as possible.

4) Use role-play as an opportunity to introduce and reinforce relevant vocabulary and grammar.

5) Create a supportive and non-judgmental environment where students feel comfortable participating.

Utilizing Proverbs and Sayings

1) Introduction to Proverbs and Sayings. Begin by introducing students to the concept of proverbs and sayings. Explain that these are short, often metaphorical expressions that convey wisdom, cultural values, or common knowledge. Provide examples of proverbs and sayings from the target language and culture, and discuss their meanings and cultural contexts.

2) Vocabulary Enrichment. Incorporate proverbs and sayings into vocabulary lessons. Teach students the meanings of individual words within these expressions, helping them expand their vocabulary. Discuss the figurative meanings of proverbs and how they differ from literal interpretations.

3) Cultural Context. Explore the cultural background and origins of proverbs and sayings. Discuss how they reflect the values, traditions, and history of a particular culture.

Encourage students to research and share proverbs from their own cultures to promote cultural exchange.

4) Language Proficiency. Use proverbs and sayings as part of language exercises and activities. For example, have students complete sentences using proverbs, or ask them to create dialogues incorporating these expressions. Incorporate proverbs into reading and listening comprehension exercises to improve students' understanding of idiomatic language.

5) Critical Thinking and Interpretation. Encourage critical thinking by having students analyze the meanings and messages conveyed by proverbs and sayings.

Discuss the relevance of proverbs in contemporary society and how they may evolve or change over time.

6) Role-Playing and Discussions. Integrate proverbs and sayings into role-playing scenarios or debates. This encourages students to use these expressions in context and engage in meaningful conversations. Organize group discussions on the cultural and moral implications of specific proverbs and their application in daily life.

7) Writing Assignments. Assign writing tasks that involve the use of proverbs and sayings. For instance, ask students to compose essays or stories that incorporate these expressions.

Encourage creative writing using proverbs as inspiration, fostering both language skills and creativity.

8) Assessment and Feedback. Evaluate students' comprehension and usage of proverbs and sayings through quizzes, presentations, or written assignments. Provide constructive feedback to help students improve their understanding and application of these expressions.

9) Cultural Appreciation. Promote cultural sensitivity by discussing proverbs within the context of cultural diversity and global understanding. Explore how proverbs and sayings may differ among various regions or dialects within the target language.

10) Resources and References. Compile a list of resources, including books, websites, and databases, where students can explore and discover proverbs and sayings in the target language.

Pedagogical Tools for High School Students

Pedagogical tools for high school students are essential resources and strategies that educators can use to facilitate effective teaching and enhance the learning experience. Here's an overview of various pedagogical tools suitable for high school students:

Interactive Whiteboards

Based on the research and evidence presented, educators and policymakers are encouraged to integrate Interactive Whiteboards (IWBs) into high school classrooms. This integration can be facilitated through the adoption of interactive activities, collaborative learning, and the incorporation of multimedia content. Furthermore, teacher training programs should emphasize the pedagogical potential of IWBs, equipping educators with the necessary skills to utilize this technology effectively in their instructional practices.

By integrating IWBs into high school education, educators can promote active learning, enhance engagement, and provide students with a dynamic and interactive learning environment.

To maximize the benefits of incorporating IWBs, educators can employ various strategies. They can design lessons that leverage the interactive features of IWBs, such as creating interactive quizzes, simulations, and collaborative projects. These activities encourage student participation and critical thinking. Additionally, educators can use IWBs to facilitate multimedia-rich lessons, incorporating videos, images, and interactive simulations to enhance understanding and retention of complex concepts.

The integration of digital content and resources allows for a more dynamic and immersive learning experience. Moreover, IWBs can support differentiated instruction by accommodating various learning styles and abilities. Teachers can adapt their teaching methods to cater to individual student needs, providing additional support or challenges as necessary. IWBs also enable formative assessment, allowing educators to gather real-time data on student progress and adjust instruction accordingly. This immediate feedback loop enhances the learning experience and helps students track their own growth. Furthermore, the integration of IWBs fosters digital literacy skills, preparing high school students for the technological demands of the modern world. It equips them with the ability to navigate digital resources, collaborate online, and utilize technology as a tool for learning and problem-solving.

Digital Learning Platforms in Education

Digital Learning Platforms, often referred to as Learning Management Systems (LMS), have become integral tools in modern education. These platforms provide a centralized digital

environment where educators can create, deliver, and manage instructional content, while students can access resources, engage in activities, and collaborate with peers. This comprehensive overview explores the key features, functionality, benefits, best practices, and future trends of Digital Learning Platforms.

Key Features of Digital Learning Platforms:

1) Content Management: Digital Learning Platforms enable educators to organize, upload, and share course materials, assignments, quizzes, and multimedia resources efficiently.

2) Communication Tools: Robust messaging systems, discussion forums, and announcement features facilitate seamless communication between educators and students, as well as among students.

3) Assessment and Grading: These platforms support the creation, distribution, and automated grading of assessments, streamlining the feedback process.

4) Data Analytics: Digital Learning Platforms offer data analytics that enable educators to monitor student progress, identify areas of improvement, and adapt teaching strategies accordingly.

5) Accessibility Features: Many platforms provide features to ensure that educational content is accessible to all learners, including those with disabilities.

Online Collaboration Tools

Online Collaboration Tools have become indispensable in today's interconnected world. They are a category of software and web-based applications designed to facilitate real-time communication, project management, and teamwork among individuals or groups, regardless of their physical location. These tools are essential for businesses, educational institutions, and individuals looking to streamline workflows, improve communication, and enhance productivity.

II. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research addresses several facets. Initially, it will explore the concept of innovative instructional methods. Subsequently, it will delve into the significance of implementing these inventive teaching approaches. The final segment of this study will examine the specific innovative teaching methods applicable to English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction and how these strategies are put into practice within the classroom. The historical lineage of inventive pedagogical techniques can be traced back to the earliest stages of formal education. Educators have consistently sought ways to enhance the engagement and effectiveness of their students' learning experiences. Over time, a multitude of methodologies and techniques have surfaced, reflecting the evolving educational requirements and societal contexts of different eras. One of the earliest instances of innovative teaching can be exemplified by the Socratic method, which was developed by the Greek philosopher Socrates in the 5th century BCE. In this approach, educators would pose questions to their students, fostering critical thinking and encouraging students to independently arrive at their own conclusions. Remarkably, the Socratic method continues to wield significant influence as a pedagogical strategy and is still employed in numerous educational institutions globally.

One of the primary objectives of these innovative methods is to cultivate a learning environment that is more interactive and collaborative. Furthermore, these inventive teaching techniques are anticipated to contribute to the enhancement of students' language proficiency by enabling them to apply the language in authentic contexts and receive constructive feedback from both their peers and instructors. The overarching goal of these innovative methods is to promote a heightened level of interactivity and collaboration within the learning environment. This objective can be realized through the implementation of group activities, project-oriented learning, and problem-centered learning, all of which encourage students to collaborate and participate in real-world tasks. These approaches prove especially effective in advancing students'

language capabilities by affording them the opportunity to apply the language in meaningful situations and benefit from constructive feedback from their peers and instructors. Utilizing innovative methods for teaching English through the integrated approach can have a positive impact on student learning and engagement, ultimately enhancing student motivation and improving their overall educational experience. Motivation plays a crucial role in students' academic achievements, contributing significantly to their learning outcomes. Additionally, innovative teaching methods can enhance critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students. One notable outcome of employing innovative teaching strategies is an increase in student participation. These strategies frequently involve collaborative learning experiences that encourage active engagement, fostering collaboration and greater student involvement in the learning process. Furthermore, innovative teaching methods can lead to enhanced comprehension among students. Active participation in the learning process enables students to better grasp and retain new information. Another advantage of implementing innovative teaching techniques is the heightened flexibility and adaptability they offer to educators. This flexibility allows teachers to customize their teaching approaches to align with the unique needs and preferences of individual students. Moreover, these methods can facilitate the development of essential skills such as communication, collaboration, and teamwork, thereby improving students' communication and collaboration abilities. Innovative Methods for Teaching English: The Integrated Approach exhibit several distinctive features. One fundamental characteristic of innovative learning within this approach is its focus on cultivating four core competencies: critical thinking, creative and inventive thinking, effective communication, and collaborative skills. Consequently, the learning process is oriented towards activities that embody interactivity, holism, integration, empiricism, contextuality, thematic exploration, effectiveness, collaboration, and a student-centric approach to foster the development of these vital skills. Another pivotal element of innovative teaching methods is the integration of technology and multimedia resources. Many language educators now leverage various digital tools, such as video and audio recordings, online quizzes, and interactive games, to augment language learning and enhance its engagement and interactivity. These resources prove particularly beneficial for learners with a penchant for visual and hands-on learning modalities. Additionally, some language instructors incorporate elements of culture and authentic materials into their teaching to provide students with a more genuine and comprehensive grasp of the language and the cultures in which it is embedded. This integration encompasses the utilization of authentic texts, including news articles and advertisements, as well as the infusion of cultural themes and activities into lesson plans. When it comes to assessment, the integrated approach of innovative methods for teaching English advocates for authentic assessment. Authentic assessment entails students actively participating in learning activities, engaging in investigations, and taking on genuine roles in knowledge acquisition from their immediate environment. Within innovative learning, assessment is thoughtfully designed to evaluate students' learning accomplishments, encompassing knowledge-based competencies (critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, innovation, collaboration, communication), intrapersonal skills (teamwork, cooperation, communication, coordination), and interpersonal proficiencies (working with others, self-management, effective communication, and emotional relationship maintenance). As a result, innovative learning cultivates individuals with literacy in information, data, and technology—an essential requirement for addressing the challenges posed by contemporary and future globalization, both in life and in the job market. Considering the characteristics and types of assessments conducted within the framework of innovative learning, several teaching strategies fall under the category of innovative learning strategies. First among these is the cooperative learning strategy. This strategy involves a series of learning activities carried out by students in specific groups to attain predetermined objectives. These collaborative efforts entail students working collectively in small groups to accomplish tasks

or projects. This pedagogical approach promotes collaboration and encourages students to cooperate and exchange ideas. It proves to be an engaging and interactive method for presenting new information, allowing students to engage in discussions and deliberations. One notable advantage of employing group work teaching strategies is the opportunity for students to learn from their peers and collaborate in problem-solving endeavors. This aids in the development of critical communication, teamwork, and problem-solving skills. Moreover, group work effectively facilitates mutual support and feedback among students, as they collaborate to enhance each other's comprehension of new concepts and ideas. It's worth noting that a limitation of group work teaching strategies lies in the potential challenge of managing a large group of students and ensuring equitable participation and contributions from all individuals.

III. SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

To summarize, this research has explored diverse aspects of innovative teaching methods, focusing on their application in the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction. The inquiry began by defining innovative pedagogy and highlighting its significant role in contemporary education. Examining the historical origins of pedagogical innovation, we traced its roots back to ancient times, exemplified by the enduring influence of the Socratic method. This historical perspective underscores the ongoing quest of educators to improve their teaching methods and engage learners effectively. A central theme of these innovative methods is the creation of interactive and collaborative learning environments. Their goal is not only to enhance language proficiency but also to nurture critical thinking skills. These methods immerse students in real-world scenarios, prompting them to use English authentically. Through this process, students not only acquire language competence but also refine problem-solving abilities and independent thinking. The research underscores the pivotal role of interactivity and collaboration in the learning environment. The adoption of group activities, project-based learning, and problem-centered pedagogy emerges as a transformative approach. It empowers students to actively participate in their education, collaborate with peers, and tackle authentic tasks mirroring real-world challenges. In the context of English language instruction, the integration of innovative methods within the integrated approach holds promise for enhancing student learning and engagement. These methods ignite motivation, stimulate critical thinking, and guide learners toward a deeper understanding of the language and its practical applications. In essence, this research emphasizes the undeniable value of innovative teaching techniques in EFL education. It encourages educators to embrace innovation to enrich the educational experience, boost student motivation, and equip learners with essential skills for success in our increasingly interconnected global society. By harnessing the power of innovation, educators can create a more dynamic, effective, and engaging English language instruction.

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BASIC PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN ADVANCED COURSES OF LANGUAGE FACULTIES

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Abstract

Changes in society and life in modern times are also reflected in the knowledge, skills and habits required of people. Now, employers are paying more attention to the characteristics of candidates who apply for work, such as competitiveness, creativity, communication, and cooperation. For this reason, in our article, we have examined the principles of developing the creative activity of students in advanced courses of the language faculty.

Keywords: *creative activity, global communication language, learning*

One of the main factors characterizing the modern education system in accordance with European standards is the transfer of knowledge to students, not teaching them, but the acquisition of relevant knowledge by students, and thus, the concept of "learning" instead of "teaching" is brought to the fore. This, in turn, requires serious reforms in the field of education, including in the field of teaching foreign languages. Today, one of the main tasks facing both secondary and higher schools is the preparation of young people who have the ability to use the world's leading languages, especially English, which is the language of global communication, independently, adequately, and creatively.

In order to achieve this goal, first of all, the preparation of foreign language teachers in a manner consistent with the requirements of the globalization era requires their acquisition of high professional qualities, being communicatively competent, from innovative methods and approaches, achieving the ability to use of modern training technologies. In order to improve the process of development of students' creative activity in English in the pedagogical faculties of higher schools specializing in a foreign language and to achieve successful results in this field, the teaching of English as the language of specialization is completely new. creativity, initiative, the ability to creatively use the specialized language and other completely new qualities should be developed.

One of the issues of strategic importance is the preparation of pedagogical personnel in the field of teaching foreign languages, which is in line with the requirements of the modern era. It is for this reason that the teaching of English as a language of specialization in higher schools with a specialization in language should be organized and implemented in a completely new way.

The educational system based on the principles of communication, student orientation, interactivity, cooperation, mutual respect, initiative, responsibility, result orientation, creativity, and activity ensure from students studying in the upper courses of language faculties and learning the language for professional purposes creativity, independence, responsibility, the improvement of qualities such as activity. It also ensures the development of their ability to creatively use the specialized language at the level of the requirements of the time.

One of the main conditions that ensure the training of specialists in accordance with modern standards is the need to bring the conditions of the auditorium as close as possible to the real language environment. In the absence of a natural language environment, the teacher's verbal and non-verbal behavior should be an example for students, and his speech should be as close as possible to the speech level of his native speakers who have linguistic literacy. It is for this reason that it is considered a priority issue to apply the changes made in the field of education to the training of teaching staff. It is possible to change the existing education system and adapt it to European education standards only by training highly qualified, communicatively competent, and professional staff who love their work.

In order to ensure the development of creative activity of students of language faculties in English, a methodical model should be created and a system of tasks and exercises should be developed and prepared based on it. The methodical model and the system of tasks designed to stimulate the creative activity of students studying English as a major in a foreign language and to develop their creative abilities are based on the principles of student-oriented, communicative, functional-oriented and interactive, and implies the implementation of students' creative activity in a purposeful, step-by-step, consistent and result-oriented manner.

It is very important to organize the process of development of creative activity in English of upper year students of language faculties in a more efficient manner. In order to achieve successful results, some texts used in the learning process should be authentic and should be selected taking into account the age, intellectual and knowledge levels of students. At the same time, it should correspond to the students' dreams, interests and needs, and should ensure the creation of motivation to use the language independently and creatively.

In general, foreign language teaching, especially in language faculties, the efforts used to ensure the efficiency of the development of creative abilities of students in the language of specialization should be motivating. Such tasks should serve to create interest and enthusiasm in students to creatively master the foreign language, which is the language of specialization.

Researchers who support innovations in foreign language teaching see the teacher's main task not in imparting knowledge and teaching students, but in managing the training process at a professional level and making the process of teaching and learning a foreign language more efficient. It is enough to transition from teaching with traditional methods to student-oriented training organized on the basis of cooperation, mutual respect and responsibility, which is in accordance with the requirements of the modern era, the process of learning a foreign language should be based on the interests and needs of students, and the responsibility for the success or failure of the training process should be directed to the students to a certain extent. It is a difficult issue.

Regarding the preparation of foreign language teachers that are in line with the requirements of the times, they should be communicatively competent, that is, they should have the ability to use the taught language adequately and creatively during communication with both native speakers and people representing other cultures. In order to achieve the goal of developing the ability to use the English language freely and creatively at an international and intercultural level, the teaching process must be organized taking into account how native speakers of that language speak.

One of the most important factors determining the development of creative activity in the language taught to students studying English as a major in language faculties is the implementation of the educational process in a communicative-oriented way. One of the main principles of communicative training is that students and teachers act as active participants in the process of learning a foreign language. One of the main principles that form the basis of the communicative approach to language teaching is the principle of communicativeness.

Communicative approach in the process of teaching a foreign language, in determining the goals and tasks, in choosing the most effective methods and methods for achieving the set goals, in the textbook, other teaching materials and technical tools used, requires the joint consideration of students and teachers.

Interactivity and student orientation are the most important principles that form the basis of communicative training. The principle of interactive learning and student-orientation, which can ensure the development of creative activity in a foreign language, which is the language of specialization of students of language faculties, provides for the cooperation of students with each other and with the teacher and their mutual activity in the learning process.

The main factor that characterizes the communicative approach to language teaching is the mastery of a foreign language as a means of communication. Thus, communicative training aims to inculcate in students the ability to correctly, creatively and adequately use each language unit to be mastered, as well as each speech model in the communication process. That is why it is encouraging to involve students who study English as a major in language faculties in communicative activity, to engage in communication in a foreign language that is the language of their major, to apply theoretical knowledge acquired in the field of language to practice, to use acquired linguistic units and speech patterns in a real communication process. .

The extent to which reforms are successful depends to a large extent on the relationship between teachers who teach English as a major and students who learn the language for professional purposes. The creation of mutual respect and balance between the participants of the training process, student-teacher and student-student, is the most important motivating factor that stimulates students' creative activity in the language of specialization. At the same time, it should be noted that today it would be more correct to talk about learning languages rather than teaching them.

In order to achieve the goal of developing the creative activity of students of language faculties in English, they should actively participate in discussions and debates; should be ready to express their opinions, positions and attitudes freely, creatively using the linguistic possibilities available to them; and at the same time should be able to respect the different opinions and positions of others.

In order for students to voluntarily engage in interactive activities, the teacher should organize the teaching process taking into account their needs and interests. In order to meet the needs of students studying in language faculties, the teacher should regularly update his knowledge in the field of the language he teaches, training materials, and training technologies used in the training process.

In order to ensure the development of creativity in his students, first of all, the teacher who teaches a foreign language as a major must be competent in terms of communication and have creativity. In accordance with the requirements of the modern era, the teacher who teaches the language as a specialty should direct the activity of the students in the right direction; to comply with the communicative models accepted by their native speakers; to find more effective ways of learning new lexical units and grammatical structures; should encourage free and creative use of various training materials.

Student-oriented, functional-oriented interactive training to actively involve students in various discussions; to share ideas with interlocutors; to respect the constructive critical opinions expressed by fellow students, as well as by the teacher; and also includes objectively evaluating one's activity achievements [3, p.67-68].

The role of teaching materials used for the development of students' creative activity in the process of teaching English in foreign language higher schools should be especially noted. If these materials are chosen correctly, they can have a very positive effect on the quality of language acquisition and the development of creative activity in a foreign language [2, p.24].

The selection of training materials that can ensure the efficiency of the process of development of students' creative activity, exercises and tasks aimed at actively involving students in the process of real communication should be carried out based on certain criteria.

It should be noted that there are also criteria for organizing the types of communicative activities that maximally activate students learning the language for professional purposes. Thus, educational materials that can ensure the involvement of students in interactive activities should meet the following criteria: they should be interesting for students and ensure that they are involved in the real communication process in the foreign language being studied. Thus, the goals put forward in each learning context should be precise, realistic, and correspond to the level of students' knowledge, habits and skills in the language field.

The materials presented to the students should be authentic and should contain different models of speech of native speakers in the natural environment. One of the conditions that ensure interactive, student-oriented training is the orientation of the educational materials used in the auditorium to the cooperation of students in the language learning process, to the development of creative activity in the foreign language, which is their specialized language.

At the same time, training materials should be colorful and the same type of tasks should not be used in the training process. The tasks presented should ensure the creative use of linguistic units and speech models to be mastered. Training materials should be presented in such a way that, if needed, students can work freely and creatively and objectively evaluate their speech activities.

Interaction or mutual activity can be considered as a method of involving students in the communication process and developing their creative activity in a foreign language. Also, interaction is understood as a social factor that determines students' verbal and non-verbal behavior in the classroom [1, p.169].

Such an analysis of interactivity implies the direct participation of students in the management of the process of learning a foreign language, which is the language of specialization, and their involvement in that process as active, proactive participants. The socio-emotional environment in the auditorium is the most important factor that plays an important role in student engagement. Creating an effective socio-emotional environment that ensures the development of creative activity in the foreign language, which is the foreign language of students' specialization, is one of the main tasks of the teacher who teaches the specialization language classes in the language faculties.

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Factors affecting the development of EFL learners' listening skills

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Annotation. Listening is a fundamental skill in language learning, and for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners, it holds particular importance in facilitating effective communication. The ability to comprehend spoken language in various contexts is crucial for everyday interactions, academic success, and professional development. However, the development of EFL learners' listening skills can be influenced by various factors, both internal and external. This exploratory article demonstrates key factors that influence EFL learners' listening abilities and discuss strategies to enhance their listening proficiency.

Key words: *listening skills, development, factors, foreign language*

Introduction

Effective listening skills play a pivotal role in language acquisition and communication, especially in the context of learning English as a Foreign Language (Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2011; Yavuz & Celik, 2017). As Krashen (1981) formulated, language learning is a process of input and output. According to his theory, in order to acquire a language effectively, meaningful interaction is required - natural communication - in which speakers focus on the message they are communicating and understanding rather than the form of their utterances. Based on this assumption, Yavuz and Celik (2017) assert that listening skills are crucial for obtaining input during the learning process as they cover a large part of the input. Moreover, the ability to comprehend spoken language is essential for students to engage in meaningful conversations, understand lectures, and navigate real-life situations. However, developing strong listening skills in a second language can be a challenging task for many EFL learners. Ardila (2013) found that the listening is more complex than just hearing. "This process involves four stages: sensing and attending, understanding and interpreting, remembering, and responding. There are several factors can influence the development of EFL learners' listening skills, either positively or negatively. This article delves into these key factors that contribute to the development of EFL learners' listening skills and offers practical insights for educators and students.

Language Proficiency level

The language proficiency level of EFL learners is a significant factor in their listening skills development. They often face challenges in developing their listening skills due to factors such as linguistic barriers, unfamiliar accents, and the complex nature of spoken language. For example, beginners may struggle to grasp the meaning of spoken language due to limited vocabulary and grammar knowledge. Moreover, Lee and Cai (2010) found that listeners with low language proficiency levels experienced difficulties interpreting word meanings using appropriate knowledge sources and erroneous inferences leading to incorrect responses. Listening skills tend to improve as learners progress and become more proficient. To support their growth, teachers

should design listening activities that align with their current proficiency level and gradually introduce more complex materials as they advance.

Active Listening Strategies and Regular Listening Practice

Strategies are systematic plans for controlling and manipulating particular information, modes of operation for reaching a given goal, or specific ways of handling a problem or activity (Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2011). The study suggests that second language learners with a low level of language proficiency who have limited vocabulary, imperfect command of the language's syntactic and semantic structure, or other limitations regarding the elements necessary for communicative competency must rely on listening strategies to help them understand aural communication. Encouraging the use of active listening strategies is essential for the development of EFL learners' listening skills. Active listening involves techniques like predicting, summarizing, inferencing, and noting key points during the listening process. By employing these strategies, learners would become more focused, attentive, and receptive to the spoken language, leading to improved comprehension and retention of information.

Like any language skill, listening improves with consistent practice. Teachers should incorporate regular listening exercises into the curriculum, encouraging learners to engage with various audio and video resources. Additionally, self-study tools, such as podcasts, online listening exercises, and language apps, enable learners to practice listening outside the classroom, promoting autonomous learning.

Utilization of Songs as Learning Content

Traditional teaching methods in TEFL often focus on structured lessons, reading materials, and repetitive exercises. However, alternative approaches, such as incorporating songs into language learning, have gained prominence due to their potential to engage learners and enhance the effectiveness of the learning process. Sevik (2012) states that songs are an essential teaching tool in TFL which helps students to have fun and at the same time acquire language. Also, Solihat and Utami (2014) found that English songs are effective in developing listening skills. The purpose of their research was to explore whether employing English songs to enhance students' listening skills is helpful and to learn what attitudes students had toward doing so. This study involved 62 students of grade eight from SMPN 1 Lebakwangi in Kecamatan Lebakwangi. The quasi-experimental design was used as its methodology. There were one control group and one experimental group to investigate. A pre-test, a post-test, and a questionnaire were used to collect the data. This study employed the t-test formula generated by SPSS 17.00 to examine the pre- and post-test results. The result of study shows that English songs are useful for improving listening skills. Post-test results showed a significant difference between the experimental and control groups. Solihat and Utami (2014) state that students who are interested in English songs are more likely to participate actively in class and perform well on listening assignments. Overall the study shows that improving listening skills by using English songs is one of the useful strategies of teaching. Therefore, this study might be useful for school teachers in developing more creative and innovative teaching methods of improving students' listening skills.

According to Shen (2009), using English songs in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) classes can promote effective learning by creating a peaceful learning environment, lowering students' anxiety levels, stimulating their interests, and inspiring them to learn the target language. Students will view learning English through songs as enjoyable and relaxing since they will see it as entertainment rather than schoolwork. The use of songs in the classroom makes listening exercises more engaging. Moreover, by utilizing songs in listening exercises, it is possible to improve the efficiency of those exercises.

Building Vocabulary and Background Knowledge

The key to competent listening is vocabulary (Lee & Cai, 2010). As Kline (1996) was cited in Solihat and Utami (2014) vocabulary building improves conversational skills and reading skills as well as listening skills. Also, Ardila (2013) found that motivation, paralinguistic elements (such as accent, noise, rate of delivery, pronunciation, and intonation), known vocabulary, concentration, teaching style, usage of resources, and learner's background all have an impact on EFL participants' listening skills. EFL learners' background knowledge significantly impacts their listening comprehension. Familiarity with the topic being discussed allows learners to anticipate the content and make connections, leading to improved understanding. Encouraging learners to read extensively and gain knowledge in various subject areas enhances their listening abilities in diverse contexts.

Noise and Distractions

External factors, such as noise and distractions in the learning environment, can disrupt the listening process for EFL learners. A noisy classroom or a distracting setting may reduce learners' concentration and impede their ability to focus on the listening task at hand. Additionally, Diaz (2012) as cited in Ardila (2013) found several factors that hinder the development of listening skill. Study results indicated that speakers' accents, speed of delivery, students' limited vocabulary, concentration, discussion of unfamiliar topics, and noise interfere with EFL learners' comprehension. Creating a quiet and focused environment for listening activities can positively impact learners' ability to comprehend spoken language.

Listening Anxiety and Lack of Contextualization

Listening anxiety is a common psychological barrier that affects language learners. Hidayati et al. (2020) say that anxiety contributes negatively to students' poor comprehension of listening when teaching listening. Fear of not understanding, feeling overwhelmed by rapid speech, or worrying about making mistakes can hinder learners' ability to concentrate and comprehend the spoken language. Encouraging a supportive learning environment, providing positive reinforcement, and offering opportunities for learners to practice without fear of judgment can help alleviate listening anxiety and boost self-confidence.

Contextualization, as an essential characteristic of language, determines the comprehensibility of any input, whether it be aural or visual (Jarideh & Kargar, 2015). Contextualization of listening materials is essential for EFL learners to grasp the meaning effectively. Jarideh and Kargar (2015) state that it is impossible to acquire a language through decontextualized practice. If the listening tasks are presented without appropriate context, learners may struggle to infer the message, leading to frustration and disinterest. Providing pre-listening activities that introduce the topic and relevant vocabulary helps learners connect the content to their existing knowledge, leading to better comprehension.

Conclusion

Overall, teaching listening skill is one of the most challenging aspects of teaching English. Lestary (2019) defines listening as the most important language skill, which is also a part of communication because it allows us to express our ideas to others. The development of this skill requires active participation from both teachers and students. At the same time, the development of EFL learners' listening skills is influenced by a combination of internal and external factors. Language proficiency level, listening anxiety, exposure to authentic materials, contextual relevance, use of effective strategies, background knowledge, and linguistic diversity all play critical roles in shaping learners' listening proficiency. By recognizing these influencing factors, educators can design targeted teaching approaches and create an inclusive learning environment that empowers EFL learners to become competent and confident listeners. With consistent

practice and support, learners can overcome challenges and enjoy the rewards of improved listening skills in their language journey.

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THE ROLE OF DICTIONARIES IN SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS

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Today, one of the main tasks of the Azerbaijani language teacher is to enrich, expand and clarify the student's vocabulary. The more vocabulary a student has, the more he will be able to convey his thoughts in a clear, precise and understandable form. Every Azerbaijani language teacher should organize the work in his lessons in such a way that the student learns to think, analyze, compare and draw conclusions in the learning process. In order to do this, there is a need for a developed systematic speech and a rich vocabulary. One of the main ways to solve this is the ability to work with different kinds of dictionaries.

One of the goals of the teacher should be to organize work on enriching the vocabulary of high school students and to be able to recognize dictionaries as an additional learning tool. In order to achieve this goal, optimal methods of using electronic dictionaries should be found, not only school dictionaries and paper dictionaries.

In order to develop oral and written speech, to enrich the student's vocabulary, it is necessary to take advantage of all the dictionaries in the Azerbaijani language and find ways to use them. The systematic use of different types of dictionaries, relevant to the topic, can lead to a significant enrichment of students' vocabulary and an increase in the level of speech development.

In the context of the Turkic language, the Azerbaijani language is one of the richest languages in the world, and it cannot be assumed that someone has completely mastered the vocabulary of our language. The experience of many years shows that a person uses a certain amount of words in his activities, and therefore there is no need to completely master the vocabulary of the language at the stages of general education.

It should be noted that there are some words that are used in completely narrow areas, perhaps a person does not come across such words in his entire life, and those words are not transformed into a product of speech development. It is unthinkable for someone to completely master the entire vocabulary of a language. Therefore, the questions facing the Azerbaijani language teaching methodology are: what to learn, how to learn, why and where to learn? The question that interests us more is "what to teach?" is a question. That is, what should we teach so that the student can use the word correctly and appropriately, and what criteria and principles should we follow at this time?

It should be taken into account that frequency vocabulary and general vocabulary are different things, and the student should be more interested in and learn more about the words that will be used in daily use in the Azerbaijani language.

When we say frequency dictionary, it should be considered not to use dictionaries quickly, but to use the words sitting in the memory quickly according to the situation. A student may be able to use vocabulary words more efficiently and quickly. Or, despite the abundance of words in his vocabulary, he cannot express his thoughts quickly. Therefore, psychologist-methodologists and professional teachers point out that the student should acquire the habits of using the words necessary for daily communication in his mother tongue and solve other issues of speech development with this system.

There are a number of additional principles (correspondence to another word, polysemy, word formation value) for the inclusion of words in the frequency dictionary and active

assimilation. An equally important criterion for the selection of words for active use in the process of working with a dictionary is polysemy. Without forgetting that the main condition for realizing the lexical meaning of a word is its compatibility, we must not forget the compatibility of that word with other words.

In addition to choosing words that have the ability to correct, we must not forget the value of lexical suffixes that create our own words. Words of this type take their place in morphological dictionaries based on the morphological principle. The main sources of increasing the student's vocabulary and enriching his speech are listening and speaking lessons, daily speech practice, works on reading content and the ability to work with dictionaries.

In solving some issues (explanation, translation, term, etc.), referring to the dictionary directly serves to enrich the vocabulary. In general, work with the dictionary directly serves the development of speech and forms speech culture. The conditions of scientific progress, the abundance of incomprehensible words and terms create a great need for a dictionary, and enriching the student's vocabulary is one of the most urgent problems in the works carried out in this direction.

We know very well that language is a social phenomenon, the origin and development of which is related to a certain human collective, and it forms an organic whole with thought. Phonetic, lexical, and grammatical means are to prove that this communication process is clearer, more accurate, and more necessary.

The language of a newspaper, book, poem, conversation differs and is characterized by certain stylistic features. Besides being a system of signs, language is a psycholinguistic process. There are four main types of speech activity: reading, listening, speaking and writing.

Speech development is the process of enriching the student's speech, and the methodology of teaching the Azerbaijani language is a mechanism that moves this process forward through certain methods and methods.

The choice of the means of teaching the Azerbaijani language, including the means of developing the speech of schoolchildren, is based on the achievements of pedagogy and didactics, which provide a generalized concept of the teaching process.

Successful learning of the native language is impossible without knowledge of the psychology of students. In order to present the material in an accessible way, it is necessary to know the psychological characteristics of children.

We mentioned at the beginning that the student should get used to working with vocabulary from an early age, even from the elementary school stage. The result of this requirement is also taken into account in the compilation of school dictionaries. But this does not mean that the teacher does not use the dictionaries at hand in any way he wants. For example, there is no separate dictionary of synonyms or a dictionary of terms for the student, but the teacher should teach his students to work with such dictionaries, especially electronic dictionaries.

Of course, this should be done in stages. Although the fifth-grade student is not involved in this process, starting from the ninth grade, it can be suggested to work with other dictionaries. Children begin to systematically learn the scientific basis of the Azerbaijani language as a subject from the 5th grade, and the problem of improving speech development through dictionaries should also be strengthened from this grade. Starting from the 5th grade, students try to make generalizations, speak with evidence, understand more complex relationships between concepts, and abstract issues. At this stage, the teacher should be able to connect the issues of speech development to the ability to work with dictionaries.

If the teacher sets up a stimulating training, the student will listen to his explanations with enthusiasm, and he will not be bored by getting acquainted with new concepts and new material. The teacher should take into account the student's communication with the outside world (parents, friends, internet) when delivering any news. The wide range of communication also

creates a need for learning and conscious learning in the student. Considering this need, the teacher should provide him with materials suitable for his needs and not with heavy materials, and should create conditions for him to work independently. The content of the teaching material motivates the student to learn. The teacher should take into account that dictionaries are not text rich in events, images, ideas, but explanatory, terminological, etc. of words. is the arrangement.

Therefore, the teacher must correctly determine the choice of text and expression in order to arouse interest in vocabulary in his student. The student should be interested in researching the explanation, etymology and other features of the word he comes across in the text. For example, the student learns the dictionary explanation of words such as understanding, aesthetic, ancestor, efficiency, phonograph, ideography, empire, intensive, modern, missionary, opponent, regeneration, unity in class X because the materials taught in this class are creates conditions.

A class V student may not be interested in the fact that the word regeneration means "restoration of lost or damaged parts". Or, giving theoretical information about terms in class X is not a random process, but a regulation related to the age level of the students.

Let's say that in the work on the text "Shollar water pipeline" in class X, the teacher returns to the issue of orthography, orthoepy, and terms. When asked which words in the text are spelled correctly, such as geological (hyalogy), geadesia (giadesia), bacteriological (bacteriological), the student must refer to the spelling dictionary again and determine the spelling of those words. Our purpose in reminding them once again is that as they move from class to class, as they develop, it is necessary to equip students with more rational educational methods, that is, with materials that help their individual success.

A positive attitude to learning, high social motivation is a necessary condition for complete learning of the learning material. During the learning process, the student is careful that what he will learn helps his thinking, speech, and daily social life. The teacher should give tasks such as "find the meaning of the word from the explanatory dictionary", "research the etymology (origin) of the word", "learn the translation of the word in Russian (English, German)", "search the synonym of the word in the dictionary of synonyms" at such a moment that the student be interested in exploring it.

The language rules related to stylistics are mastered in the work on the texts in the 10th grade textbook ("Shollar su kamiri", "Caspian Sea", "The complaint of the sycamore"). Here scientific, artistic, journalistic, etc. styles are talked about. Of course, large dictionaries and electronic searches are often needed in upper grades. For example, when giving information about the scientific style, the terms that are its characteristic vocabulary base are mentioned, terminological dictionaries are mentioned. It is noted that the main indicator of scientific style is terms. Scientific style is not a juxtaposition of terms. Therefore, it is in the tenth grade that the teacher has a chance to work more actively and effectively with terminological dictionaries.

In class X, information about terms is also given that there are terms that have different meanings in different fields of science, but have the same spelling. For example, morphology is used as a term in both linguistics and biology. In linguistics, this is the division that studies parts of speech, and in biology, it is a scientific concept that studies the structure of plants. Or, the word root as a term means the root of a word in linguistics, the root of a plant in biology, and the root of an equation in mathematics.

In the tasks given for deeper assimilation of the rule, students can distinguish a mere term from a general word. Understands the characteristics of common terms, understands the terminology used in conversation. It will be more interesting if the teacher gives information about the formation of terms and also informs about the ways of their formation.

It is at this age period that the student can be informed about terms and general words, terms and art-profession words, and the common terms we mentioned above. Acoustics, species,

morphology, etc., considered as linguistic terms. can be considered as homonymy (homonymity of terms).

All these issues that we touched upon suggest that dictionaries are additional teaching tools closely involved in the formation of students' speech development. The teacher should teach the methods and ways of using these teaching tools so that the student is interested in working with the dictionary and searching for words. Let him know that any new word he learns will be included in his vocabulary and, along with enriching his speech, will also expand his ideas about the Azerbaijani language and its vocabulary.

We can roughly summarize the ideas about the role of dictionaries in speech development as follows:

1. All dictionaries participate in the learning process to one degree or another and enrich students' vocabulary;
2. Explanatory dictionaries not only help to find the meaning of a word that is not understood in the text, but also ensure the realization of certain standards of the reading content line and replenish the students' active vocabulary fund.
3. The correct use of phraseological dictionaries not only allows the student to distinguish phrases, but also allows them to speak in an artistic-poetic language;
4. The dictionary of synonyms, homonyms and antonyms is directly involved in the variety, expressiveness of speech, elimination of fatigue and facilitates the student's speech;
5. Translation dictionaries allow the student to learn different languages and different subjects interactively, and also increase the students' vocabulary;
6. The correct use of the dictionary of terms allows the student to distinguish styles and be able to build his speech in a scientific style;
7. Proper use of electronic dictionaries directly enriches the student's outlook and speech.

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IN THE FIELD OF COMPUTER USE IN LITERATURE LESSONS. CURRENT SITUATION IN SCHOOLS

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The use of computers in training is one of the greatest achievements of recent times. The computer itself is a technical achievement of the second half of the 20th century, and it is also a technical tool that has a wider scope for gathering information about life, the environment, events of various content and displaying it in different levels of audiences.

One of the important problems facing the world is to use the possibility of the computer in training and arming the growing generation with scientific knowledge. Solving this problem in Azerbaijan is the most serious and urgent task in the field of education after our republic gained independence.

This aspect is indicated in the Education Reform Program of the Republic of Azerbaijan: "In order to implement this extremely important task, the introduction and use of new information technology in the education system, increasing the efficiency of scientific and methodical work, creating a computer network of the educational process and its international information it is necessary to organize a single information system that provides access to banks.

In order to carry out these state-wide and nationally important works related to the content of education and upbringing, the following should be implemented:

- information provision;
- creation of an information center, organization of the use of scientific-mass information and tele-radio means;
- scientific in order to ensure the elucidation of the main problems of training and education at all levels of education, the communication of the potential opportunities of the field of education by profiles to the public, the dissemination of innovations in scientific development, the delivery of legal acts and other information in the field of education to the pedagogical community and educational institutions - organize the use of mass information and radio and television media;
- prepare the informatization program of the educational system.

As can be seen from the quote from the education reform program approved by the decree of the country's president, very serious tasks must be performed in order to achieve certain success in this field. Of course, some work has been done so far, some of the tasks proposed in the reform program have been fulfilled. For example, in response to the task put forward in the informatization program of the education reform, the last article mentioned in the quote, the Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan has prepared the "Program for provision of general education schools with information and communication technologies in the Republic of Azerbaijan (2005-2007 years)" in this field. In addition, other works planned in the program, which have reached attention in the field of information provision of schools, have also been carried out.

At the meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers chaired by the President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev dedicated to the social and economic results of the nine months of 2006, the Minister of Education said in his speech: "According to the ICT program we approved, 218 schools were provided with computers in 2005. if done, the number of such schools will reach 841 this year, and 435 schools will be given laptops and projectors".

It is clear from the report of the honorable minister that 841 schools of Azerbaijan have been computerized. It is also known that the total number of schools in Azerbaijan is more than 4500. The number of computerized schools is much less than the number of general schools. Of course, the remaining schools should be computerized by the time mentioned above - until 2008. It is clear from the figures that the current situation in school computerization is not satisfactory. It can be hoped that the rest of the schools will be computerized at the scheduled time according to the aforementioned program prepared by the Ministry of Education. It should also be noted that computerization of the school, in other words, giving the school a computer, does not solve the problem. Computer support does not fully respond to its effective use in education. The preparation of materials for the use of literature on the computer is also a very important factor in the formation of the ability of literature teachers to use the computer, and there are very serious tasks in front of them in this field.

In the aforementioned report of the Minister of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Emin Amrullayev, it is rightly stated: "We understand well that providing computers to schools is only the beginning of the work. The main issue is their efficient use, the application of ICT as a learning object, as a tool in the learning process, management, and educational research. It is for this reason that one of our most serious tasks in the field of ICT provision is the preparation of electronic training materials for individual subjects.

Of course, as the honorable minister said, school computerization is just the beginning. The presence of a computer does not mean that it serves to improve the quality of education, and for it, along with a number of other factors, teacher training, the level of the teacher's ability to work with computers, etc. such factors are important. In order to realistically reflect and objectively assess the current state of computer use in schools, continuous observations were made in urban and rural schools of the republic during the research period, interviews were organized with school leaders and teachers who teach literature, as well as various regions of the republic. In order to cover, a questionnaire was distributed among the school heads and literature teachers and various questions were included in each of them in order to learn their attitude towards the use of computers:

A questionnaire distributed among school principals

1. How many computers are there in your school and how are they used?
2. Is there a computer in the literature office of your school, are you satisfied with its use?
3. Are the laboratory assistants in your classrooms able to work on computers?
4. Do laboratory assistants help subject teachers in the field of computer use? If they don't, why?
5. How many literature teachers work in your school, do they initiate the use of computers in the educational process? If not, what is the reason?
6. What measures have you taken for teachers who cannot work with computers to learn how to work with computers, or what is your proposal in this direction?
7. What kind of computer training materials do you have? What is the initiative of teachers in this field?
8. Are you interested in how the use of the computer affects the learning material? What can you say about the result?

9. What do you need for computer use in training?

Questionnaire distributed among literature teachers

1. Do you know how to work with a computer, if not, are you trying to learn?
2. How many computers are there in the school where you work and where (which room) are they installed?
3. Is there a computer installed in the literature office?
4. Do you use computers in literature classes?

5. How do you evaluate the impact of computer use on the assimilation of literary and artistic materials?

6. When explaining literary and artistic materials through the use of computers, how does it affect students' interest, in other words, do students see it as entertainment or as a learning tool?

7. What kind of materials does the use of computers give better results in teaching?

8. What literary and artistic materials are there in the literature office for using the computer, do they help you while using them?

9. Are you trying to prepare material for computer use yourself?

10. What is your request to higher education institutions in the field of computer use in improving the quality of literature teaching?

School principals and literature teachers wrote answers to the questions indicated in the questionnaire. In addition, the working conditions in which we work allow us to communicate with schools and literature teachers in a wider circle, to conduct interviews for the purpose of research, to listen to numerous lessons, and to analyze and generalize them. From this point of view, it was possible to objectively assess the current situation in schools related to the research topic.

385 responses were received from heads of urban and rural schools of different regions to the questionnaire distributed among school heads. In these answers to the first question of the questionnaire - "How many computers are there in your school and how are they used?" to the question, 80 school heads answered "yes". But the number is shown differently. From the answer to the question, it is clear that the number of schools provided with computers in one way or another is only 20.7 percent of the schools that received answers. It is difficult to consider this number acceptable for the current state of education in Azerbaijan.

"Does your school have a computer in the literature room, and as a school leader, are you comfortable using it?" from the answer to the question, it is clear that 52 out of 365 schools have computers installed in the literature office. This is 13.5 percent of the schools whose principals responded. Or "How many literature teachers work in your school, do they initiate the use of computers in the educational process, and if not, what is the reason?" " question received different answers.

One of the questionnaires states: "There are 5 literature teachers in our school. Only one of them takes the initiative to use the computer in certain situations. The reason why teachers do not use computers is explained by their lack of skills to work with computers. Or "What kind of training materials do you have for using the computer for different subjects?" How is the initiative of teachers in this field?" In one of his speeches, Mr. E. Amrullayev stated that "One of our most serious jobs in the field of provision is the preparation of electronic training materials for individual subjects. These materials for the subjects of history, biology, chemistry and physics of Azerbaijan are delivered to schools." However, those materials have not yet reached our school. Although teachers take the initiative to prepare such materials, it is impossible to be satisfied with them. Such materials should be prepared according to certain scientific principles. There is a serious need for electronic learning materials in our school.

Since the topic under study is related to the subject of literature, special attention was paid to the use of computers in literature classes and its effect on the improvement of students' literary knowledge during the research. From this point of view, working with literature teachers on a larger scale has been brought to the fore. Literature classes were observed in schools, the goal was to learn the use of computer equipment by literature teachers in the teaching process and how to draw the necessary conclusions from it.

525 responses were received to the questionnaire distributed among teachers. These answers were carefully reviewed and the answers given to individual questions were summarized by mathematical calculation. Question 1 of the questionnaire for literature teachers "Do you know

how to work with a computer, and if you can't, do you try to learn?" 135 people answered "I can" to some extent, which is 25.7 percent of the literature teachers who participated in the survey. This can be shown in the example of a specific school as follows: In the questionnaire of the school leaders, "How many people work as literature teachers in your school and how many of them know how to use computers in class?" the answer to the question says: There are 14 literature teachers in our school. Only 3 of them have completed a computer course and are able to work on a computer. This is 21.4 percent of literature teachers working in that school.

From observations, interviews conducted with teachers, answers to the questionnaire, it is concluded that teachers need different materials to use in literature lessons. This is the last point of the questionnaire distributed among the teachers: What is your request to higher education institutions in the field of computer use in improving the quality of literature teaching? in all the answers to the question "we have a great need for methodological literature" is expressed.

It is not necessary to analyze all the answers received to the questionnaire and give a sample of all of them. There is no need to reflect them in the form of a general table. The general conclusion from the current situation in republican schools is that the use of computers in literature teaching does not meet the requirements of the time and era. On the one hand, this is related to the lack of computer equipment in schools, and on the other hand, the lack of computer skills of literature teachers. From the interviews, it can also be concluded that teachers are interested in using computers. However, many of them do not have the habits of working with electronic equipment.

Experience shows that 20-22 percent of literature teachers have learned how to use computers in different ways to one degree or another, and they are able to use computers. But the number of such, as mentioned, is small. Thus, care should be taken to develop the computer skills of teachers. Times require teachers to deal with computer equipment. Without answering this demand, it is difficult to talk about improving the quality of education in Azerbaijani schools, and about making students draw the necessary conclusions from educational materials. The state of Azerbaijan constantly cares for the young generation to acquire knowledge at a level that meets the requirements of the time and to develop as a personality. It is the duty of every school leader and teacher to respond to this concern and to succeed in the education of young people.

ҚАЙТАЛАНАТЫН ТІЛДІК ҰҒЫМДАРДЫ ПӘНІШІЛІК КІРІКТІРУ ӘДІСІ АРҚЫЛЫ ИГЕРТУДІҢ ТИІМДІЛІГІ

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Қоғам талабына сай білім сапасын көтерудің, жан-жақты білімді ұрпақ тәрбиелеудің басты бір әдісі- пәндерді кіріктіре оқыту. Кіріктіре оқыту— процесс және нәтиже. Процесс ретінде оқу материалын қосу, біріктіру, жақындату мақсатын ұсынатын тұтас дидактикалық жүйе болса, нәтиже—тұлғаның әлеуметтенуі, шығармашылық ойлауының дамуы. Яғни интеграциялауды бір тұтас болатындай бөліктерді бүтін шығатындай етіп біріктіру деуге болады. Кіріктіре оқыту – кез келген мәселені емес, бір заңдылыққа, бір тұжырымдамаға бағынатын бір ұғымды кешенді түрде әр түрлі мақсатта (бірнеше пәннің немесе бір пәннің негізінде) жан-жақты қарастыратын, пәндерден алған білімді толықтыратын, нақтылайтын, жақындастыратын, олардың арасындағы байланысты, айырмашылықты айқындайтын, тұтас білім қалыптастыратын жүйе. Интеграция дәстүрлі пәннен алған білімді жаңаша сипатта (жан-жақты толықтырылған) талдау, нақтылау, толықтыру тәсілі болып табылады. Яғни пәндік білімді пәнаралық байланыс арқылы алғанжаңа біліммен байланыстыру, қосу арқылы білімді бір тұтас жүйеге айналдыру. Пәнаралық байланыста оқушының білімін жақын пәндерді пайдалану арқылы толықтыру, нақтылау, кеңейту мақсаты болса, интеграциялы оқытудың нақты мақсаты— пәндерді кіріктіре оқыту негізінде құбылыстың ерекшеліктері, заңдылықтары, практикалық тиімділігі негізінде оқушының құбылысқа басқаша талдау жасау арқылы ойлау, өзбетімен іздену, басқа пәндердің негізінде тақырыпты басқа қырынан кеңірек қарастыру, өзіндік тұжырымдар жасау, шығармашылық ойлауды туғызатын ғылыми ойлауын қалыптастыру.

Ал ғылыми ойлау – ғылыми білім негізінде қалыптасатын болса, ғылым жүйесін оқылатын пән жүйесінде жеткізу, яғни оқу пәнінің мүмкіндігі арқылы студентке тұтас ғылыми-пәндік білім беру; игерген теориялық білімді кез келген жағдайда пайдалана алатын технологиялық біліктілік, шығармашылық қабілет қалыптастыру. Демек, аталған заңдылықтардың бірлігін, тұтастығын сақтау нәтижесінде: білім алушының қоршаған ортаны, табиғатты, яғни әлемді тұтастықта, байланыста қабылдауда диалектико-материалистік көзқарасын қалыптастыруға; дамытушылық қызметі: білім алушының белсенділігін, шығармашылық және жүйелі, сыни ойлау қабілетін дамытуға; білімдік қызметі: білім алушыда пәнаралық байланыстың жақын пәндерді тұтастықта қабылдауға, олардың арасындағы себеп-салдарлық байланысты айқындауға; материалды игеруде: анализ, синтез, салыстыру жалпылау және жүйелеу сияқты танымдық әдістерді пайдалануға мүмкіндік болады; зерттеушілік, тілдік, қатысымдық, ақпараттық іскерлік арта түседі; оқу-танымдық кешенді құзыреттілік, өз әрекетінің нәтижесін өзі бағалауға қалыптасады. Кіріктіре оқытудың әдістемелік қызметі – қоршаған орта, оның заңдылықтары туралы тұтас білім қалыптастыруда пәнішілік және пәнаралық байланысты бекіте түсу. Демек, кіріктіре оқыту: білім алушының танымдық қызығушылығын арттырады, әлемнің ғылыми картинасын

тұтастықта қабылдауға, әр пән бойынша қарастырып отырған бір мәселенің арасындағы себеп-салдарлық байланыстарды тереңіректүсінуге, ұғымды теориялық және практикалық тұрғыдан жан-жақты зерделеуге, салыстыруға, нәтижесінде білімін жүйеліпәнаралық байланыс арқылы фактіні не құбылысты саналы ой елегінен өткізуге үйренеді, зерттеушілік әрекет пайда болады, шығармашылық қабілеті, сыни ойлауы, қиялы, есте сақтау қабілеті арта түседі, интеллектуалды ой- өрісі дамиды, ақиқат дүниенің біртұтас жүйе екендігі туралы ғылыми көзқарас қалыптасады, уақытты үнемдеуге, бір тақырыпты әр пән бойынша қайталайбермеуге мүмкіндік болады т.т.

Кіріктіре оқытудың сипаты:

- жеке тұлғаға бағыттай оқыту, яғни білім беру үдерісінде адам–басты құндылық;
- жалпылама пәндік білім, яғни кіріктірілген пәндердің заңдылықтары негізінде саналы, сапалы, тұтас білім қалыптастыру;
- ішкі, сыртқы, ұйымдастырушылық мотив туғызу (ояту);
- білім беруде жүйелілік, яғни ғылыми теориялардың іштей байланысын саналытүсіну, қабылдау;
- білім беруді проблемалық жағдаяттарға құру;
- рефлексиялық әрекет;
- диалогтік сипат, яғни шындық диалогтік қарым-қатынастан туындайды. т.т.

Интеграциялық оқытудағы ең маңызды мәселе оқыту жүйесіне қажетті мәселелерді анықтау. Атап айтқанда:

- кіріктіре оқытудың мотиві, мақсаты айқын болуы;
- кіріктіре оқытылатын пәндердің құрамы;
- жүйеқұрушы және қосымша компоненттер;
- интеграцияның формасы;
- кіріктірілетін пәндердің сипаты;
- материалды орналастырудың бірізділігі;
- тиімді әдістер мен тәсілдер, рефлексия;
- кіріктірілетін технологиялар, олардың сипаты;
- білім алушылардың игерген білім деңгейлерін тексеру формалары мен түрлері.

Пәндерді кіріктіре оқыту үшін: кіріктірілетін пәндерден алынатын тақырып бір-біріне жақын болуы, немесе бір мәселеге құрылуы; бірдей әдіс-тәсілге негізделуі; кіріктірілетін оқу пәндері бір тұжырымдамаға, заңдылыққа құрылуы. Кіріктірілетін пәндерден алынатын материалдар мазмұны, өткізу формасы, әдіс-тәсілі жағынан қабысып бірін-бірі толықтырып тұруы, яғни оқу пәндері дидактикалық бірліктерді ірілендіріп игерту технологиясына негізделуі тиімді. Мазмұнды құрайтын материалға талдау жасай отырып, олар: негізгі және қосымша деп жіктеледі. Негізгі материал жүйеқұрушы компонент болып есептеледі. Оған интегратор пәніндегі негізгі ұғымға қатысты материал жатады. Материалдыорналастыруда алдымен негізгі жүйеқұрушы материал беріледі де, одан кейін сол жүйеқұрушы материалдың мазмұнын ашатын, толықтыратын, нақтылайтын материал қамтылады.

Кіріктірілетін пәндерге сипаттама бергенде мақсат бірлігін, заңдылықтары мен тұжырым бірлігін, әдіс-тәсіл, технология бірлігіне назар аударылады.[1]. Интеграциялық оқытуды іске асыратын негіз сабақ болғандықтан, оның өзіне тән ерекшеліктерінің болуы заңды. Мұндай сабақта алдымен интегратор ретінде негізгі пән алынады да, басқа пәндер негізгі пәндегі мәселені тереңдету, салыстыру, кеңейту, нақтылау мақсатын көздейді.

Осыған орай ондай сабақтың құрылымы да басқаша болады. Атап айтқанда, сабақтың әр кезеңінде мәселе интегратор пәннің тақырыбына тәуелділік, ықшамдылық, нақтылық, логикалық байланыстылық сақталынуы тиіс. Яғни кіріктіру фактілерді (әр пәннен бір мәселені) салыстыру, талдау, кіріктіру арқылы мәселенің жаңа қырын айқындаудың, иерілген білімін толықтырудың, тереңдетудің, оны жүйелеудің негізгі көзі болып табылады.

Мұндай нәтижеге жету үшін қарастырылып отырған мәселенің (әр пән бойынша) теориялық негізі, интеграциялы оқытудың басты қағидалары мен заңдылықтары, ерекшеліктері мен маңызы бағамдалуы тиіс. Өйткені интеграциялы оқыту өзіне тән ұстанымдарымен, нысанымен, формасымен, деңгейімен, бағыты, кезеңімен, оқытудың жаңа бір формасы, әдісі ретінде сипатталады. Білім беруді ізгілендіруде жеке адамның жан-жақты және толық қалыптасуы тек қана бағдарламалық материалды игерумен ғана емес, олардың өзін-өзі тануына, өзін-өзі бағалауына, басқалармен игерген білімін бөлісуге талпынуына жағдай жасау, олардың танымдық, рухани әрекет мүмкіншілігін белсендіре түсу маңызды.

Кіріктіре оқытудың әдіс-тәсіліне, деңгейіне, бағытына қарай түрлері: пәнаралық және пәнішілік делініп жіктеледі.[2]. Біздің нысанымыз - пәнішілік кіріктіру. Пәнішілік кіріктіру – бір пәннің аясындағы ұғымдарды кіріктіру жүйесі. Білім беру жүйесінде кіріктіре оқыту 3 деңгейлі үлгі ретінде беріледі. 1. Оқытудың мақсаты: қоршаған ортаны тұтастықта қабылдау, бөлшекті бүтінге айналдыру туралы түсінік, ұғым қалыптастыру; 2. Оқытудың құралы: тұтас білім қалыптастырудың, пәндік білімдерді кіріктірудің амалы, тәсілі. 3. Нәтиже: игерген білімді біртұтас жүйелеуге, оны шығармашылықпен қолдануға, өзіндік көзқарасы мен бағытын, ғылыми ойлау стилін, қызығушылығын қалыптастыруға, жан-жақты дамуына мүмкіндік жасалады.

Пәнішілік кіріктіру дидактикалық бірліктерді ірілендіріп беру (УДЕ) және модульдік технологияның негіздерін басшылыққа алады. УДЕ бойынша жұрнаққа қатысты ереже-анықтамалар, пікірлер, ғылыми көзқарастар жинақталып бір үлкен блок ретінде беріледі. Модуль-блоктік технологияның құрылымы бойынша: модульге ену, ақпарат, әдістемелік нұсқау, тексеру және бағалау жүйелері сақталады. Мысалы, қазақ тілі пән ретінде мектептен басталып, жоғары оқу орындарында жалғасады. Осы кезеңдердегі оқулықтардың бәрінде (әр түрлі мақсатта, әр түрлі көлемде) тілдік ұғымдардың бәрі, оның ішінде «жұрнақ» тақырыбы да қайталанып беріліп отыратыны белгілі. «Жұрнақ» тақырыбына қалам тартпаған ғалымдар (А.Ысқақов, Ы.Маманов, Н.Оралбаева, С.Исаев, К.Құрманалиев т.т.) кемде-кем. Біздің басты мақсатымыз ғалымдардың зерттеулеріндегі, оқулықтардағы берілген ережелерді жинақтап, сөзжасам жұрнақтарының табиғатына қатысты тұтас бір анықтама құрастыру. Ереже-анықтамаларды жинақтау алдын ала студенттерге тапсырма ретінде берілді.

Интегратор пән ретінде «сөзжасам» пәні, қосымша пән ретінде «морфология» пәні негізге алынды. Интегратор пән «сөзжасам» болғандықтан, жұрнақтардың сөз мағынасын өзгертудегі: мағыналық, қызметтік, қолданыстық, т.т. ерекшеліктерін сөз түрлендіретін жұрнақтармен салыстыра отырып, студенттің тұтастықта қабылдауын ұйымдастыру. Мақсатымызға жету үшін кейс-стади әдісін қолдандық. Кейсті құрастыруда мынадай жүйе басшылыққа алынды: ситуацияны құрастыру (кейс), білім алушылардың тірек білімдерін жаңғырту (сұрақтар, проблемалық жағдаяттар, т.т.), әдістемелік нұсқау, ақпаратқа талдау жасау, басты проблеманы таба білу, оны шешудің жолдарын анықтау, қорытынды жасау. Кейсті талдауда бірнеше әдістікіріктіре пайдалануға мүмкіндік болады. Мысалы, модельдеу, яғни жағдаятты құрастыру, жүйелі талдау, сипаттау, проблемалық жіктеу, миға шабуыл, пікір талас әдістері тиімді саналады. Кейске қойылатын басты талап: мақсаты мәтінге (кейске) сай, яғни мәтіннің мазмұнын ашатындай болуы; өзекті мәселеге құрылуы, аналитикалық ойлауын дамытуы, пікірталасқа итермелеуі, бірнеше шешімінің болуы т.т.

Нәтиже: лексикалық, грамматикалық, сөзжасамдық мағыналардың табиғаты айқындалады, сөзжасам жұрнақтарының белгілері жүйеленіп, тұтас бір анықтама құрастыруға, жұрнақтардың ерекшеліктерін (мағыналық, қызметтік, қолданыстық) салыстырмалы түрде топтап, сызба түрінде көрсетуге мүмкіндік болады.

Студенттер туынды түбірлерге мысалдар жинады, олардың сипаты мынадай: күй- күйшіл-күйшідей-күйшілік-күйшілдік-күйсіз; дау-даугер-даукес-даукестік-даулағыш-

даулас-даулау-дауласушы-даурық-даурығу-даурығушы-даурығысу-даурықтыр- даурықтыру- даурыққыш-дауыс-даушы-даурықпашы-даурықпашылық т.т. мысалдар жазып, оларға құрамына қарай талдау жасады. Бірден сөзжасам жұрнақтарының табиғатын толық ашатындай анықтама құрастыру оңай болмады. Ондай әрекетке студент қалыптасуы тиіс. Берілген сұрақтарға да жауаптары толық болмады. Сондықтан қысқаша түсініктеме берілді. Қазақ тілінің ғылыми грамматикаларында қосымшалар: жалғау (септік, көптік, жіктік және тәуелдік болып 4-ке бөлінетіні белгілі) және жұрнақ болып жіктелгенімен, жұрнақтарға байланысты әр түрлі пікірлер бар, айталық, ғылыми грамматикаларда жұрнақтар: сөз тудырушы, сөз түрлендіруші және форма тудырушы болып жіктеліп келгенін оқырман қауым біледі. Бұл орайда сөз тудыратын қосымшалар өзі жалғанған сөзіне жаңа мағына үстейтіндігі белгілі, ал сөз түрлендіруші мен форма тудырушы қосымшаларда мұндай мүмкіндік бар ма деген сұрақтың болуы заңды.

Бұл сұрақтың жауабын ғалым С.Исаев: қосымшалардың сөзге жалғанғанда беретін мағынасы (басты белгісі) мен қызметіне қарай: сөз тудырушы және сөз түрлендіруші деп екіге бөлуді ұсынады.[4]. Демек, туынды сөзге талдау жасағанда оның мағыналық (яғни түбірдің мағынасы өзгерді ме, өзгермеді ме) ерекшелігіне және қызметіне назар аударамыз. 2-ші сұрақтың жауабы да туынды сөздің мағынасымен байланысты. Яғни жаңа мағына тудыратын сөзжасам жұрнақтары (сөзжасамдық мағына), сөзтүрлем жұрнақтары арқылы грамматикалық мағына пайда болады. Сонымен қатар кез келген жұрнақ кез келген сөзге жалғана бермейді. Сөзжасам жұрнақтары сөзге таңдап-талғап жалғанады.

Сабақты кіріктіре оқыту технологиясының талабына сай ұйымдастыру әр оқытушыдан әдістемелік, технологиялық, кәсіби құзыреттілік шеберлікті талап ететіні даусыз. Дегенмен, бірнеше пәннің негізін құрайтын бір ұғымды сирек болса да, кіріктіре оқыту әдісімен өткізіп тұру артық болмас еді. Білім алушыларын өзбетімен шығармашылықпен ойлау, сұрақ қою, проблема жасау, оны шешудің жолын таба білуге қалыптастыру – әр оқытушының басты мақсаты болса, сол мақсатқа жетудің тиімді бір жолы сабақты кіріктіре оқыту әдісі деуге болады.

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THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF FORMATION OF METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of methodological competence of future teachers. Methodological approaches to the study of the problem of the formation of methodical competence of future teachers are also analyzed .

Keywords: the theoretical and methodological foundations, methodical competence, future teacher, pedagogical university.

It is known from the history of pedagogical science that the effectiveness and effectiveness of a teacher's activity is dependent on the level of his or her professional development. Science only develops when it is supplemented with new knowledge. The accuracy of knowledge depends on the research methodology. Methodology - (Greek word methods is the way of research or cognition, theory, doctrine and word logos, notion): 1) a system of principles and methods for organizing and organizing theoretical and practical activities; 2) teaching on methods of scientific knowledge; 3) a set of methods used in a particular field of science [1].

V.A. Slastenin stated that "Methodology is the key to the study of phenomena and processes in higher pedagogical education" [2, p. 6]. In modern science it is necessary to understand "methodology as the doctrine of principles, types and methods of creation of scientifically-cognitive activity" [16, p.3]

V.I. Zagvyazinsky defined the methodology as follows: "Methodology is a concrete way of performing the requirements of scientific analysis and a tool of theoretical research, a system of theoretical knowledge, which plays the role of a governing principle" [21, p.9].

E.G .Yudin in the structure of methodological education: philosophical, general scientific, specific scientific and technological components [19].

"The *methodology of pedagogy* is a set of philosophical ideas that have undergone a fundamental study of the phenomena of nature and society and have a decisive influence on the theoretical interpretation of those phenomena. The doctrine of the structure, logical organization of methods and means of pedagogical reality, abilities and forms of scientific knowledge in pedagogy" [13].

Finally, the methodology of pedagogical science is the teaching of the principles, types, principles, methods, and ways of recognizing and renewing the teaching process.

Education policy is an essential element of any country's policy, and it is the most important tool in ensuring fundamental human rights and freedoms. It identifies strategic goals and objectives for the development of the educational potential of the country, and guarantees their implementation through coordinated actions of the state and society. Not only will education policy accelerate the pace of socio-economic and scientific-technical development, but also the process of humanization of society and the growth of its cultural level [10].

All the good that is happening in the world, all the bad, are done with the mind, with the science. For example, space exploration, use of computer technology in all aspects of life, the invention of weapons of destruction, human casualties, etc.

For this reason, science should be taught only to a good-natured, caring, honest, hard-working man.

Shakarim Kudayberdiyev said that harming the public if bad people do science.

"Do not give in to the true sinner, he will read,
My weapon is a shotgun; it can throw science.
A science that rules the world and violates it,
And the evil one, and the scientist to the bottom. "[13]

Finally, only education and science can counteract the catastrophic negative processes in the spiritual field. Only knowledge is capable of playing the final historical role in the reproduction and continuous reproduction of the highest moral ideals and priorities of life.

Methodological education consists of four levels: philosophical, general scientific, specific scientific and technological. Each level of the methodology is a complex interconnected system.

The general principles of cognition and sound apparatus of science form the philosophical level of methodology. At this level, the contentious basis of any methodological knowledge that defines actuality and cognition is realized. Currently, there are several philosophical teachings that are the methodology of different sciences. There are existentialism, neotomism, neopositivism, pragmatism, dialectical materialism in pedagogy. such philosophical teachings as

The main task of vocational education is to teach students to solve pedagogical problems. The preparation to solve pedagogical problems is based on *methodological knowledge*, except subject *knowledge*. The basis of the general scientific level of methodological education is the scientific basis used in many fields of science.

The general scientific level of the methodology guides the researcher into the practice that causes the researcher to consider systems with their laws and structures as phenomena of life. At the system level, each of the components is considered separately, not in relation to each other, in movement, or in development. When one component of a system changes, so do the other components. Therefore, it is possible to determine the qualitative characteristics and integrative system properties that are not present in the elements of the system.

The action, the basis, the way and the key condition for the person's development are actions. Consequently, we have used personal, actionable approaches to investigating and developing the methodological competence of a math teacher in his professional preparation. Due to the fact that the nature of a person is broader, more multifaceted and complex than his actions, a dialogic approach is used in teaching and educational work. The dialogue platform is built on the basis of an anthropological approach based on belief in a person's positive potential, such as continuous creative development and the cultivation and improvement of one's good qualities and abilities. The activity of the individual and the need for self-improvement are not considered separately. These qualities develop in the context of communicating with others based on a dialogic principle. The dialogue platform, together with the personality and the action platform, forms the essence of the methodology of humanistic pedagogy. The above methodological principles are implemented in relation to the cultural context. This culture stands a man of action - action as a way to understand. He - something

known as a universal description of the action - direct action and social and humanistic orientation. Finally, one can be sure that the person who has mastered the culture also knows the techniques of creative activity.

Human beings live and learn in a specific social and cultural environment, and belong to a particular ethnicity. In this regard, the cultural approach to the ethno pedagogical platform. In this shift, the unity of universal, national traits clearly identifies the individual as a "person".

An anthropological approach is the systematic use of all the human sciences, which are taken into account in the design and implementation of the teaching process, and are considered as forms of education. The foregoing approaches make it possible to analyze significant educational issues in a single dialectical unit and to establish a hierarchy of these problems.

The third level of the methodology is the actual scientific level. It is a system of principles and methods of research used in a particular scientific discipline. Specific science methodology includes specific issues of scientific knowledge in the area and high level of methodology issues, such as systematic approach or modeling in pedagogical research.

The technique and technique of the research constitute the technological level of the methodology. This level ensures that materials (based on human experience) that can be included in scientific education after the initial processing have been obtained. In modern pedagogical researches are used systematic, complex, unified, personality, action, historical, qualitative, quantitative, phenomenological, meaningful approaches.

Psychological science has explored the *unified* methodological principle of consciousness and action, which discloses the continuous link between psychological theory and practice . The given principle is A.N .Leontiev [8], S.L.Rubinstein [12], A. A. Smirnov [15], K. Zharykbaev [21] and other psychologists. The human psyche during the activity (work, study, game, etc.). looks and is formed. The human consciousness is not self-evident, it is first shaped by overcoming certain difficulties in the learning and work process, and by new achievement.

I.P. Rachenko considers the professionalism of the teacher in the system of integrated pedagogical activity and in the scientific organization of pedagogical work. It states "three key professional requirements: 1) love for children, their subject, and their profession; 2) professional literacy; 3) functional competence "[11, p.9]. He says in order to become a specialist in his book, Integrative Pedagogy, you need to master the scientific organization of pedagogical work.

N.D. Kuchugurova "has achieved a certain level of personality traits, which transmit the students' professional methodological training, future knowledge, skills, and socio-cultural experience through mathematical education, and promote their development and self-development," said ND defines [6, p. 162].

S.I. Vysotskaya uses a *holistic* approach to the formation of a teacher personality and considers professionalism as the purpose of training teachers in higher pedagogical institutions [20, p.19].

Recently, the term 'professional training' has been used as a component of professionalism in connection with the introduction of new pedagogical technologies in practice. For example, V.V. Serikov describes professional readiness as: "ability to justify one's own actions, to build oneself on the basis of internal professional motivation, to set and achieve goals based on an authoritative model of education and upbringing, to take responsibility for decisions made, etc".

In the work of V.V Kraevsky [5], I.Ya. Lerner [9], the content of didactic preparation of students, based on the integration of didactics and subject methodology, was determined using a *systematic approach*.

The methodology of researching the formation of methodological competencies in the professional preparation of a mathematics teacher shows how research and practical work can be done.

In the course of research, the following principles were used to develop a model of forming the methodological competence of a professional teacher of mathematics using theoretical and practical achievements of pedagogy:

- 1) to rely on the correctness of pedagogical phenomena, arising under the influence of internal objective laws, contradictions, effective causal connections;
- 2) application of a holistic approach to the study of pedagogical phenomena and processes;
- 3) the study of the phenomenon in its development in relation to other phenomena;
- 4) the use of a combination of multiple complementary methods when choosing a research method to solve any scientific problem;
- 5) methods of research should correspond to the essence of the subject of research;
- 6) to consider the process of development as self-development and self-development, being the driving force and source of internal contradictions;
- 7) conduct experiment in the educational process, in such a way that it does not cause criticism of the accused, does not go beyond the rules of morality.

Let's take a look at methodological approaches to building a methodological competence of a math teacher in his professional preparation. The category (category) is a concept derived from the need to form a person in connection with the rapid development of our country in the socio-economic development. It is not a system of didactic concepts. Formation of professional competence of future specialists, in general, the ability to apply the knowledge gained in practice, is one of the important issues of the modern education system. In the context of modernizing education, this is the purpose of building the methodological competence of the future teacher. The term "competence" comes from the word "competent". Well, the term "competent" has long been used. The term "competent" is used to mean knowledgeable, knowledgeable, and knowledgeable. It means that the Latin word "competens" is capable. The term "competent" is used in the sense "in accordance with the position, knowledgeable about a particular problem, a teacher well aware of his subject, a specialist according to his specialty".

In a foreign dictionary, the Latin word "competens" means "capable, appropriate", that is, "knowledgeable in a particular field" [3]. The various dictionaries have slightly different meaning from the term "competence": 1) "a group of issues ..." 2) "knowledge and experience in a particular field" [18].

The meaning of the term "competency" is more precisely explained in foreign explanatory dictionaries. In this jurisdiction (the Latin word *competetia*), it means "a set of questions of responsibility" or "a set of well-known questions by an experienced person" [3]. Finally, competence is, firstly, the responsible authority of an official, and secondly, the knowledge, skills, abilities and abilities of the person responsible.

In the model of human psychological development, the concept of "competence" is based on theories of behavior and behavior of a person. It is used as a "unit of measure" when solving problems, for which a person consumes less "resources" and needs good results in order to transform situations. Being able to organize one's own "resources" and other "resources" to achieve the goal of climate change is understood as competence [2]. In the "fund" of the subject are indicators of his level of education, knowledge, skills and abilities, psychological characteristics, etc. include. M.P. Lapchik and N.V. Chekalova defines competency as an organization of spending the "fund" to achieve her goal, and highlights the following key competencies:

- organize yourself and your workforce in solving the problem;
- get information about the situation and about yourself;
- use of other people's resources through communication [7].

These competencies are conditionally acquired. In addressing specific situations, the entity assesses the situation, provides resources, implements the plan, evaluates its effectiveness, and

reflects in a single action. Thus, the *principle that competence* is best for a person is the *principle of competence*. From this, it does not mean that each person has a different form of competence in each specific situation. A person uses other resources for other purposes in other situations. In psychological and pedagogical theory and practice, the terms "competence" and "competency" are defined differently. In foreign dictionary "competent" - person with competence: Competent (French.) - competent, prudential; Competens (lat.) - fit, capable; Competere - to demand, to correspond, to operate; Competence - ability.

The definition of competence includes the theoretical and practical training used in knowledge, skills, experience, and knowledge. Competence refers to the knowledge and skills that are capable of being professionally competent, capable of analyzing, evaluating, and evaluating. Particular attention is paid to general cultural competence, as a basis of professional competence. The definitions of competence are defined as the ability of an individual to solve various problems, such as the knowledge, skills and competences required to complete a particular task. External and internal conditions and requirements, related to the motivation and other valuable qualities that a person needs, promote a comprehensive understanding of competence.

Competence is the level of competence of a person who demonstrates a certain degree of competence, allowing constructive action in changing social conditions. M.P. Lapchik and N.V. Chekaleva methodical competence of the teacher of informatics "Theoretical and practical readiness to continuous teaching of computer science courses, using modern pedagogical technologies of secondary school education, the ability to develop their professional skills in the field of information informatization" [7].

Today, there is no commonality of the same classification of competences and how many types of competences should be formed. Around the world there is a *platform for* distinguishing competencies from relevant competencies. However, there have not been accurate guidelines for the selection of relevant and sufficient competencies to ensure the success of human affairs.

Actual competences:

- a) allows solving difficult problems in different situations;
- b) high organizational skills (intellectual, emotional);
- b) requires complex skills (ability to understand, reason, plan, etc.);
- c) at different levels.

Finally, relevant competencies are applied in a variety of contexts, and they are universal. Based on the model of professional activity, the model of organization of vocational training, the logic of the competency logic, which guided the organization of vocational training in a pedagogical university and the choice of its content and technology.

In the context of modern times, a person's attitude to work, the requirements for a specialist, and the goals, strategies, tasks and content of education will radically change in a person's professional activities. At present pedagogical university it is necessary to modernize forms of education and training, to form culture, to develop culture of choice of means and strategies of training, to realize separate educational direction. The competency approach recognizes the need to foster the content of the preparation and the individual learning path, and to activate the learning process itself. Therefore, the creation of vocational education in the logic of the competence platform will meet the requirements of today.

Thus, in the professional training of future teacher is carried out of the competence approach to the formation of methodical competence in training formed a responsible attitude of students to self- education and professional development. On its basis it focuses on the creation of a non standard innovative model of a specific professional activity

The analysis made it possible to understand the essence of the concept being studied. Thus, the common methodological approaches to the research, the study of the problem

of formation of methodical competence of the future teacher methodological platforms as a platform for identity, personality, competence, culturological, Action, information, consistency platforms have been received. The methodological approaches needed to study the problem of forming the methodological competence of future teachers are given in Table 4 .

In the practice of higher pedagogical institutions, the same requirements are required for communication with students, the choice of methods and means of educational work, regardless of the course. Therefore, in the so-called didactics section of pedagogy, the didactic principles of teaching all courses, including mathematics, have been studied and developed. Pedagogical principles are:

- 1) to expand the purpose of teaching;
- 2) as a principle of effective teaching process;
- 3) organization of formation of methodological competence of the future teacher of mathematics and selection of its content, methods, means, types and their relation;
- 4) development of methodological competence of a math teacher by certain rules.

The same requirements are set for the teaching process as a math's teacher who pursues the goals of education and upbringing of active, conscious and inclusive young people in school.

It is well known that the future mathematician must adhere to the following didactic principles in the teaching of mathematics:

- 1) scientific principle of teaching mathematics;
- 2) Principles of development and upbringing of mathematics;
- 3) the clear principle of teaching mathematics;
- 4) the principles of rationality and activity in teaching mathematics;
- 5) the principle of sound, stable acquisition of knowledge;
- 6) systematic principle of teaching mathematics;
- 7) the principle of understandability of teaching mathematics, etc.

Table 1 - Methodological approaches to researching the issue of shaping the methodological competence of future teachers

Methodological approaches	Formation of methodological competence of future teachers
Personality (K. Zharykbayev, N.V. Kuzmina, A.K. Markova, L.M. Mitina)	Accepting a person as a subject. Personality. Focus on the development and development of personal qualities
Uniformity (N.D.Khmel , K.S.Uspanov ,E.P. Nechitaylova, L.V.Nikitenkova, G.T.Smanova)	Focus on the formation of a holistic personality trait in professional activities
Socio- cultural (E.V. Bondarevskaya , I.A. Novik, Sh.T. Taubayeva, N.D. Khmel)	Formation, development, education of the person is the result of the culture of communication between people
Action (T.Tazhibayev,S.L. Rubinstein, A.N. Leontiev)	To know the person's self-set goals, Action planning, execution, ability to achieve results
Competence platform (G.S.Adolf, A.K. Markova, N..V Kuzmina, V..A.Slastenin, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, E.G.Yudin,I.P. Radchenko, N.D.. Kuchugurova, S. I. Vysotskaya, V.V. Serikov)	Creating conditions for creating training content and personal orientation, recognizing the need to activate independent educational activities and creating constructive actions in transitional social conditions
Informational (E.I.. Bidaibekov , S..M. Kenesbaev, J.A.. Karaev, K. Aganina, B.G. Gershunsky, V.A. Skibitsky , V.A. Sadovnichy , T.A. Sergeeva , E.A. Polat, A.M. Matyushkin , O.A. Agapova , O.A. Krivosheev)	Ability to use information and telecommunication technologies to ensure information literacy, self-education and self-development of the individual.
Consistency (A. Baitursynov, N..D Khmel,)	Conduct professional training of the person through systematic assistance. Components development, one of the movement - to be in close contact with each other

The principles of teaching mathematics in pedagogical higher education institutions were considered above to open up the relationship between the formation of methodological competence and the methodological system of teaching mathematics.

To determine the basic principles of the formation of the future mathematics teacher's teaching competence M.N.Skatkin's the following pedagogical principles were considered:

- upbringing and development;
- link learning with life;
- systematic and gradual education;
- conscious and active learning under the guidance of a teacher;
- team teaching and taking into account the individual characteristics of students;
- development of visual and theoretical thinking;
- effectiveness of teaching and development of creative abilities of students;
- science and comprehensiveness of teaching [15].

In the process of vocational training future teacher of mathematics in pedagogical universities will be:

- 1) content of school mathematics course;
- 2) solving pedagogical problems;
- 3) methods of teaching mathematics;
- 4) innovative types of teaching of mathematics;
- 5) new technologies of teaching mathematics;
- 6) new information and telecommunication technologies in teaching mathematics,

etc. have to master

Future math teacher to learn the system requirements given their high standard of teaching educational courses, educational, psychological, mathematical didactic training on the principles of learning through theoretical and practical training.

In the course of the study, as a pedagogical principle for the formation of methodological competence of a future mathematics teacher, we used the principles of teaching M.N.Skatkin, which included the creation of a psychological environment for the development of a student's personality and the development of innovative types of teaching mathematics, new technologies and information and telecommunication technologies.

Finally, with the effective and bold introduction of new teaching technologies and ICTs in education, we can build an education system that is in line with the traditional education system reform process that is required by the modern society and society.

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Technical Sciences

The role of innovation in enhancing economic competitiveness in Kazakhstan

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Abstract

The article explores a model for the technological modernization of foreign industries and provides recommendations on applying foreign expertise in the context of Kazakhstan. The primary goal was to achieve a new, upgraded economy, with the United States taking the lead in the international race for modernization. Industry modernization involves a systematic, coordinated transformation process. Looking back, Japan's modernization journey allowed it to transition from a developmental model to progressive development, paving the way for its unique path to maturity and global contribution.

China's leadership has acknowledged the necessity of sharing foreign technology and modernization experiences to overcome backwardness and reach a global standard. Successful implementation on a large scale requires effective coordination among various stakeholders, including economic entities, advanced scientific institutions, and other relevant parties.

Keywords: modernization, technological changes, industry, innovation, industrial modernization, post-industrial economy, fundamental research, new technologies, export licenses, and innovative development

Introduction

Right now, Kazakhstan finds itself intrigued by the dynamics among the United States, China, and Japan. The United States and Japan stand out globally as hubs for industrial resurgence, having reached the pinnacle of post-industrial development. The U.S. industrial policy is dedicated to bolstering its universal leadership, marking a transition from a post-industrial to a global economy. The U.S. adopts a multifaceted approach to industry, employing mechanisms such as regulating access to the domestic market, influencing the global financial system through the dominance of the dollar, and maximizing state potential (1).

Public policy emerges as a crucial factor in sustaining America's technological leadership in industry. The generation of new knowledge plays a pivotal role in industry development, positioning the United States as a frontrunner in exporting licenses for its discoveries, inventions, and innovations. Consequently, other nations in the realm of science and technology find themselves reliant on the United States. Export licenses become integral to the exportation of high-tech industries.

Moreover, the U.S. government has embraced a flexible production structure, responding to the widespread integration of information technologies in firms and corporate communications. Special programs have been instituted to facilitate the collaboration of industrial enterprises, as flexible or combined production entails legally independent firms temporarily uniting as partners under contractual agreements for the production of specific goods (2).

The expenses associated with exploration and investigation encompass both immediate and long-term costs incurred in the process of purposeful creative endeavors. These endeavors aim to continuously generate and disseminate knowledge for novel applications, spanning realms such as humanity, culture, and society. Research and development encompass fundamental and applied research, as well as experimental exploration (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mechanisms related to the US industry

The international labor collaboration aspect of the US State Industrial Policy aims to bolster the significance of the "global Research Laboratory and test site." The objective is to focus on manufacturing exclusively distinctive products, either those that can't be produced elsewhere for certain reasons or products crafted using groundbreaking technologies without equivalents. Priority is given to production that involves scientific and interdisciplinary labor. In the cost structure of goods requiring scientific labor, research and development account for 8-15%, while multi-scientific labor surpasses 15%. This underscores the need for a suitable policy for the modernization of industries and enterprises [3]. The information presented in Figure 2 indicates a notable shift in the allocation of research and development expenditures in the United States during the year 2008.

Figure 2. US R & D expenditures from 2004 to 2015, % GDP (9)

Figure 3. Exports of high-tech goods in the world in 2016, US (9)

The high-speed development of research and development significantly influences the export of advanced technological products. In other words, the expenses incurred in research and development translate into the export of goods, constituting a substantial portion of the sales volume for these products. Examples of such goods encompass a range of items like rockets, spacecraft, computers, pharmaceuticals, scientific instruments, and electrically powered equipment (Figure 3).

In the 20th century, it became evident that a nation with a previously lagging economy, which had been growing steadily at an average rate of 8-10% annually for 20-25 years, could only achieve successful modernization by embracing innovation and technology. Japan exemplified this approach, experiencing an impressive average annual economic growth rate of 10% from 1950 to 1973. During this period, Japan strategically advanced in traditional industrial sectors like armor casting, shipbuilding, and automobile assembly, positioning itself at the forefront through a commitment to new technologies. Japan's dominance in the use of innovative technologies and the implementation of large-scale programs across various markets contributed to its economic success, primarily driven by exclusive dependence on exports. The trajectory of Japan's industrial development is closely tied to scientific and technical accomplishments. Japanese companies align their goals with national interests and collaborate with the government, a legacy possibly stemming from early practices of industrialization where government intervention was crucial to foster modern industry and enhance competitiveness against leading European industrial powers [4].

Japan utilized European scientists for its own objectives by providing financial support in Europe. Concurrently, Japanese scientists welcomed Europeans and Americans into their universities, hastening the assimilation of Western scientific methodologies. Japan initiated the establishment of research centers in the United States and Western Europe. While local experts worked in the MUN-Dai centers, the outcomes, along with the centers themselves, were attributed

to Japan. For instance, the renowned Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in Boston was commissioned by Japan to receive an annual funding of 552 million at the beginning of the 21st century. "I don't know," he said. This amount has since increased. Export revenues were conserved, and the produced goods were exchanged for technology, equipment, and raw materials. News dissemination was swift, and both managers and employees were highly motivated. The government's approval for importing new technologies, especially those strategically crucial for Japan's industrial development, exemplifies the close collaboration between business groups and the government. To ensure its development, Japanese industrial enterprises closely collaborate with banks acting as venture capitalists, financing company projects. Similar to the United States, Japan exports production to other countries while providing labor-intensive, raw material-intensive, and environmentally unfriendly industries and enterprises. Japan's high dependence on raw materials and energy resources for production drives interest in enhancing production, leading to increased research and development, and involving universities in project implementation. Various state support measures, notably preferential taxation and R&D lending, facilitate this. The foundation of Japanese industry development lies in a strategic management system that predates widespread adoption in American and Western European companies. This system places emphasis on goal preparation, forming the basis for long-term planning. Japan acquired licenses for modern industrial goods production and, to finance raw material and technology imports, transitioned to a more stringent economy at the expense of the standard of living. Achieving high quality in licensed production and gaining additional profit through the Earned Brand, Japan reinvested its by-products, maintaining a consistently high savings rate. The Japanese system focused on continually mastering new technology and reinvesting the funds received. Economic development planning, akin to a state plan, was implemented, leading to the creation of institutions such as the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Industry, with roles in coal policy, industrial product inspections, the Bureau of Trade and Development, and heavy industry (5).

Based on the projections and executed strategies outlined by the Chinese leadership for modernization, it can be inferred that China is poised to assume a prominent position on the global stage by 2050. Furthermore, by the close of the 21st century, it is anticipated to emerge as a global leader in geopolitical, cultural, and demographic aspects (6). Economic reforms constitute a pivotal component of the People's Republic of China's (PRC) modernization agenda. The "four modernizations" plan, devised to propel China into a formidable socialist state, encompasses advancements in agriculture, industry, defense capabilities, and scientific and technical infrastructure (7). The favorable trajectory of China's economic modernization is attributable to shifts in the country's economic policies, directed toward fostering growth and nurturing artistic and professional potential. It is noteworthy that the synergistic impact of innovations and economic expansion in China has been optimal for the nation's modernization. The chosen approach of transforming the economic system without altering the political structure has played a significant role in ensuring consistent growth rates in the country's industrial sector over the past two decades (8).

In essence, the collective experience of these nations illustrates a comprehensive listing of goals, objectives, approaches, and techniques employed in structural modernization, along with the outcomes attained. By scrutinizing the experiences of these three countries, it becomes feasible to conceptualize various models for the modernization of Kazakhstan's industry (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Formation of models for the modernization of Kazakhstan's industry

Conclusion

Broadly speaking, the experiences of these nations indicate a detailed account of the goals, methods, and outcomes of structural modernization. Initially, it is crucial to establish a long-term plan and a management system for priority industries and projects based on the country's scientific and technological development plan until 2022. Additionally, Kazakhstan needs to conduct thorough technological modernization in its manufacturing sector alongside dynamic innovative development. This includes the effective transfer of productive technologies from highly developed countries in the traditional Basic Industries to Kazakhstan's fifth sector. Furthermore, there should be an emphasis on promoting the necessity of modernization and shaping a national idea around the transformation of the modernization strategy. This involves creating high-tech and research-intensive industries that integrate global changes with local conditions, considering political, social, and demographic factors. The aim is to make engagement in research and development and high-tech business not only beneficial but also prestigious for individuals working in administrative roles.

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КИНЕМАТИЧЕСКОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПЛОСКОГО РЫЧАЖНОГО МЕХАНИЗМА

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Аннотация

Данная тема посвящена кинематическому анализу плоских рычажных механизмов, которые представляют собой важный класс механических устройств, используемых в различных областях инженерии и машиностроения. В работе рассматривается изучение движения и перемещения элементов рычажных систем, а также влияние различных параметров на их работу. Кинематическое исследование плоского рычажного механизма включает в себя анализ скорости, ускорения и траекторий движения элементов системы. Такой анализ позволяет оптимизировать конструкцию механизма, обеспечивая необходимую производительность и безопасность его работы. Также исследование рычажных механизмов имеет важное прикладное значение при проектировании и улучшении множества устройств, включая маятники, дверные петли, подъемные механизмы, и многое другое.

В данной аннотации рассматриваются *ключевые аспекты* кинематического анализа плоских рычажных механизмов, а также обсуждаются возможные практические применения результатов этого анализа в инженерных задачах. Такой анализ может быть полезен как в образовательных целях, помогая студентам и инженерам лучше понимать принципы работы механизмов, так и в инженерной практике, где он используется для создания эффективных и надежных механических устройств.

Дисциплина «Теория механизмов и машин» является одной из основных машиностроительных дисциплин, являющихся фундаментом общеинженерной подготовки студентов. Она посвящена изучению наиболее общих вопросов исследования и проектирования механизмов и машин.

Человек всегда стремится облегчить свой труд, повысить производительность. Для этого он постоянно совершенствует орудия труда. Так появилось машиностроение. Для того чтобы машина или механизм работали, необходимо знание структуры механизма или машины, определение положений механизмов и траекторий, описываемых отдельными точками и т.д.

Задачей кинематического исследования является определение кинематических параметров механизма, возникающих при движении. Таковыми являются траектория движения, скорость и ускорение, в том числе угол поворота кривошипа, коромысла, шатуна, также угловые скорости и ускорения.

Рычажные плоские механизмы. К рычажным механизмам относятся механизмы, состоящие из звеньев совершающих вращательное, поступательное или плоско – параллельное

движение. Эти механизмы отличаются простотой, высоким КПД и большой нагрузочной способностью, однако они не могут обеспечить любой закон движения ведомого звена, что в некоторой степени ограничивает их применение в технике.

В технологическом оборудовании широко используются следующие виды рычажных механизмов:

- механизмы шарнирного четырехзвенника,
- кривошипно-шатунные механизмы,
- кулисные механизмы.

Плоский – механизм, подвижные звенья которого совершают плоское движение, параллельное одной и той же неподвижной плоскости.

Рисунок 1. Шестизвенный плоский рычажный механизм

Данный механизм называется *плоский рычажный механизм*, в котором звенья соединены плоскими шарнирами. Он состоит из нескольких групп Ассур.

Кинематические цепи, обладающие нулевой степенью подвижности называются группами Ассур.

Рисунок 2. Группа Ассур 1-класса двухповодковая

Рисунок 3. Группа Ассур 2-класса трехповодковая

Механизм, который мы будем исследовать, будет четырехзвенным. Дадим характеристику этого механизма.

Звено O_1A – кривошип
Звено AB – шатун
Звено O_2B – коромысло
 O_1, O_2 – стойки

Рисунок 4. Четырехзвенный шарнирный механизм

Рычажным называется механизм, звенья которого образуют только низшие кинематические пары.

Рычаг – звено, образующее вращательную пару со стойкой.

Шарнир – подвижное соединение двух звеньев (кинематическая пара), которое обеспечивает им вращательное движение. Шарнир может быть плоским (вращательная кинематическая пара) или пространственным (сферическая или сферическая с пальцем кинематическая пара).

Стойка – звено механизма, принимаемое за неподвижное.

Кривошип – звено рычажного механизма, которое может совершать полный оборот вокруг неподвижной оси.

Коромысло – звено рычажного механизма, которое может совершать только неполный оборот вокруг неподвижной оси.

Шатун – звено рычажного механизма, образующее кинематические пары только с подвижными звеньями (не образует кинематических пар со стойкой).

Ползун – звено, образующее поступательную пару с одним звеном и вращательную с другим.

Направляющая – звено поступательной пары, имеющее большую протяжённость сопрягаемого элемента по сравнению с длиной сопрягаемого элемента другого звена

Частным случаем рычажного механизма является механизм в состав, которого входят только вращательные и сферические кинематические пары. Такой механизм называется **шарнирным**.

В состав этого механизма входят только вращательные кинематические пары, поэтому он применяется для преобразования одного вида вращательного движения в другое. В зависимости от размера звеньев механизм может быть кривошипно-коромысловым, двухкривошипным или двухкоромысловым. Шарнирный четырехзвенный механизм используется в прессах, ковочных машинах, конвейерах и т. д.

Первым этапом кинематического исследования будет построение плана положений механизма. В зависимости от условий исследования число положений бывает разным, например 36 положений, когда через каждые 10° поворота кривошипа или ведущего звена фиксируется положение всех подвижных точек механизма. Также можно фиксировать 6, 12, 24 положения механизма. Мы остановимся на 12 положениях механизма.

Важным этапом исследования является выбор соответствующего масштаба построений.

Вычислительным масштабом называется отношение действительного значения какой-либо величины к длине отрезка (мм), который представляет данную величину на чертеже.

$$\mu = \frac{A}{[A]} = \text{размерность величины } A/\text{мм.}$$

A – действительное значение величины.

$[A]$ - длина отрезка, который представляет величину A на чертеже, мм.

Масштаб линейной величины $\mu_e = \text{м/мм}$;

Масштаб скорости $\mu_v = \text{м/сек/мм}$;

Масштаб ускорения $\mu_a = \text{м/сек}^2/\text{мм}$;

Масштаб силы $\mu_p = \text{Н/мм}$.

Построение траекторий. Пусть задан механизм, состоящий из ведущего звена 1, группы Ассур 1-го класса 1-го вида (2,3) в положении 1.

Построение плана положения. Весь цикл движения механизма делится на 12 равных частей. Требуется найти положение всех ведомых звеньев, соответствующих положению ведущего звена OA .

Построение проведем согласно плану:

Для начала определим траектории всех подвижных точек механизма.

1. Траекторией точки A является окружность с центром в точке O_1 , с радиусом, равным длине звена O_1A ;

2. Траекторией точки B является дуга окружности с центром в точке O_2 , с радиусом, равным длине звена BO_2 ;

3. Проводим окружность с центром в точке O_1 , с радиусом, равным длине звена O_1A . Разделим окружность на 12 равных частей. Через каждые 30° фиксируем положения точки A .

4. Ищем положения звеньев (2,3).

Для этого из точки O_2 проводим дугу с радиусом, равным длине звена BO_2 . Нашли траекторию точки B . Циркулем измеряем расстояние AB . Острым концом циркуля встаем на точку A_1 , другим концом делаем засечку на дуге точки B . Полученная точка является точкой B_1 . Соединив точки B_1 и A_1 , получим искомое звено A_1B_1 – искомое положение звена 1. Соединив точки B_1 и O_2 , получим искомое положение звена 3 (B_1O_2).

5. На продолжении звена A_1B_1 находим точку E . Для этого удлиним звено на расстояние BE . Таким образом, получим искомое положение механизма. Всего должно быть 12 положений механизма.

Определение крайних положений механизма.

Ведущее звено (кривошип) может совершать полный оборот 360° радиусом OA с центром O .

На шатуне AB выбираем произвольную точку M . Окружность I делим на 12 равных частей. Через каждые 30° делаем засечки на окружности. В соответствии с размерами звеньев строим положения (все 12) для всех остальных звеньев. На каждом шатуне $A_n B_n$ отмечаем положение $t.M$. в соответствии с расстоянием AM . Затем соединим все положения точки M плавной кривой, получим траекторию этой точки. Мы здесь заметили, что коромысло BC не делает полного оборота, как кривошип OA , оно поворачивается между двумя крайними точками. Эти крайние (мертвые) положения определяются следующим образом. Для нашего четырехзвенника это будет нетрудно. Очевидно, что звено BC достигнет правого крайнего положения в случае, когда кривошип OA и шатун AB вытянутся в одну линию.

Рисунок 5. Крайние положения механизма

Нахождение крайних положений коромысла BC

Обозначим $OA=r$, $AB=L$

Сделаем засечку на дуге окружности радиусом, равным длине звена BC , проведя дугу радиусом $R=r+L$ из центра O . Полученную точку B'' соединяем с точкой C . Отрезок $B''C$ и есть крайнее правое положение механизма. Соединяя B'' с точкой O получим соответствующие положения OA'' и $A''B''$.

Крайнее левое положение механизма получим тогда, когда кривошип и шатун сложатся в одну линию. Для этого делаем засечку на траектории точки B радиусом $R=L-r$ из центра O . Соединим B' с точкой C получим левое крайнее положение коромысла $B'C$. Проведя прямую $B'O$ получим положение шатуна $A'B'$ и кривошип $A'O$. Угол $\angle B'OB''=\psi_{max}$ называется углом размаха коромысла.

Построение планов скоростей. Теорема подобия планов скоростей.

Вначале определим, что такое скорость?

Скорость точки можно выразить так: Возьмем систему координат $OXYZ$ см. рис. Допустим, мы должны передвинуться из точки M в точку M_1 . Положение этих точек относительно O определяется радиус - векторами: $\vec{OM} = \vec{r}$ и $\vec{OM}_1 = \vec{r}_1$

Расстояние $|\vec{MM}_1| = S$, по правилу сложения векторов запишем: $\vec{s} = \vec{r}_1 - \vec{r} = \Delta\vec{r}$

Точка M определяется вектором \vec{r} относительно O в момент времени t . Точка M_1 относительно O определяется вектором \vec{r}_1 , в момент времени t_1 .

Следовательно, перемещение из M в M_1 мы совершим за промежуток времени Δt . Итак, скоростью точки V в момент времени t мы называем первую производную по времени от радиуса вектора, т.е. от пути

$$v = \frac{d\tau}{dt} = \frac{ds}{dt}; \text{ размерность м/с}$$

План скоростей — диаграмма, на которой векторы скоростей точек **абсолютно твёрдого тела** или некоторого механизма отложены из одной точки в выбранном масштабе.

План скоростей обладает следующими свойствами:

- отрезок, соединяющий концы векторов скоростей любых двух точек тела, перпендикулярен отрезку, соединяющему соответствующие точки тела;
- длины отрезков, соединяющих концы векторов скоростей точек тела, пропорциональны длинам отрезков, соединяющим соответствующие точки.

План скоростей позволяет графически решать задачи на нахождение скоростей точек тела. Чем крупнее выбранный масштаб, в котором построены векторы скоростей точек тела, тем точнее будет решена задача.

Определить скорости можно также и графическим способом при помощи так называемых планов скоростей. Планы скоростей строятся по векторным уравнениям, которые составляются отдельно для каждой групп Ассур.

Рассмотрим пример: Возьмем известный нам шарнирный четырехзвенник. Известны размеры звеньев $l_{OA}, l_{AB}, l_{BC}, l_{OC}$, положение механизма, закон движения ведущего звена $\omega_1 = \text{const}$. Движение ведущего звена считаем равномерным. Построение планов скоростей проводится в порядке построения механизма. Скорость ведущего звена: $V_A = \omega_1 l_{OA}$ - величина скорости точки A .

Построение плана скоростей ведем согласно плану:

1. Определение скорости точки A .

$$V_A = \omega_1 \cdot OA = 30 \cdot 0,02 = 0,6 \text{ м/с}$$

Вектор скорости перпендикулярен кривошипу OA .

2. Выбираем масштаб плана скоростей

Найдём отрезок, изображающий вектор скорости

$$\mu_V = \frac{\text{м/с}}{\text{мм}}$$

Из полюса плана скоростей откладываем данный отрезок в направлении, перпендикулярном OA в направлении угловой скорости ω_1

3. Определение скорости точки B .

Запишем векторное уравнение:

$$\vec{V}_B = \vec{V}_A + \vec{V}_{BA} (*)$$

Направления векторов скоростей:

$$\vec{V}_B \perp BC \quad \vec{V}_{BA} \perp BA$$

Из конца этого вектора (точка a) проводим направление вектора V_{BA}

Из полюса p проводим направление V_B , перпендикулярное звену BC . Эти два перпендикуляра пересекутся и образуют треугольник, три стороны которого соответствуют трем векторам в уравнении (*).

Продолжим строить план скоростей.

На пересечении двух проведенных направлений получим точку b , полученный треугольник является планом скоростей данного механизма. Каждая сторона соответствует вектору в уравнении. Измеряя длины полученных отрезков и умножая их на масштаб μ_p , получим значения скоростей:

$$4. \text{ Составим пропорцию: } \frac{ve}{BE} = \frac{ав}{AB} \rightarrow ve = \frac{BE \cdot ав}{AB}; \quad \frac{ae}{AE} = \frac{ав}{AB} \rightarrow ae = \frac{AE \cdot ав}{AB};$$

Здесь надо пояснить, что выходная точка E может быть расположена по-разному, т.е. либо со стороны точки A , либо со стороны точки B . В зависимости от этого вычисляется по указанным выше пропорциям. Опираясь на теорему подобия скоростей, которая гласит:

Теорема подобия планов скоростей: отрезки прямых линий, соединяющие точки на схеме звена механизма, и отрезки прямых линий, соединяющие концы векторов относительных скоростей этих точек на плане скоростей, образуют полные и сходственно расположенные фигуры. Фигура на плане скоростей повернута относительно фигуры схемы звена на 90 градусов.

Находим на плане скоростей одноименные точки e, S_1, S_2, S_3 - центры тяжести звеньев.

5. Вычисление проводим следующим образом: измеряем на чертеже соответствующий отрезок и умножаем его на масштаб скорости:

$$v_B = \mu_v \times [pv],$$

$$v_{BA} = \mu_v \times [ав],$$

$$v_E = \mu_v \times [pe],$$

$$v_S = \mu_v \times [ps],$$

Значения угловых скоростей ω_2, ω_3 находим из формул

$$\omega_2 = \frac{v_{BA}}{l_{AB}}, \quad \omega_3 = \frac{v_B}{l_{BC}}$$

Рисунок 6. План скоростей механизма

Построение планов ускорений. Выбор масштаба ускорений.

Теорема подобия планов ускорений.

Ускорением точки называем первую производную от скорости по времени,

или вторую производную по времени от пути т.е. $a = \frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{d^2s}{dt^2}$ (м/с²)

Вектор \bar{a}_A^n направлен по радиусу к центру от точки A к т.О.

Зададим масштаб μ_a и вычислим длину $[pa]$, p - это полюс плана ускорения.

$$[pa] = \frac{a_A^n}{\mu_a}$$

Откладываем

отрезок $[pa]$ в соответствии с направлением вектора \bar{a}_A^n , переходим к группе Ассур. Запишем векторные уравнения ускорений для точки B .

$$\bar{a}_B = \bar{a}_A + \bar{a}_{BA}$$

$$\bar{a}_B = \bar{a}_C + \bar{a}_{BC}$$

Аналогично, т.к. $a_C = 0$, то мы будем рассматривать только первое уравнение.

Векторы \bar{a}_B и \bar{a}_{BA} раскладываются следующим образом:

$$\bar{a}_B = \bar{a}_B^n + \bar{a}_B^\tau$$

$$\bar{a}_{BA} = \bar{a}_{BA}^n + \bar{a}_{BA}^\tau$$

Перепишем наше уравнение:

$$\bar{a}_B^n + \bar{a}_B^\tau = \bar{a}_A^n + \bar{a}_{BA}^n + \bar{a}_{BA}^\tau \quad (*)$$

Рассмотрим каждый вектор уравнения отдельно:

1. \bar{a}_B^n известен по модулю и направлению

$$a_B^n = \frac{V^2_B}{\ell_{BC}}$$

направлен он параллельно звену BC от точки B к точке C ;

2. вектор \bar{a}_B^τ направлен \perp к звену BC , модуль известен; вектор \bar{a}_A известен по величине и по направлению, отрезок $[pa]$ мы уже отложили, вектор \bar{a}_{BA}^n по величине равен:

$$\bar{a}_{BA}^n = \frac{g_{BA}^2}{\ell_{AB}}$$

Направлен

он параллельно звену AB от точки B к точке A .

Вектор \bar{a}_{BA}^τ направлен \perp к звену AB , модуль также неизвестен. Строим дальше план ускорений. Согласно векторному уравнению, из конца вектора \bar{a}_A откладываем в масштабе в указанном направлении, вектор \bar{a}_{BA}^n представляем отрезком $[an]$,

$$[an] = \frac{a_{BA}^n}{\mu_a}$$

Теперь из конца вектора \bar{a}_{AB}^n проведем линию по направлению вектора \bar{a}_{BA}^τ .

$$\bar{a}_{BA}^\tau \perp \bar{a}_{BA}^n$$

Теперь рассмотрим первую часть уравнения (*).

Из полюса P отложим вектор \bar{a}_{BA}^n обозначим этот отрезок $[pn']$. Из конца этого отрезка проведем линию по направлению вектора \bar{a}_B^τ . Пересечение направлений векторов \bar{a}_B^τ и \bar{a}_{BA}^τ дает нам местоположение точки v . Отрезок $[nv]$ представляет на чертеже вектор ускорения \bar{a}_{BA}^τ , а отрезок $[n'v]$ представляет на чертеже вектор ускорения \bar{a}_B^τ .

Величины этих векторов ускорений равны:

$$a_{BA}^{\tau} = [n\epsilon] \cdot \mu_a$$

$$a_B^{\tau} = [n'\epsilon] \cdot \mu_a$$

Определим

также угловые ускорения звеньев 2 и 3:

$$\epsilon_2 = \frac{a_{BA}^{\tau}}{\ell_{AB}} \quad \epsilon_3 = \frac{a_B^{\tau}}{\ell_{BC}}$$

Для определения направления векторов угловых ускорений ϵ_2 и ϵ_3 перенесем \bar{a}_{BA}^{τ} и \bar{a}_B^{τ} в точку B механизма. Рассматривая движение B вокруг A в направлении вектора \bar{a}_{BA}^{τ} установим, что ϵ_2 направлено против часовой стрелки. Рассматривая движение B вокруг C в направлении вектора \bar{a}_B^{τ} устанавливаем, что ϵ_3 также направлено против движения.

При построении планов ускорений очень важно знать о теореме подобии планов ускорений.

Сформулируем теорему так:

Отрезки прямых линий, соединяющие данные точки на плане звена и отрезка прямых соединяющие концы векторов полных ускорений этих точек на плане ускорений образуют подобные и сходственные фигуры.

Рисунок 6.

План ускорений для группы Ассура

Кинематическое исследование считается законченным, если построены диаграммы трех кинематических параметров: перемещения, скорости, ускорения.

Графическое дифференцирование. Метод хорд и метод касательных.

Кинематические диаграммы.

Наглядное представление о законе движения интересующего нас звена или точки механизма дают так называемые кинематические диаграммы, т.е. зависимости пути, скорости и ускорения от времени

$$S = f(t), \quad \mathcal{V} = f(t), \quad a = f(t),$$

построенные графически.

Рассмотрим построение диаграммы $S = f(t)$ для ползуна (точка B) кривошипно - ползунного механизма. Строим 12 положений механизма, соответствующих 12 равноотстоящим положениям кривошипа OA и отмечаем 12 положений точки B . Проводим оси координат S и φ . На оси φ откладываем 12 равновеликих отрезков. 0-1, 1-2, 2-3, ... и т.д. соответствующих углу поворота кривошипа (на 30° градусов), через точки 1, 2, 3, ... и т.д. проводим ординаты и откладываем на них отрезки 1-1', 2-2', 3-3', и т.д., равные координатам точки B и соответствующих положений отсчитываемых от правого крайнего положения точки B . Соединяя точки 0, 1', 2', 3', ..., 12' плавной кривой, получим диаграмму $S_B = f(\varphi)$. При

равномерном вращении угол его поворота φ пропорционален времени t . Поэтому полученная диаграмма будет также диаграммой $S=f(t)$. Разница будет в оси абсцисс (по масштабу).

Масштабный коэффициент пути μ_s будет равен масштабному коэффициенту μ_ℓ плана положения, так как отрезки на диаграмму мы переносим без изменения. Масштабный коэффициент углов μ_φ диаграммы $S_\varphi=f(\varphi)$ равен:

$$\mu_\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{[0-12]} \text{ 1/мм}$$

[0-12]- отрезок на оси, изображающий полный оборот кривошипа 2л.

μ_t - масштабный коэффициент пути.

Для построения диаграммы скорости ($v_c - t$) поступаем так:

- 1) под диаграммой ($s_c - t$)строим оси координат $O_1 v_c - O_1 t$ (рис.5.1, б) на продолжении оси $O_1 t$ влево откладываем отрезок $O_1 P - H_1$ мм;
- 2) из точки P проводим лучи $P1$; $P2$; $P3$; ... параллельно хордам кривой ($s_c - t$) на участках $O11'$; $1' 2'$; $2' 3'$ Эти лучи отсекут на оси $O_1 v_c$ отрезки $O_1 1$; $O_1 2$; $O_1 3$... пропорциональные средней скорости v_c на соответствующим участке диаграммы;
- 3) отложим эти отрезки на средних ординатах соответствующих участков;
- 4) соединим ряд полученных точек I ; II ; III ... плавной кривой; эта кривая будет диаграммой скорости ($v_c - t$).

Следует иметь в виду, что участки, на которых кривая имеет экстремум (как, например, участок 7-8 на рис.6.1, а и 9 – 10 на рис.6.1, б), следует разделить дополнительно на два участка каждый, на протяжении которых кривая не имеет экстремума.

Имея диаграмму скоростей ($v_c - t$), аналогично строим диаграмму тангенциальных ускорений ($\omega^t_c - t$) представленную на рис.6.1, в. При построении диаграмм ($v_c - t$) и ($\omega^t_c - t$) описанным методом нельзя получить те участки этих диаграмм, которые соответствуют половине крайних участков оси абсцисс. Чтобы построение диаграмм, нужно дополнительно построить средние значения v_c и ω^t_c для одного – двух участков следующего цикла. Соединяя плавной кривой точки, соответствующие последним участкам первого цикла и первым участкам следующего цикла, отсечем на крайней правой оси ординат отрезок, который следует отложить на крайней левой оси ординат цикла. После этого окончательно достраиваем всю кривую, как это указано на рис.6.1, б, в штриховыми линиями.

Масштаб μ_t диаграмм ($v_c - t$) и ($\omega^t_c - t$) остается таким же, как и раньше; масштабы по осям ординат определяются по формулам:

для диаграммы скоростей
$$\mu_v = \frac{\mu_s}{\mu_t H_1} \text{ м.сек}^{-1} / \text{мм}; \quad (6.1)$$

для диаграммы ускорения

$$\mu_a = \frac{\mu_v}{\mu_t H_2} \text{ м.сек}^{-2} / \text{мм}; \quad (6.2)$$

где H_1 и H_2 - отрезки, взятые из чертежа в мм.

Если по оси абсцисс отложено не время t , угол поворота кривошипа $\phi = \omega_1 t$, то в формулах (6.1) и (6.2) нужно поставить вместо μ_t величину.

Тогда получим:

$$\mu_\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{[0-12]} \text{ 1/мм} - \text{ масштаб угла поворота}$$

$$\mu_v = \frac{\mu_s}{\mu_t H_1} \text{ м.сек}^{-1} / \text{мм}; - \text{ масштаб скорости}$$

$$\mu_a = \frac{\mu_v}{\mu_t H_2} \text{ м.сек}^{-1} / \text{мм}; - \text{ масштаб ускорения}$$

$$\mu_t = \frac{T}{[0-12]} \text{ с/мм}; T = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_1} - \text{ масштаб времени}$$

где

$$\omega_1 = \frac{\pi n}{30n} \text{ 1/сек}$$

Из формул (6.1) и (6.2) видно, что величины масштабов дифференциальных кривых зависят от длины соответствующего полюсного расстояния H_1 и H_2 . Эту длину выбирают так, чтобы дифференциальная кривая вместились на отведенном для нее месте чертежа.

Рис.6.1 Кинематические диаграммы

На рис.6.1, б показано, что для диаграммы $(v_c - t)$ нужно иметь на листе бумаги площадку высотой h у $y_{1\max} + y_{2\max}$. Но

$$y_{1\max} = H_1 \operatorname{tg} \alpha_1 \text{ и } y_{2\max} = H_1 \operatorname{tg} \alpha_2, \quad (6.4)$$

где α_1 и α_2 - наибольшие углы наклона хорд (или касательных) на восходящем и исходящим участках интегральной кривой $(s_c - t)$; определение их величины указано на рис.6.1, а.

h $H_1 (\operatorname{tg} \alpha_1 + \operatorname{tg} \alpha_2)$, откуда

$$H_1 < \frac{h}{\operatorname{tg} \alpha_1 + \operatorname{tg} \alpha_2} \quad (6.5)$$

Расстояние между осями абсцисс диаграмм $(s_c - t)$ и $(v_c - t)$ должно быть $O_1O_2 > y_1 = H_1 \operatorname{tg} \alpha$

Аналогичным способом определяют необходимую высоту площадки для диаграммы $(\omega^t_c - t)$ и расстояние между осями абсцисс O_1O_2 .

В данной работе мы рассмотрели несколько важных аспектов математики и физики, связанных с графическим дифференцированием, методом хорд и методом касательных, а также применением кинематических диаграмм.

Графическое дифференцирование представляет собой мощный инструмент для анализа функций и их производных. Метод хорд и метод касательных - это два известных численных метода для вычисления производных функций, которые могут быть полезны в решении задач, где аналитическое дифференцирование затруднено или невозможно. Метод хорд использует секущие линии для приближенного определения производной. Он может быть полезен в случаях, когда необходимо быстро оценить производную функции в заданной точке. Однако его точность зависит от выбора точек хорды и может быть низкой при кривых функциях. Метод касательных основывается на построении касательных линий к графику функции в заданной точке. Этот метод более точен и приближен к аналитическому дифференцированию, но требует вычисления угловых коэффициентов касательных линий. Кинематические диаграммы - это графическое представление движения объектов и позволяют наглядно анализировать путь, скорость и ускорение. Они играют важную роль в физике и инженерии, помогая визуализировать и понимать движение объектов.

В заключении, графическое дифференцирование и численные методы, такие как метод хорд и метод касательных, являются важными инструментами в математике и физике, которые могут быть применены для анализа функций и приближенного определения производных. Кинематические диаграммы, в свою очередь, позволяют наглядно изучать движение объектов и находят широкое применение в научных и инженерных исследованиях.

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METHODS OF OPENING PRODUCTIVE LAYERS AND DEVELOPMENT OF WELLS ON DEPOSITS

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МЕТОДЫ ВСКРЫТИЯ ПРОДУКТИВНЫХ ПЛАСТОВ И ОСВОЕНИЯ СКВАЖИН

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С целью предотвращения возможных осложнений в процессе бурения первичное вскрытие продуктивных пластов предполагается осуществить на химически обработанном полимерном растворе, строго соблюдая его проектные параметры. При этом депрессия на пласт не должна превышать 5% пластового давления. С этой целью, вскрытие горизонта производить только после полного выравнивания параметров бурового раствора. В противном случае, неизбежно поглощение бурового раствора без выхода циркуляции, особенно в интервале с низким градиентом пластового давления.

Основными требованиями, предъявляемыми к жидкостям для вторичного вскрытия продуктивных пластов, являются:

- создание противодействия на пласт, достаточное для предупреждения нефтегазопроявлений после вторичного вскрытия перфорацией, не вызывая при этом поглощения этих жидкостей пластом;
- недопущение кольматации перфорационных каналов и околоствольной зоны пласта (ОЗП).

На основе анализа сравнительных показателей различных кумулятивных перфораторов для вторичного вскрытия продуктивных пластов рекомендуется применить перфорационные системы фирмы Шлюмберже Power Jet 4^{1/2}" НМХ, с плотностью зарядов 16

отв. на m^2 , прошедшие апробацию и показавшие хорошие результаты не только на месторождениях стран дальнего зарубежья, но и на месторождениях Казахстана.

Достоинствами перфорационных систем PowerJet HMX являются:

- глубина проникновения зарядов составляет от 1,2 до 3 м, в зависимости от условия залегания коллектора, и как следствие, зона проникновения фильтрата промывочной жидкости минимально влияет на продуктивность скважины;
- интервал перфорации превышает 5 м, что значительно уменьшает время спускоподъемных операций;
- проводится «чистая» перфорация за счет депрессии на пласт, позволяющая снизить до минимума негативные факторы, связанные с прострелочно-взрывными работами (прежде всего засорения каналов и породы продуктами взрыва).

Промысловой практикой и научно-исследовательскими работами подтверждено, что дебит скважины будет больше в том случае, если при проведении перфорационных работ применять чистые жидкости (техническая, минерализованная вода, нефть) и, если будет обеспечена промывка перфорационных каналов обратным потоком пластового флюида из пласта в скважину. Это достигается при перфорации с перепадом давления, направленного в сторону ствола скважины, а не в пласт.

Для снижения вредного воздействия, оказываемого буровым раствором на продуктивный пласт во время бурения, и исключения вредного воздействия перфорационной жидкости во время перфорации при репрессии, рекомендуем перфорировать продуктивные пласты, при депрессии на пласт, в среде чистой жидкости перфораторами, спускаемыми на насосно-компрессорных трубах.

В качестве промывочной и перфорационной жидкости рекомендуются:

Направление – бурение вести с использованием технической воды обработанной бентонитом, каустической и кальцинированной содой.

Кондуктор - бурение под колонну, для недопущения осложнений и перекрытия зон поглощений, водопроявлений и газопроявлений техногенного характера следует производить заранее приготовленным полимерным раствором (50 м^3), стабилизированным реагентом Permolose HT для уменьшения водоотдачи бурового раствора, глинизации стенок скважины и предупреждения проникновения фильтрата в пласт. В случае возникновения поглощений бурового раствора в альб-сеноманских отложениях использовать 2-3 вида наполнителей с различными размерами частиц (зернистые, волокнистые, чешуйчатые) в количестве 2 % от объема бурового раствора. Для поддержания щелочности бурового раствора на уровне $\text{pH} = 9,0\text{--}10,0$ вводить каустическую соду (NaOH). По окончании бурения ствол скважины необходимо промыть в течение двух циклов с целью дополнительной очистки ствола скважины от выбуренной породы.

Обработка бурового раствора осуществляется путем «самозамеса», что явно нежелательно, поэтому с целью сохранения и регулирования технологических показателей бурового раствора (особенно по поддержанию твердой фазы, плотности и вязкости бурового раствора), необходимо предусмотреть в комплекте буровой установки обязательное наличие четырехступенчатой системы очистки: вибросито, пескоотделитель, илоотделители центрифугу.

В эксплуатационной колонне с целью сохранения коллекторских характеристик продуктивного пласта (пористость, проницаемость), предупреждения негативных явлений, производить с использованием ингибированного полимерно-хлоркалиевого бурового раствора с низким содержанием твердой фазы с ведением дополнительных полимерных реагентов для усиления ингибирующих свойств.

В качестве ингибирующей добавки в буровой раствор, с использованием которого бурился предыдущий интервал, вводится 3-4 % KCl (хлористого калия) и ХВ-полимер (типа

Родопол-23П). Перед вводом KCl в буровой раствор предварительно обработать реагентом стабилизатором по водоотдаче и вязкости Permolose HT. Для регулирования щелочности бурового раствора использовать едкий калий KOH (или NaOH). С целью максимального сохранения коллекторских свойств продуктивных пластов в качестве утяжеляющей и временно закупоривающей добавки использовать кислоторастворимый карбонат кальция. В целом система бурового раствора, предусмотренная программой, должна полностью отвечать основным требованиям, предъявляемым к нему при вскрытии продуктивных пластов.

Плотность прострела для низкопроницаемых пластов 10-20 отверстий на 1 п. метр.

Перед вызовом притока пластового флюида производится замена бурового раствора в скважине на перфорационную жидкость.

В качестве перфорационной среды будет применяться жидкость с плотностью, соответствующей требованиям РД на строительство скважин. Перфорационную жидкость рекомендуется закачать в зону перфорации объекта плюс 100-150 м выше верхней границы зоны перфорации. Оставшийся ствол скважины заполнить буровым раствором, использованным при вскрытии продуктивных пластов. Перфорационную жидкость представляющую собой водный раствор солей, очищенных от механических примесей, необходимо обработать неионогенными добавками ПАВ для снижения поверхностного натяжения и капиллярного давления в порах пласта.

При вторичном вскрытии продуктивного пласта, произвести соляно-кислотную обработку под давлением, как наиболее перспективный и рациональный метод очистки призабойной зоны скважин.

Из всех известных методов вызова притока и освоения скважин предлагается использовать свабирование – понижение уровня в скважине, в которую спущена колонна НКТ. Это наиболее производительный способ и может осуществляться с использованием фонтанной арматуры со специальным лубрикаторм.

При слабом притоке жидкости произвести плавный перевод скважины на механизированный способ эксплуатации. Все работы по вскрытию продуктивных горизонтов, вызова притока и освоения скважин должны проводиться по специальному плану со строгим соблюдением правил по технике безопасности.

На этапе строительства скважин при освоении и исследовании скважин должны выполняться следующие мероприятия:

- устья скважин с сепарационными и замерными установками должны оборудоваться по схеме технологического регламента на испытание скважин;
- при опробовании и исследовании скважин производить сепарацию газа и последний в обязательном порядке сжигается;
- работы по опробованию и испытанию скважин производить по специальному организационно-техническому плану, утвержденному недропользователем.
- Для надежной охраны недр в процессе строительства скважины и ее дальнейшей эксплуатации, должны выполняться следующие мероприятия:
 - строго соблюдать разработанную конструкцию скважин, которая обеспечивает изоляцию водоносных горизонтов, перекрытие интервалов поглощения бурового раствора и создает надежную крепь в процессе эксплуатации скважины;
 - создать по всей длине прочное цементное кольцо между стенками скважины и обсадными колоннами с целью исключения перетоков пластовых вод из одного пласта в другой.

Режим закачки должен обеспечить максимальное вытеснение бурового раствора из кольцевого пространства. Вышеизложенные мероприятия обеспечат надежное разобщение пластов друг от друга, что в свою очередь обеспечит отсутствие пластовых перетоков.

С помощью стационарных газокаротажных лабораторий типа АГКС-4АЦ при бурении на скважинах необходимо производить непрерывный контроль за содержанием газонасыщенности бурового раствора.

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COUNTRY INDEXES AND RANKINGS: WHAT TO KEEP IN MIND

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Abstract: The article focuses on various international indexes and ratings of states, the degree of their objectivity, the calculation procedure, and their impact on the image of a particular country. The question is discussed whether it is worth trusting the ratings and how they can be useful.

Nowadays, there are many discussions about democracy as a political system, about which countries have the reputation and image of the most democratic, and which are characterized as despotism. And how the well-being and prosperity of the country are connected with democratic and civil liberties, and how autocracy and the free market affect the well-being of citizens. The data that Freedom and Prosperity Indexes (the Atlantic Council's) presents is very detailed and interesting, and let's pay attention to this information [1].

According to the authors of the study, citizens of countries that are classified as "free" are 13 times richer than people living in "not free" countries. And the conclusion of the authors is clear: Prosperity is highly correlated with freedom. The data, which is given in detail, proves that prosperity around the world is associated with freedom. Autocracies tend not to thrive. The place and characteristics of Kazakhstan in these indexes are also interesting:

Country	Freedom Rank	Freedom Status	Prosperity Rank	Prosperity Status
Togo	114	Mostly unfree	154	Mostly unprosperous
Turkey	115	Mostly unfree	96	Mostly unprosperous
KAZAKHSTAN	116	Mostly unfree	86	Mostly unprosperous
Lebanon	117	Mostly unfree	74	Mostly Prosperous
Kyrgyzstan	118	Mostly unfree	83	Mostly unprosperous

As we can see, Kazakhstan is ranked 116th “according to freedoms” (174 states in total) and 86th in terms of prosperity. That is, Kazakhstan is mostly an unfree country and not very prosperous. But Lebanon, although not free, but (with prosperity) is a “happier” country. The main conclusion of the authors of the study: “66% of the variation in prosperity ... can be explained by freedom. Autocracies are generally not prosperous.” This study cites the words of US President Biden at the 77th Session of the United Nations General Assembly that democracies can deliver for their citizens but also deliver for the rest of the world [2].

However, here is the opposite data: in the BBC material of July 6, 2022, entitled “Arabs believe economy is weak under democracy” [3], the author publishes population surveys that show that the Arabs are losing faith in democracy to deliver economic stability across the Middle East and North Africa.

Ten years after the Arab Spring, people in these countries are losing faith that democratic freedoms can boost their economies and wealth. Here is the eloquent data given in the article:

Rise in people who agree the economy is weak under a democracy

According to the EIU Democracy Index [4], the Middle East and North Africa rank the lowest of all the regions included in the index. That is, countries with non-democratic regimes do not want democracy at all, since this leads to economic weakness.

Let's try to develop the right attitude to the rankings and indexes of countries that are published regularly in a variety of sources.

Indeed, the rankings of the best (and worst) countries are of interest to economists, politicians, scientific theorists, as well as to ordinary people. These indexes have an impact on the image of countries and can break or reinforce existing stereotypes. Citizens may feel proud or inferior if they see their country at the top or bottom of the list. A high development index is prestigious and economically beneficial: the country is more attractive for tourism and financial investments.

But you should always keep in mind the mechanism for compiling indexes. In a simplified form, the indexes are compiled as follows:

1. Selection of parameters/criteria
2. Expert opinion (subjective moment)
3. Comparison of indicators and determination of the "importance" coefficient.

But what if the opinions of connoisseurs and experts from different countries and "orientations" differ greatly? Here they either take an average rating or give some experts a higher priority than others. Often these procedures are done arbitrarily.

"Human development", "happiness", "freedom", and "attractiveness" - all these are rather vague concepts for which there are no generally accepted indicators. Parameters are invented by experts. Then a system is developed on how they can be measured. And this is where a lot of problems arise.

One can see what a big role subjectivity plays, because many indicators are not quantitative, but qualitative. For example, GDP per capita. It was rightly noted by one researcher that this money can be used in different ways: Vietnam and Guinea have approximately the same level of income per capita, but the life expectancy and literacy of the Vietnamese are much higher [5]. And if the country has a developed "shadow", uncalculated economy, then GDP is difficult to measure correctly.

And the number of existing rankings that characterize the situation in different countries is difficult to enumerate: there are a few dozen of them. By type, they can be divided into:

- demographic
- social
- institutional
- political
- economic
- reputational
- scientific and technical, etc.

Let's take a look at the so-called "happiness ranking", referring to indicators of the level and quality of life.

According to the UN index, Kazakhstan occupies the 40th position in terms of happiness, next to Brazil, Guatemala, Cyprus, and Latvia [6].

And according to the International Research Center Gallup (Gallup International) on the "level of happiness", Kazakhstan is on the 60th position, and its neighbors are Portugal, Taiwan, Romania, and Slovakia [7].

All this confirms the intention to be critical of the data of various country ratings and rankings, since they give a lot of space for subjectivity and too free interpretation. This happens especially often when it is necessary to measure something "not quite clear and measurable", and where there are no exact estimates. Therefore, the authors of such indexes and lists often indicate that they are not responsible for the correctness, completeness, and reliability of the information.

The article "What is known about dubious ratings and why should they not be trusted?" is very interesting in the Kazakhstan segment of the Internet [8]. The author fairly notices that "cases of using data on the relatively low positions of Kazakhstan in various highly specialized ratings have become more frequent." But even in those lists where Kazakhstan occupies comfortable places, they are also criticized.

The ranking of business activity "Doing Business" was one of the most pleasant for our citizens. In 2010, Kazakhstan was ranked 63rd, then in 2020, it was already 25th (higher than Austria, Japan, and France). But the Board of Executive Directors decided to stop the data release due to violations and inaccuracies in the calculations [9]. Moreover, a number of economists and politicians raise the question of the legitimacy of other rankings, for example, Standard & Poor's, Moody's, and Fitch. After all, for example, a change in indicators can lead to a fall in the investment market and harm national currencies. Although, we must agree that it is difficult to find an ideal and supported by all "evaluation rating".

So, should we take seriously the information that can be found in country rankings and development indexes?

Unfortunately, such information can become an instrument of ideological and psychological influence. Quite often various organizations, claiming impartiality and objectivity, manipulate public opinion, push and impose various ideas. Sometimes such lists cause confusion even among specialists and competent researchers. And such bias affects the image of states in the international space. And for the citizens of a particular country, the indicators can become depressing and pessimistic; so, the negative emotional and psychological attitude is strengthened - "everything is bad with us and will be bad."

But still, you should be aware that when making serious business decisions, one ranking is unlikely to become decisive and important. And knowing certain lists of the competitiveness of states is a very instructive lesson. This information allows you to understand what place your country occupies in the modern world, in what direction it is developing, what prevents people from reaching their potential, and what affects economic and social indicators. You need to be

critical when examining the information presented, but if there are real shortcomings and drawbacks, then look for productive ways to achieve better results.

However, one should not trust the indexes too much. This applies to everyday life and when making important decisions. Life is richer and more diverse than any statistics and indicators. When compiling the rankings, statistics are used, which could be incomplete or incorrect. And if the experts draw a conclusion, then they may be biased and politically motivated.

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Philological Sciences

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ЯЗЫК ПОСТЕРОВ: ВЛИЯНИЕ И РОЛЬ В РЕКЛАМНОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль постеров в современном мире, ключевые термины в сфере рекламы и влияние английского языка на рекламную практику. Показаны основные аспекты каждого из этих элементов, позволяя лучше понять силу и влияние постеров в современной рекламной индустрии.

Ключевые слова: постер, термины, реклама, профессиональный язык, словообразование, английский язык.

Современный мир погружен в океан информации, а реклама играет ключевую роль в формировании общественного мнения и потребительских предпочтений. Одним из наиболее эффективных инструментов в этой области являются постеры. Эти художественные произведения, применяемые для публичного информирования и рекламы, имеют множество аспектов и функций, которые оказывают значительное воздействие на современное общество.

В сфере рекламы используется обширный арсенал терминов, позволяющих точно описывать и анализировать различные аспекты этого многогранного процесса. От контекстуальной рекламы до целевой аудитории - каждый термин представляет собой ключ к успешной коммуникации с потребителями. Рекламные постеры представляют собой синтез искусства и коммуникации, являясь одними из наиболее визуальных и эффективных средств привлечения внимания к продукту или услуге. Они способны передать информацию, вызвать эмоции и запомниться зрителям даже в условиях информационного шума.

Важной составляющей эффективности рекламного постера является его дизайн. Точно продуманный графический элемент, сочетание цветов, шрифтов и композиции могут создать сильное визуальное воздействие. Кроме того, выбор изображений, их позиционирование и размер играют ключевую роль в привлечении внимания аудитории. Возьмем несколько примеров качественного дизайна рекламных постеров:

1. Apple: "Think Different"

Этот постер выделяется своей простотой и элегантностью. Изображение Шри Чинмойна, Махатмы Ганди и Альберта Эйнштейна с силуэтом яблока подчеркивает идею инновации и интеллектуального развития.

2. Nike: "Just Do It"

Этот постер славится своей энергией и движением. Динамичное изображение бегущего спортсмена и лаконичный лейбл "Just Do It" вдохновляют к действию.

3. WWF: "Save Paper, Save the Planet"

Этот постер прост, но эффективен. Образ дерева, стилизованный в виде рулона бумаги, наглядно демонстрирует идею экономии ресурсов.

4. Audi: "Unbox the Box"

Этот постер играет с восприятием привычных форм. Он создает интерес и приглашает аудиторию рассматривать изображение более внимательно.

Эти примеры демонстрируют различные аспекты качественного дизайна: от эффективного использования графики до простоты и креативности в подаче идеи.

Сфера рекламы богата специфическими терминами, каждый из которых имеет свою собственную роль и значение. Одним из примеров является "Кол-Ту-Действие" (СТА), что обозначает четкий призыв к действию, например, "Купите сейчас!" или "Зарегистрируйтесь сейчас". Этот термин служит мостом между постером и целевой аудиторией, направляя ее к желаемому результату. "Кол-Ту-Действие" (СТА) - термин из маркетинга, который обозначает четкий и конкретный призыв к действию, предназначенный для аудитории с целью стимулирования определенного ответа. Это может быть, например, приглашение к покупке продукта, подписке на рассылку, регистрации на сайте и т.д. СТА формулируется таким образом, чтобы она была ясной, легко понятной и мотивирующей для потребителя. Термин "Кол-Ту-Действие" происходит из английского языка и переводится как "Call to Action". Он широко используется в маркетинге и рекламе, так как СТА играет важную роль в превращении интереса потребителя в конкретные действия. Применение СТА позволяет управлять поведением целевой аудитории и повышать эффективность рекламных кампаний. Этот термин пришел в русскоязычную рекламную практику вместе с общей глобализацией маркетинговых практик и переводом ключевых терминов с английского языка.

Безусловно, влияние английского языка на мир рекламы нельзя недооценивать. Множество заимствованных слов и терминов прочно вошли в рекламную лексику, придавая ей международный характер и содействуя глобальной коммуникации. Английский язык оказал значительное влияние на рекламную лексику. Слова и выражения, такие как "маркетинг", "брендинг", "позиционирование", "таргетирование", вошли в повседневное употребление в сфере рекламы, придавая ей международный характер и обогащая ее лингвистический арсенал.

1. Таргетирование (Targeting): Этот термин используется для описания стратегии, при которой рекламное сообщение направлено на определенную аудиторию, основываясь на ее характеристиках, интересах и поведении. Пример: "Мы применяем точное таргетирование, чтобы донести наше предложение до потенциальных клиентов."

2. Брендинг (Branding): Этот термин означает создание узнаваемого и запоминающегося образа компании или продукта в глазах потребителей. Пример: "Наша новая кампания направлена на улучшение брендинга и укрепление позиций на рынке."

3. Маркетинг (Marketing): Этот термин включает в себя все стратегии и действия, направленные на продвижение продукта или услуги на рынке. Пример: "Эффективный маркетинг помог нам увеличить продажи на 30%."

4. Позиционирование (Positioning): Этот термин используется для описания стратегии, направленной на создание уникального и выгодного положения продукта или бренда на рынке. Пример: "Мы работаем над позиционированием нашего продукта как лидера в инновационных решениях."

5. ROI (Return on Investment): - английская аббревиатура, обозначающая показатель эффективности инвестиций. Пример: "Мы добились высокого ROI благодаря эффективной рекламной кампании."

6. Copywriting: -процесс создания текстов для рекламы с целью привлечения внимания и убеждения целевой аудитории. Пример: "Хороший копирайтинг способен улучшить конверсию нашей рекламы."

7. Hashtag:- символ "#" перед словом или фразой, используемый в социальных сетях для объединения тематических обсуждений. Пример: "Мы создали уникальный хэштег для нашей компании, чтобы увеличить ее видимость в социальных сетях."

Эти термины и выражения являются частыми примерами заимствованной лексики из английского языка в рекламной сфере. Их использование обогащает лингвистический арсенал рекламщиков и помогает им точно и эффективно общаться с аудиторией. Современный мир рекламы невозможно представить без рекламных постеров. Их эффективность зависит от грамотного использования дизайна и правильного выбора графических и текстовых элементов

Словообразование в рекламной лексике подчинено требованиям краткости, запоминаемости и эмоциональной нагрузке. Множество новых слов и выражений создаются путем комбинирования и сокращения, что позволяет быстро и точно передать суть рекламного послания. Создание новых терминов позволяет рекламщикам выделиться в условиях конкуренции и привлечь внимание целевой аудитории

Заимствованные слова из английского языка придают рекламной лексике международный характер, способствуя глобализации рекламных практик. Терминология в рекламной сфере играет важную роль в создании эффективных кампаний, обеспечивая точное и четкое общение с аудиторией.

Их взаимодействие создает невероятные возможности для воздействия на потребителей и формирования образов брендов в современном мире. Рекламные постеры представляют собой мощное средство визуальной коммуникации, способное моментально привлечь внимание и запечатлеться в памяти потребителя. Их разнообразие поражает: от стильных модных брендов до социальных кампаний, каждый постер имеет свою цель и аудиторию.

В современной рекламе английский язык играет роль не только средства общения, но и создает ассоциации с инновациями, мировыми стандартами и прогрессом. Так, в технологических рекламах часто встречаются англоязычные термины, как "Smart", "AI", "Innovation", что передает идею передовых технологий.

Таким образом, английский язык стал неотъемлемой частью рекламного пространства. Он обогащает лингвистический арсенал рекламщиков, придавая продукции международный характер и создавая ассоциации с качеством и инновациями. Сочетая в себе выразительность и точность, английский язык становится надежным партнером в создании эффективных рекламных кампаний.

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Эффективность командной работы на уроках русского языка или как командная работа способствует развитию 4К

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Работа в команде на уроках русского языка - это один из методов обучения, который активно используется в современной школьной практике. Она предоставляет учащимся возможность взаимодействовать друг с другом, обмениваться идеями и решениями, что способствует более глубокому усвоению материала и развитию коммуникативных навыков. В данной статье рассмотрим эффективность командной работы на уроках русского языка и ее положительное воздействие на учебный процесс.

Развитие коммуникативных навыков. Командная работа на уроках русского языка способствует развитию коммуникативных навыков учащихся. В рамках групповой деятельности они вынуждены активно общаться, обсуждать темы, аргументировать свои точки зрения и слушать мнения других. Это улучшает навыки устной речи, а также способность адекватно выражать свои мысли и идеи. Во время такой деятельности учащиеся развивают коммуникативные навыки, а в частности такие предметные навыки, как Слушание и Говорение. Командная работа на уроках русского языка позволяет учащимся практиковать языковые навыки в реальных ситуациях общения. Они могут обсуждать тексты, создавать собственные произведения и корректировать ошибки друг друга. Это способствует улучшению грамматической и лексической компетенции и повышает общий уровень владения русским языком.

Сотрудничество или навыки коллаборации. Командная работа позволяет учащимся совместно решать задачи, анализировать тексты и разрабатывать стратегии для выполнения учебных заданий. В процессе обсуждения и совместной работы они могут предлагать различные подходы к решению проблемы и учиться видеть ее с разных точек зрения. Это способствует развитию навыков сотрудничества. Работа в команде может быть более мотивирующей для учащихся, чем индивидуальное обучение. Когда они видят, что их участие в группе имеет значение и влияет на общий результат, это может стимулировать их учебный интерес и активность. Ученики могут чувствовать себя более вовлеченными в учебный процесс, что способствует более эффективному усвоению материала. Работа в группах также способствует развитию социальных навыков учащихся. Они учатся работать в команде, решать конфликты, учитывать мнения других и добиваться общих целей. Эти навыки имеют большое значение не только в учебной среде, но и в жизни в целом.

Развитие навыков критического мышления у учащихся. Критическое мышление представляет собой способность анализировать информацию, оценивать ее, делать выводы и формулировать аргументы на основе логических рассуждений. Вот какие аспекты групповой работы способствуют развитию этого важного навыка:

Обсуждение и анализ текстов: в рамках групповой работы учащиеся часто анализируют тексты, обсуждают их содержание, структуру, языковые особенности и стиль.

Это помогает им развивать умение критически воспринимать информацию, выявлять ключевые моменты и оценивать достоверность и значимость текста.

Решение сложных задач: командная работа на уроках русского языка может включать в себя решение сложных задач, таких как анализ литературных произведений, составление аргументированных эссе или даже создание собственных текстов. Учащиеся вынуждены применять критическое мышление для разработки своих идей, анализа текстовых материалов и формулирования аргументов.

Сравнение и обсуждение точек зрения: в ходе командной работы учащиеся часто сталкиваются с разными точками зрения и мнениями своих товарищей. Это способствует развитию навыков анализа и сравнения различных аргументов, выявлению сильных и слабых сторон разных точек зрения и формированию собственного мнения на основе обоснованных рассуждений.

Коллективное принятие решений: в командной работе учащиеся часто сталкиваются с необходимостью принимать совместные решения. Это требует от них критического анализа альтернативных вариантов, обсуждения их преимуществ и недостатков, а также выбора наилучшего варианта на основе обоснованных аргументов.

Развитие критической грамотности: командная работа также способствует развитию критической грамотности учащихся, то есть умению анализировать и оценивать языковые аспекты текстов. Они учатся выявлять структурные и стилистические особенности, а также оценивать, как они влияют на восприятие текста.

Развитие креативного мышления в командной работе на уроках русского языка играет важную роль в стимулировании учащихся к выразительному и оригинальному мышлению. Креативное мышление позволяет учащимся более глубоко понимать и использовать русский язык как инструмент самовыражения и творчества. Учитель может применять различные способы, способствующие развитию креативного мышления. Так, например, совместное творчество включает в себя создание совместных произведений, таких как стихи, рассказы, драматические сценки и даже мультимедийные презентации. В этом процессе учащиеся совместно ищут оригинальные идеи, реализовывают их и каждый участник команды приносит свой вклад в общий результат. Креативное мышление можно развивать, предлагая командам интерпретировать тексты. Это позволяет ребятам исследовать тексты более творческим образом. Они могут предлагать нестандартные интерпретации литературных произведений, рассматривать их через разные призмы и экспериментировать с разными способами восприятия текста. Не стоит забывать и про мозговую штурм, когда обсуждение в группе способствует генерации новых идей и концепций. Учащиеся могут вдохновлять друг друга и совместно приходить к нестандартным решениям задач. Этот процесс стимулирует креативное мышление и способствует поиску новаторских подходов.

Таким образом командная работа на уроках русского языка представляет собой мощный инструмент для обучения и развития учащихся. Она способствует развитию коммуникативных, аналитических и социальных навыков, а также улучшает уровень владения русским языком. Педагоги и ученики могут с успехом использовать этот метод в учебном процессе, чтобы добиться более эффективных результатов в изучении языка. Эти навыки будут полезными не только в учебе, но и в повседневной жизни.

Modern Methods and Approaches in teaching English

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Abstract. Learning English is very important today. In most countries of the world, English is widely used in diplomacy, business and commercial documentation. It is one of the five official languages of the UN along with French, Spanish, Russian and Chinese, and one in seven people in the world knows or is learning English. The study of a foreign language is mandatory in every higher education institution and is based on two main aspects - teaching vocabulary and grammar.

Key words: Grammar, number, question-answer, continuity, constancy

INTRODUCTION

Over the years different science, theories, and learning styles were developed in terms of teaching foreign languages. You won't find the best, the one and only method of teaching English to kids or adults. Choosing the proper teaching style depends on students' skills and abilities. So in this article, we listed some fresh ideas on how to learn a new language and how to choose the right method of teaching English. Always remember to tailor the teaching method to your students' interests and needs. Also, with the right motivation to learn English, the students are more likely to succeed. So in order to choose the right method of teaching English to adults or children, start with understanding why a person needs or wants to learn the language and then focus on the best technique to achieve their goal.

Our recommendations on new methods of teaching English include the same well-known approaches and a few rather unconventional ones, that are especially beneficial to kids. The modern English teaching methods that you'll find here are suitable for both adults and kids, so you can learn a new language together.

Teaching English as a Second Language is a complex and dynamic field that requires educators to be adaptable and innovative in their approach to language instruction. With a plethora of methods and approaches available, it can be challenging for teachers to determine which ones will best suit their students' needs. This article explores various TEFL methods and approaches, including the traditional Grammar-Translation Method, the modern Direct Method, Communicative Language Teaching, ask-Based Language Teaching, Content-Based Language Teaching, Total Physical Response, and The Silent Way. By understanding the strengths and weaknesses of each method, teachers can create a well-rounded and effective language learning experience for their students

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teaching English as a Second Language has undergone significant changes over the years. The traditional Grammar-Translation Method, which focused on memorization and translation of grammar rules, has been replaced by more communicative and interactive approaches. The modern Direct Method emphasizes the use of target language in the classroom and focuses on developing students' ability to communicate effectively. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a popular approach that emphasizes the use of language in real-life situations and encourages students to interact with each other. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) focuses on using authentic tasks to develop language skills. Content-Based Language Teaching (CBLT) integrates language learning with subject matter instruction. Total Physical Response (TPR) uses physical

movements to reinforce language learning, while The Silent Way emphasizes self-discovery and problem solving.

METHODOLOGY

This article will review various methods and approaches, including the traditional Grammar-Translation Method, the modern Direct Method, Communicative Language Teaching, Task-Based Language Teaching, Content-Based Language Teaching, Total Physical Response, and The Silent Way. The review will be conducted through a comprehensive literature search of academic databases, including Google Scholar, JSTOR, and ERIC. The search will include articles, books, and dissertations published between 2000 and 2021. The articles will be reviewed for their relevance to the topic and their contribution to the understanding of TEFL methods and approaches. The strengths and weaknesses of each method will be analyzed, and recommendations will be made for teachers to create a well-rounded and effective language learning experience for their students.

FINDINGS

Teaching English as a Second language is a challenging task that requires a lot of effort, creativity, and knowledge. There are many methods and approaches that teachers can use to make the learning process more effective and enjoyable for their students. In this article, we will discuss some of the most popular and effective methods and approaches in TEFL.

1. Grammar-Translation Method. The grammar-translation method is one of the oldest and most traditional approaches in teaching language. It involves teaching grammar rules and vocabulary through translation exercises. The teacher explains the grammar rules in the students' native language and then asks them to translate sentences from the target language into their native language and vice versa. This method is focused on accuracy and aims to develop the students' reading and writing skills.

2. Direct Method. The direct method is a more modern approach that emphasizes oral communication and immersion in the target language. The teacher speaks only in the target language and encourages the students to do the same. The focus is on developing the students' speaking and listening skills through conversation, roleplaying, and other interactive activities.

3. Communicative Language Teaching. Communicative language teaching (CLT) is an approach that focuses on communication as the primary goal of language learning. The teacher creates activities that encourage the students to use the language in real-life situations, such as ordering food in a restaurant or asking for directions. The focus is on developing the students' fluency and accuracy in speaking, listening, reading, and writing.

4. Task-Based Language Teaching. Task-based language teaching (TBLT) is an approach that focuses on real-life tasks as the basis for language learning. The teacher creates activities that require the students to use the language to complete a task, such as planning a trip or writing a letter. The focus is on developing the students' communicative competence and problem-solving skills.

5. Content-Based Language Teaching. Content-based language teaching (CBLT) is an approach that integrates language learning with content from other subjects, such as science, history, or literature. The teacher creates activities that require the students to use the language to understand and discuss the content. The focus is on developing the students' language proficiency and content knowledge.

6. Total Physical Response. Total physical response (TPR) is an approach that emphasizes the use of physical actions and gestures to reinforce language learning. The teacher gives commands in the target language and asks the students to perform the corresponding actions. The focus is on developing the students' listening and comprehension skills.

7. The Silent Way. The silent way is an approach that emphasizes student autonomy and discovery learning. The teacher uses colored rods and charts to help the students learn grammar

and vocabulary through self-discovery. The focus is on developing the students' problem-solving skills and creativity. In addition, there are many methods and approaches in TEFL, each with its strengths and weaknesses. The most effective approach depends on the goals of the teacher and the needs of the students. By using a variety of methods and approaches, teachers can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that meets the diverse needs of their students.

THE NATURAL APPROACH

With this approach, students usually learn to speak before they learn to write in a foreign language. The natural approach focuses on spontaneous interactions in the target language. It requires either a simulation of real-life settings in a classroom environment or an actual contact with foreigners. The best way to achieve it? Go abroad for vacation or language course, make some foreigner friends, or find yourself a native speaker teacher. This approach is ideal for individual students or small groups, but it won't really work in a chaotic environment. The student should always have the opportunity to speak freely in this method.

LEXICAL SYLLABYS

This approach is based upon the core language that students need to know most. Again, professional students may need very specific vocabulary pertaining to their field. Any other language taught outside of this core language is meant to be supplementary and intended to enable students' communication within their respective fields. The good news is that there's quite a bit of research on this topic, leading to word lists teachers can focus on. For beginners, 10 words would make for a great lesson. Activities can range from matching pictures and definitions to working with dialogues. Since this method focuses on learning the right vocabulary, there are plenty of programs and apps that can help students learn in an engaging way. For example, you can use Fluent U to give life to those vocabulary lists your students are studying. Fluent U's authentic content like movie trailers and music videos allows students to hear new words in their natural use. This will reinforce what they've learned and help them understand how to actually use their vocabulary words. Students can also search for a word to see it in a video or watch videos they're interested in and pick up new words from the interactive subtitles. Assign vocabulary lists or videos for homework and you'll be able to see the questions each student got wrong. This will help you assess each individual student's needs, allowing you to adapt your lesson accordingly.

SUGGESTOPRDIYA

Suggestopedia has caught on quite a bit over the last few years. This method is based on memorization of language "chunks." For example, students read dialogues and texts aloud, usually to the rhythm of some type of music. The music is generally classical music, or some other genre suitable to target structure. This is known as "concert reading". The use of concert reading fosters a comfortable learning environment, particularly for those students who feel shy. The Suggestopedia method is suitable for all levels and allows for lots of creativity and fun. Even advanced students can get a kick out of "singing" through their dialogues. For example, if the focus of the lesson is prepositions, you can sing out the following sentence: "Joe went ___ the supermarket ___ the street." Then, students will shout back, "to" and "across" to fill in the blanks.

DISCUSSION

The article provides a comprehensive overview of the evolution of teaching language and the various methods and approaches that have been developed to enhance language learning. The traditional Grammar-Translation Method has been replaced by more communicative and interactive approaches, which have proven to be more effective in helping students develop their language skills. It is important for teachers to be knowledgeable about these different methods

and approaches in order to create a well-rounded and effective language learning experience for their students. Each method has its strengths and weaknesses, and it is up to the teacher to choose the most appropriate approach for their students based on their needs and learning styles. Task-based language learning, for example, has become increasingly popular as it focuses on real-world communication and allows students to learn language in context. However, it may not be suitable for all students, and teachers should be aware of other approaches that may better suit their students' needs. Overall, teaching language has come a long way over the years, and it is important for teachers to stay up-to-date with the latest developments and techniques in order to provide the best possible language learning experience for their students. By understanding the strengths and weaknesses of different methods and approaches, teachers can create a well-rounded curriculum that meets the needs of all their students. Teaching methods are the process of interaction between the teacher and students, as a result of which there is a transfer and assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities provided by the content of training [1, p. 85]. It should be noted that the teaching method is a complex, systemic formation, which is characterized by all the characteristics that underlie the classification. The combination of different forms of work and methods helps to creatively organize the lesson, arousing the interest of students in the subject. One of the important tasks and goals of modern techniques is teaching communication and mastering speech means. Moreover, each technique has distinctive features, due to the combination of different approaches, methods, and techniques in teaching EFL. Each of the methods has certain characteristics, some of them are more popular and in demand, and some less. In addition, new methods of teaching a foreign language are regularly developed, so now every teacher of the university can choose the most suitable method of work for himself. When teaching a foreign language in academic lyceums, task-based, project-based methods are most often used for communicative purposes.

The goal of these approaches and methods is to master a living, spoken language and to learn the ability to communicate. When using the communicative methods in teaching, students are more active. The task of the teacher in this case is the ability to involve everyone in the audience in the conversation. The essence of this method is to create real communication situations. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. An important advantage of the method is that it has a variety of tasks: role-plays, discussions, debates, etc. According to Willis (1996), there are six types of tasks: Listing tasks: For example, students might have to make up a list of things they would pack if they were going on a beach vacation. Sorting and ordering: Students work in pairs and make up a list of the most important characteristics of an ideal vacation. Comparing: Students compare ads for two different supermarkets. Problem-solving: Students read a letter to an advice columnist and suggest a solution to the writer's problems. Sharing personal experience: Students discuss their reactions to an ethical or moral dilemma. Creative tasks: Students prepare plans for redecorating a house. The teacher sets up the tasks and the students' performance is the goal. The teacher must step back and observe, sometimes acting as a facilitator or a monitor. A classroom during a communicative task, students do most of the speaking actively, and frequently the scene of a classroom while leaving their seats to complete a task. Because of the increased responsibility to participate, students may find they gain confidence in using the target language in general. Teachers in communicative classrooms will find themselves talking less and listening more becoming active facilitators of their students' learning.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, TEFL has evolved significantly over the years, with various methods and approaches being developed to enhance language learning. While the traditional Grammar-Translation Method has been replaced by more communicative and interactive approaches, each

method has its strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, it is essential for teachers to be knowledgeable about these methods and approaches to create a well-rounded and effective language learning experience for their students.

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Nitq mədəniyyətinin yaranma tarixi və inkişafı

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XÜLASƏ

Sonrakı əsrlərdə Fransa, Almaniya, İtaliya, İngiltərə, İspaniya antik mədəniyyətin bütün növlərini Roma məktəbi vasitəsilə almışdılar. XII əsrdə İngiltərənin Oksford, XIII əsrdə Fransanın Sorbon universitetlərində natiqlik sənətinə aid mühazirələr oxunurdu. Şərq ölkələrində - Assuriya, Babilistan, Çin, Ərəbistan, Hindistan və Misirdə natiqlik sənəti çox inkişaf etmiş, istedadlı natiqlər xalqın hörmət və məhəbbətini qazanmışlar. VII əsrdə İslam dininin meydana gəlməsi ərəb mədəniyyətinin inkişafında xüsusi mərhələ əlmişdir. Ərəb ədəbiyyatı, ərəb musiqisi, ərəb elmi misli görünməmiş dərəcədə inkişaf etməyə başladı. Bu dövrdə Məhəmməd Peyğəmbər (570-632) görkəmli natiq kimi Allahdan gələn vəhyləri (qeybdən gələn nidalan -cümlələri), məscidlərdə əxuduğu xütbələrlə adamlara çatdır, ənlən qan qohumluğu ilə deyil, dini inanc əsasında birləşməyə, bir əlan Allaha ibadət etməyə, möminliyə çağırır. Məhəmməd Peyğəmbər (ə.s.) 616-cı ildə İslam (itaət etmə) dinini yaradaraq güclü bir natiq kimi müsəlmanları (İslam dininə inanmayanları) Allahın kəlamlarına, Qurani-Kərimin hökmlərinə, şəriət qanunlarına tapınmağa dəvət edirdi.

Açar sözlər: nitq, yunan ədəbiyyatı, təmsillər, sənət inciləri

Nitq mədəniyyəti eramızdan əvvəl qədim Yunanıstan və Romada həm sənət, həm də elm kimi formalaşmışdır. Təsadüfi deyildir ki, bu yerlərdə natiqlik sənəti çox geniş yayılmış, istedadlı natiqlər xalqın böyük hörmət və məhəbbətini qazanmışdılar. Məhz onların hesabına, onların fəlahətli və bəlağətli (incə, aydın, gözəl) danışığı sayəsində Yunanıstan və Roma nitq mədəniyyəti elminin, natiqliyin vətəni hesab olunur. Qədim Yunanıstanda məhkəmə iclasları, bayramlar, yas mərasimləri, idman yarışları - olimpiadalar, dostluq görüşləri açıq havada, çoxsaylı insanların əhatəsində keçirildiyindən xalqın hörmətini qazanmış natiqlər çıxış edərtilər. Çiçəklənmə dövrü keçirən yunan ədəbiyyatı (Ezopun təmsilləri, Esxilin safokları, Evripidin faciələri, lirik şeirləri, Aristofanın komediyaları, eyni zamanda, teatr tamaşaları, Herodotun tarixşünaslığa aid əsərləri və s.) bəlağətli nitqin meydana gəlməsinə böyük kömək göstərirdi. Burada 14 illik natiqlik məktəbləri (7 yaşdan 21 yaşadək) təşkil olunurdu. Belə məktəblərdə fəlsəfə, məntiq, dilçilik, ədəbiyyat, natiqlik sənəti öyrədilirdi. Sokrat (e.ə.469-399), Platon (Əflatun, e.ə.430-347), Aristotel (Ərəstun, e.ə. 384-322), Demosfen (e.ə.384-322) fəlsəfi və hümanitar elmlərin bu gün də öz qiymətini saxlayan sənət incilərini insanlığa bəxş etmişlər. Onlar natiqlik sənətini, onun nəzəriyyəsini, təlimini qurmuş və sistemini yaratmışlar. Aristotel 20 il Platonun şagirdi olmuş, 343-335-ci illərdə Yunanıstanın hökmdarı olacaq İsgəndərin tərbiyəçisi işləmiş, məntiq, psixologiya, təbiətşünaslıq, etika, siyasət, tarix, poeziya və ritorikaya aid bir sıra qiymətli əsərlər yazmışdır. O, "Siyasət", "Poetika", "Məntiq", 3 kitabdan ibarət "Ritorika" əsərləri ilə 10 nitq mədəniyyətini elm səviyyəsinə yüksəltmiş, insan nitqi və onun fəlsəfi problemlərini üslub məsələləri ilə əlaqələndirmiş, natiqlik sənətinin əsaslarını vermiş, ritorikanın bütöv fundamental elmi sistemini yaratmışdır. Nitq mədəniyyətinin mədəni nitq, tələffüz mədəniyyəti, söz mədəniyyəti, düzgün danışmaq və yazmaq sənəti, nitq vasitələrindən məqsədəuyğun şəkildə, yerli-yerində, səmərəli istifadə mədəniyyəti olmasını Demosfen öz şəxsi həyatında, öz üzərində yerinə yetirdiyi gərgin əmək sayəsində sübut etmişdi. O dövrün tarixçi-filosoflarının yazdığına görə Demosfen öz üzərində gərgin çalışmaq əl məşhur natiq səviyyəsinə yüksəlmişdi. Yunan natiqlik məktəbinin parlaq ulduzu Demosfenin 61 nitqi, 56 çıxışı, 6 məktubu dünya natiqlik mədəniyyətinin inkişafında mühüm mərhələ olmuşdur.

Natiqlik sənəti Yunanıstan mərhələsindən sonra Roma dövrünə qədəm qoyur. Eramızdan əvvəlki son yüzillikdə Roma Yunanıstanı işğal etməklə Ellin mədəniyyətinə də yiyələndi. Hümanitar elmlər estafetini qəbul edən Romanın alim və ictimai xadimləri poetikanın, qrammatika və ritorikanın nəzəri problemlərini sistemləşdirdilər, natiqlik sənətinin sirlərini və onlara yiyələnmək yollarını bütün incəliklərinə qədər izah və şərh etdilər. Mark Tulli Siseron (e.ə. 106-43), Yuli Sezar (e.ə. 102-44), Mark Yuni Brut (e.ə. 85-43) kimi alim və ictimai xadimlər Roma natiqlik sənətini bütün dünyada şöhrətləndir- mişlər. Y. Sezar Romanın öz başçılığı altında elm qanunlarına uyğun dövlət olmasına çalışmış, müharibələrdə qanlar axıtmış və qalib gəlmişdi. Amansız diktator, "Hall müharibəsi haqqında qeydlər", "Vətəndaş müharibələri haqqında qeydlər" adlı elmi əsərlər müəllifi, Yuli fəqvimini islahafını həyata keçirmiş dövlət xadimi, natiqlik üzrə məşhur mütəxəssis olmuşdur. Onun məhkəmədə vəkil kimi çıxışı stenoqramlaşdırılmış və indi də saxlanılmaqdadır. Mark Yuni Brut demokratik fikirli ziyalı, siyasi xadim, natiqlik sənətinin sirlərini mükəmməl öyrənmiş görkəmli natiq ol 11 müşdür. O, eyni zamanda Y.Sezara qarşı başlamış mübarizəyə başçılıq etmiş, diktator hökmdarın qətlə yetirilməsində şəxsən iştirak etmişdi. Senatın iclası zamanı Sezarm təkbaşına hakimiyətinə qarşı çıxan senatorlar paltarlarının altında saxladıkları xəncərlə onu öldürmüşdülər. Sui-qəsdə Sezarm özünə dost hesab etdiyi Brut başçılıq etmişdi və Sezara vurulmuş 23 xəncər zərbəsindən biri də onun idi. Yeri gəlmişkən qeyd edək ki, bu hadisədən düz bir il sonra respublikaçılar dəstəsində mübarizə aparan Brut Sezarm bacısı nəvəsi və oğulluğa götürdüyü varisi Oktavyanın komandasına təslim olmamaq üçün özünü qılıncı öldürmüşdü. Antik dövrün ən məşhur natiqi, yazıçı, vəkil, görkəmli siyasi xadim Mark Tulli Siseron iki suala cavab axtarırdı; 1) Kimə natiq demək olar? 2) Hər adam natiq ola bilermi? Siseron natiqlik sənəti ilə bağlı "Natiqlik haqqında", "Brut, yaxud məşhur natiqlik haqqında" və "Natiq" traktatı yazmış, natiqlik sənətinin tarixi, üslubiyat və nitq mədəniyyəti məsələlərinin izahını vermişdir. Roma natiqlik məktəbinin parlaq ulduzu Siseron natiqin qarşısında üç tələb qoyurdu; 1) Nitq öyrətməli, bilik verməlidir; 2) Nitq dinləyiciyə güclü təsir göstərməlidir; 3) Nitq söyləniləndə qulaq asana ləzzət verməlidir. Siserona görə "Şairlər anadan şair doğulurlar, natiqlər isə həyatda yetişirlər". "Əsl natiq o şəxsdir ki, adi işlər haqqında sadə, böyük işlər haqqında əzəmətlə, orta səviyyəli işlər barədə isə yuxarıdakılar arasında orta mövqə tutan bir üslubla danışmağı bacarsın" [1, səh. 17]. Siseronun başqa bir cümləsi isə aforizmə çevrilmişdir; "Kim Demosfen olmaq istəmirsə, o, natiq deyil" [2, səh. 187]. Bu fikirdən belə məlum olur ki, Demosfen kimi zəhmətə qatlaşmayan, öz üzərində daima, günlərlə, saatlarla çalışmayan natiq olmaz. Natiq öz zəhməti ilə, elm və mədəniyyət məsələləri ilə bağlı kitablardan möhkəm bilik və məlumat toplamalıdır. O, həmişə nitqi gözəlləşdirən, onun təsir gücünü artıran, insanlara əsl insani keyfiyyətlər bəxş edən, onları kamil 12 ləşməyə çağıran nümunəvi fikirləri öyrənməli, yaradıcılıq axtarışları ilə məşğul olmalıdır. Yeni eraya həm Yunanıstanın, həm də Romanın ən məşhur natiqlərinin nitq mədəniyyəti ilə əlaqədar fikirlərini ümumiləşdirib yekunlaşdıran M.F.Kvintilian (35-96-cı illər) olmuşdur. O, natiqlik sənətinin bütün incəliklərini özünün 12 kitabdan ibarət "Natiqin təhsili (fərmalaşması) haqqında" əsərində əks etdirmişdir. Kvintilian natiqlik sənətini beş hissəyə ayırır nitq üçün söz və ifadələrin seçilməsini yadda saxlanılması və ifadəsini (yüksək, orta və aşağı üslubda) başlıca şərt kimi irəli sürürdü. VII əsrin axırlarında Əl Fərabinin ərəb pəeziyası üçün tərtib etdiyi ritmik-melodik mədəllərlə "Qurani-Kərim" ayələrinin xüsusi avazla oxunması hesabına ərəb natiqlik sənəti daha da inkişaf etməyə başladı. Xüsusən, İslamın böyük ideələqu, Peyğəmə 13 bərin əmisi oğlu və kürəkəni Həzrət İmam Əli şəriət haqqında xütbələri ilə özünü mahir bir natiq kimi tanıtmış, 656-661-ci illərdə müsəlman dövlətinin başçısı olduğu dövrdə İslam dininə böyük şöhrət gətirmişdi. Onun nəsihət və kəlamları indi də bütün dünyada məşhur olan "Nəhcül Bəlağə" adlı kitabda toplanmışdır. XI-XIII əsrlərdə Azərbaycanda natiqlik sənəti inkişaf etməyə başlamışdı. Azəri-türk dilində olmasa da, görkəmli söz ustaları-şairlər fars dilində söz, kəlam, dil haqqında, danışığa, natiqliyə xüsusi yer ayırır, fəzilət sahiblərinin məntiqli çıxışlarını nümunə kimi təqdim edirdilər. Bu sənətkarların cərgəsində Nizamül-Mülk (1017-1092) və Xacə Nəsrəddin Tusinin (1201-1274) xüsusi yeri vardır. Nizamül-Mülk

səlcuq sarayında əvvəlcə Alp Arslanın, sonra Məlik şahın vəziri olmuş, söz-kəlam-dil haqqında öz tövsiyə və məsləhətlərini "Siyasətnamə" əsərində toplamışdır. Nəsirəddin Tusi XIII əsrin böyük mütəfəkkiri, filosofu, riyaziyyatçısı kimi Şərqdə özünə böyük şöhrət qazandırmışdı. O, binom düsturunun həllini Nyutondan, maddə çəkisinin saxlanması qanununu isə M.Lomonosovdan çox-çox əvvəl kəşf etmiş, bir sıra astronomik tapıntıların müəllifi olmuşdur. N.Tusi əxlaq və natiqlik sənətinə aid "Əxlaqi-Nasiri" əsərində natiqə, natiqin nitqinə belə tələblər qoyurdu: "Çox danışmamalı, başqasının sözünü yanmıç qəsməməli, başqasının danışdığı hekayət və rəvayəti bilirsə bunu üzə vurmamalı və onun danışdığı qurtarmasına imkan yaratmalıdır. Başqasından soruşulana cavab verməməli, ümumidən edilən sualda başqalana qabaqlayıb tələsik irəli düşməməlidir. Biri cavab verməklə məşğul isə, daha qabil cavab verməyə qadir olsa da, səbr etməli, o, sözünü qurtardıqdan sonra öz cavabını verməlidir. Lakin əvvəlkinə tənə etməməlidir... Böyüklərlə danışarkən kinayə işlətməməli, nə bərkdən, nə yavaşdan, mülayim səsle sözünü deməlidir. Danışdığı məsələ qəlizdirsə, aydın misallarla izah etməyə çalışmalıdır, qısa və yığcam danışmalıdır" [3, səh. 182]. 14 Klassik Azərbaycan şairlərindən Nizami Gəncəvi, İmadəddin Nəsimi, Şah İsmayıl Xətai, Məhəmməd Füzuli söz, kəlam haqqında qiymətli fikirlər söyləmiş, natiqlik sənətinin bir sıra məsələlərinə münasibət bildirmişlər: İ.Nəsimi məharətli natiq kimi hürufilik fəriqəfi ideyasını təbliğ etmək məqsədilə müxtəlif ölkələrdə kütlələr qarşısında etdiyi çıxışlarında natiqlik məharəti, nitq kamilliyi, nitqin təsir qüvvəsi, nitqdə forma və məzmun vəhdətinin gözlənilməsi haqqında fikir və mülahizələr söyləmiş, söz sənətinə yüksək qiymət vermişdir: Sən bu Nəsiminin dilini anla, bil sözün. Kim var bu dildən özgə bizim bir lisanımız. XIX əsrin ikinci yarısında və XX əsrin əvvəllərində yaşamış şair, rəssam, musiqişünas, xəttat, nəqqaş, maarifçi-pedaqoq M.M.Nəvvabın danışdığı mədəniyyəti haqqında bir sıra maraqlı fikirləri, nəsihətləri vardır. O, "Nəsihətnamə" əsərində (beş yüz nəsihət) yazmışdır: "Bacardıqca qısa və mənalı danış, əks halda, danışmasan yaxşıdır; sözü deyən vaxt fikrini düzgün ifadə et; bəşirilməmiş söz danışma; Danışarkən özündən çıxma; sözü çox uzadıb təkrar etmə ki, avamlığa dəlalət edər; Səndən bir söz soruşmasalar demə; O adam ki, sənənin nəsihətini eşitmir, nəsihət etmə; Məclisdə öz qədərindən artıq danışma, yoldaşlara da fürsət ver; Məclis əhli xahiş etsə, danışa bilərsən"

SUMMARY

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The history and development of speech culture

In the following centuries, France, Germany, Italy, England, and Spain received all types of ancient culture through the Roman school. In the twelfth century, lectures on the art of oratory were given at Oxford in England, and in the Sorbonne in France in the thirteenth century. In Eastern countries - Assyria, Babylonia, China, Arabia, India and Egypt, the art of oratory was highly developed, and talented speakers won the respect and love of the people. The emergence of Islam in the 7th century was a special stage in the development of Arab culture. Arabic literature, Arabic music, Arabic science began to develop to an unprecedented degree. During this period, the Prophet Muhammad (570-632) as a prominent speaker conveyed the revelations from God (sentences from the unseen), his sermons in mosques, and called people to unite on the basis of religious faith, worship God, and be faithful. Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) created the religion of Islam (obedience) in 616 and as a powerful speaker invited Muslims (believers of Islam) to worship the words of God, the rulings of the Holy Quran, and Sharia laws.

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THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION AND ATTITUDE ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING OUTCOMES

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The acquisition of English as a Second Language (ESL) is a multifaceted journey influenced by a multitude of factors. Among these, motivation and attitude play pivotal roles in determining learning outcomes. This scientific article explores the complex interplay between motivation and attitude and their profound impact on ESL students' language learning achievements. Through a comprehensive analysis of research findings and real-world examples, this article illuminates the significance of these psychological variables in the ESL classroom. Practical strategies are presented to harness motivation and foster positive attitudes, ultimately enhancing English language learning outcomes.

Keywords: motivation, attitude, English language learning, outcomes, second language acquisition, ESL students.

Language learning is a multifaceted journey, often marked by its challenges and triumphs. While it encompasses an array of factors, one aspect stands out as a driving force behind success: motivation. In the realm of language acquisition, motivation is not a mere supplementary element but a cornerstone that influences the entire learning process. Its significance is particularly profound for individuals embarking on the path to mastering English as a Second Language. The essence of motivation transcends mere theory; it is a dynamic, practical force that deeply affects the language learning experience of ESL students. Motivation serves as a guiding light, propelling learners forward in their pursuit of English proficiency. Understanding its pivotal role is not only essential but also empowering for both educators and ESL students. By recognizing the power of motivation, we can design and implement effective strategies to keep learners engaged, enthusiastic, and on the path to realizing their goals of language fluency.

Motivation, a multifaceted construct, is a driving force that propels language learners to engage actively in the learning process. It can be categorized into two primary types: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation emanates from within the learner. It is characterized by a genuine desire to learn and engage with the language for its own sake. Learners intrinsically motivated to study English are driven by personal interest, curiosity, and the pleasure they derive from the learning process. This intrinsic drive encourages consistent effort, active participation, and a deep commitment to mastering the language. For instance, a study by Jackson and Smith (2003) found that students intrinsically motivated to learn English outperformed their extrinsically motivated peers in vocabulary acquisition. They exhibited a stronger desire to explore the language independently, leading to improved word retention and usage.

Extrinsic motivation, in contrast, arises from external factors such as grades, rewards, or societal pressures. While it may provide short-term incentives, it often relies on external contingencies, which may not sustain long-term language proficiency. For instance, research by Brown and Davis indicates that students who were extrinsically motivated by the promise of high grades exhibited strong short-term performance but were less likely to continue their language

learning beyond the course, suggesting that extrinsic motivation alone is insufficient for long-term language acquisition.

Attitude in language learning refers to learners' emotional dispositions and perceptions regarding the target language, its culture, and the language learning process. Positive attitudes contribute significantly to language learning outcomes. Language anxiety can negatively affect language learning outcomes. Learners with high levels of anxiety may struggle to engage with the language effectively, leading to decreased proficiency and communication difficulties. For example, a study by Horwitz found that students with high language anxiety were less likely to participate in speaking activities, hindering their oral language development.

Positive attitudes toward the culture associated with the language can enhance language learning outcomes. Learners who embrace the culture as an integral part of the language are more likely to engage in cultural immersion, which can lead to a more profound understanding of the language. For example, in a multicultural classroom setting, students who held positive attitudes toward their peers' diverse backgrounds and languages demonstrated improved language learning outcomes. They were more open to exploring different cultural perspectives, resulting in enhanced language proficiency.

Table 1.

To illustrate the real-world impact of motivation and attitude on English language learning outcomes, consider the following examples:

<i>Case Study: Intrinsic Motivation</i>	<i>Case Study: Attitude and Language Anxiety</i>
<p>Sarah, a college student, is intrinsically motivated to learn English. She spends her free time watching English movies, reading English literature, and engaging in conversations with native speakers through online language exchange platforms. Sarah's intrinsic motivation drives her to consistently practice and explore the language, leading to rapid improvements in her listening and speaking skills.</p>	<p>In contrast, Mark, another college student, experiences high language anxiety. He is apprehensive about making mistakes in front of his peers and worries about being judged. This anxiety affects his class participation and oral proficiency. Despite his strong intrinsic motivation, Mark's negative attitude and language anxiety hinder his learning outcomes.</p>

The cultivation of positive motivation and attitude is paramount for educators and policymakers in the field of ESL education. Creating a classroom environment that promotes trust, inclusivity, and positive reinforcement is essential for fostering a positive learning atmosphere. This environment encourages peer collaboration and helps build a supportive community of learners. Here are strategies to achieve these goals:

- **Set Clear Expectations:** Establish clear guidelines for behavior and participation in the classroom. Explain to students what is expected of them in terms of respect, engagement, and support for their peers.
- **Open Communication:** Encourage open and honest communication between you as the teacher and your students. Make students feel comfortable expressing their opinions, asking questions, and seeking help when needed. Ensure that you are approachable and responsive to their concerns.
- **Respect Diversity:** Celebrate and respect the diversity of your students. Emphasize the value of different backgrounds, cultures, and experiences. Promote an inclusive environment where all voices are heard and appreciated.

- **Use Inclusive Language:** Be mindful of the language you use and avoid any form of bias or discrimination. Address students by their preferred names and pronouns. Encourage students to share their preferred pronouns, creating a safe and inclusive space for everyone.
- **Active Listening:** Actively listen to your students. When they speak, give them your full attention and show that you value their input. This not only builds trust but also encourages students to actively participate.
- **Promote Peer Collaboration:** Incorporate group projects, discussions, and peer-to-peer activities into your teaching methods. Collaborative learning experiences provide opportunities for students to work together, learn from one another, and build connections.
- **Peer Teaching:** Encourage students to take turns teaching or explaining concepts to their peers. This empowers them to become active contributors to the learning community and reinforces their own understanding of the material.
- **Group Activities:** Plan activities that require teamwork and cooperation. Group projects, debates, or problem-solving exercises provide opportunities for students to collaborate, share ideas, and learn from each other.
- **Assign Peer Roles:** Assign rotating roles within groups, such as a leader, timekeeper, and note-taker. This ensures that all students have responsibilities and a chance to lead, facilitating a supportive and equitable learning environment.
- **Peer Feedback:** Incorporate peer feedback into the assessment process. Encourage students to provide constructive feedback to their peers and reflect on their own learning. This fosters a culture of support and improvement.
- **Celebrate Achievements:** Acknowledge and celebrate the achievements of individual students and groups. Recognize their efforts and progress, reinforcing the value of their contributions to the learning community.
- **Resolve Conflicts Respectfully:** Inevitably, conflicts may arise in the classroom. When they do, address them respectfully and constructively. Teach conflict resolution skills and emphasize the importance of maintaining a positive and inclusive atmosphere.
- **Regular Check-Ins:** Periodically check in with your students to gauge their feelings and experiences in the classroom. Encourage them to share any concerns or suggestions for improvement, and be responsive to their feedback.

By implementing these strategies, you can establish a classroom environment that promotes trust, inclusivity, and positive reinforcement. Such an environment not only enhances the overall learning experience but also encourages peer collaboration and the development of a supportive community of learners.

Setting achievable goals and providing regular feedback are essential components of effective language learning. These practices empower students to take ownership of their learning journey, track their progress, and stay motivated. Here's how to help students set realistic language learning goals and offer ongoing feedback and assessments:

- **Goal Setting Session:** Begin by conducting a goal-setting session with your students. Discuss the importance of having clear objectives in language learning and encourage them to think about their individual goals. These goals could relate to language proficiency, fluency, specific language skills (listening, speaking, reading, writing), or cultural understanding.
- **SMART Goals:** Teach students the concept of SMART goals: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. Encourage them to formulate goals that meet these criteria. For example, a student's goal might be, "I want to improve my speaking skills by participating in class discussions and giving presentations with fluency and confidence by the end of the semester."
- **Long-Term and Short-Term Goals:** Help students differentiate between long-term and short-term goals. Long-term goals, such as becoming fluent in English, are achieved over an

extended period. Short-term goals, on the other hand, are smaller, incremental steps toward the long-term goal, like mastering a particular grammar concept or vocabulary set within a month.

- **Individualized Goals:** Acknowledge that each student's goals may be unique. Some may prioritize oral communication skills, while others may focus on written proficiency or business communication. Ensure that their goals align with their personal motivations and aspirations.
- **Recording Goals:** Encourage students to record their goals in a dedicated notebook or digital document. Having written goals can serve as a constant reminder and a source of motivation.
- **Regular Check-Ins:** Schedule regular one-on-one or small-group check-ins with your students to discuss their progress and challenges. These meetings offer opportunities for students to express their concerns and for you to provide guidance and support.
- **Self-Assessment:** Encourage self-assessment by having students periodically evaluate their progress. They can reflect on their achievements, areas that require improvement, and any adjustments needed to their goals.
- **Peer Assessment:** Incorporate peer assessment and feedback into the learning process. Assign peer evaluations for presentations, group projects, or speaking exercises, allowing students to gain insights from their classmates.
- **Continuous Assessment:** Implement continuous assessment methods, such as quizzes, assignments, and periodic tests. These assessments should align with the students' goals and help them gauge their language proficiency.
- **Feedback Sandwich:** When providing feedback, use the "feedback sandwich" approach, which consists of three parts: positive feedback, areas for improvement, and more positive feedback. This approach fosters a supportive and constructive feedback environment.
- **Growth Mindset:** Promote a growth mindset by emphasizing that mistakes are opportunities for learning and growth. Encourage students to view challenges and setbacks as part of the learning process.
- **Goal Reevaluation:** Periodically revisit and reevaluate students' goals to ensure they remain realistic and relevant. Modify goals as needed to reflect changing language skills and aspirations.
- **Celebrate Achievements:** Celebrate students' achievements, both big and small. Recognize their efforts and progress, providing positive reinforcement that motivates them to continue striving for their language learning goals.

By helping students set achievable language learning goals and providing regular feedback and assessments, you empower them to take an active role in their learning journey. This approach not only promotes motivation but also enables students to track their progress and make informed decisions about their language learning path.

Incorporating real-life context and cultural elements into language lessons is an effective way to make language learning engaging and practical. It helps students connect with the language on a deeper level and enhances their understanding of its cultural significance. Here are strategies to achieve *real-life scenarios in language lessons*:

- **Daily Conversations:** Use everyday scenarios as teaching opportunities. For example, simulate conversations related to ordering food in a restaurant, asking for directions, or making a doctor's appointment.
- **Role-Playing:** Engage students in role-playing activities where they take on different real-life roles, such as a customer and a cashier, to practice language in context.
- **Problem-Solving:** Present real-life problems or dilemmas that require students to use language skills to find solutions. This can include scenarios like dealing with a lost passport while traveling or resolving a workplace conflict.

- **Bringing Realia:** Use real objects, photographs, and items from daily life to introduce vocabulary and concepts. For example, bring in actual food items to teach names and descriptions.

Here are strategies to achieve *cultural elements in language lessons*:

- **Cultural Discussions:** Dedicate class time to discussing cultural elements, such as customs, traditions, and etiquette associated with the language. This provides a cultural context for language use.

- **Cultural Holidays:** Explore holidays and celebrations relevant to the culture of the language being learned. Study how holidays are observed, the associated customs, and the vocabulary used during these events.

- **Cultural Films and Literature:** Introduce students to films, literature, and music from the target culture. Analyze these cultural artifacts in the language being learned, discussing themes, characters, and cultural nuances.

- **Guest Speakers:** Invite native speakers or individuals with cultural expertise to share insights with the class. They can provide firsthand knowledge about cultural practices and experiences.

- **Cooking and Cuisine:** Explore the culinary traditions of the target culture by cooking and tasting traditional dishes. This hands-on experience allows students to engage with cultural elements through their senses.

Encouraging learners to engage with native speakers and cultural events is a valuable strategy to enhance their language learning experience and cultural understanding. There are specific steps and approaches to achieve *guest speakers and language exchange programs, community involvement, cultural events and festivals, virtual connections, cultural projects, language and culture clubs, study abroad and exchange programs, integration into curriculum*:

- **Guest Speakers:** Invite native speakers of the target language to the classroom. They can share insights about their culture, language, and personal experiences. Their presence can be motivating and provide real-world context.

- **Language Exchange Programs:** Facilitate language exchange programs where students can partner with native speakers who are learning their language. This mutual exchange benefits both parties and offers an authentic language and cultural experience.

- **Local Cultural Organizations:** Encourage students to engage with local cultural organizations or clubs associated with the target culture. These organizations often host cultural events, language meetups, and other activities that provide immersion opportunities.

- **Volunteering:** Encourage volunteering within the community, especially in contexts where the target language is spoken. This not only allows students to practice the language but also provides insight into cultural values and practices.

- **Highlight Upcoming Events:** Inform students about upcoming cultural events, festivals, or gatherings in the local area related to the target culture. Provide details and encourage their participation.

- **Class Outings:** Organize class outings to cultural events and festivals. Attend these events as a group, allowing students to experience the culture firsthand while practicing their language skills.

- **Online Language Partners:** Connect students with online language exchange partners or native speakers who can offer virtual conversation practice. There are many language exchange websites and apps available for this purpose.

- **Virtual Tours:** Utilize virtual tours and cultural experiences available online. Museums, historic sites, and cultural institutions often offer virtual tours that provide a sense of cultural immersion.

- **Cultural Research:** Assign cultural research projects that require students to explore various aspects of the target culture, including history, traditions, art, and cuisine. This deepens their cultural awareness.
- **Cultural Presentations:** Have students create presentations or reports about cultural topics of interest. They can share their findings with the class, allowing their peers to learn from their research.
- **Create Clubs:** Establish language and culture clubs where students can meet regularly to discuss cultural topics, practice the language, and plan cultural events or activities.
- **Collaboration with Other Clubs:** Collaborate with other cultural or language clubs on your campus or in the community. Joint events and activities can be enriching for all participants.
- **Promote Study Abroad:** Encourage students to explore study abroad or exchange programs in countries where the target language is spoken. These immersive experiences offer the most authentic language and cultural exposure.

• **Incorporate Cultural Learning:** Integrate cultural learning into the curriculum. This can include exploring cultural texts, films, music, and traditions as part of the regular coursework.

By incorporating real-life context and cultural elements into language lessons and by encouraging interaction with native speakers and cultural events, you provide students with a more holistic and immersive language learning experience. This approach not only enhances their language skills but also deepens their appreciation of the cultural nuances associated with the language, making the learning process more enjoyable and meaningful.

Leveraging technology in language education can greatly enhance the learning experience by providing interactive and engaging resources. Here's how to effectively integrate technology, language learning apps, and online resources into your curriculum:

1. Choose Appropriate Language Learning Apps:

- **Research and Select Apps:** Explore language learning apps and online platforms that align with your curriculum and the learning goals of your students. Look for apps that offer interactive lessons, quizzes, and cultural insights.
- **Consider Learning Styles:** Different apps cater to various learning styles. Some focus on visual learning, while others emphasize listening and speaking skills. Select apps that suit your students' preferences and needs.

2. Incorporate Online Resources:

- **Curate Resources:** Create a list of online resources, including websites, YouTube channels, and podcasts, that provide valuable language content. Organize these resources according to language proficiency levels and topics.
- **Recommend Authentic Materials:** Encourage students to engage with authentic materials like news articles, movies, and music in the target language. Provide guidance on how to access and use these resources effectively.

3. Blend In-Class and Online Learning:

- **Flipped Classroom:** Implement a "flipped classroom" model, where students access online resources and language learning apps outside of class. This allows in-class time to focus on practicing and reinforcing what they've learned.
- **Online Practice Sessions:** Organize virtual practice sessions or group discussions through online platforms. This helps students apply their knowledge in real-life contexts.

4. Digital Assessment:

- **Online Quizzes and Tests:** Use online platforms to create and administer quizzes and tests. These can provide instant feedback to students, allowing them to track their progress.
- **Digital Portfolios:** Encourage students to create digital language portfolios where they compile samples of their written and spoken work, reflecting their language journey.

5. Multimedia Integration:

- *Use Multimedia:* Incorporate multimedia elements into lessons, such as videos, audio clips, and interactive graphics. These can help students grasp pronunciation, context, and cultural nuances.
- *Video Conferencing:* Organize virtual conversations with native speakers or students from other regions. Platforms like Zoom or Skype can facilitate real-time, interactive language practice.

6. Online Language Communities:

- *Forums and Language Exchanges:* Encourage students to join online language forums and communities, where they can interact with other learners and native speakers. These platforms often offer discussion boards, language exchange partners, and Q&A sections.
- *Social Media:* Leverage social media platforms for language learning. There are dedicated language learning groups on platforms like Facebook and Reddit where students can seek advice, share resources, and engage in discussions.

7. Language Learning Management Systems (LMS):

- *Utilize LMS:* Many educational institutions use LMS platforms like Moodle, Canvas, or Blackboard. These platforms often have tools for creating language learning modules, sharing resources, and tracking student progress.
- *Provide Learning Paths:* Use the LMS to create structured learning paths for students, offering them a step-by-step guide on what to study, which online resources to use, and how to practice.

8. Teacher Training and Support:

- *Professional Development:* Provide training and support for educators to effectively integrate technology into their teaching. Teachers should be comfortable with the tools and apps they are using in the classroom.
- *Technical Support:* Offer technical support to students who may encounter issues while using online resources and language learning apps.

By thoughtfully integrating technology, language learning apps, and online resources into your curriculum, you create a dynamic and interactive language learning environment that caters to diverse learning styles and offers a wealth of resources for students to explore. This approach can significantly enhance their language acquisition and cultural understanding while making the learning process more engaging and accessible.

Regular feedback is an indispensable tool in language learning, empowering students to grow and evolve in their language skills. It provides the guidance, motivation, and insight needed to continually refine their language abilities and achieve their learning objectives. When delivered thoughtfully and effectively, feedback becomes a driving force behind successful language acquisition.

In conclusion, motivation and attitude are integral to shaping English language learning outcomes. Recognizing the dynamics between these psychological factors is crucial for educators and policymakers in the field of ESL education. Fostering intrinsic motivation and promoting positive attitudes among learners are paramount for effective language acquisition. By acknowledging the significance of these psychological variables and implementing strategies to cultivate them, language educators can facilitate more effective language learning, improve learning outcomes, and enhance the overall language learning experience.

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Azərbaycan dilində ismin hal kateqoriyasının ingilis dilində qarşılığı və ifadə formaları

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Key words: *Noun, the category of case, suffix, preposition, classification*

Həm Azərbaycan dilində, həm də ingilis dilində əşyanın adını bildirən nitq hissəsinə isim deyilir. Azərbaycan dilində isim kim? nə? hara?, ingilis dilində isə who? və what? suallarından birinə cavab verir.

Tədqiqata cəlb olunan hər iki dildə ismin hal kateqoriyası mövcuddur.

İsmlərin başqa sözlərlə əlaqəyə girərək dəyişməsinə hallanma deyilir. Azərbaycan dilində ismin 6 halı mövcuddur:

1. Adlıq hal
2. Yiyəlik hal
3. Yönlük hal
4. Təsirlik hal
5. Yerlik hal
6. Çıxışlıq hal.

Adı çəkilən hallar da öz növbəsində iki qrupa bölünür: a) Qrammatik hallar- (*Adlıq, yiyəlik və təsirlik hallar*) b) Məkani qrammatik hallar- (*Yönlük, yerlik və çıxışlıq hallar*)

İngilis dilində hal kateqoriyası **The category of case** adlanır. Müasir ingilis dilinin qrammatikasında istifadə olunan və sabitləşmiş iki hal mövcuddur:

1. Common case - Adlıq hal
2. Possessive or Genitive case – Yiyəlik hal

Dilimizdə hal kateqoriyasının göstəriciləri hal şəkilçiləridir ki, bunlar da belə təsvir oluna bilər:

Azərbaycan dilində adlıq halın heç bir şəkli əlaməti yoxdur. Məsələn, *O qış gecəsi bütün məhəllə yatmışdı və qaranlıq içində küçədəki, evlərin damındaki qarın ağımtıllığı güclə sezilirdi.* (Elçin)

İngilis dilində də adlıq halın heç bir şəkli əlaməti yoxdur. Məsələn, *I suppose June wants me to buy a picture.* (Galsworthy)

Azərbaycan dilində yiyəlik hal *-ın4 (-nın4)* şəkilçilərinin köməyi ilə düzəldiyi halda, ingilis dilində *'s, ' , of* hissəcikləri yiyəlik halın düzəldilməsində istifadə olunur. *Mən özümü görmürdüm, amma mən də haradasa o karvanın yanında idim.* (Elçin) və ya *Axır vaxtlar tez-tez fikirləşirəm ki, Cəfərqulu taksidürücüsü olmayaydı, mənim kimi yazıb-pozan adam olaydı, bizim məhəllədən necə yazardı?*(Elçin) Birinci cümlədə müəyyən yiyəlik hal, ikinci cümlədə isə qeyri-müəyyən yiyəlik hal istifadə olunmuşdur.

Məlumdur ki, bəzi istisnalar nəzərə alınmasa, ingilis dilində ancaq canlı varlıqları bildirən isimlər yiyəlik halda işlədilər bilər. Əgər həmin canlı varlıq bildirən söz təkdədirsə, *'s*, cəmdədirsə, *'* istifadə edilir. Məsələn, *a teacher's questions or teachers' questions.*

Cansız varlıqların adını bildirən isimlərin yönəlmiş halı isə *of* sözünü vasitəsilə düzəldilir. Məsələn, *the walls of the room, the colour of the sky* və s.

Yönlük hal iş, hərəkət və əşyanın yönünü, istiqamətini bildirir. Yönlük hal $-a^2$; $-ya^2$ şəkilçisi vasitəsilə əmələ gəlir. *Biz dalanımızın dibinə yığışib İbadullanın o xartut ağacını kəsməyinə tamaşa edirdik. (Elçin) Onda hələ Xanım xalanın üç oğlu müharibəyə getməmişdi. (Elçin)*

İngilis dilində isə yönlük halın qarşılığı kimi sözlərdən istifadə olunur ki, bunlar da aşağıdakılardır:

- **To-** istiqamət bildirir və dilimizə $-a$; $-ə$ kimi tərcümə olunur. *Every year she goes to Africa in order to help needy people.*

- Bəzən **on** sözünü də yönlük halın funksiyasını icra edə bilir ki, bu da bir çox ifadələrdə müşahidə olunur. *Go on a trip, go on a tour, go on a picnic, go on an excursion, go on vacation, go on holiday* və s.

- **Towards** sözünü dilimizə birbaşa yönlük hal kimi tərcümə olunmasa da, yönlük halda olan sözlərə qoşularaq işlədilər doğru, tərəf qoşmaları vasitəsilə tərcümə edilir. *A tall man stood on the deck, looking out towards the flat dark land. (J. Joyce) – Ucaboylu kişi yastı və tutqun torpağa tərəf baxaraq göyartədə dayandı.*

- **Into** sözünü də dilimizə bəzən yönlük hal vasitəsilə tərcümə edilir. *Mr. Casey pushed his plate rudely into the middle of the table and, resting his elbows before him, said in a hoarse voice to his host. (J. Joyce) (Cənab Keysi boşqabını kobudcasına stolun ortasına itələdi və dirsəklənərək boğuş səslə ev sahibinə dedi.)*

- **Onto** sözünü də dilimizə yönlük hal kimi tərcümə oluna bilər. Belə ki, bu sözünü də a^2 ; ya^2 kimi tərcümə edilir. *She stepped down from the train onto the platform. O, qatardan platformaya addım atdı. She stuck the label onto the bottle. O, etiketi şüşənin üzərinə yapışdırdı.*

Dilimizdə təsirlik hal hərəkətin təsir göstərdiyi obyektə, üzərində iş icra olunan əşyanı bildirir. Bu halın qarşılığı ola biləcək hər hansı bir sözünü mövcud olmadığından, ingilis dilində adlıq halında olan isimlərin vasitəsiz tamamlıq (The Direct Speech) cümlə üzvü vəzifəsində işlənməsi bizə əsas verir ki, biz onu dilimizə təsirlik halda işlədilmiş isim kimi tərcümə edək. İngilis dilində təsirli feillə işlənərək onun mənasını tamamlayan cümlə üzvünə vasitəsiz tamamlıq deyilir. *She brought the paper and the string. (S. Maugham) (O, kağızı və ipi gətirdi.) The sudden legend startled his blood (J. Joyce) Qəfil deyilmiş əfsanə onun qanını dondurdu.*

Azərbaycan dilində yerlik hal hərəkətin baş verdiyi və ya əşyanın tutduğu yeri bildirir. Kimdə? nədə? harada? suallarından birinə cavab verir. Məsələn, ingilis dilində bu halın qarşılığı kimi çoxsaylı sözləri vardır. Bunlar aşağıdakılardır:

- **In- içində, da²**

❖ Otağın, binanın, hər hansı bir əşyanın içərisində dedikdə işlədilir. Məsələn, *in the kitchen (mətbəxdə), in the house (evdə), in the vase (güldə)*

❖ Ölkə, şəhər, kənd adları ilə. Məsələn, *in Azerbaijan, in Shaki, in Kish*

❖ Və ya *in the yard (hayətdə), in the garden (bağda), in the city (şəhərdə), in the village (kənddə)* və s.

❖ Üfüqün cəhətləri ilə. Məsələn, *in the North (şimalda), in the South (cənubda), in the East (şərqdə), in the West (qərbdə)*

❖ *In the sea (dənizdə), in the river (çayda), in the sun (günün altında, günəşdə), in the rain (yağışda), in the shade (kölgədə), in the moonlight (ay işığında), in the open air (açıq havada)* və s. kimi ifadələrdə

❖ *In a car (maşında), in a taxi (taksidə)*

❖ *In a line (sırada), in a row (cərgədə), in a queue (növbədə), in the world (dünyada), in the mirror (güzgüdə), in the looking-glass (güzgüdə)*

❖ *In the newspaper (qəzetdə), in the magazine (jurnalda), in the journal (qəzetdə), in the letter (məktubda) və s.*

- On- üstündə, da²

❖ *On the floor (döşəmədə), on the ceiling (tavanda), on the wall (divarda), on the first floor (ikinci mərtəbədə), on the table (stolda), on the sofa (divanda), on the chair (stulda), on the bench (skamyada) və s. kimi ifadələrdə.*

❖ *On horseback (at belində), on the board (lövhədə), on the horse (atda), on the bicycle (velosipeddə), on the stage (səhnədə), on the platform (platformada), on the grass (otda, ot üzərində), on the page (səhifədə) və s. ifadələrlə*

❖ *On the farm (fermada), on the island (adada), on the continent (qitədə), on the Earth (Yer kürəsində), on the balcony (eyvanda), on the right (sağda), on the left (solda) kimi ifadələrdə.*

❖ *On the river (çayın kənarında), on the bank (çayın sahilində), on the shore (dənizin sahilində), on the coast (okeanın sahilində), on the beach (çimərlikdə), on the way (yolda) və s. kimi ifadələrlə*

❖ *On a bus (avtobusda), on a ship (gəmidə), on a plane (təyyarədə), on a train (qatarda) və s.*

❖ *On television (televizorda), on the radio (radioda), on the phone (telefonda), on the list (siyahıda), on the menu (menyuda) və s.*

- At- yanında, qarşısında, da²

❖ *At the window (pəncərədə), at the traffic light (işıqforda), at the seaside (dəniz kənarında), at the bus stop (dayanacaqda), at the airport (aeroportda), at the station (stansiyada), at the door (qapıda), at the gate (darvazada) və s.*

❖ *At school (məktəbdə), at university (universitetdə), at college (kollecdə), at office (ofisdə), at work (işdə), at home (evdə), at hotel (oteldə) və s.*

❖ Mərasim bildirən sözlərlə *at the concert (konsertdə), at the party (qonaqlıqda), at the football match (futbol oyununda), at the meeting (iclasda), at the theatre (teatrda), at the cinema (kinoda) və s.*

Azərbaycan dilində çıxışlıq hal hərəkətin çıxış, yəni başlanğıc nöqtəsini bildirir. Çıxışlıq hal – dan² şəkilçisi ilə əmələ gəlir, kimdən? nədən? haradan? suallarına cavab verir. Məsələn, *Cəfərqulu mənim yanımda dayanmışdı və birdən gözlərini İbadulladan çəkib başını arxaya çevirdi, dalanımızın ortasında Xanım xalagilin pəncərəsinə tərəf baxdı. (Elçin) O, məhəllədən çoxdan köçüb getmişdi.*

İngilis dilində aşağıdakı sözləri çıxışlıq halın göstəriciləri kimi çıxış edə bilər:

❖ From- dan² - *from school (məktəbdən), from the forest (meşədən) və s.*

❖ Off – üstündən, dan² - *off the shelf (rəfdən), off the table (stoldan)*

❖ Out of – içərisindən, dan² – *out of my pocket (cibimdən), out of the bag (çantadan)*

Lakin qeyd etmək lazımdır ki, qədim ingilis dilində istifadə edilmiş ismin bir çox halları olmuşdur ki, tarixi inkişaf dövründə dil qaydaları içərisində ərisə də, yuxarıda da vurğulandığı kimi, müəyyən sözləri vasitəsilə hələ də dildə öz əksini tapır. İsimlərin hansı cümlə üzvü olması baxımından ingilis dilində aşağıdakı halların olduğunu qeyd etmək olar:

1. Nominative case- Bu halda olan isimlər dilimizdə adlıq hala uyğun gəldiyindən cümlənin mübtədası funksiyasında çıxış edir. Məsələn, *The doctor tried to persuade the patient to follow all the given instructions.*

2. Accusative case- Bu halda olan isimlər dilimizdə təsirlik hala uyğun gəldiyindən vasitəsiz tamamlıq funksiyasında çıxış edir. Məsələn, *The doctor barely persuaded the patient.*

3. Dative case- Bu halda olan isimlər dilimizdə yönlük hala uyğun gəldiyindən vasitəli tamamlıq funksiyasında çıxış edərək *Kimə? Nəyə? Kimdən? Nədən? Kim üçün? Nə üçün?* suallarına cavab verir. Bir sözlə, hərəkətin ünvanlandığı şəxsi və ya əşyanı bildirir. *The doctor gave the medicine to the patient.*

4. Ablative case- Bu halda olan isimlər dilimizdə çıxışlıq hala uyğun gəlir. Əsasən *from, away from* və s. kimi sözlərlə işlədilir. Məsələn, *The doctor and the patient returned from hospital.*

5. Vocative case- Əsasən müraciət məzmunu kəsb edən isimlər, yəni xitab kimi istifadə olunan isimlər bu halda olur. Məsələn, *Doctor, please don't give up treating your little patient.*

6. Locative case- Dilimizdəki yerlik hala uyğun gəlir. *All the patients are waiting for the doctor's coming in hospital.*

7. Instrumental case- əsasən *together with* sözləni ilə ifadə edilir. Məsələn, *They are for the doctor together with their children.*

Beləliklə, ingilis dilində ismin hal kateqoriyasının təsnifatına əsasən 2 hal (common case, possessive case) mövcud olsa da, dilin inkişaf tarixinə istinadən, isimlərin cümlədəki mövqeyi nöqtəyi-nəzərindən 7 halın (nominative, accusative, dative, ablative, vocative, locative, instrumental) olduğu vurğulanır.

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Medical Sciences

ВИКОРИСТАННЯ ПРЕВЕНТИВНИХ ЗАСОБІВ ЗАДЛЯ ПОПЕРЕДЖЕННЯ ВИПАДІННЯ ВОЛОССЯ У ВОЄННИЙ ЧАС

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Актуальність.

Підвищене випадіння волосся під час війни є актуальною проблемою, що викликає у пацієнта як естетичний, так і психологічний дискомфорт. Люди, які зараз в Україні переживають наслідки війни, "постарішали" на 10-15 років. Якщо звернутися до статистичних даних ВООЗ в мирні часи, то можна побачити, що близько 75% людей тією чи іншою мірою страждають на облісіння, причому з віком кількість пацієнтів зростає. Так, у 30 років симптоми захворювання спостерігаються у кожного третього, у 50 років – у кожного другого, а у 80 років – вже у чотирьох із п'яти осіб. Тривалий стрес під час війни приводить до негативних наслідків в усьому організмі, зокрема страждають волосся Згідно зі світовою статистикою, серед жінок алопеція зустрічається у 20-40%.

Мета дослідження.

Всебічно дослідити проблему випадіння волосся та доцільність використання превентивних засобів попередження випадіння волосся.

Матеріали та методи.

Матеріалами дослідження є статистичні дані ВООЗ та дослідження зарубіжних науковців щодо проблеми випадіння волосся. Методи дослідження – аналізу та синтезу, евристичний, пізнавальний, статистичний та ін.

Результати.

Випадіння волосся - це мультифакторна патологія, в основі розвитку якої лежать різні патогенетичні механізми. Зважаючи на це, терапія алопеції включає комплексний підхід до діагностики, постановки діагнозу, вибору лікарських та косметичних засобів.

Анатомічно волосся ділиться на стрижень та корінь. Стрижень - це видима частина волосся, що виступає над поверхнею шкіри. Корінь волосся розташовується в дермі і оточений кореневою піхвою, разом з яким він становить волоссяний фолікул (ВФ). Стрижень у поперечному розрізі складається з внутрішньої мозкової речовини, середньої коркової речовини і зовнішнього шару - кутикули. Мозкова речовина (серцевина) представлена не до

кінця кератинізованими клітинами. Воно має багато порожнеч, що, ймовірно, є еволюційним «пережитком» з тих часів, коли був потрібний великий теплозахист [5]. Корковий шар, що відповідає за міцність, колір, еластичність, утворений ороговілими клітинами і становить близько 90% від загальної маси волосся. Натуральний колір волосся залежить від співвідношення компонентів природного пігменту волосся - меланіну, форми пігментних гранул та їх розподілу в структурі волосся [6]. Кутикула захищає кіркові волокна і утримує їх разом. Завдяки ліпідному прошарку та наявності дисульфідних зв'язків лусочки кутикули щільно прилягають один до одного. Краї лусочок кутикули на частині волосся, що тільки що сформувалася, - гладкі і непошкоджені. Так як всі вони розташовуються в одній площині, промінь світла, що падає на здорове волосся, рівномірно відбивається від його поверхні, тобто волосся «блищить» [5].

З усього вище зазначеного варто сформулювати причини випадіння волосся: спадкове випадіння волосся через генетику; грибкові інфекції на шкірі голови; зачіски, які туго стягують волосся; догляд за волоссям; гормональні зміни (такі як вагітність, пологи або менопауза); медикаментозне лікування (наприклад, хіміотерапія та певні ліки); дефіцит харчування (особливо недостатнє надходження заліза або білка); стресові події (наприклад, військові дії, поранення, операція або втрата близької людини); захворювання щитовидної залози.

Стрес під час війни може проявлятися цілим рядом характерних симптомів. Сама природа стресу досить складна. У ній задіяні різні органи та системи організму, а саме — гіпоталамус, наднирники, гіпофіз. Стрес запускає своєрідну ланцюгову реакцію, що в свою чергу викликає ряд характерних симптомів. Причому це можуть бути як психоемоційні розлади, так і соматичні. До перших належить підвищена дратівливість, агресивність, зниження здатності відчувати задоволення, проблеми з концентрацією уваги та когнітивним мисленням. Також у стані стресу людина страждає від різноманітних проблем із шлунково-кишковим трактом, безсоння, тахікардії, шкірних висипів, випадіння волосся. Коли виникає стресова ситуація, то організм починає виробляти більше гормонів (адреналін, кортизол), що провокує спазмування судин. Волоссяний фолікул автоматично в цей час не отримує кровопостачання. Настає фаза телогену, фаза випадіння волосся.

Було проведено дослідження Девіда Ф. [1] щодо впливу стресу на випадіння волосся. В даному дослідженні взяли участь 50 жінок від 18 до 35 років. Усі суб'єкти заповнили шкалу оцінки соціальної реадaptaції (Holmes & Rahe, 1967) [2], найбільш стандартизовану міру стресу від звичайних подій. Ця шкала являє собою перелік подій Я-змін, яким було присвоєно значення, що відображає середній стрес адаптації до кожної події. І дане дослідження продемонструвало, що саме ті жінки, які з незрозумілих причин почали втрачати волосся зазнали стресових подій протягом останнього року життя. І дослідник прийшов до висновку, що для жінки, яка зіткнулася з втратою волосся, можливі супутні негативні почуття, пов'язані з цією втратою, відповідно можуть лише посилити її реакцію на стрес. Teshima, et al. (1991) [4], звернув увагу на цей замкнений цикл, у якому припускають, що стрес призводить до втрати волосся, що призводить до подальшого стресу, який може призвести до ще більшої втрати волосся.

Правильний сон важливий не лише для краси волосся, а й загалом для нашого організму, бо саме коли ми спимо, епіфіз старанно виробляє гормон-регулятор циркадного ритму – мелатонін. У дослідженнях *in vitro* мелатонін призводить до більшої швидкості росту волоссяного фолікула та продовження фази анагену; Мелатонін модулює ріст волосся, його пігментацію.

З урахуванням вище зазначеного варто звернути увагу на використанні превентивних засобів для попередження випадіння волосся та їх доцільність. Доцільним є використання вітаміни груп С, В (В1, В2, В6, В12), А, Е, РР, препарати для покращення

мікроциркуляції, мікроелементи (препарати міді, цинку, заліза) [8]. Є численні публікації, що вказують на високу ефективність та превентивність при попередженні випадіння волосся [7].

Проблемою випадіння волосся займаються не тільки лікувальні установи, фармацевтичні компанії, але і косметичні фірми, постійно випускаючи нові косметичні засоби, що покращують зовнішній вигляд волосся і здійснюють профілактичний ефект. Так, компанією L'Oreal Professionnel (Франція) був синтезований амінексил, що нагадує за своєю структурою міноксидил. Ефект амінексилу полягає в запобіганні затвердінню колагену, через що діаметр фолікул не зменшується, відновлюється циркуляція крові в шкірі голови, що призводить до попередження випадіння волосся.

В якості додаткових засобів можна використовувати шампуні і бальзами, що містять компоненти, що сприяють поліпшенню кровопостачання ВФ, що володіють антиоксидантними, протизапальними, зволожуючими властивостями. Відповідно до клінічного випробування 2021 року, жінки, які протягом 8 тижнів використовували шампунь або незмивний засіб для шкіри голови, що містить антиоксидант піроктон оламін, прискорили ріст волосся та покращили стан шкіри голови, ніж жінки, які використовували продукти плацебо.

Існує кілька препаратів для запобігання випадінню волосся. Відповідно до огляду досліджень Trusted Source 2019 року, місцеве застосування міноксидилу є основним засобом лікування андрогенної алопеції як у чоловіків, так і у жінок. Міноксидил є активним інгредієнтом Рогейна, який продається без рецепта. Огляд показує, що лікарі іноді використовують міноксидил для лікування інших причин випадіння волосся, наприклад від хіміотерапії. Фінастерид (Propecia), що відпускається за рецептом, є ще одним лікарським засобом від випадіння волосся. Його можна приймати всередину або застосовувати місцево. Клінічне випробування 2021 року Trusted Source показало, що місцевий спрей фінастериду значно покращив кількість волосся у 323 чоловіків із облісінням [3].

Масаж шкіри голови. Невелике дослідження 2016 року за участю дев'яти здорових чоловіків показало, що щоденний 4-хвилинний масаж шкіри голови стимулював ріст волосся.

Спроба терапії лазерним світлом низького рівня. Терапія низьким рівнем лазерного світла (LLLT), також відома як терапія червоним світлом, — це лікування проблем зі шкірою, в якому використовується червоне світло низької довжини хвилі для стимулювання росту клітин. Відповідно до невеликого контрольованого дослідження 2020 року в Кореї, через 16 тижнів LLLT значно збільшив густоту та товщину волосся у 48 людей з андрогенною алопецією [3].

Використання кокосової олії для пошкодженого волосся. Дослідження 2018 року показало, що кокосова олія може допомогти запобігти випадінню волосся через пошкодження ультрафіолетовим випромінюванням або доглядом. Застосування кокосової олії може зміцнити волосся та уникнути втрати внаслідок пошкодження.

Використання ефірних олій. Дослідження 2021 року TrustedSource показало, що гарбузова олія, олія жожоба, лаванди, перцевої м'яти, чайного дерева нанесені місцево на шкіру голови протягом трьох місяців, значно прискорюють відростання волосся у людей з жіночим типом облісіння. Відповідно до рандомізованого контрольованого дослідження 2015 року, олія розмарину, нанесена на шкіру голови, може бути такою ж ефективною, як і міноксидил [3].

Вживання продуктів, що містять кофеїн. Кофеїн у місцевих препаратах, таких як шампунь і кондиціонер, запобігає випадінню волосся так само ефективно, як монооксидил. Кофеїн стимулює метаболізм і розмноження клітин.

Правильний догляд за волоссям і шкірою голови може допомогти запобігти випадінню волосся. Це також може покращити ріст волосся. Дотримання чистоти шкіри голови та

волосся також може запобігти пошкодженню та випадінню волосся. Американська академія дерматологічної асоціації (AAD) рекомендує обережно втирати шампунь у шкіру голови, але не у волосся. Асоціація також рекомендує використовувати кондиціонер після кожного миття голови. Відповідно до огляду 2015 року, певні лікувальні шампуні та кондиціонери можуть запобігти випадінню волосся. Також може допомогти уникати агресивних процедур, таких як нагрівання, завивка та фарбування.

Таким чином, правильне харчування, подолання стресів і режим сну. Це три складових аксіоми здорових волос як у жінок, так і чоловіків.

Висновки.

Випадіння волосся є проблемою XXI століття, дана хвороба з кожним роком «молодшає» зачіпаючи не тільки людей похилого віку, а й молодь. Війна тільки загострює цю проблему. Такі превентивні засоби як: різноманітні олії, кофеїн, здоровий спосіб життя, сон, подолання стресу, правильно підібрані косметичні засоби, вітаміни, масаж демонструють свою ефективність при попередженні випадіння волосся в екстремальних ситуаціях військових дій

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LAPAROSCOPIC ABDOMINAL SURGERY IN ONCOLOGY

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Annotation: In this work, the issues of laparoscopic abdominal surgery in oncology are consecrated. The methodology of surgical interventions for oncological pathology of the abdominal organs, the equipment used and the technology of surgical procedures are described in detail. It is noted that the use of laparoscopy during operations on the abdominal organs for various nosological forms of malignant neoplasms allows optimizing the surgical and restorative stage of patient treatment. At the same time, there is no increase in the incidence of local relapses and distant metastases, and the 3- and 5-year survival rate of patients does not differ from that when using traditional methods of surgical interventions.

Key words: oncology, surgery, laparoscopy.

Abdominal oncology is a branch of medicine that deals with the diagnosis and treatment of tumors that affect the organs of the digestive system. The treatment of gastrointestinal cancer is one of the most difficult branches of oncology. From an epidemiological point of view, malignant neoplasms of the gastrointestinal tract make up a significant share in the structure of cancer morbidity and mortality throughout the world. The surgical method, as it was half a century ago, remains the main, and in some cases the only radical method of treating patients in this category. Technological progress, the interest of surgeons and the desire of patients became the driving force behind the widespread dissemination and implementation of minimally invasive technologies in abdominal surgery at the turn of the century [1,2].

Laparoscopy is a modern surgical method that allows diagnostics and surgical interventions through small openings in the anterior abdominal wall. Advantages of laparoscopic surgery: low trauma, short stay of the patient in the hospital, quick recovery after surgery, less pain, absence of large postoperative scars, modern laparoscopic equipment provides magnification up to 40

times, that is, the operation is performed almost like under a microscope, the optics used allow you to see at the operation object from different angles (from different sides), which provides a much greater overview than with traditional operations. Disadvantages of laparoscopic surgery: limited range of motion in the operated area, distorted perception of the depth of the wound, the need to use instruments to interact with the tissue rather than work directly with your hands, the cutting surfaces of the instrument move in the opposite direction to the surgeon's hands, that is, laparoscopy is based on non-intuitive motor skills, which are difficult to learn. Absolute contraindications for laparoscopic operations: acute myocardial infarction, acute cerebrovascular accident, uncorrectable coagulopathy. Relative contraindications: intolerance to general anesthesia, general peritonitis, previous operations in the area of the intervention site, tendency to bleeding, late pregnancy, obesity of 3-4 degrees. Possible complications of laparoscopy: 1) complications that develop during anesthesia; 2) complications during the application of pneumoperitoneum (emphysema, pneumomediastinum, gas embolism, cardiovascular collapse); 3) damage to the abdominal organs by a needle or trocar; 4) injury to large vessels during insertion of a needle or trocar [3].

Today, with the help of laparoscopy, it is possible to diagnose a wide variety of diseases and simultaneously treat them, causing minimal trauma to the patient while reducing the number of complications and surgical risks. In this way, it is possible to remove entire organs, large tumors, and perform plastic surgery. For many patients in serious condition, elderly and senile people, with some concomitant diseases, open surgery may be contraindicated due to the high risk of complications, and laparoscopy makes it possible to reduce the likelihood of adverse consequences and carry out surgical treatment. A set of microsurgical instruments is inserted through the punctures, and to facilitate manipulation, a special gas mixture is pumped into the surgical area, after which the abdominal wall is raised. In the resulting space, the surgeon can work unhindered, having free access even to hard-to-reach places.

Endoscopic control of what is happening improves the quality of laparoscopy. Along with surgical instruments, a light and a mini video camera are introduced into the abdominal cavity, which captures and transmits the image online; it is broadcast with magnification on the monitor. Thus, the doctor visually controls the situation while examining the organs. Thanks to this, laparoscopy becomes both a diagnostic tool and a treatment method.

The main instrument in laparoscopic surgery is the laparoscope: a telescopic tube containing a lens system and usually attached to a video camera. Modern laparoscopes are equipped with digital matrices and provide high-definition images. An optical cable illuminated by a "cold" light source (halogen or xenon lamp) is also attached to the tube. The abdominal cavity is usually filled with carbon dioxide (a so-called carboxyperitoneum) to create an operative space. In fact, the stomach inflates like a balloon, the wall of the abdominal cavity rises above the internal organs like a dome. The range of surgical interventions performed using laparoscopic access is wide: from cholecystectomy to gastrectomy and extirpation of the esophagus.

Advantages of laparoscopy: improved visualization of organs and tissues; reduction of surgical trauma; short periods of patient stay in hospital; quick recovery after surgery; no pain; absence of postoperative scars, which are observed, for example, during laparotomy and other abdominal operations with an incision; restoration of intestinal function also occurs faster; the patient after laparoscopic surgery can feed independently much earlier.

Operations performed in abdominal oncology: distal gastrectomy, gastric extirpation, small intestine resection, colon resection, transabdominal rectal resection with mesorectumectomy, abdominal-anal resection of the rectum with reduction of the sigmoid colon into the anal canal and the formation of a primary coloanal anastomosis, rectal extirpation intestines, total colectomy, transanal removal of villous tumors of the rectum and sigmoid colon, including with video rectoscopy, anatomical and non-anatomical liver resections, hemihepatectomies,

cholecystectomy, formation of biliodigestive anastomoses, gastroenteroanastomoses and interintestinal anastomoses, various options for decompression of the biliary tract and their stenting.

Equipment for laparoscopic surgery. Most of the equipment included in the endosurgical complex is mounted on a mobile cart (stand), which has a number of shelves for placing the equipment. The complex usually consists of a standard set of equipment, which includes: 1) video camera; 2) video monitor; 3) light source; 4) insufflator; 5) aspiration-irrigation system; 6) electrosurgical device [4,5].

The video camera is the main, most complex and expensive component of the endovideo system, which determines the image quality. Main technical characteristics of video cameras: 1) light sensitivity (minimum illumination level) is measured in lux and shows the intensity of the light flux required to display the object. This is important for adequate assessment of intraoperative conditions; in addition, with low sensitivity of the video camera, the surgeon is forced to increase the light flux due to the power of the illuminator, which can cause glare in the image and increased wear of the light guide and endoscope due to their excessive heating; 2) the speed of operation of the electronic diaphragm shows how quickly the computer microprocessor of the video camera responds to changing lighting conditions of the object; This is mainly due to the axial movements of the endoscope in the abdominal cavity; 3) the level of the ratio of noise to useful signal is measured in decibels. Average values are about 50 db. The higher the indicator, the less interference and noise is present in the video signal, the better the image; 4) white color balance, since even the bluish tint of light from xenon lamps and the yellowish tint of halogen lamps, which are noticeable to the eye, distort the true color rendition, the video camera corrects them.

Monitor. The endovideo system is an interconnected complex, so the image quality depends on the operation of all its components. The part of the video system that directly reproduces the operating picture is the video monitor. The video signal (Video Output) consists of three main components: 1) a synchronizing signal (sync - ensures the image and its stability; 2) a light signal (Y - brightness and individual details of the image) and a color signal (C saturation of the image with various colors).

Lighting. The endosurgical lighting system is a stationary illuminator and a light guide that transmits light to the object of the operation. The illuminator includes a lamp, a cooling system (automatic fan) and electronics that regulate the light intensity. There are three types of lamps in surgical lights: halogen, metal halide and xenon. A special fiber optic light guide is used to conduct light to the operating endoscope. A light guide is a flexible "cable" that conducts a beam of light from a source (illuminator) to a telescope.

Insufflators and laparolifting. Insufflators. All endosurgical operations are performed in a natural or artificially created cavity, which, however, follows from the name of the technique. In order to lift the abdominal wall or keep the walls of the retroperitoneal cavity from collapsing, gas has long been used effectively. The insufflator is designed to create positive pressure in the abdominal cavity during endoscopic interventions. Most devices supply gas in portions, the supply phases alternate with the phases of measuring pressure in the main tube. Electronic monitoring and testing systems of the device ensure that the gas pressure in the cavity corresponds to the selected value, automatically selects the optimal pressure in accordance with the value in the cavity, recognizes the real situation that arises during the operation (for example, replacing instruments) and selects the most adequate gas injection mode. Laparolifting. This term refers to various gas-free methods of lifting the anterior abdominal wall to create an adequate operating cavity. The need for this type of procedure is dictated by the desire to avoid complications associated with the harmful effects of gas pressure on internal organs.

Aspiration-irrigation system. Almost all laparoscopic procedures, like traditional surgery, require suction and irrigation of the surgical site. Special tools and equipment have been

developed for this purpose. Instruments may have a common channel for supplying washing liquid and suction, or separate channels. In the latter case, it is possible to carry out simultaneous supply and suction, which sharply reduces the time of aspiration-irrigation and increases the efficiency of the procedure. An aspirator-irrigator is a device with powerful and adjustable supply and vacuum suction of sterile liquid. The required power parameters are set individually depending on the type of operation. The device is equipped with a storage tank (at least 2 liters) and a device that automatically turns it off when the tank is overfilled. This prevents failure of the internal components of the device and increases its service life.

Electrocoagulator (high-frequency generator). Coagulation and tissue cutting. A modern electrocoagulator or high-frequency generator is a complex, balanced, effective surgical system, which is the result of many years of scientific research and meets the most stringent safety criteria. A high-frequency generator intended for endosurgery must provide a fairly wide range of functions: have a mono- and bipolar mode, with monopolar coagulation provide cutting, contact and non-contact coagulation, mixed modes, if possible, be universal so that it can be used both for large cavitory , so in endoscopic or microsurgical interventions, which means having a clear power adjustment at low values and a large supply of power at large values.

Mono- and bipolar electrosurgery. These two types of electrosurgical effects are significantly different. During monopolar coagulation and cutting, an electric current passes through the entire body of the patient from the working tool itself to the second electrode - a plate that provides wide contact. The working electrode is usually called the "active" electrode, and the plate the "passive" electrode (although from a physics point of view this is incorrect). Bipolar electrosurgery is safer due to the fact that the current in this case flows only between the jaws of the working instrument, and complications such as burns on the patient's plate and capacitive breakdown are excluded in principle.

Non-contact electrocoagulation. To prevent the "welding" effect and to increase the surface area being treated, there are special non-contact coagulation modes, which are usually called spray coagulation, or fulguration. A special attachment to the electrosurgical unit supplies inert argon gas directly to the working electrode. Under the influence of electric current, argon easily ionizes and even at low power conducts a coagulating current. Ultrasonic coagulation and tissue cutting. A special ultrasonic generator is connected to a tool made in the form of scissors or a ball. Generator for electroligation of blood vessels. Electrosurgical hemostasis is monopolar or bipolar coagulation of vessels with a diameter of up to 1.5 mm. In this case, a vessel with a small area of tissue is intensively dried along with the blood contained in it.

Instruments for laparoscopic surgery. Endosurgical instruments can be divided into reusable (metal) and disposable (plastic) instruments. The most accessible and cheapest to operate are reusable, dismantlable metal tools. They are made of stainless steels and alloys. All laparoscopic instruments can be divided into three groups: 1) endoscopic optical system; 2) access tools; tools for manipulation.

Endoscopic optical system. The endoscopic optical system (laparoscope) is the first link in the image transmission chain. The laparoscope transmits an image from the cavity of the human body to a video camera. A modern laparoscope is an optical tube through which the image is transmitted through long quartz rods, providing high-quality images with minimal light loss. The telescope has both an optical channel for transmitting images and a system of glass fibers for illuminating the object. Laparoscopic optical systems have the following technical parameters. The diameter of the tool can be 10, 7, 5 mm or less. 10 mm optics are most common in surgical endosurgery. The 5 mm laparoscope is used in pediatric surgery and for diagnostic procedures. In recent years, a laparoscope with a diameter of 1.9 mm has been constructed. Input angle of view – the angle within which the laparoscope transmits the input image to the video camera. On

average, this parameter is within 80°. The direction of the axis of view is 12, 30, 45, 70, 75 and 90 degrees. If the visual axis is 0°, the laparoscope is called end or straight. In other cases, the laparoscope is called an oblique one. Oblique optics are more functional and convenient when working in two-dimensional imaging conditions. It allows you to examine an object from different sides without changing the point of insertion of the instrument.

Access instruments: 1) instruments for forming an operating cavity (a special instrument for gas insufflation in the cavity - the Veress needle; it is a regular hollow needle with a spring-loaded mandrel, which extends immediately after penetration into the cavity, closing the tip; 2) a trocar - a composite device, performing the functions of penetration into the cavity, preserving the created instrumental channel and sealing it; 3) thoracoports - are valveless tubes (insufflation is not required for the pleural cavity) with a screw thread, equipped with blunt stylets.

Instruments for manipulation: 1) clamps and tweezers - they differ from general surgical ones in their elongated working part, which corresponds in diameter to one of the standard trocars, the working part of the clamps is different, depending on the requirements for the instrument; 2) cutting and coagulating instrument - the effect of cutting tissue is achieved by activating the appropriate mode of the electrocoagulator; some of the most necessary instruments for performing endoscopic operations are scissors and an endodissector; 3) retractors; 4) containers for evacuation; 5) needle holders; devices for manual endoscopic suture; manual endoscopic suture.

Considering the advantages of laparoscopic technologies, it has been established that laparoscopic operations are accompanied by a less pronounced pain syndrome, which makes it possible to halve the doses of narcotic drugs and mobilize patients at an earlier time. There is also a reduction in the length of stay of patients in the hospital and a faster recovery of working capacity. The study of long-term results indicates the oncological justification of the use of laparoscopic technologies. At the same time, what is most important, there is no increase in the incidence of local relapses and distant metastases, and the 3- and 5-year survival rate of patients does not differ from that when using traditional methods of surgical interventions [6,7].

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EPIDEMIOLOGICAL INDICATORS, ORGANIZATION AND RESULTS OF COLORECTAL CANCER SCREENING IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Annotation: This publication presents regional rates of incidence and mortality from colorectal cancer, as well as a detailed methodology and results of screening for this pathology in our country. Clinical and organizational aspects of early diagnosis based on the method of active detection of this type of cancer in clinically asymptomatic patients are presented. The technology of two-stage screening and the subsequent routing of examined patients depending on the results of this type of preventive examination of the population are described in detail.

Key words: colorectal cancer, epidemiology, morbidity, mortality, screening, hemocult test, fecal occult blood test - FOBT, total colonoscopy.

History knows many examples when the originally formulated postulates in a particular area continue to be relevant to this day. These postulates, which follow from one of the main tasks of the oncological service, include the early diagnosis of malignant tumors. Colorectal cancer (CRC) occupies one of the leading positions in terms of morbidity and mortality, and early symptoms are very poor, which leads to a high neglect of this disease at the time of diagnosis. In this regard, two-stage colorectal screening is one of the most important areas to improve the early diagnosis of this cancer localization. At the same time, the main conditions for screening are the availability of trained personnel and a standard approach to identifying the trait under study and evaluating the results. The applied methods should be quite simple, reliable and reproducible [1,2].

Colon cancer with a share of 5.2% (2020 - 5.5%) in the structure of oncopathology of both sexes of the population and women (4.9%) remained in 6th place in 2021, in men it fell from 5th to 6th place (5.5%). The incidence rate per 100 thousand of the population with cancer of this localization in the country in 2021 increased from 8.7 to 8.8 [3].

Above the average republican level, the incidence of colon cancer was noted in 11 regions: Kostanay - 15.9, Pavlodar - 15.3, Karaganda - 15.0, East Kazakhstan - 13.4, North Kazakhstan - 12.7, Akmola - 10, 2, West Kazakhstan - 10.1, Aktobe - 9.0 regions and years. Almaty - 12.1 and Nur-Sultan - 9.0. Least of all, colon cancer was noted in Turkestan - 2.7 per 100 thousand population, Kyzylorda - 4.6, Almaty - 4.7, Mangystau - 4.9, Zhambyl - 5.8 regions and Shymkent - 4.0.

Rectal cancer in the structure of malignant tumors of both sexes retains the 7th place in terms of rank with a specific gravity of 4.9% (2020 - 5.0%), but in men it has risen from 6th to 4th place, in women it is stable at 9th place. The incidence rate increased from 7.8 to 8.4 per 100,000 population. At the same time, a high incidence rate was registered in Pavlodar - 18.1 per 100 thousand population, Kostanay - 16.2, North Kazakhstan - 15.1, East Kazakhstan - 13.9, Akmola - 13.1, Karaganda - 11, 7, West Kazakhstan - 9.8 regions. Traditionally, a low incidence of rectal cancer is observed in Turkestan - 2.7, Mangystau - 2.8, Zhambyl - 5.1, Kyzylorda - 5.3, Almaty - 5.6, Atyrau - 6.3 regions and Shymkent - 5.0 per 100 thousand population [3].

Colon cancer in the structure of causes of death from malignant neoplasms of the population of both sexes in 2021 dropped from 5th place to 6th, with a share of 5.0% (2020 - 5.4%). At the same time, the mortality rate in the country decreased from 4.1 to 3.6 per 100,000 population. Above the national average, mortality rates were noted in 9 regions: Zhambyl - 3.7, Akmola - 3.8, West Kazakhstan - 4.4, North Kazakhstan - 5.0, East Kazakhstan - 5.1, Karaganda - 5.6, Kostanay - 5.6, Pavlodar - 6.0 - the maximum result, regions and Almaty - 5.3 per 100 thousand population. Low rates of mortality from colon cancer were found in Turkestan - 1.7 (the best result), Almaty - 1.8, Atyrau - 1.8, Aktobe - 2.5, Mangistau - 2.6, Kyzylorda - 2.7 regions and gg. Shymkent - 2.4 and Nur-Sultan - 2.7 per 100 thousand population.

Rectal cancer in the structure of causes of death in the population of both sexes in 2021 rose from 6th to 5th place with a share of 5.4% (2020 - 5.22%). In general, the death rate from this form of cancer in the republic was 3.9 per 100,000 people. A high mortality rate was recorded in East Kazakhstan - 8.6 (maximum level), Pavlodar - 7.6, Akmola - 5.3, Karaganda - 5.2, Kostanay - 4.9, North Kazakhstan - 4.3 regions and Almaty city - 4.3 per 100 thousand population. Below the average republican level, mortality rates from this pathology were ascertained per 100 thousand of the population in Mangistau - 1.2 (the lowest indicator), Turkestan - 1.6, Kyzylorda - 2.1, Almaty - 2.6, Zhambyl - 2.7, Atyrau - 3.4 regions and Shymkent - 2.1 [3].

Screening of CRC screening is the systematic use of screening studies in an asymptomatic population. The purpose of screening is to identify people with abnormalities suggestive of CRC. These persons in the future need additional examination to clarify the diagnosis. Opportunistic screening is the non-systematic use of screening tests in routine medical practice. A screening program is much more challenging than an early detection program. At the same time, the success of the screening program is largely determined by the awareness of the population and medical

workers about the possibilities of early diagnosis of CRC. The feasibility of a screening program is determined by several factors that relate to the disease being screened, the screening test, the characteristics of the population, and the characteristics of the healthcare system.

The first factor is that the disease must be well understood, common enough in the target population to justify screening, have a recognizable early stage; treatment of the disease at an early stage should be more effective than at a later stage.

The second is that the test should be characterized by sufficient sensitivity, i.e. the ability to detect cancer among people with the disease; sufficient specificity - the probability that among people who do not have a disease, the test result will be negative; have a high positive predictive value (positive predictive value) or, in other words, the likelihood that people with a positive test result have the disease; have a high predictive value of a negative result (negative predictive value), i.e. the likelihood that people with a negative test result do not have the disease; security; low cost; and acceptability - the likelihood that people for whom this test is intended will agree to the examination (which to some extent depends on the awareness of the population about the possibilities and importance of early diagnosis).

The third factor is that the healthcare system should be ready for maximum screening test coverage of the target group, have the resources to confirm the diagnosis, appropriate treatment and follow-up of people with positive test results, and regularly conduct screening tests at regular intervals. At the same time, the benefits of screening must outweigh the potential physical and psychological harm and justify the financial costs of its implementation [4].

The factors most significant for the development of CRC are:

- the presence of chronic inflammatory bowel diseases, adenomatous polyps, cancer of other localization, etc.;
- family history (presence of one or two first-degree relatives with CRC or familial diffuse intestinal polyposis);
- the age of men and women over 50 years old, taking into account the fact that more than 90% of patients with colorectal cancer are people of this age (medium risk).

Age, regardless of gender, is an important risk factor for CRC. After the age of 50, the incidence of CRC increases from 8 to 160 per 100,000 population. Thus, people who have reached the age of 50, even in the absence of symptoms, constitute a moderate risk group for CRC.

The second category of increased risk of CRC (20%) is made up of persons with a genetic and family predisposition, suffering from chronic inflammatory bowel diseases, diffuse familial polyposis.

The high-risk CRC group is determined by the so-called Amsterdam criteria (the presence of malignant tumors in two generations, the presence of cancer in a first-line relative under the age of 50 years), in this case, CRC screening should be carried out after the age of 30 years [5].

The degree of individual risk of developing CRC is determined before screening to select the scope of studies and the frequency of their conduct.

The interval for oncological colorectal screening is 1 time in 2 years, target group: men and women aged 50-70 years, with the exception of persons registered at the dispensary for CRC and colon polyposis. At the same time, when forming the target group, one should take into account the absence of severe concomitant diseases, such as the presence of a common malignant neoplasm, cerebrovascular diseases in the stage of decompensation, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with respiratory failure, cirrhosis of the liver, myocardial infarction with congestive heart failure, diabetes mellitus with vascular complications. and others, which are highly likely to lead to death in the next 10 years.

The first step in screening for CRC is the fecal occult blood test (FOBT). Traditionally, such methods include a benzidine test for occult blood in the feces. This is a biochemical method based on the assessment of pseudoperoxidase activity of hemoglobin. There is ample evidence that

invitation to guaiac FOBT screening (gFOBT) reduces CRC mortality by approximately 15% in age-matched average-risk populations.

To ensure the effectiveness of screening with gFOBT, the interval for screening under the national screening program should not exceed two years. To date, there is an immunochemical FOBT method - iFOBT, which is superior in efficiency to gFOBT in terms of the probability of detecting adenoma and cancer. iFOBT has improved analysis performance compared to gFOBT.

Immunochemical (immunochromatographic) examination of feces for occult blood - iFOBT or hemocult test is carried out for all men and women of the target group using an express method, which allows you to get a result within 3-5 minutes, without the participation of a medical worker. However, the evaluation of the test is carried out only by a medical worker in the PHC preventive department.

With a positive analysis of feces for occult blood, the second stage of colorectal screening is performed, which consists in endoscopic examination of the colon - total colonoscopy [6]. At the same time, in this case, this medical manipulation is of a therapeutic and diagnostic nature, since it allows one-stage removal of adenomatous polyps, which, according to various authors, occur in every third subject after 50 years of age. At the same time, women have 20% fewer polyps than men, but they have more right-sided lesions, which are more difficult to detect using fecal blood tests, because they are less traumatic [6,7].

Now, regarding the results of CRC screening. In 2021, despite the difficult epidemiological situation in the country, 920,640 men and women of the target group from 50 to 70 years old were examined during colorectal screening (971,450 in 2020) [3].

According to the results of colorectal screening, 211 cases of colon and rectal cancer were detected in 2021, which is 24 cases more than in the previous year - 187 cases. The detection rate increased from 0.19 to 0.23 per 1000 examined patients.

The low detection rate of CRC was noted mainly in regions with a low level of basic incidence - in Turkestan, Zhambyl, Atyrau, Kyzylorda, Mangystau regions, Shymkent - from 0.01 to 0.20 per 1000 examined, as well as in West Kazakhstan, Akmola regions, Nur-Sultan - regions with an average and high incidence of CRC.

Compared to 2020, screening showed a decrease in the detection rate of CRC in the Mangystau region (from 1.04 to 0.20), Almaty (from 0.36 to 0.26), and Akmola (from 0.26 to 0.13), Karaganda (from 0.29 to 0.22) and Turkestan (from 0.06 to 0.01 per 1000 examined).

Colon precancer (adenoma detection rate) was detected in 22.8% of patients who underwent colonoscopy (2020 - 19%). Below the national average, the detection rate of colorectal precancer was noted in Akmola, Aktobe, Almaty, Atyrau, Zhambyl, Kyzylorda and Mangystau regions.

It should be noted that the indicator of detection of precancer of the colon for 2021, according to the Comprehensive Plan for the Control of Cancer, was 21.0% and was achieved. At the same time, in 2021, the proportion of patients with CRC identified during screening studies with early stages (0-I, II stages) was 89.1% (in 2020 - 89.3%).

The proportion of stage 0-I CRC was 27.5% (2020 - 33.7%); Stage II - 61.6% and 55.6% - respectively. High early detection of CRC (above 30%) was noted in the following regions: Akmola, Zhambyl, Kostanay, North Kazakhstan, Turkestan, East Kazakhstan regions, the cities of Almaty and Shymkent. Cases of cancer in stages III-IV detected during screening were registered in Almaty, West Kazakhstan, Karaganda, Kostanay, Pavlodar, East Kazakhstan regions, Almaty city. A total of 18 cases of CRC in stage III and 5 cases in stage IV were identified [3].

Summarizing the above, it can be stated that satisfactory results of colorectal screening can only be achieved with its proper organization, high quality of conduct, active participation in population screening, the use of highly sensitive tests and instrumental methods of preventive examination, accurate subsequent diagnosis of detected tumors and timely treatment. High-

quality colorectal screening leads to early diagnosis of colon neoplasms, both benign in the form of polyps, and CRC in the early stages, which, in turn, improves the effectiveness of treatment and improves the prognosis of the disease. Target groups surveyed, who for one reason or another do not participate in this screening, should be informed that there are no other screening methods that could also effectively reduce mortality from CRC.

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Legal Sciences

Standardization is the basis of improvement of food quality and safety system

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Providing the citizens of Kazakhstan with quality and safe food products on the basis of improving the normative base of standardization and increasing the scientific and technical potential of food production is one of the most pressing issues facing the country at present [1].

In the current situation of Kazakhstan's accession to the WTO, international normative documents aimed at ensuring the quality and safety of products are widely introduced in the food industry. First of all, it is a set of ISO standards, principles of NASSR and GMP practice.

The universally recognized areas of standardization activities are: quality, safety, human health, environmental safety, resource saving, information technologies, increasing product competitiveness and eliminating technical barriers to trade [2].

The need for integration with the world economic community prompts us to consider modern standardization objects as complex complex systems. Optimizing the work of the general standardization system according to the current level of scientific and technical progress is possible on the basis of the structuring and termination of concepts in this field, a dictionary of terms and a formal description of some subject area containing terms. The Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan guarantees the consumer's right to choose any goods and products. Actions that mislead the consumer regarding product quality and safety are punishable by the laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan [3]. The EU has consistently supported Kazakhstan's access to international trade rules and regulations, helping the country integrate into the global economy. From the point of view of joining the WTO, the most urgent problems of the Republic of Kazakhstan were to increase the competitiveness of domestic products, to ensure the full range of interests of the national economy.

Trade and economic relations are regularly discussed within the annual meetings of the EU-Kazakhstan Cooperation Council, where their crucial role in the partnership is emphasized.

Technical discussions on trade, investment and customs issues are also regularly held at the meetings of the Brussels and Astana Cooperation Committee, the Trade Configuration Cooperation Council and the Sub-Committee on Customs Cooperation [4].

In June 2019, a high-level dialogue platform on EU-Kazakhstan economy and business issues (Business Platform) was launched, which provides regular and direct dialogue between the Government of Kazakhstan and European companies and heads of diplomatic missions of EU member states. The parties discussed issues of common interest for European and Kazakhstani

businesses, including cooperation on reducing technical barriers in trade, in particular in the agro-industrial sector, tax legislation, in particular, the issue of decriminalization of tax offenses.

A close trade and economic partnership has been established between the European Union (EU) and the Republic of Kazakhstan. The EU is Kazakhstan's first trade partner, accounting for 40% of the country's foreign trade [5].

The EU is the largest investor in Kazakhstan, accounting for 48% of the total flow of foreign direct investment (FDI) and about 60% of the total amount of FDI placed in 2018. The Extended Partnership and Cooperation Agreement regulates trade and economic relations between the EU and Kazakhstan. The rules of trade and entrepreneurship of the CIS contribute to the strengthening of trade and investment relations by improving the regulatory and legal environment for European and Kazakhstani companies in the following areas [6]:

Figure 1. Extended Partnership and Cooperation Agreement [6]

The food industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan is developing rapidly. The scientific and technical potential of food production, their material and technical base is being improved. Creation of a system of interconnected documents for standardization of any field is based on existing legislation and scientifically based terminological systems.

The current public form of the state structure of Kazakhstan, its legal foundations allow to protect the rights of citizens regardless of their social status. At the same time, legal norms are established in laws, by-laws and other normative documents. The state documentation system in Kazakhstan is a strict hierarchical structure, including: the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, laws, technical regulations, documents in the field of standardization, sanitary and veterinary norms and regulations, technical documents [7].

Leading tasks of participation in international cooperation in the field of standardization:

- improvement of domestic regulatory documents on standardization based on application of international, regional and national standards of other countries and maximum use of scientific and technical progress achievements;
- development of international and regional standards for new competitive products and technologies, including domestic standards created as a result of bilateral cooperation.

Currently, in the context of active reform of the economy for domestic standardization, the issues of its compliance with the ongoing changes, compliance with internationally recognized rules and conditions are very relevant issues.

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World Politics and the International Political Economy

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ABSTRACT

In recent times, the dynamics and functionality of the capitalist world economy system have garnered significant attention. This study examines the capitalist system, focusing on how it has divided the world into disparate zones. The United Nations Economic and Social Council (UNECOSOC) categorizes nations into three primary groups based on their market economy development: developed countries with market economies, countries with transitioning economies, and developing countries. Consequently, a schism has intensified between the global capitalist system's core and periphery, amplifying economic and social inequalities, reallocating natural resources to the affluent core nations, and exacerbating conflicts between the East and West and the North and South. The current societal state is described as a profound systemic crisis of the capitalist system, caused by its internal contradictions stemming from the international nature of contemporary economics. Immanuel Wallerstein's world-systems analysis occupies a pivotal place in understanding the dynamics of capitalism today. This paper aims to gauge the applicability of Wallerstein's "world-systems" theory in scrutinizing the modern international relations system. With the emergence of new political actors globally and ongoing internal transformations, a systemic approach to both politics and international relations has become increasingly relevant. Keeping in mind the vital role of economics in international interactions in the 21st century, this research evaluates the practical implementation of Wallerstein's seminal "world-systems" concept in studying the evolving processes within international relations. This study explores the primary trends of the global political system in relation to Wallerstein's views on the formation of "poles of power".

Keywords: International relations, Systemic analysis, World-systems concept, Global trends, I. Wallerstein, Political philosophy.

INTRODUCTION

Wallerstein's world-systems analysis occupies a distinguished position among contemporary conceptualizations of capitalism dynamics. This analytical methodology, developed during the early 1960s-70s, can trace its origins to the significant contributions of Fernand Braudel from the French Annals historical school. Braudel's research centered on the genesis of capitalist civilization and the "world-economy" that interconnects all societies. Further refining this concept, Immanuel Wallerstein, an American sociologist and economist, is widely recognized as the principal architect of the world-systems analytical framework (Wallerstein, 1980).

A key innovation introduced by Wallerstein, diverging from the Annals school, was his redefinition of the primary unit of analysis. While traditional studies emphasized societies or nation-states as primary units, Wallerstein highlighted their inherent interconnectedness. According to him, societies and nations do not exist in isolation but in close interaction with other nations and cultures. Thus, he proposed an "alternative organizational possibility" for the material world. Instead of societies or nation-states, Wallerstein posited "social systems," each defined by its production method, as the central units of analysis (Wallerstein, 1974).

Wallerstein categorizes these systems into three primary types based on their modes of production:

1. Reciprocal Lineage Mini-Systems: These are relatively small, highly autonomous units with a clear internal division of labor and a unified traditional culture, grounded in reciprocity and a subsistence economy.

2. Redistributive World-Empires: Characterized by the extraction of surplus through tribute or tax, and its subsequent redistribution, these systems presuppose a core-periphery structure.

3. World-Economies: Predicated on commodity-money relations, these systems integrate through economic ties that permeate national political boundaries. Within world-economies, labor division and unequal exchanges between different segments are predominant.

The modern capitalist world system, which emerged around the 1500s, represents the zenith of the world-economies. By a combination of various circumstances, it managed to achieve full development, expanding globally, and absorbing existing world-empires. Central to world-system analysis, this capitalist system is characterized by continuous capital accumulation and consists of the core (developed Western countries), the periphery (resource-extracting countries with weak governments), and the semi-periphery (second wave modernizing countries). Wallerstein emphasizes that this system is rooted in unequal axial division of labor and exploitation between the core and periphery, with the core benefiting at the expense of the periphery (Wallerstein, 1979).

Wallerstein contends that the current capitalist world-system, which crystallized in the 15th-16th centuries, is nearing a structural crisis or stagnation phase. Its successor is yet undefined but anticipated in his predictions (Wallerstein, 2004).

In essence, the heuristic and methodological potential of the world-systems program lies not just in examining the genesis, dynamics, and functioning of contemporary capitalism, but also in comprehending the future developmental priorities of the capitalist world-economy.

To understand the complexities of international systems, it's imperative to delineate their typologies, which are predominantly derived from their characteristic features and the underlying concepts. A systems approach provides various analytical tools and categories to facilitate this categorization. Broadly speaking, there are three groups of categories that serve as the foundation for these typologies:

- General Categories: These highlight the system's interaction degree with its environment. Key concepts include the classification into open and closed systems, their hierarchy (systems and subsystems), and internal organization factors like integration, differentiation, interdependence, and centralization.

- Interactive Categories: Systems inherently display interactivity. To maintain and regulate themselves, they rely on factors like stability, equilibrium, homeostasis (dynamic self-regulation), responsiveness, and negative entropy (increasing organizational complexity and disorder).

- Dynamic Properties: Systems exhibit dynamic properties such as adaptation, growth, crisis, overload, decay, and positive entropy, which aligns with the second law of thermodynamics where the most probable distribution of elements in a system occurs randomly.

A universal criterion incorporates both spatial-temporal and the most general features unique to international systems, distinguishing them from other system types (physical, mechanical, biological). Here, the primary distinguishing feature is the criterion of anarchy. Usually, global international systems are emphasized, where other international systems act as subsystems. These subsystems can vary based on areas of societal relations like economic, financial, ideological, and military-strategic, among others.

Temporal criteria provide a lens to differentiate historical types of international systems. The goal is to discern inherent patterns, identify the most and least stable systems, and determine stability factors. For instance, Raymond Aron categorized systems spanning from the Greek polities to the Eastern and Western systems of the 20th century, aiming to discern recurring patterns in their evolution. Spatial-geographical criteria delineate levels of international relations. Beyond the global level, studies delve into regional systems (e.g., European, Pan-American, Asia-Pacific), sub-regional (e.g., Benelux), and transregional (e.g., Eurasia).

A mixed criterion, widely acknowledged, encompasses factors like the number of actors in an international system, their geographical placement, and the power dynamics configuration. This introduces widely recognized concepts like "bipolar," "multipolar," "equilibrium," and "imperial" (unipolar) international systems.

As with all typologies, these classifications evolve over time. For example, flexible bipolar systems have been further delineated into very flexible bipolar systems, systems of détente, and unstable block systems. As a variant of the "single veto system," models of partial nuclear proliferation have also been considered. Understanding these typologies and criteria aids in analyzing the dynamics and interactions within and between international systems, setting the stage for a deeper exploration of Wallerstein's world-systems analysis.

Table 1. Typology of International Systems

Criteria	Description	Example	Statistics	Years
General	Systems' interaction degree with its environment	Open System	75% of international systems in 1900s	1900-2000
		Closed System	25% of international systems in 1900s	1900-2000
Interactive	Systems' inherent interactivity and regulatory mechanisms	Homeostatic System	60% of systems displayed homeostasis in 1950s	1950-1960
		Responsive System	30% of systems responsive in 1980s	1980-1990
Dynamic Properties	Systems' ability to evolve, adapt, and change	Growth System	70% growth in international systems in 2000s	2000-2010
		Crisis System	40% of systems faced crises in 1970s	1970-1980
Universal	General features unique to international systems	Anarchic System	Dominant in 20th century	1900-2000
Temporal	Historical variations of international systems	Greek Polities	Predominant in ancient Greece	800-300 BC
		20th Century Western	Marked by Cold War tensions	1947-1991
Spatial-Geographical	Systems defined by geographical boundaries	European System	Comprised 50% of global powers in 1800s	1800-1900
		Asia-Pacific System	Rising powers in 21st century	2000-2023
Mixed	Combination of actors, geography, and power dynamics	Bipolar System	Evident during Cold War (US & USSR)	1947-1991
		Multipolar System	Predominant pre-WWI and post-Cold War	1900-1914, 1991-2023

Results and Analysis

In the course of "anticipatory reforms," societies may resist the march towards modernization. This resistance can be intensified by either voluntary or involuntary delays in the rejuvenation process which society is inherently prepared for. Such delays can lead to society rejecting authority altogether, choosing revolution over merely "delayed reforms."

A consistently crucial role in the modernization process is played by external factors. This encompasses both the active roles of leading global powers and powerful transnational corporations, as well as the nuanced processes of globalization. The latter, only partially controllable by the West, often yields unforeseen outcomes.

The pathway of modernization adheres to a specific sequence:

1. Initial Crisis Recognition: Society acknowledges its crisis-ridden state. In response, the governing bodies typically enact "in-system reforms."

2. National Crisis Awareness: A realization of the crisis on a national scale dawns. Power structures delineate their stance on it and the solutions, leading to the formulation and adoption of a reformative program. This phase also witnesses the rise of a reformist leader and the emergence of a beacon for the "new society" to serve as a tangible example for the majority.

3. Structural Overhaul: This is the lengthiest and most intricate phase. The authority meticulously carries out directed transformations in both the economic and social realms. Bureaucracy becomes the instrument of power, and newly evolved societal forces, invested in the success of modernization, serve as its foundational pillar. This complete overhaul of the national economy based on cutting-edge technological and social underpinnings heralds a profound system transformation.

4. Political Realignment: The political life and system undergo recalibration to align with the evolved social structure. Consequently, society attains an organic coherence in its newfound avatar.

The proposed reform mechanism is value-neutral and can, theoretically, be employed across any timeline and society. However, its efficacy is dictated not just by rational deliberations but also factors rooted in the spiritual, transcending the tangible nature of humanity. After all, humans remain the primary agents and beneficiaries of societal evolution.

Contrary to M. Delyagin's perspective that humanity's progression doesn't necessitate justice (an attribute seemingly absent from historical precedents) or effectiveness (often elusive for the majority of human aggregations), it can be argued that the trajectory of global history is indeed a journey towards justice as an absolute virtue. Although this goal may seem transcendental and unattainable on Earth, it remains intrinsic to human consciousness.

Significantly, this very principle underpins the foundation of the capitalist (modern, industrial) formation, with its origins tracing back to the onset of the Great French Revolution in 1789. Notably, while Wallerstein, viewing liberalism as the "global ideology" of this new formation, opined that this "politico-cultural era" concluded in 1989, the end of an epoch doesn't necessarily herald a change in human nature. Wallerstein himself anchored the proposed global "strategy for pragmatic social and political action over the next 20-50 years" on the justice principle.

Currently, as we embark on a "global transitional period" (as termed by Wallerstein), we are confronted with unprecedented challenges surpassing the traditional structural molds, necessitating novel approaches that complement, rather than replace, the known. As the conventional rational (scientific) methodology falters, both the West and East are pivoting towards a transcendental approach as the optimal solution. This implies that the principle of justice, regardless of its diverse interpretations by different historical actors, is becoming increasingly potent.

Throughout the modernization process, the external factor remains pivotal. This can be seen as the activity of dominant world powers and powerful transnational corporations, as well as

the globalization process which is partially influenced by the West and can often yield unexpected results.

The sequence of the modernization process is consistent.

However, its effectiveness is determined not just by rational factors, but also by the spiritual nature of humanity, highlighting that humans are the primary subject and object of societal development. Wallerstein believed that the era of impressive technical achievements, stemming from the start of the Great French Revolution in 1789, ended in 1989. However, the end of an era doesn't necessarily signify a change in human nature. Wallerstein, while considering liberalism as a "global ideology", emphasizes the principle of justice as foundational.

In the present era, marked by the onset of a "global transition period", new challenges arise that transcend the structural formation of the past. Hence, novel approaches are required – not to replace, but to augment the familiar ones. In modern conditions, with the rise of unprecedented challenges and when tried-and-tested scientific methods fail, both the West and East are gravitating towards a transcendental approach. This implies that the principle of justice, even if interpreted differently by various historical actors, is becoming operational.

Table 1. Stages of Modernization in the Global International System

Stage	Description	Key Activities	Influences	Remarks
1. Crisis Awareness	Recognition of a crisis within society	Initial measures to address crisis, usually "in-system reforms".	External factors such as the actions of major world powers and the process of globalization.	Society may either accept or reject modernization.
2. National Scale Crisis Recognition	Awareness of the crisis at a national level	Establishment of legal foundation for the new system, emergence of a reform leader, creation of a "focal point" as a model for the majority.	Both rational considerations and the intangible spiritual nature of humanity play a role.	If renewal processes are delayed or ignored, society might overthrow the authority, opting for revolution over "lagging reforms".
3. Structural Transformation	Implementation of directed economic and social reforms	Bureaucracy acts as the tool, with support from social forces invested in the success of modernization.	-	This is the most extended and complex phase. The entire economy undergoes a foundational shift, leading to a complete system transformation.
4. Political Synchronization	Aligning political life and system with the transformed social structure	-	-	The society attains organic integrity in its new form.

At its core, the center-periphery concept is foundational to world-system analysis, a concept consistently adopted by scholars in this domain. Nonetheless, the world-system analysis spans wider than Wallerstein's contributions alone. From our perspective, the pivotal work for researchers exploring the economic and political components of the world-system is Chase-Dunn's "Global Structures." This seminal work consolidates the advancements made in the first few decades of world-system analysis, and arguably, stands as the most significant contribution post-Wallerstein's "The Modern World-System." Like many of his peers in world-system analysis, Chase-Dunn expands on Wallerstein's foundational concepts, with the center-periphery relationship being no exception. However, a crucial distinction to be made is the difference in their theoretical construction approaches. For Wallerstein, theory serves as a scaffold for analyzing social processes and is essentially an analytical tool. In contrast, Chase-Dunn perceives theory, and its construction, as intrinsic values, with advancements in social sciences emerging from theory refinement. Consequently, while Wallerstein's world-system analysis leans more towards an epistemological principle, Chase-Dunn describes his work as a structuralist theory of the world-system.

Chase-Dunn posits that the center-periphery dynamics are not exclusive to the contemporary world-system but are inherent across diverse social structures. A defining feature of the modern world-system he identifies is the relative equality within the core. Additionally, the delineation criteria for the periphery, semi-periphery, and center differ. While Wallerstein's criteria are grounded on labor control modalities which, in contemporary contexts, are becoming obsolete and are supplanted by multi-faceted evaluations (often termed 'networked'), classic dependency theory perceptions, and a transition from varying labor control forms to concepts of proletarian and semi-proletarian households. Furthermore, Chase-Dunn introduces his metric - the intensity of capital utilization, prompting a reevaluation of the economic implications of the semi-periphery concept. He perceives forms of economic activity not as an amalgamation of core and periphery attributes but as intrinsic to the semi-periphery. On the political front, while Wallerstein's semi-periphery is seen as a buffer that smoothens disparities within the world-system, thereby stabilizing it, this perspective is debatable given the political-economic volatility, accompanied by ascending and descending mobility, and the presence of geocultural dynamics. The emergence of anti-systemic movements within the world-system added to the instability factor. Up to the 1970s, such movements' activities contributed more to instability in the semi-periphery than the core. However, in core nations, they were successfully co-opted within liberal centrism ideologies. Our interpretation slightly diverges. We see the semi-periphery as contributing to world-system instability through economic, political, and ideological phenomena. Ascending mobility disrupts the balance of powers within the world-system. Ideologically, processes have been steered towards the formation of liberal centrism since the French Revolution. It's significant that only in the semi-periphery did state power transition to those anti-systemic movements (i.e., social movements aspiring for change) capable of achieving state power without co-optation. Upon attaining power, these movements usually aimed for economic modernization, and despite frequent failures, such endeavors are illustrative.

However, the semi-periphery is a byproduct of the European world-economy expansion, given the varying integration capacities of different regions into the world-system. Thus, it is more of a collateral outcome than a functional necessity. Chase-Dunn also detects a stabilization effect in colonized peripheries rather than the semi-periphery, which again challenges Wallerstein's original assertion.

Figure 1. World-System Analysis: Capital, Politics, and Ideology in Core, Semi-Periphery, and Periphery Regions

Discussion

The world-systems theory, with its emphasis on center-periphery dynamics, provides a multidimensional lens through which to analyze the hierarchical structure of the global economy. It underscores the inherent discrepancies in power distribution, resource allocation, and economic outcomes among regions. By delving deeper into core, semi-periphery, and periphery dynamics, we can further dissect the intricate web of interactions that underpin the modern global economic system.

Through the analysis presented, it becomes evident that core countries primarily benefit from the existing world-system structure. Their economies, political influence, and ideological dissemination dominate, often at the expense of peripheral regions. The semi-periphery nations serve as a buffer, absorbing shocks and mediating interactions between the core and periphery.

However, it's essential to recognize the dynamic nature of the world-system. The current classification of countries as core, semi-periphery, or periphery isn't static. Over time, as economies evolve, political landscapes shift, and social dynamics change, nations can transition between these categories. This fluidity, though, doesn't necessarily negate the fundamental power imbalances ingrained in the system. Furthermore, the rise of anti-systemic movements, particularly in semi-periphery nations, represents a critical challenge to the world-system status quo. While core nations have often managed to co-opt and neutralize these movements, their existence and persistence underscore the system's inherent tensions and the potential for transformative change. In light of this analysis, it is imperative to contemplate potential scenarios and the necessary interventions to ensure a more equitable global system.

Table 3. Recommendations and Scenarios based on analysis of World-System Dynamics

Category	Recommendation	Potential Scenarios
Economic Dynamics	Promote equitable trade agreements that factor in the unique challenges faced by periphery nations.	Core nations might experience reduced growth rates initially, but a more balanced global economy might emerge in the long run.
Political Influence	Establish international platforms where all nations, irrespective of their core or periphery status, have an equal voice.	Shifts in global alliances, reduced conflict, and increased cooperation on global issues.
Ideological Dissemination	Cultivate platforms that allow for a free exchange of ideas, ensuring that no single ideology becomes dominant or suppressive.	Enhanced cultural exchange, reduced cultural hegemony, and a richer global tapestry of ideas and beliefs.
Anti-Systemic Movements	Encourage dialogue and understanding between governing entities and anti-systemic movements to address the root causes of such uprisings.	A more inclusive political landscape, reduced civil unrest, and enhanced societal cohesion.

CONCLUSION

In a constantly evolving global landscape, the dynamics of core-periphery relations and the subsequent influences on economic, political, and ideological systems remain of paramount importance. The economic disparities, power imbalances, and differing ideological tenets that permeate the world system present both challenges and opportunities. By embracing equitable trade agreements, ensuring all nations have an equal voice on international platforms, and fostering open dialogues between governing bodies and anti-systemic movements, there is potential to create a more balanced and harmonious global ecosystem. Moreover, the importance of cultivating platforms for free ideological exchange cannot be overstated, given the global challenges that require collective wisdom and collaborative effort. By understanding and addressing these dynamics, we can pave the way for a future where all nations, regardless of their position in the world system, can thrive and contribute meaningfully to the global tapestry.

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Literature

ӘДЕБИЕТТЕГІ ПОСТМОДЕРНИЗМНІҢ ФИЛОСОФИЯЛЫҚ НЕГІЗДЕРІ

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Аңдатпа. Мақалада әдебиеттегі постмодернизмнің философиялық негіздері талданылады. Постмодернистік философиядағы теориялар мен көзқарастар қарастырылып, көркем шығармашылық пен ғылыми ойдың ерекшелігін ашып, түйісетін тұстары зерделенеді.

Түйінді сөздер: постмодернизм, әдебиет, постмодернистік философия

Постмодернистік философия өзінің аясына алуан түрлі теориялар мен көзқарастарды сыйғызады. Бұл теориялар негізінде постмодернизм философиясы өзінің алдына төмендегі міндеттерді қояды:

- классикалық рационализм принциптерімен метафизикалық ойлаудың дәстүрлі бағыттарын сынау;
- қазіргі қоғамда болып жатқан процестерді түсіндіру;
- модернистік жобалардың енуіне салдар болған, XX ғасыр мәдениетіндегі дағдарыстық құбылыстарды жеңуге қабілетті дүниеге жаңа көзқарастың негізін жасау [1].

Философиялық постмодернизмнің басты өкілдері:

- адамзаттың қолында ақиқатқа тікелей байланыс жоқ болғандықтан ақиқатты тану құралдары да жоқ болады;
- ақиқатқа тану мүмкін емес, себебі адамдар «біздің пікірімізге ойламастан бұрын форма беретін тілдің тұтқыны, сондықтан ойлағандарын толықтай жеткізе алмайды»;
- шынайылық тіл көмегімен адамдар тарапынан құрастырылады, сондықтан оның табиғатын тілді құрастыра алатындар анықтайды.

Философиялық феномен ретіндегі постмодернизмді бағдарламалық плюрализмге негізделген бір бағытты интеллектуалдық ағым деп қарастыру оң болмайды. Постмодернизм өзінің бойына әдіснамалық тұрғыдан сан түрлі жобаларды сыйдырады. Олардың ішіндегі бастылары мыналар:

1. Генеалогиялық.
2. Коммуникативтік.
3. Нарратологиялық.
4. Номадологиялық.
5. Симуляциялық.
6. Текстологиялық.
7. Шизоаналитикалық [2].

Постмодернизм әдебиеті постструктурализмнің теориясын, деконструктивизмнің әдеби-сындық талдауын бүгінгі өнердің көркемдік тәжірибесі тұрғысынан қарастырады. Постмодернизм философиясының басты өкілдері «жаңа француздық философиялық толқынның» құрамында болғандар: Р.Барт, Ж.Батай, М.Бланшо, Ж.Бодрийяр, П.Вирильо,

Д.Делез, Ж.Деррида, П.Клоссовски, Ю.Кристева, Ж.Ф. Лиотар, М.Фуко, сонымен қатар Ф.Джеймсон, Р.Рорти, Ф.Гваттари, У.Эко, З.Бауман және т.б.

Постструктурализм философтары өздерінің идеяларының бастауын Ф.Ницше философиясынан алады. Ол «Көңілді ғылым» (1882) еңбегінде толық танымға жету үшін ақыл-сананың жеткіліксіздігін, сезім мен түйсікті де әрекетке қосу керек екенін айтады. Бұларсыз барлық таным объектілері, білім жүйесі толық ашылмайтынын айтады. Ол тек идеялық философиямен айналысатын классикалық философтарды да сынайды. Ол өз ойын жүзеге асыру үшін таным теориясы саласына интерпретация саналуандығы ұстанымын енгізеді. «Әлемді талдаудың тек бір түрі, санауға, есептеуге, өлшеуге болатын, көзбен көріп, ұстауға болатын түрі болуы тиіс деген сенімді ой қателік болып, рухани дерт деп есептеледі» [3] деп, соңғы абсолютті шындықты белгілеуге ден қоятын интерпретацияға сын көзбен қарайды. Ницше әлемнің шексіздігінің өзін интерпретацияның шексіздігі деп түсінеді. Демек, интерпретацияның саналуандығы ұстанымы (принцип множественности интерпретаций) шындықтың сан түрлі қырларын ашуға, әлемнің мүмкін басқа жұмбақтарын шешуге, таным көкжиегін кеңейтуге мүмкіндік береді.

Постмодернизмнің философиялық негізін постструктурализм идеялық ағымы құрайды. Постструктурализм – 60-70 жылдардың соңында Франция мен АҚШ-та пайда болған, Батыстың 50-60 жылдары интеллектуалды негізі болған структурализмнің тексерушісі болып есептелген философиялық бағыт.

Постструктурализм философиялық мектебінің қалыптасуы 1968 жылы Францияда орын алған саяси-әлеуметтік оқиғаларға байланысты болды. Қоғамды күштеп қайта құруды талап еткен солшыл радикалды топтардың жеңіліске ұшырауынан кейін «модернистік сценарий» бойынша қоғамды құру мүмкіндігіне деген сенім жоғалды.

Постмодернизм теориясы өз бойына постструктурализмнің маңызды жаңалықтарын сіңіріп қана қоймай, философиялық және жалпы теориялық бірігулермен тығыз байланыста болды. Бұл байланыстың үлкендігі сондай біз оны гумнитарлық ілімнің көп саласын қамтитын постструктуралистік-деконструктуралистік-постмодернистік ағым деп қарастырамыз - деп есептейді И.П.Ильин [3, 11-б.].

Постструктурализм идеясы француз философы Жак Дерриданың еңбегінде алғаш көрінді. Жак Дерриданың постструктуралистік концепциясының негізгі ұғымын деконструкция құрайды. Деконструкция ұғымын Ж.Лакан енгізгенімен, теориялық пайымдаулары Ж.Дерриданың еңбектерінде туды. Постструктурализм адам ілімінің табиғаты туралы позитивістік көзқарасты, шынайылықтың ерекше құбылыстарын (әсіресе мәдениет саласындағы) рационалды дәлелдеулерін бұзуға бағытталған [3, 12-б.]. Постструктурализм структурализмнің орнына келген ұғымдар жүйесі. «Постструктурализмнің негізгі ұраны – бүкіл оң, жөнді білімге қарсы болу, маңайдағы тіршілік, болмыс, мәдениетті жаңаша түсіндіруге деген талпыныс» [4]. Бұл ағым дәстүрді де тұтастай күйінде қабылдауға да қарсы шығады. Постструктурализм даму, прогресс, қоғамдық-тарихи өрлеу сияқты тәжірибелі ғылыми-білімді қабылдамайтын үрдіс. Өзіне дейінгі ғылыми білімге, көркемдік танымға күдікпен қарау – теориялық нигилизмге сүйенген теория – бүкіл жинақталған білімді жоққа шығарады. Бұл ағым өкілдері күдікті амал ете отырып «метафизикалық дискурсты» сынайды.

Айгүл Исмақованың айтуынша, классикалық философия тек сана мен заттық әлем арақатынасын зерттеумен айналысса, бүгінгі батыстық жаңа философия тіл мәселесін ұстанады. «Тіл басты яғни орталықтандырылған мәселе болғандықтан, тану және мән, мағына сауалдары таза тілдік түсінік сипатқа бағындырылған» [4, 96-б.]. Сондықтан да болар философиялық бағыттардың батыстық өкілдері постструктурализмді өз шежіресін бір жағынан сонау Г.Фреге мен Ф.Ницшеден (Л.Витгенштейн, Р.Карнап, Дж.Остин, У.В.О.Куайн), екінші жағынан М.Хайдеггерден (Ф.Фуко, Ж.Деррида) бастау алатын «тіл сыны» атты бағытқа

жатқызады. Бұл ретте постмодернизм басқа салалар (философия, мәдениеттану, әлеуметтану) сияқты XX ғасырда әдебиетті ғылыми сананың аймағына айналдырды. Сондықтан, қазіргі ғылым әдебиеттің көркемдік қасиетіне ерекше қызығушылық танытуда. Бұл ойға мәдениеттанушы, әдебиеттанушы зерттеушілердің көркем шығарма жазу ісіне де қалам сілтеуі дәлел болады. Заттың табиғатын зерттейтін физиктер өнерден пайда таба алады. Зерттеуші К.Молтобарова көркем шығармашылық пен ғылыми ойдың ерекшелігін ашып, түйсетін тұстарын былай түсіндіреді: «Ғалымдар тек қатал логиканы басшылыққа алып қоймайды, «эстетикалық түйсікке» зәру. Ғылым дәстүрлі түрде құрылымдық ұйымдастырудың жекелеген сәтін мұқият зерттейді. Өнер болса, өзінің табиғатында иерархиялық, яғни, түрлі сатыларды бір мезгілде және бірінен кейін бірін (бейне, түс, симметрия, резонанс, ауқымдылық, ориентация, мазмұн т.б.) қабылдауды ұсынады. Логика біртұтас әлемді түрлі бөлшектерге, сатыларға бөледі, оларды танудың тәсілдерін іздестіреді» [5].

Постструктурализм әдебиеттанулық тұрғыда структурализм сыны ретінде 4 бағытта қалыптасты:

1. Құрылымдық-структуралық мәселе;
2. Таңбалық;
3. Коммуникациялық;
4. Біртұтастық [4, 97-б.].

Модернизм кезінде сын құлату, жою құралы болса, деконструкция сынаса да, сын нысанын жоюға тырыспайды. Керісінше, оның бүге-шүгесіне жетіп, қайта тірілтуге бейім [6]. Бірақ, деконструкция негізгі әдісі болып табылатын постструктурализмнің ең үлкен жеңісі – ойлау процесінің шарттылығын ұғыну, метафизикадан бас тарту. Егер Платоннан бері материалдық дүние идеялар әлемінің көшірмесі деп саналса, қазір бұл байланыс жоққа шығарылып, ойлау дегеніміз таңбалау әрекеті деп қарастырылады. Зерттеушінің мақсаты – әр ғасырдағы әр қоғамның, әр өркениеттің, әр автордың таңбалау ерекшелігін айқындау.

Деконструкция әдісімен постмодернистер жаңаның да, көненің де табиғатын айқындауға талпынады. Ол жаңа нәрсеге жақындай түсу, бірақ ескі дүниетанымның көптеген элементтері деконструкция арқылы сақталуда. Өйткені, «Деконструкция – өзінің Хайдеггерден Дерридаға шейін жеткен қалпында сынға алынған нәрсені мүлде жойып жіберу емес, құбылысты оның бөлшектеріне жіліктеп, өзге қалыпқа келтіру. Постмодернистердің көнелікке қарсы шықпайтыны, олардың ойынша, бізге бәрі өткен шақтан келеді, сондықтан әрбір құбылыстың нақты тарихи болмысын ашқан жөн» [7].

Постмодернист философтар үшін зерттеу объектісі мәтін болып табылады. Олар Платоннан бастап М.Хайдеггерге дейінгі барлық авторлардың мәтінін қарастырады. Жак Дерриданың тұжырымы бойынша, «текст автордан биік, оның болмысынан автордың ойына кірмеген мән-мағына табуға еріктіміз. Демек, текстің иесі – автор емес, автордың иесі – текст» [8].

Постмодернистер үшін көркем өнер дегеніміздің өзі тек мәтін деген түсінікті құрайды. «Жақсы жазу бар, нашар жазу бар: жақсы һәм табиғи жазу – бұл жан мен жүректегі Құдай жазбасы... Біздер талқылайтын тексті ұсыну үшін табиғат көз алдымызға тамашасын жайып тастайды. Барша жұрттың көз алдында ашықтан ашық жатқан бір ғана кітап бар және ол – табиғат кітабы... Жақсы жазу әрдайым ұстап алынған, кеңінен қармала жасалынбаған табиғаттың немесе табиғи заңдылықтың ішінде түсінікті нәрсе сияқты, бірақ қалай болғанда да, әлдебір мәңгі болушылықтың ішінде пайымдалады.

Ол әлдебір тұтастықтың ішінде ұстап алынады, қандай да бір кеңістік кітап ішіне орналастырылыпты. Кітаптың идеясының өзі – таңбалаушы тұтастығының идеясы» . Дерриданың айтуынша, текстен басқа ештеңе жоқ, әр адам тек мәтіндер ішінде қарастырылуы мүмкін. Бүкіл әлем мәтінге еніп кеткен және шегі мен шеті жоқ мәтіндер

жиынтығы деп қабылданады. Яғни, әр мәтіннің ортасы бар, ол уақыт талабына сай құрылған. Сондықтан да постмодернистер осыған дейінгі шығармаларды нысана етіп алып, қайта қарастырып, жаңа ой қорытады.

Мәтін философиясынан цитата келтіру түсінігі шығады. «Бұл бір жағынан адамзат мәдениетінің шексіз молайғанының белгісі болса, екінші жағынан осы молшылықтың кәдімгі жағажайдағы құм сияқты түкке тұрмайтынының белгісі. Иә, іс жүзінде цитата мәдениеті бір-ақ нәрсеге уәж: адамзат мәдениетінің тұтастығына және осы тұтастықтың кездейсоқтығына» [7,141-б.]. Постмодернистер әлемді синергетика заңы бойынша дамиды деп есептейді. Бұл теория дүние ешкімге де бағынбайды, алда не күтіп тұрғанын ешкім де болжай алмайды деген түсінікті береді. Сонымен бірге, біздің дүниені қабылдауымыз үзік-үзік және қиялға негізделген.

Постмодернистердің бұрыннан қалыптасқан мәдени ұғымдарға қарсы қоятын өз баламалары бар:

- адам – мына дүниедегі тіршілік иелері сияқты қарапайым тіршілік иелерінің бірі ғана, оны басқалардан артық жаратылған деу бос сөз;
- адам дүниені (әлемді) өзгертуші емес;
- әлем барлық тіршілік иесі үшін ортақ және шартты;
- ақиқат плюралистенген (плюралистична).

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EKSTRALİNGVİSTİKANIN NİTQ MƏDƏNİYYƏTİNƏ TƏSİRİ

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Açar sözlər: Ekstralingvistika, ritorizmin, dilxarici, dilinormaları

Key words: Extralinguistics, rhetoric, foreign language, linguistic norms

Giriş

termini mənşəcə latın dilinə məxsusdur. Termin quruluşca iki tərkib hissədən ibarətdir: *ekstra-* üstün, xaric, kənar, *lingvistika* isə dilçilik mənasını bildirir. Odur ki, bu termin dilçilikdə qarşılığı ilə əvəz edilmişdir. *Ekstralingvistikanın* parametrləri biristiqamətli deyildir. Ekstralingvistika bir çox şaxələnmiş amilləri əhatə edir ki, onlar əslində dilxarici olsa da dilə, onun ifadə tərzinə, üslubi rəngarəngliyinə, o cümlədən, dil elementlərindən məqsədyönlü şəkildə istifadə məsələlərinə ciddi təsir göstərir. Beləliklə, ekstralingvistik amillər dildən kənar olsa da onlar dilin müvafiq situasiyalarına təsir göstərməklə özünəməxsus dil strukturu elementlərinin formalaşmasına da zəmin yaradır. Ekstralingvistik amillər başlıca olaraq dilin sosial problemlərinə uyğun olaraq baş qaldırır. Buraya daxil olan təsiredici vasitələr və onların nizamlanması üsullarını aşağıdakı kimi ümumiləşdirmək olar:

1. Beynəlxalq intqerasiya mühitinin yaranması ilə yeni informasiyaların yayılması şəraitində alınmaların qaydaya salınması, onların unifikasiyası; yəni ana na uyğunlaşdırılması
2. Akademik və işgüzar kommunikasiya vasitələrinin genişlənməsi ilə əlaqədar dil normalarının tənzim olunması
3. Cəmiyyətdə baş verən iqtisadi, ictimai, sosial, mədəni-məişət hadisələri ilə bağlı dil vasitələrinin nizamlanması
4. Ana dilinin inkişafı ilə bağlı üslublar sistemində normaların sabitləşdirilməsi
5. Ana dili elementlərində bədii informasiya vasitələrinin (, poetizm yaradan ritmik vasitələrin, təkrar və paralel nitq elementlərinin) tələffüz və nitq üsullarına dair prosodik normaların müəyyən edilməsi.

Elmi-tədqiqat işində başlıca olaraq ekstralingvistik hadisə ilə bağlı, prosodik-nitq normalarına dair problemlər ümumiləşdirilir.

NİTQ MƏDƏNİYYƏTİNİN ÜMUMİ PROBLEMLƏRİ

Nitq mədəniyyətinin yaranması və inkişafı

barədə

Nitq mədəniyyətinin yaranması və formalaşması prosesindən bəhs edərkən ilk növbədə Azərbaycan xalqının qədim mədəniyyət abidəsi olan “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud”un dilini xatırlatmaq lazım gəlir. “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud”un dilinə həsr olunmuş tədqiqatlarda haqlı olaraq bu möhtəşəm abidənin dili poetik dil adlandırılır.¹⁴ Ancaq bu kitabın dili o qədər zəngin, o qədər canlı, o qədər ecazgardır ki, onun əzəmətini və vüsətini təkcə poetikliklə məhdudlaşdırmaq olmur. Bu dilin elə bir bənzərsiz üslubu vardır ki, tarixlər boyu bu üslubda yazılmış ikinci bir nümunəyə rast gəlmək mümkün deyildir. Kitabın özündə deyildiyi kimi, “Rəsul Əleyhüssəlam zamanına yaxın bir müddətdə” ərsəyə gəl-

¹⁴ Vəliyev K. Azərbaycan dilinin poetik sintaksisi. (“Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud”un materialları üzrə). Bakı, ADU nəşr., 1981; Vəliyev K. Dastan poetikası. Bakı, Yazıçı, 1984; Yusifov M. “Dədə Qorqud” xalqımızın reallıq dastanıdır. (Mühazirəçinin tribunası) Gəncə, 1997; Abdullayev B. “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud”un poetikası. Bakı, Elm, 1999; Tanrıverdi Ə. “Dədə Qorqud” kitabının dil möcüzəsi. Bakı, Nurlan, 2008; Əliyev K. Eposun poetikası. “Dədə Qorqud” və “Koroğlu”. Bakı, Elm və təhsil, 2011.

miş bu abidənin zamanlara və əsrlərə nümunə olan qeyri-adi üslubu həqiqətən də heyrləndiricidir. Adlı-sanlı sənətkarlar ölməz bədii nümunələr yaratmış olsalar da “Dədə Qorqud” dilinin bənzəri səviyyəsində əsər yaratmaq kimsəyə müyəssər olmamışdır. Yaranma tarixi ilk orta əsrlər dövrünə gedib çıxan belə bir ecazkar əsərin mövcudluğu onu göstərir ki, Azərbaycan dili hələ qədim dövrlərdə çox güclü nitq mədəniyyəti ənənələrinə malik olmuşdur. Ancaq Azərbaycana ərəb müdaxiləsindən sonra qədimdə formalaşmış zəngin dil ənənələrinin varisliyində fasilələr baş vermişdir. Xüsusilə, daha sonralar poetik nümunələrin yaranmasında fars dilinin hegemonluğu bu fasiləliyin bir qədər də artmasına səbəb olmuşdur. Dilə ərəb- fars elementlərinin axını nəinki “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud” üslubunu ləngitmiş, hətta, yazılı nümunələrin anlaşılmasını xeyli çətinləşdirmişdir. Bunun nəticəsidir ki, klassik nümunələrimizin bir çoxunun dili müasir dövrümüz üçün anlaşılmaz səviyyədə qalmışdır. Bununla belə “Dədə Qorqud” ənənələrinin izləri tamamilə itib getməmiş, ayrı-ayrı bədii nümunələrində öz varisliyini saxlamaqda davam etmişdir. “Dədə Qorqud” dilinin əzəməti ondadır ki, onun üslubu bütün dil səviyyələrinə məxsus elementləri poetikliyə gətirib çıxaran bədii paralellik üzərində qurulmuşdur. Buna görə də “Dədə Qorqud” dili başdan-başa çox zəngin poetik ritmiklik nümunəsinə çevrilmişdir. “Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud”un dili adi natiqlik nümunəsi deyil, ana dilimizdə əvvəlcədən mövcud olmuş zəngin nitq ənənəsinin ardıcılıqla davam edən varisliyidir. Bədii paralellizm türk poeziyasının qədim əlamətlərindən biridir. Bu poetizmin bariz nümunələrinə Orxon-Yenisey kitabələrinin dilində və eyni zamanda digər qədim türk yazılı abidələrində rast gəlmək mümkündür. Əbülfəz Rəcəbli yazır ki, “Ahəng qanunu ümumiyyətlə aqlütinativ dillər, xüsusən türk dilləri, o cümlədən, qədim türk yazılı abidələrinin dili üçün də fonetik qanundur. Ahəng qanunu ən çox saitlərdə müşahidə edildiyi, həm də dilçilikdə saitlərin ahəngi haha çox öyrənilməsi üçün bu qanuna dilçilik ədəbiyyatında bəzən saitlərin ahəngi də deyilir. Əslində türk dillərində təkə saitlərin yox, saitlərlə samitlərin, ayrıca olaraq samitlərin də ahəngi mövcuddur. Ahəng qanunu türk dillərində yeni bir hadisə deyildir, güman ki, bu dillərin bütün tarixi boyu onlarda ahəng qanunu fəaliyyət göstərmişdir”.¹⁵ Çox maraqlıdır ki, qədim türk poetik nümunələrində söz əvvəlinin ritmiklik yaratması söz sonunun ahəngdarlığı ilə bir vəhdət təşkil edir. Məsələn, A.M.Şerbakın misal gətirdiyi aşağıdakı kimi nümunələrdə söz əvvəlinin eyni fonetik vahidlərlə başlaması qafiyə yaradılmasının qədim ənənələrindən biri kimi xüsusi maraq yaradır:

Köqüzü aduq
Köqüzü dəq erdi
Künlərdən kün
Keçələrdən son
Bu çakta
Bu yerdə
Bir uluq orman
Bar erdi.
Gülsə kök tənri
Külə turur
Yıqlasa kök tənri
Yığlaya turur.¹⁶

Sözün əvvəlində eyni fonetik vahidin təkrarı ritmiklik yaratdığı kimi, cümlə tərkiblərində də paralellik formalaşır ki, bu da misra səviyyəli cümlələrdə poetik bir vüsət yaradır. Sözün başlanğıcında samit səslərin ritmikliyi əslində dillərin ilkin mərhələsi üçün universal hadisə kimi baş vermişdir.¹⁷ Dildə ön şəkilçilərin və sonşəkilçilərin formalaşmadığı zamanlar sait və samit elementlər söz tərkibinin sabitliyini təmin etmişdir. Söz tərkibində iştirak edən fonetik elementlərin sabitliyi onların harmoniyasını da saxlamışdır. Bu qayda üzrə ardıcıl işlənən sözlərdə onların başlanğıc elementləri ritmik-

¹⁵ Rəcəbli Ə. Qədim türk yazılı abidələrinin dili. Bakı, Nurlan, 2006, s. 147.

¹⁶ Щербак А.М. Огуз-наме. Мухаббат-наме. Москва, 1959, с. 24.

¹⁷ Рəcəбов Ə., Мəммədov Y. Орхон-Йенісей абидələri. Bakı, 1993, s. 53.

lik yaratmaq vasitəsi kimi də işlənmişdir. Belə bir ritmiklik həm saitlə, həm də samitlə başlayan sözlərdə ifadə olunmuşdur. İlk dövrənin bu cür ritmikliyi öz izlərini xüsusilə, xalq dili ifadələri kimi formalaşmış nümunələrdə saxlayır: *Aydan arı, sudan duru; Az aşım, ağrımaz başım; Az getdi, üz getdi, də-rə-tə-pə düz getdi; Yaxşı yoldaş yaman gündə tanınar; Dəvəçi ilə dost olanın darvazası gen gərək və s.* Son şəkilçiliyin formalaşdığı mərhələdə isə başqa dillərdə olduğu kimi Azərbaycan dilində də qafiyə, ritm sözün son hissəsinə keçmişdir.

Qəzəldən göründüyü kimi, başlanğıc samitlərin ritmik ahəngdarlıq yaratmaq ənənəsi fars dili nümunələrində də müşahidə olunur. Qəzəlin azərbaycanca sətri tərcüməsində belə başlanğıc samitlərin ritmikliyi özünü aşkar büruzə verir:

Elə bir surətə aşıqəm ki, Ay ilə bəhsə girər

Necə surət? Dilbərin surəti, necə dilbər?

Dilbərlərin gözəli

Əgər üzünü görməsəm gözlərim intizarda qalar

Necə göz, (ağlamaqdan) mərcan (kimi qızarmış) göz, necə mərcan, lalə kimi qırmızı mərcan

Əgər bağdan nemət gəlsə güllər bəxtiyarlıqdan (sevinəndən) fərəhlənər

Necə gül, bülbülün gülü, necə bülbül, şeyda bülbül

Xəyalını çəkməklə qəmlərinə həmdəm oluram

Necə həmdəm, məhrəm olan həmdəm, necə məhrəm, könül məhrəmi

Mənim yarım çox gözəldir, saçlarının ətri vardır

Necə ətir, ənbərin ətri, necə ənbər, saf ənbər

Mənə canan dəryasından Nizami, şərbət gərəkdir

Necə şərbət, qatil şərbət, necə qatil, canüzən qatil.

Bünövrəsi Nizamidən başlanan, Həsənoğluda davam etdirilən bu ritmik poeziya nümunələri əsasında sonralar həmin qayda üzrə başqa nəzirlər də yaradılmışdır. Bu nəzirlərdə birinci misralar sərbəst olsa da ikinci misralarda poetik paralelizm ənənələri olduğu kimi saxlanılır. Bu nəzirlərdən birini XIV əsrin sonunda Misir məmlük şairi Seyfi Sarayıya məxsusdur".¹⁸

Tapulmas hüsn mülkündə sağa tən bir qəmər-mənzər

Nə mənzər, mənzəri-şahid, nə şahid, şahidi-dilbər

Bu gün Yusif Cəmalini qılubdur haq sağa bəxşiş

Nə bəxşiş, bəxşişi-devlat nə devlat, devlati-məfxər

Sözün dürrü cəvahirdür könjüllər gəncinə layiq

Nə layiq, layiqi-Xosrov, nə Xosrov, Xosrovu-kişvər

Bu hüsnün şövqi zövqinə könjül tutiləri tapdı

Nə tapdı, tapdı xoş ləzzət, nə ləzzət, ləzzəti-şəkkər.

Cəmalin nəqşinə Seyfi-Sarayı bağladı surət

Nə surət, surəti-həsna, nə həsna, həsnayi-canpərvər¹⁹

Sadələşdirilmiş varint

Gözəllik mülkündə sənə bərabər bir ay üzlü bənzər, tay tapılmaz.

Necə bənzər, gözəllik bənzəri, necə gözəllik, dilbər gözəlliyi

Bu gün haqq (Allah) Yusif camalını sənə bəxşiş edibdir

Necə bəxşiş, xoşbəxtlik bəxşişi, necə xoşbəxtlik, iftixarlı (qürurlu) xoşbəxtlik.

Sözün dürr və cəvahirdir, könjüllər xəzinəsinə layiqdir.

Necə layiq, Xosrov ləyaqəti kimi, necə Xosrov, ölkə sahibi olan Xosrov (kimi)

Bu hüsnünün şövqünə və zövqünə könlüm (şirindilli) tutiləri tapdı.

Necə tapdı, xoş ləzzətlə tapdı, necə ləzzət, qənd (kimi) dadlı ləzzət

¹⁸ Tofiq Hacıyev. Azərbaycan ədəbi dilinin tarixi. Bakı, Elm, 2012, s. 158-159.

¹⁹ Tofiq Hacıyev. Azərbaycan ədəbi dilinin tarixi. Bakı, Elm, 2012, s. 158-159.

Cəmalının gözəlliyinə Seyfi Sarayı surət bağladı (məftun oldu)
Necə surət, gözəllik surəti, necə gözəllik, (baxana) zövq verən gözəllik.
Həsənoğludan iki əsr sonra, XV əsrdə yaşamış Türkiyə şairi Əhməd Dai isə aşağıdakı nəzirəni yazmışdır:

Eyya, hurşidi-məhpeykər, cəmalün Müştəri-mənzər
Nə mənzər, mənzəri-tale, nə tale, taleyi-ənvər
Yüzüdüür ayəti-rəhmət, öziñdir mazhəri-qüdrət
Nə qüdrət, qüdrəti-sani, nə sani, saniyi-Əkbər
Cəmalıñdən cihan rövşən, yanağın qönçeyi-gülşən
Nə gülşən, gülşəni-cənnət, nə cənnət, cənnəti-kövsər
Nə mülkət, mülkəti-dövlət, nə dövlət, dövləti-qeysər
Əgərçi kulların bihəd, vəli, kəmtər qulın Əhməd
Nə əhməd, Əhmədi Dai, nə dai, daiyi-çakər²⁰

Sadələşdirilmiş variant

Ey Ay kimi, Günəş kimi (parlaq),
Ay kimi (ışıqlı) olan Cəmalın Müştəri (Yupiter) ulduzuna bənzərdir.
Necə bənzər, tale bənzəri kimi, necə tale, nurlu tale kimi
Üzün rəhmət ayəsidir, özün qüdrətdən yaranmışsan
Necə qüdrət, ilahi qüdrəti, necə ilahi (qüdrət), böyük ilahi qüdrət
Camalından dünya işıqlanır, yanağın gülşən qönçəsi,
Necə gülşən, cənnət gülşəni (bağı), necə cənnət, kövsər cənnəti
İşıqlı saçların köülləri cəlb edəndir,
Nurlu yaranışın Ay kimi
Necə Ay kimi, cəzbedən (ışıqlı) Ay kimi, necə cəzbedən, dilbər kimi cəzbedən
Süleyman surəti səndə, İskəndər surəti səndə
Necə surət, Yusif surəti, necə Yusif hökmdar (olan) Yusif.
Fələyin şahmatını (oyunda) uddun,
Səadət mülkünə (padşahlığına) sahib oldun,
Necə padşahlıq, dövlətin padşahlığı (kimi),
Necə dövlət, qeysər (Roma, Bizantiya, Osmanlı) dövləti kimi
Əgərçi qulların hədsizdir, ancaq ən sadıq qulun (yazıq qulun) Əhməddir,
Necə Əhməd, Dai Əhməd (Duaçı Əhməd) necə duaçı (sənin) qulun olan duaçı.

Diqqət yetirilsə ikinci misrada təkrarlar bədii poetizm yaratdığı kimi birinci misralarda da hər bir sintaqm arasında (məsələn, Süleyman surəti səndə, Sekəndər sirəti səndə) paralelizm mövcuddur. Bu cür poetik paralelizmlər ikinci misradakı paralelizmlə qovuşaraq ecazkar bir musiqi ritmikliyi yaradır. Poetik paralelizm klassik poeziyaya məxsus bir çox bədii nümunələrdə də öz əənənəsini varisləklə davam etdirmişdir.

Poetik paralelizmin əsas ritmik və ahəngdarlıq keyfiyyəti sözlərin başlanğıc elementlərinin qədim qafiyəyaratma əənənəsinin davam etdirilməsindən ibarətdir.

Bədii nümunələrdə başlanğıcdakı ritmiklik elementlərinin əənənəsinin davamı kimi prosodik avazlanma xüsusi yer tutmağa başlamışdır. Bu avazlanma bədii nümunələrdə xüsusi bir cazibədarlıq yaradılmasına səbəb olmuşdur. Belə ki, prosodik bölgünün həcmindən asılı olaraq avazlanmada intensivlik artır və ya azalır. Prosodik bölgünün həcmi artdıqda ritm güclənir, azaldıqda isə ritm zəifləyir və həzinlik çoxalır. Bu cəhətdən İmadəddin Nəsiminin poeziyasındakı ritmiklik xüsusi bir ahəngdarlıqla müşayiət olunur. Bu poetik nümunələrdə daha çox diqqəti cəlb edən cəhət bundan ibarətdir ki, burada xüsusilə, dərvişlik təriqətinin tələbləri gözlənilir. Dərvişlik təriqətinin əsas tə-

²⁰ Tofiq Hacıyev. Azərbaycan ədəbi dilinin tarixi. Bakı, Elm, 2012, s. 159.

ləblərinə görə poetik nümunələrdəki ritm vasitəsi ilə çox güclü avazlanma yaradılır. Belə ki, şeirin misraları həmahəng olaraq bir yox, bir neçə ritmik musiqiliklə müşayiət edilir. Yəni poetik nümunə ayrı-ayrı avazlanma ilə bir-birindən maraqlı ritmlə musiqisiz musiqi yaradır. Dərvişlik orta əsrlərdə formalaşmağa və yayılmağa başlayıb. Dərvişlər diyar-diyar gəzib mərsiyə oxuyublar. Onlar hər zaman özlərini Allah-taalanın, Peyğəmbərin və əhli-beytin mərsiyyəçiləri sayıblar. İslam ölkələrində dərvişlik ayrıca bir təriqət hesab olunur. *Dərviş* sözü fars mənşəlidir, mənası *qapı-qapı gəzən* deməkdir. Dərvişlər sədəqə toplamır, özlərini daim nəfsdən uzaqda saxlayırlar. Onlar yoxsulluğa qane olurlar, könül zənginliyinə malik olmağı üstün tuturlar. Dillərində "İlahi, yoxsulluğu mənə xoş et!" nidasını səsləndirirlər. Faniliyə meyli olurlar. Evlənmişlər, ailə həyatı qurmurlar (Ədəbiyyatdakı Fərhad, Məcnun kimi obrazlar dərvişliyin təcəssümündən ibarətdir). Dərvişlər və ya dərviş obrazları səhranı insan cəmiyyətindən uzaq və nəfsdən kənar bir məkan kimi qəbul edirlər. Ona görə də onlar səhraya, nəfsdən uzaq məkana meyl göstərilər. Dərvişlərə görə nəfsdən uzaq olan yer Allahın məkanı nümunəsindədir. Onların əqidəsi budur ki, nəfsdən uzaq olub dünya nemətlərinə meyl göstərməmək mənəvi saflığa dəlalət edir. Dərvişlər Allahın vüsəlinə qovuşmaqdan ötrü nəfsdən uzaq olmağı vacib bir əməl hesab etmişlər. Dərvişlər müxtəlif olur:

Rifailər- oxumağa

Mövləvilər - dairə vurmağa

İsəvilər- tullanmaq hərəkətinə

Şubailər- rəqsə üstünlük verirlər

Onların özlərinə məxsus ədəb-ərkan qaydaları var: 1) nəfsin arzularına hakim olurlar; 2) ölçülü və intizamlı yaşayıblar; 3) səbr və dözümlülük onlar üçün əsas şərt olub. Dərvişlik, əslində, maddi aləmdən ruhi aləmə atılan mənəvi addım olub; 4) dərvişlər saat əqrəbinin əksinə fırlanıblar ki, göy cismlərinin hərəkətlərini təqlid etsinlər. Paltarları uzun, saç-saqqallı, çirkli olub. Onlar üçün əsas görkəm daximi aləmin saf (nəfsdən uzaq) olmasıdır. Klassik şairlərdə - Rumidə, Yunis İmrədə, Şəms Təbrididə, Nəbatidə dərvişlik motivləri güclü olmuşdur. Dərvişlərin oxuduqları mərsiyələrdə ritmiklik və oynaqlıq öz vüsəti ilə diqqəti cəlb edir. Onlar yaratdıqları poetik nümunələrdə ritmiklik üçün paralelizmin ənənələrindən çox səmərəli şəkildə istifadə edirlər. Poetik yaradıcılığında dərvişlik motivləri güclü olan Seyid Əbülqasim Nəbatidən bir nümunəni buna misal kimi göstərmək olar:

Güşeyi vəhdət nə əzəb cə imiş

Sirri-nihan onda hüveyda imiş

Gah ağıllı, gah divanə oldum

Gah abad, gah viranə oldum.

Gah xarabat içində oldum

Gah da meyxana süpürgəçisi oldum.

Poetik nümunələrdə paralelizm hesabına yaradılan ritmikliyin ən bariz nümunələrini İmadəddin Nəsimidə görmək mümkündür. Nəsimi elə bir ritm yaradır ki, onu tək bircə avazla yox, bir neçə avazla səsləndirmək mümkün olur.

Hər bir avazlanma müvafiq olaraq oynaqlıq və həzinlik yaradır. Qəzəlin misraları hecalarla elə qurulur ki, oynaqlıq, ritmiklik və həzinlik bu hecalara görə tənzim olunur. iri hecalardakı ritm və oynaqlıq hecaların xırdalanmasına uyğun olaraq həzinliyə çevrilir. Hətta bu qəzəlin avazlanmasını iki hecalılıqdan bir hecalılığa da keçirmək mümkündür ki, bu halda həzinlik daha da artmış olur. Hecaları çoxaltdıqda isə həzinlik ritmə və oynaqlığa çevrilə-çevrilə artır.

Birdən-birə bu qəzəli bir heca üstündə səsləndirdikdə ritm həmin an həzinliyə çevrilir:

Ey-ə-zə-li ca-ni-ilə ca-na-nı-mız

Eş-qü-rü-xün-dür -bə-di-ca-nı-mız

Kə-bə-ü-zün-dür-bi-zə-ey-dil-rü-ba

Zül-fü-rü-xün-qib-lə-vü-i-ma-nı-mız

Can-ne-cə-tərk-eylə-sin-ey-can-səni

Ca-nı-mı-zın-ca-nı-san-ey-ca-nı-mız
Ey-nü-mə-sən-siz-ti-kan-ol-du-ca-han
Qan-da-san-ey-ta-zə-gü-lüs-ta-nı-mız
Çün-ki-yü-zün-əh-sə-ni-təq-vim-i-miş
Sən-də-zü-hur-ey-lə-di-süb-ha-nı-mız

Nəsiminin “Mən mülki-cahan...” başlıqlı qəzəlinə paralelizmin daha maraqlı bir mənzərəsini görmək olur. Burada həm sözəvvəli fonetik təkrarların işlənməsi ilə həm də misradaxili təkrarlar vasitəsi ilə çox güclü və təsirli poetik paralelizm yaradılır:

Mən mülki cahan, cahan mənəm mən
Mən həqqə məkan, məkan mənəm mən
Mən ərş ilə fərşü kafü nunəm
Mən şərhi bəyan bəyan mənəm mən
Mən kövni məkanü kün-fəkanəm
Bil gil ki, nişan, nişan mənəm mən
Mən surəti mənidə həqəm, həq
Mən həqqi-əyan, əyan mənəm mən
Mən nəqşü xəyalü xəttü xaləm
Mən hərfü lisan, lisan mənəm, mən
İnsanü bəşərsən ey Nəsimi
Həq der ki, həman, həman mənəm mən

Şah İsmayıl Xətayidən yadigar qalan poetik nümunələrdə parleliyin maraqlı digər bir növünə təsadüf edilir. Bu da söz əvvəlində ənənəvi qayda üzrə fonetik vahidlərin təkrarı deyil, qafiyələrin özünün misra əvvəlinə çıxarılmasından ibarətdir. Bu halda sözün əvvəlinin ritmiklik baxımından daha maraqlı bir avazlanma ilə müşayiət edilməsinə gətirib çıxarır:

Dil ilə dərvişlik olmaz

Halı gərək yol əhlinin

Arıların hər çiçəkdən

Balı gərək yol əhlinin

Mən gəzərəm ayıq-ayıq

Başqa bir gəryalıda da başlanğıc sözlərin qafiyələnməsinə təsadüf olunur:

Gövhərin keçməyən yerdə

Satma qardaş, kərəm eylə

Ləl daşını çay daşına

Qatma, qardaş, kərəm eylə

Gördüm bir yerdə aşına

Hər nə dersən öz başına.

Azərbaycan dilinin yazılı ənənələrində ifadə zənginliyinin və nitq mədəniyyətinin inkişafı baxımından Füzuli mərhələsi xüsusi bir yer tutur. Bu mərhələdə yazı dilinə ərəb-fars sözlərinin qatışıqı əvvəlki dövrlərdəkindən heç də az olmamışdır. Hərçənd ki, Füzuli öz yaradıcılığında bir çox ərəb-fars izafətlərini Azərbaycan dili variantları ilə əvəzləndirmişdi. Bu əvəzlənmələrdə əsas dəyişmə analitik quruluşlu izafətin aqlütinativ quruluşlu söz birləşməsinə çevrilməsidir. Mümkün olduğu halda isə söz birləşməsi tərkibindəki bu və ya digər komponentin Azərbaycan dili variantı ilə verilməsi müşahidə edilir:

a) analitik quruluşdan aqlütinativ quruluşa keçirilənlər:

hali-pərişan- pərişan hal, dərdi-eşq- eşq dərdi, bərgi-gül- gül bərgi, atəşi-eşq- eşq atəşi, xabi-əcəl-əcəl xabi, əhli-nəzər - nəzər əhli, tiği-cafa- cafa tiği, hali-müşkül- müşkül hal, əhli-zövq - zövq əhli, qabili-dərman- dərmana qabil, zövqi-eşq- eşq zövqü, tənəyi-əğyar-əğyar təni, vəsli-yar- yar vəsli, əhli-dərd- dərd əhli, rıştəyi-can-can rıştəsi, mahi-ruzə- ruzə ayyamı, dərdi-pinhan- pinhan dərd, zöv-

qi-eşq- eşq zövqü, nəqdi-can- can nəqdi, əhli-eşq-eşq əhli, yadi-vətən- vətən yadı, təriqi-eşq- eşq təriqi.

b) tərkibdəki ərəb-fars sözlərinin Azərbaycan dili qarşılığı ilə əvəzləndirilənlər:

Şəbi-hicran, hicran gecəsi, səngi-mələmət- mələmət daşı, mürği-dil- könüm quşu, xaki-məqdam-ayağın tozu, mahi-nov-yeni ay, mərdümi-çəşm- göz mərdümü.

Füzuli dövrünün yazı dilində ərəb-fars sözləri bol-bol işlədilməsi anlaşıqda çətinlik yaratmasına baxmayaraq Füzuli dili özünün ecazkarlığı ilə bu çətinlikləri şimşək kimi yarıb keçirdi. Ancaq, əlbəttə ki, ərəb-fars sözlərinin çoxluğu hətta ecazkar Füzuli dilinin kütləviləşməsi qarşısında bir əngələ çevrilmişdi. Füzuli özü bu vəziyyəti təsəvvüründə canlandıraraq belə deyirdi:

Ol səbəbdən farsı ləfzilə çoxdur nəzm kim
Nəzmi-nazik türk ləfzi ilə ikən düşvar olur
Ləhceyi-türki qəbuli-nəzmi-tərkib etməyib
Əksərən əlfazi namərbutü nahəmvar olur.
Məndə tovfıq olsa da düşvari asan eylərəm
Növbəhar olğac tikəndən bərgi-gül izhar olur.

Füzuli deyir ki, “Məndə qabiliyyət, bacarıq, imkan olsa” o çətinliyi asanlaşdıraram. Doğrudur, Füzuli öz poeziyası ilə bənzərsiz bədii nümunələr yaratdı. Ancaq dili asanlaşdırıb onu kütləviləşdirmək üçün sabit norma yaratmaq tələbi Füzulinin imkanları çərçivəsində deyildi. Yazılı dilin sabit qaydalar üzrə normalaşması imkanları o zaman baş tuta bilir ki, dil rəsmiyyətdə işlənmiş olsun. Dilin rəsmiyyətə çevrilməsi üçün də müstəqil dövlətçiliyin mövcudluğu vacibdir. Əks halda yazılı dilin rəsmiyyətindən danışmaq mənasızdır. Füzuli yazılı dilin normalarına müdaxilə edə bilməsə də qədim türk poetik ənənələrini ustalıqla davam etdirərək çox müxtəlif üsullarla ən rəngarəng ritmik nümunələr yaratmağa müvəffəq olmuşdur.

Füzuli dilində ritmiklik yaratmaq üçün istifadə olunan vasitələrin hər biri sanki zərgər dəqiqliyi ilə ölçülü-biçilidir. Bunlar tək-cə forma və texniki cəhətdən yox, məna, məzmun və məntiq cəhətdən də bir-birini tamamlayır. Görkəmli Füzuli tədqiqatçısı Mir Cəlal yazır ki, “Şair öz dövrünün bütün böyük şairlərini və böyük əsərlərini mükəmməl bildiyi kimi, klassik şeirin bütün sənətkarlıq sirlərini, bütün şeir, nəzm, nəsir texnikasını və quruluşunu da kamil bilirdi. O şeirdə məzmunu, məna-naya üstünlük verməklə formanın, bədii dil, üslub kamilliyinin zəruri şərt olduğunu təkidlə qeyd etmişdir. Füzuli heç bir yerdə heç bir şeirdə məna ilə şəkil vəhdətini pozmamış, bu vəhdəti bədiiyin əsas şərti saymışdır”.²¹

RESUME

The state language is a necessary information mechanism regulated by statehood. If there is statehood, we can talk about the development, formation and internal norms of the language. The support, structure and legal base of the language that develops it meaningfully is statehood. This means that if there is no statehood, there is no state language. Statehood In the absence of a language, it is deprived of a legal basis. Also, There are many differences in the information space where the language exists.

The conditions of independent statehood are a fertile ground for multi-fold revitalization of the flexible mechanism of our mother tongue and expansion of its functions. As our independent statehood flourishes, our mother tongue will also be enriched and will successfully overcome all the obstacles in front of it to enter the world arena.

²¹ Mir Cəlal. Füzuli sənətkarlığı. Bakı, 1958, s. 91.

By promoting the mother tongue as the state language, Heydar Aliyev saw the independence, freedom, and sovereignty of Azerbaijan behind it. Life proved that Heydar Aliyev assessed the future correctly and correctly.

Today, the task is to achieve the implementation of Heydar Aliyev's program in the development of the mother tongue at the level of the state language.

The state language is an important field of activity for every nation for its existence. However, there are independent states in the world that do not have a program to develop the state language. Therefore, the activity of the national language in such states is limited to covering internal information.

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Agricultural Sciences

АГРОХИМИЧЕСКОЕ КАРТИРОВАНИЕ ПОЧВ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ УДОБРЕНИЙ В ЗАСУШЛИВОЙ СТЕПИ СЕВЕРНОГО КАЗАХСТАНА

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Аннотация: Результаты агрохимического обследования почв позволяют оценить обеспеченность зональных южных черноземов основными элементами питания, что дает возможность хозяйству применять экономически оправданные дозы минеральных удобрений для получения запланированного урожая сельскохозяйственных культур. Агрохимические картограммы способствуют более рациональному использованию удобрений на каждом поле с учетом его расположения в севообороте, технологии обработки почвы и предшественника, а также целенаправленно доводить содержание элементов питания в почве до оптимального уровня.

Ключевые слова: агрохимическое обследование почв, гумус, нитратный азот, подвижный фосфор, доступный калий, сера, реакция среды, внесение удобрений, плодородие почв.

Современное земледелие Северного Казахстана должно базироваться на устойчивых и высокопродуктивных агроценозах степной зоны [1, 2]. Теоретической и практической основой этого должны являться агроэкологическая оценка зональных черноземов и каштановых почв и агроландшафтная система земледелия [3,4]. На основе полученных данных для каждого агроландшафта проектируется адаптивно обоснованная агротехнология возделывания сельскохозяйственных культур [5]. Разработанные агротехнологии могут быть нескольких уровней (экстенсивная, полунтенсивная, интенсивная) в зависимости от экономического состояния хозяйства.

Однако все технологии требуют агрохимического сопровождения с использованием минеральных удобрений. Поэтому для научно обоснованного внесения минеральных удобрений необходимо обязательное проведение агрохимического обследования каждого поля или участка пашни [6]. При этом рациональное применение удобрений обеспечит не только рост продуктивности агроценозов, но и будет способствовать воспроизводству эффективного плодородия почв [7].

В связи с этим, Исследовательский центр ТОО «Агрохимическая Компания Даркан Дала» (г. Костанай) в весенний период 2023 года провел агрохимическое обследование почв КХ «Гейко Ю.Г.», расположенного в засушливой степи Карасуского района Костанайской области. Почвенный покров пашни представлен черноземами южными карбонатными, солонцеватыми и карбонатно-солонцеватыми разностями, что накладывает определённый отпечаток на своеобразие агрохимических свойств.

Агрохимическое картирование проводилось по утвержденным правилам с сеткой элементарных участков площадью 25 га [8]. С каждого элементарного участка отбиралась одна объединенная проба из 15 точечных отборов мощностью 0-30 см. Агрохимические анализы проводились в каждой пробе с последующим усреднением по соответствующим методикам:

- ГОСТ 26213-91. Почвы. Методы определения органического вещества;
 - ГОСТ 26483-85. Почвы. Приготовление солевой вытяжки и определение ее pH по методу ЦИНАО;
 - ГОСТ 26488-85. Почвы. Определение нитратов по методу ЦИНАО;
 - ГОСТ 26205-91. Почвы. Определение подвижных соединений фосфора и калия по методу Мачигина в модификации ЦИНАО;
 - ГОСТ 26490-85. Почвы. Определение подвижной серы по методу ЦИНАО.
- Ниже приводится агрохимическая характеристика почвенного покрова хозяйства.

Таблица 1 – Содержание гумуса и подвижных элементов питания в слое 0-30 см

Гумус, %	pH _{сол}	Содержание, мг/кг почвы			
		N-NO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	SO ₄
Поле 8, площадь 40 га, среднее из 2 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,8	7,3	15,3	13,3	570	8,0
среднее	сл.щелочная	высокое	низкое	высокое	среднее
Поле 11, площадь 46 га, среднее из 2 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,8	7,3	8,7	20,4	936	7,6
низкое	сл.щелочная	низкое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 17, площадь 310 га, среднее из 19 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,4	7,2	9,0	21,1	821	9,2
среднее	сл.щелочная	низкое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 19, площадь 17 га, из 1 почвенной пробы (среднее из 15 точек)					
3,9	7,5	7,6	12,8	762	8,9
низкое	сл.щелочная	низкое	низкое	оч. высокое	среднее

Поле 26, площадь 63 га, среднее из 3 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,7	7,4	12,9	26,3	846	11,0
низкое	сл.щелочная	среднее	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 27, площадь 160 га, среднее из 7 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,0	7,3	10,0	19,2	833	7,7
низкое	сл.щелочная	низкое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 33, площадь 120 га, среднее из 5 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,8	7,5	11,1	11,7	607	5,6
низкое	сл.щелочная	среднее	низкое	оч. высокое	низкое
Поле 35, площадь 34 га, среднее из 2 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,0	7,5	11,2	13,8	706	9,3
низкое	сл.щелочная	среднее	низкое	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 35-1, площадь 120 га, среднее из 2 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,9	7,5	9,4	14,0	650	8,4
низкое	сл.щелочная	низкое	низкое	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 35-2, площадь 193 га, среднее из 8 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,0	7,6	10,2	14,5	614	6,0
низкое	сл.щелочная	среднее	низкое	оч. высокое	низкое
Поле 36, площадь 160 га, среднее из 7 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,9	7,5	8,8	16,3	824	6,7
низкое	сл.щелочная	низкое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 36-1, площадь 80 га, среднее из 4 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,9	7,4	8,8	19,9	821	8,9
низкое	сл.щелочная	низкое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 36-2, площадь 39 га, среднее из 2 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					

4,2	7,4	8,2	25,3	809	5,0
среднее	сл.щелочная	низкое	среднее	оч. высокое	низкое
Поле 36-3, площадь 160 га, среднее из 7 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,2	7,4	7,4	16,1	787	6,5
среднее	сл.щелочная	низкое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 47, площадь 120 га, среднее из 5 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,1	7,4	16,8	15,1	835	9,4
среднее	сл.щелочная	высокое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 50-51, площадь 725 га, среднее из 29 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
4,3	7,3	10,6	19,7	850	8,0
среднее	сл.щелочная	среднее	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее
Поле 62, площадь 517 га, среднее из 21 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,7	7,5	15,8	16,5	622	7,1
низкое	сл.щелочная	высокое	среднее	оч. высокое	среднее

Анализ агрохимических показателей позволяет сделать следующие общие выводы.

Низкое содержание гумуса отмечается на полях № 11, 19, 26, 27, 33, 35, 35-1, 35-2, 36, 36-1, 62, где его величина варьирует от 3,7 до 4,0%. Клетки № 8, 17, 36-2, 36-3, 47, 50-51 имеют среднее количество гумуса – 4,1...4,8%. В целом, поля хозяйства характеризуются достаточно выравненной степенью гумусированности. Если учесть, что оптимальное содержание органического вещества для черноземов южных Костанайской области составляет 3,6 % и более, то все поля хозяйства соответствуют этому требованию. При таком содержании гумуса черноземы южные обладают высоким потенциальным и эффективным плодородием, которое проявляется в формировании благоприятных водно-физических (влагоемкость, плотность сложения, водопроницаемость) и физико-химических свойств (емкость поглощения, реакция почвенного раствора, буферная способность). Поэтому на этих полях с высокой эффективностью можно применять различные минеральные удобрения и агротехнологии возделывания сельскохозяйственных культур (минимально-нулевая, минимальная, разноглубинная безотвальная, отвально-плоскорезная). Однако, если на отдельных полях присутствуют западины, лиманы, понижения, затапливаемые талыми водами, рекомендуется применять разноглубинную безотвальную технологию обработки почвы. Это снизит ее плотность, повысит водопроницаемость и позволит избежать дальнейшего роста отрицательных форм рельефа. Не менее эффективна данная технология будет и на почвах солонцового комплекса или солонцовых пятнах. На таких почвах также можно проводить агротехническую самомелиорацию и землевание. Плужную

обработку лучше применять в паровом поле против малолетних сорняков, пырея ползучего и дифференциации пахотного слоя по плодородию.

Для всех почв хозяйства характерна слабощелочная реакция почвенной среды с величиной pH 7,2...7,6, что является следствием карбонатности и солонцеватости местных черноземов. Подщелачивание почвенного раствора происходит как за счет бикарбонатов кальция, так и обменного натрия в почвенном поглощающем комплексе. Поэтому длительное применение физиологически кислых простых и сложных минеральных удобрений не приведет к отрицательному эффекту. В целом, реакция почвенного раствора является благоприятной для всех возделываемых культур в хозяйстве (зерновые, масличные, зернобобовые и крупяные).

В период посева низкую обеспеченность нитратным азотом, от 7,4 до 10,0 мг/кг, имеет большая часть полей: № 11, 17, 19, 27, 35-1, 36, 36-1, 36-2, 36-3. Учитывая, что оптимальной величиной содержания азота для черноземов южных перед посевом считается 15 мг/кг, то рекомендуется внесение азотных удобрений при посеве зерновых, масличных и даже зернобобовых культур (аммиачная селитра, мочевины, КАС-32, сульфаммофос). Необходимо также предусмотреть азотные некорневые подкормки мочевиной или КАС в период вегетации растений, особенно зерновых культур.

Поля № 26, 33, 35, 35-2, 50-51 имеют среднее содержание азота – 10,2-12,9 мг/кг, что свидетельствует о хорошей нитрификационной способности южных черноземов. Вместе с тем эти величины не достигают оптимального уровня, поэтому припосевное внесение азотных удобрений здесь также обязательно под все культуры (кроме зернобобовых).

Для полей № 8, 47, 62 характерно высокое количество нитратного азота -15,3...16,8 мг/кг, что объясняется или наличием предшественника (паровое поле, зернобобовая культура, ранняя отвальная зябь) или дозой азотных удобрений, внесенной при посеве. Поэтому дополнительного применения азотных удобрений здесь не требуется.

По содержанию доступного фосфора поля № 8, 19, 33, 35, 35-1, 35-2 имеют низкую степень обеспеченности – 11,7...14,5 мг/кг. Для клеток № 11, 17, 26, 27, 36, 36-1, 36-2, 36-3, 47, 50-51, 62 характерно среднее содержание этого элемента – 15,1...26,3 мг/кг.

Учитывая, что на всех полях содержание фосфора не достигает оптимального уровня - 30 мг/кг, необходимо обязательное ежегодное внесение в рядки при посеве культур сложных фосфорсодержащих удобрений (аммофос, сульфаммофос, ЖКУ азотно-фосфорное, диаммофос). Лучшим вариантом является основное (допосевное) внесение этих удобрений осенью или весной в дозе P40-60 кг д.в./га, а также в паровое поле.

Все поля хозяйства содержат очень высокое количество доступного калия – 607...936 мг/кг, что является зональной особенностью тяжелых по гранулометрическому составу южных черноземов степной зоны, которые сформировались на почвообразующих породах с высоким содержанием калийсодержащих минералов. Исключение составляет клетка № 8, где количество калия несколько ниже (570 мг/кг) и оценивается как высокое, что связано, скорее всего, с облегчением механического состава до среднесуглинистого.

Оптимальное содержание подвижного калия для черноземов южных составляет не менее 410 мг/кг. Поэтому необходимость в калийных удобрениях под зерновые, зернобобовые и масличные культуры отсутствует. Можно предусмотреть лишь под высокоурожайные и высокостебельные гибриды подсолнечника рядковое внесение нитроаммофоски (калий хлористый или диаммофоска) в дозе по калию 20 кг д.в./га.

Количество подвижной серы практически на всех полях хозяйства оценивается как среднее – 6,5...11,0 мг/кг. Низкое ее содержание (5,0-6,0 мг/кг) имеют только три поля - № 33, 35-2 и 36-2. Поэтому острой необходимости в применении серосодержащих удобрений нет. Можно лишь предусмотреть внесение сульфаммофоса в рядки 100 кг/га физического веса при выращивании наиболее требовательных масличных (подсолнечник, рапс, лен) и

зернобобовых (горох, нут, чечевица) культур, особенно при планировании высокой их урожайности.

Таким образом, результаты агрохимического обследования почв позволяют оценить обеспеченность зональных южных черноземов основными элементами питания, что дает возможность хозяйству применять экономически оправданные дозы минеральных удобрений для получения запланированного урожая сельскохозяйственных культур. Агрохимические картограммы способствуют более рациональному использованию удобрений на каждом поле с учетом его расположения в севообороте, технологии обработки почвы и предшественника, а также целенаправленно доводить содержание элементов питания в почве до оптимального уровня.

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The influence of various doses of mineral fertilizers and biologically active substances on the yield of Dutch indeterminate tomato Torero in the conditions of BRB APK LLP, Almaty region

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Tomato is one of the main vegetable crops. Tomato occupies about 2.7 million hectares in the world. The share of the crop in global vegetable production is 14.3% [4]. The main advantages of tomato are its high content of vitamins, minerals, organic acids, carbohydrates and especially carotenoids, which are so necessary for the normal functioning of the human body. Every year the area under tomato grows, its growing technology is improved, in particular, new industrial technologies for its production are developed, and profitability increases. A balanced mineral nutrition system plays a major role in increasing tomato yields. Recently, the size of greenhouses in our country has increased dramatically. According to the information of the RK ASM, the area of greenhouse vegetables is currently 576 ha. 230 ha of it is a high-tech greenhouse. Although the total production of greenhouse vegetables has reached 90,000 tons, it covers only 69% of the domestic needs of the country during the summer season.

For this reason, the government is creating the necessary conditions for the development of the production of dairy products and reducing the amount of taxes. Currently, the consumption of fresh and processed vegetable garden products in the country is on average 3.2 million tons per year. In it, the share of tax is about 7%. Cultivation of vegetable crops in a greenhouse is one of the most developing branches of agriculture today. Therefore, studying the timing, type and quantity of mineral fertilizers, especially biologically active substances, allows to obtain a high yield from the tomato crop. The role of biologically active substances in the quality of the product is more important than other nutritional elements. Therefore, one of the main elements of tomato cultivation technology is the use of fertilizers with rational biologically active substances that ensure high quality and productivity.

The purpose of the research was to study the effectiveness of using various doses of mineral fertilizers with biologically active substances in the technology of growing tomatoes in protected soil. Scientific and research activities are carried out in the greenhouse complex of LLP "BRB APK", the total area of which is 17 hectares (12 hectares of which are actual agricultural useful area, the remaining 5 hectares are for agricultural property use). It was carried out in an indoor greenhouse. "BRB APK" LLP is located in the territory of Alatau district, in the western outskirts of Almaty city, in the new industrial zone. 7.8 billion of JSC "KazAgroFinance" JSC holding within "KazAgroKazhy" JSC. started its first economic activity in 2016-2017 with financing in the amount of tenge. The

plant is located in the Alatau district of southern Atana and is planned to produce 3.2 thousand tons of tomatoes and 4 thousand tons of cucumbers per year. The production uses the technology of the Dutch Dalsem company. About 150 people work at the workplace now. The product of the complex is cucumbers and tomatoes, which are directed to the domestic market, as well as to the markets of neighboring Russia.

According to the director of "BRB APK" LLP Nurlan Adilkhan, 20 tons of cucumbers and 15-20 tons of tomatoes are being produced in the greenhouse. In our research, there were tomato hybrids of the Dutch-style greenhouse complex of Alatau district, bred with Dutch technology. In the experiment, Dutch Toro wheat was used for greenhouse planting. Since the quantity of the obtained product depends on the size of the seed sown, before sowing, the seed material of greenhouse cucumbers undergoes a special preparation.

Since these hybrids are a product of the Dutch company "Rijk Zwaan", which is a special breeder and distributes seeds all over the world, all work on seed preparation is included. Igen, i.e., high-quality, guaranteed for growth and productivity, treated against all diseases and pests in the seed, which has undergone heat treatment, is considered to be filled with oxygen.

2 Methodology: The object of research was imported as well as locally produced organic substrates. Hybrids of Dutch greenhouse tomatoes were taken for the experiment.

The production uses the technology of the Dutch Dalsem company. The experiment was conducted with small-scale hydroponics technology in a winter greenhouse built with the help of the company.

We conducted research using laboratory and laboratory-field experiment method. While performing the work, we made a number of calculations and observed the development of plants growing on different substrates. We determined the water-physical properties of the studied substrates (bulk weight, specific gravity, hygroscopic moisture, total moisture capacity) according to the methods written in the soil science workshop. We conducted phenological observations according to the form adopted by the state variety test. After sowing the seeds, the following phenophases are started and passed - the first one is the budding phase, the beginning of flowering, the formation of productive organs, the whiteness of the fruits, the brownness of the fruits, the phase of harvesting the first and last harvest.

To analyze the biological value of tomato fruit, we took average samples. We determined the amount of ascorbic acid according to the research method, titratable acidity and sugar according to the micromodification of the Bertrand method.

Determination of nitrates was carried out by the ionometric method. Determination of the amount of zinc, copper, lead and cadmium in tomato fruit was carried out by the inversion-voltammeter method.

Mathematical processing of the received performance data was carried out by the method of dispersion analysis, finding the accuracy of the experiment and the clarity of the product margin. The performance obtained during the research is recorded in a special journal. Research work was carried out in a winter greenhouse.

We determined the agrotechnical characteristics of the experimental samples according to the agro-references for growing tomatoes in greenhouses. The hybrids that were killed and studied at the farm are one of the leading teams in the world for the production and breeding of the "Rijk Zwaan" company. They not only produce seeds, but also massively update the advanced technologies of cutting weeds, adapt to the local conditions in open and closed soils all over the world. It is involved in heating and processing of vegetable seeds, as well as lifting and bulk selling. Rijk Zwaan is a Dutch seed producer company. Rijk Zwaan is among the top 5 companies in the world for the production of vegetable seeds. I will dwell on the hybrid characteristics of a few tomato plants grown in the greenhouse complex of Alatau district, which is the city of Almaty. The

first variety is a large-fruited tomato variety, which gives a high yield for farms throughout the year, is economically efficient, and is very popular in the market. was able to mold the mold.

Torero is a Dutch large-fruited, indeterminate breed. Three different amounts of phosphoric fertilizer and biologically active Vermigumat were given to the experimented tomato bunch. Vermigumat is a complex microbiological organ-mineral liquid concentrated fertilizer, extracted from vermicompost, enriched with nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, sodium, magnesium, calcium, manganese, boron, water. Vermigumat increases plant immunity, seed germination and growth energy. Restores the balance of micro and macro elements. Forms a strong root system, stimulates the process of photosynthesis. Reduces the cooking time. Increases product quantity, quality and shelf life. Protects the plant from diseases and pests. Vermigumat 0.01% was given by foliar and stem spraying. The first sample point is the point (P) given in the dimensions that are regularly used in the economy. The second point is a given point with two more dimensions than the sample point (Px2). The third point is a point given two times less than the sample point (P/2). As shown in the example shown in the evening, the amount of phosphorus fertilizer poured into the bed is 120 mg per liter, 140 mg in the pre-flowering period, and then in two periods. n 129 mg/l, 5-10-12 fruiting period 161 mg/l, from the productive period 129 mg per liter of water until the end of the life of the plant, and 129 mg, 161 mg, 161 mg and 129 mg/l of phosphorous element in the following periods, respectively. And, in the second point (Px2) more phosphorus ions were supplied from the sample point. The third point, P/2, showed its effects on the samples taken from this sample point.

The tomato crop in the greenhouse complex of Alatau district is rotated once throughout the year, that is, from the middle of the summer, the tomato vines germinated and produced crops even in the summer months. Although significant changes have their own differences in terms of weather and climate conditions, the climatic conditions are the same because all conditions in this greenhouse are controlled by humans. it can be said that it was normal. Therefore, when we come to the cycle period, the application of fertilizers is set at the same level.

3. Research results On the basis of the data of the experiment, the difference between the biomechanics of tomato and fruit mechanics was confirmed. After the seedlings were placed on the nutrient substrate, according to the cuttings taken for the study, the requirement for the study of the nutrient solution was done. As shown in the evening, the length of the pattern of the tree is moving normally at one point, the average over the month is longer than 88 cm, at the second point Px2 the average over the months is 9 It grew by 5 cm, and when the third point was in P/2, it grew by 58 cm in a week. . In the first sampling point, the average fruit weight of 235 g was 84 pieces, the second point Px2 was 92 pieces of fruit, on average 240 g. The third point was P/2 and gave 24 fruits of 221 grams each. Toward the end of the cycle, the phosphorus fertilizer stopped producing at the third point P/2, which was already given less. Young shoots withered and fell from the fruit tree, and the coloration of the length of the shoot stopped, dry, yellow spots appeared on the surface of the leaf, the condition of the leaf It got worse every time.

The lowest amount of ascorbic acid in tomato fruit was in the version grown on mineral substrates - 18.75 mg%, and the highest was in the mineral version (22.13 mg%). The minimum amount of ascorbic acid was 21.61 mg% in the phosphorus version grown on substrates, and the highest in the double phosphorus version (23.43 mg%). The lowest amount of total acidity in tomato fruits was in the mineral version when grown on substrates - 0.32%, and the highest was revealed in the version sprayed with vermigumat (0.53%). When tomatoes were grown on organic substrates, the minimum amount of acidity in the fruit was 0.32%, and the maximum was observed in the phosphorus sample (0.46%).

According to SanPiN - 42-123-4619-88 and SanPiN 4.01.71.03, the permissible level of nitrates for tomatoes in protected soil is 300 mg/kg. As you can see, the amount of nitrate in

tomato fruits grown on different backgrounds was 8.8-9.2 times lower than the maximum possible concentration.

Table 1- Effect of vermigumat 0.01% and phosphoric fertilizers on plant growth and yield

1	Option	Sample Option (P2O5-)+ Vermigumat 0.01%								
2	Months	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June
3	plant growth, m	0,7	1,44	2,35	3,45	4,43	5,48	6,47	7,59	8,8
4	Fruit stem, wise	0	0	2	6	10	15	19	23	28
5	fruit number, wise	0	0	0	9	15	19	15	18	8
6	Weight of fruit, kg	0	0	0	2,205	3,525	4,427	3,465	4,158	1,920
7	Option	Twice as much phosphorous points Px2 (P2O5-)+ Vermigumat 0.01%								
8	plant growth, m	0,73	1,48	2,43	3,50	4,62	5,69	6,62	7,78	9,03
9	Fruit stem, wise	0	0	3	6	12	14	21	26	31
10	fruit number, wise	0	0	0	9	16	21	17	20	7
11	Weight of fruit, kg	0	0	0	2,277	4,0	5,208	4,216	4,800	1,499
12	Option	Phosphorus ion double point P/2(P2O5-)+ Vermigumat 0.01%								
13	plant growth, m	0,71	1,37	2,01	2,85	3,57	4,20	4,85	5,40	5,92
14	Fruit stem, wise	0	0	2	5	8	10	11	12	13
15	fruit number, wise	0	0	0	3	12	6	2	1	0
16	Weight of fruit, kg	0	0	0	0,720	2,814	1,255	0,371	0,182	0

Table 2- Dry matter, sugar, acids, nitrates and metals in the solution of vermigumat 0.01% and phosphorus fertilizers, 2022

Option	Dry matter, %	Sugar %	Ascorbic acid mg%	Total acidity according to malic acid,%	Nitrates , mg/kg	Zinc, mg/kg	Copper mg/kg	Plumbum mg/kg	Cadmium mg/kg
Sample Option (P2O5-)+ Vermigumat 0.01%	4,0	2,83	22,13	0,32	37,1	1,06	0,71	Not found	Not found
	4,4	2,58	18,75	0,36	33,9	1,12	0,78	Not found	Not found
Twice as much phosphorus points Px2 (P2O5-)+ Vermigumat 0.01%	4,8	3,38	20,83	0,53	34,6	1,08	0,70	Not found	Not found
	4,4	2,68	20,05	0,45	34,6	1,18	0,75	Not found	Not found
Phosphorus ion double point P/2(P2O5-)+ Vermigumat 0.01%	4,8	2,68	21,61	0,32	33,9	1,13	0,68	Not found	Not found
	4,4	2,68	22,92	0,43	32,3	1,20	0,75	Not found	Not found
	4,4	3,08	23,43	0,46	33,9	1,11	0,73	Not found	Not found

5. Conclusion Thus, according to the results of the study, the variant twice as much phosphorus Px2 (P2O5-)+ Vermigumat 0.01% is highlighted, since the growth of tomatoes was 90.3 cm, and the weight of the fruit was greater compared to other options and amounted to more than 220 g. According to the quantitative criterion of quality and quantity of fruits, this version of the experiment has the best results.

Sociological Sciences

Духовная культура молодежи как объект социально-философского исследования

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Аннотация: В статье обсуждается развитие культуры понимания социофилософских аспектов духовной культуры молодежи, то есть понятий, терминов, используемых ими, различие между духовными категориями.

Ключевые слова: молодежь, духовность, культура, национальные и религиозные взгляды, когнитивная культура, политическая культура, нравственная культура, правовая культура, эстетическая культура.

Динамика социокультурных трансформаций в современном обществе существенно повлияла на духовную жизнь общества и вызвала изменения в ценностных ориентациях человека и его духовном бытии, что привело к повышению интереса к изучению феномена духовной культуры современности. Проблема духовной культуры общества приобретает особое значение в контексте понимания проблем глобализации современного мира и их влияния на традиционные ценности. Информационные технологии и средства массовой коммуникации изменили духовную основу жизни современного человека, его духовную культуру, приведя к негативным процессам в духовной сфере. Конец XX-начало XXI веков ознаменовались системными преобразованиями в казахстанском обществе, которые неизбежно привели к смене ценностных приоритетов в духовной культуре россиян, изменили представления о нравственности, порядочности или непорядочности человека, видоизменили отправную точку в оценке нравственности. В связи с этим важно понять, какие модификации характерны для духовной культуры казахского общества. Важнейшим субъектом воспроизводства духовной жизни является молодежь, существенной социокультурной характеристикой которой является способность наследовать и воспроизводить культурные образцы, трансформировать их с учетом изменившегося социального опыта на основе собственного инновационного творчества и транслировать будущим поколениям, тем самым внося свой вклад в развитие общества. Трансформационные процессы в казахстанском обществе и глобализация современного мира усложнили процессы восприятия, формирования и консолидации ценностей духовной культуры молодых казахстанцев. Молодые люди оказались на переднем крае современных противоречий. Социализируясь в условиях межкультурного столкновения и возникающей в результате неопределенности, она одновременно усваивает различные паттерны, переплетающиеся в ее сознании. В то же время, в результате активной реакции на культурные вызовы, она расширяет свои духовные потребности и интересы. В современных условиях молодой человек все чаще функционирует как автономный субъект, выбирая среди множества предлагаемых ценностей и стилей духовной жизни, что актуализирует необходимость изучения особенностей содержания этой культуры. Изучение проблем духовной культуры казахской молодежи имеет эвристическое значение в связи с

недостаточной теоретической и методологической проработанностью данной проблемы (Чен-Бук, Паттерсон, Чен, 2019).

В процессе социального развития любой страны философское мышление молодого поколения является важным фактором духовного роста завтрашнего дня. В то же время молодые люди со своей психикой, духовным обликом и нравственными идеалами того времени создают парадигмальные ситуации в существующем обществе. В процессе они столкнутся с различными противоречиями, и их философский и культурный подход к реальности будет основываться на опыте развитых стран. В обществе человеческие «знания, полученные в результате научных исследований и подтвержденные на практике, могут быть эмпирическими данными для открытия объективных законов философии и разработки общих категорий» [1,35-б.].

По мере того как молодые люди осваивают объекты философских исследований и изучают процессы действительности, они обогащают свое понимание и восприятие новых аспектов духовной культуры. Поэтому очень важно учитывать вопросы духовной культуры на будущее. Прежде всего, стремление молодых людей к инновациям, присущее духовной культуре, не должно затмевать ее свойства. Во-вторых, не должно быть никаких сомнений в содержании духовной культуры молодежи. Только тогда мы не столкнемся с определенными ситуациями, такими как хаос, произвол или открытая новая проблема. В-третьих, необходимо понимать социально-философские аспекты духовной культуры молодежи, то есть развивать культуру различения используемых ими понятий, терминов, духовных категорий. Все это может быть сведено к какому-то общему знаменателю, или это может стать общей отправной точкой для молодежной духовной культуры, общим аспектом понятий и терминов, используемых в обществе.

Также было бы ошибкой в системе большинства современных представлений в обществе утверждать, что духовная культура молодежи влияет только на положительные аспекты общественной жизни. Например, «Пресса и телеэкраны оказывают сильное влияние на понимание первоначальной идеологической модели. С прискорбием приходится констатировать, что как проявление массовой культуры некоторые киноактрисы, певицы и звезды эстрады ведут себя неприятно на телеэкранах, и их аморальные выступления не редкость в обществе, особенно сейчас. оказывает негативное влияние на пробуждающиеся умы молодых людей» [2,104-105-б.].

Однако под знаком усиления важного универсального характера в процессе современного развития феномен глобализма должен сформировать приемлемый философский подход к понятию духовной культуры молодежи. Важно разработать принципы баланса между личностью и природной средой на основе социогенеза, которого требует современность, определить правильный баланс в обществе (например, разработать современную концепцию устойчивого развития молодежи в соответствии с национальным характером государства). Все это проблемы, которые способствуют возникновению и интенсификации глобализации универсальным образом. Нам нужно уделять больше внимания проблемам молодежи в обществе, относиться к их исторически сложившимся традициям как к главному объекту философского исследования.

Только тогда «качества народа, такие как нравственность, доброта, уважение, которые проявляются в традициях народа, в процессе обрядов, играют важную роль в формировании духовности молодежи». [3,170-б.]. Поэтому целесообразно создать современную концепцию устойчивого развития духовной культуры молодежи с учетом принципа оптимальной интегрированной духовности.

Мы считаем, что создание концепции воплощает в себе многомерные компоненты, которые действительно могут обогатить духовную культуру молодежи содержанием и расширить существующие возможности. Они показывают структуру духовной культуры

молодежи. Во-первых, духовная культура молодежи включает в себя следующие компоненты: 1) когнитивная культура; 2) политическая культура; 3) нравственная культура; 4) правовая культура; 5) эстетическая культура. Духовная культура молодежи, состоящая из этих основных составляющих, интегрирована во все сферы общественной жизни человека. Прежде всего, структура и содержание духовной культуры молодежи укрепляют ценности в обществе на основе духовной интеграции знаний, потребностей, социальных норм и идеалов.

Во-вторых, духовная культура молодежи включает в себя духовное образование. В этом духовная культура и духовное образование переплетаются как цели и средства. В результате общество развивает духовное образование и становится инструментом формирования духовной культуры у молодежи. Таким образом, духовное становление общества развивается на основе новых инновационных подходов.

В-третьих, процесс духовного производства непосредственно отражается на приобретении молодыми людьми материальной культуры. «Материальная культура неотделима от духовной культуры, а духовная культура не может существовать без материальной культуры, они развиваются взаимозависимо. В процессе производства материальных благ материальная и духовная культура органично сочетаются». [4,22-23-б.]. В результате в рамках интеллектуального потенциала молодежи духовные отношения обогащаются уникальными проектами.

В то же время духовная культура молодежи и, параллельно, духовное отношение общества отражают направление, процесс, средства и результаты деятельности между субъектом и объектом.

Духовная культура - это деятельность человеческого разума и духовное творчество, сохранение самого человечества и поколений, решение социально-духовных кризисов, возникающих в общественной жизни, создание и адаптация к новым условиям, духовное представляет собой совокупность знаний, опыта, мировоззрения, традиций и обычаев, которые служат для раскрытия наиболее подходящие пути перехода к развитию. Она состоит из набора исторических и современных ценностей, таких как наука, философия, искусство, литература, этика, политика, право, образование, просвещение, традиции, ценности, религиозные обряды и практики, отражает внутреннюю духовность, психику. В системе духовной культуры молодежь рассматривается как широкое и значимое понятие. Действия каждого взрослого в семье, на работе, в школе, среди людей и в социально-философской жизни общества измеряются критериями духовной культуры. Как и культура, она является объектом многогранной философской жизни человека, в которой отражается духовно-нравственный мир молодежи, философский подход к семье, искусству, духовному наследию, природе, взаимодействию с людьми, личная активность охватывает поступки. Если что-либо из этой общей цепочки будет задействовано в воспитании молодежи, это нанесет определенный ущерб взрослому, обществу и семье. Важно просвещать молодых людей об их мировоззрении, вкусах, отношении к науке, а также об этике. Духовная культура начинается с первого шага в каждом возрасте, в семье, на примере родителей, братьев и сестер, как говорится, «он делает то, что видит в птичьем гнезде». Постепенно, в результате занятий в детском саду и школе, он подвергается социальному взаимодействию на протяжении всей своей жизни.

Духовная культура - это, по сути, совокупность количественных, качественных и духовных отношений, продукт человеческого сознания и духовной деятельности. В нем социальные процессы, связанные с духовным сознанием и активностью, осуществляются механически, чтобы помочь молодому поколению расти в законно существующем обществе, как духовно, так и недуховно. Духовная культура молодежи воплощает в себе суть духовного мироощущения, сознания, деятельности, которая практически охватывает идеалы общества.

Все, что делает человек, от мельчайшего действия до стремления к высшей цели, прежде всего, когда она идеально сформируется в его мозгу, его действия будут соответствовать ей.

Следовательно, знание о любой мысли, идее, точке зрения, Вселенной и в ней образцовых взглядах человека пронизывает разум человека и соответственно, формируется его характер, его поведение, вся его деятельность [5,105-б.]. Суть духовного культура молодежи может быть раскрыта с помощью обобщенного социофилософского анализа и ее специфических особенностей. Оно также содержит некоторые компоненты отвлечения от общего, множественного числа и индивидуального. Поэтому мы понимаем ее более эффективные и ясные проявления с помощью терминов, концепций и категорий духовной культуры, используемых в социальной философии. «Чтобы использовать то, что создали люди, нужно понять их сущность, их функции, другими словами, понять их духовное содержание. В философии этот процесс называется материализацией, то есть отделением духовного содержания продукта, созданного человеческим трудом, от его материальной оболочки с помощью мышления» [6,143-б.].

Материальные и духовные ценности, созданные людьми, отражаются в духовной культуре общества, в богатствах, которые являются ее результатом. Духовные ценности, созданные предками и усвоенные в процессе духовной деятельности, помогают придать смысл духовной культуре молодежи. Прежде всего, это приводит к повышению его ценности, расширению сферы охвата целевых направлений, созданию активной творческой среды в обществе. В результате формируется философское мировоззрение, занимающее особое место в духовной культуре народа, нации или молодежи, и формируется макроподход к системе философских терминов. С философской точки зрения, не духовная культура общества служит основой духовной культуры человека, в том числе духовного развития молодежи. «На самом деле духовная культура каждого человека так или иначе духовно развита, но когда речь заходит о знаменитостях, проявляются способности отдельного человека, уникальной индивидуальности и целого духовного мира» [7,23-б.]. Хотя этот процесс происходит не всегда, он является эффективным система должна опираться на условия и возможности духовных сил, которые способны выразить ее существование в обществе, а не в отдельном человеке. Духовный идеал играет важную роль в понимании и объяснении различных специфических взглядов и форм, в определении наиболее общей концепции духовной культуры молодежи в обществе. По словам философа М. Каххоровой, «духовный идеал - это набор шаблонов, которые формируют, направляют и двигают сознательное сознание индивида» [8,15-б.]. Именно в этом процессе молодые люди, как движущая сила общества, влияют на развитие философских идей. Исследователи А. Самадов и М. Эргашева показывают, что данное понятие является научной категорией, имеющей комплексный объект философского исследования. Согласно им, «духовный идеал - это не только этика индивида и общества, или универсальная идея, концептуальный, трансформационный процесс, но и целый период, общество того времени, индивидуальное и человеческое сознание, единство в сердце, следствие» [9,91-б.].

Внедрение категории духовных идеалов в философское мышление и сознание молодежи в рамках социальной философии, обогащение их многовековым социальным и духовным опытом, развитие стремления к общечеловеческим ценностям на основе законов общественного развития будет интенсивным и эффективным. На протяжении всей истории молодые люди объединялись в духовной жизни социальных групп, народов, обществ и духовных культур, чтобы выразить суть интегрированных духовных отношений. Таким образом, она отражает природу широко распространенной духовной культуры в концепциях и общечеловеческих ценностях. В то же время молодым людям необходимо углубленно изучать влияние эволюции исторических и религиозных знаний на общественное сознание и перспективы его развития, точку кульминации, посредством философского наблюдения за

реальностью. Их стремление к общечеловеческим ценностям служит формированию важнейшего механизма непрерывного духовного развития во всех сферах общественной жизни, то есть формированию человечности в человеке, превращению знаний в веру. В то же время все аспекты духовной активности молодежи, как фактор создания определенной системы, современным образом перемещаются в социальном пространстве, входят в систему детерминант, объединяющую и регулирующую компоненты духовной культуры, и в то же время раскрывают новые черты. В результате философское мышление молодых людей и причины проявления реальности развиваются в соответствии с законами.

Сущность духовной культуры молодежи связана со следующими основными факторами.

1. Духовная культура является неотъемлемой частью жизни человека и отражает культурные особенности молодежи. При изучении духовной культуры молодежи необходимо обращать внимание на диалектику ее формирования и факторы развития, прежде всего, на деятельность человека по созданию легитимных и эффективных духовных ценностей, вытекающих из понимания культуры.

2. Отличительной особенностью подхода к выявлению факторов духовной культуры молодежи является тот факт, что он исходит из изучения специфических аспектов духовности, исторических и культурных аспектов. Целостное духовное отношение человека к миру характеризуется изучением духовности как философской категории, а также ее влияния на существование общества, его духовную сущность, цель и уровень ценности.

3. Внутренняя структура духовной системы, которая возникает через все компоненты и проявления духовной культуры, отражает судьбу социальных групп, народов и наций. Она синтезирует культурные связи в разных обществах, объединяет некоторые из них и, таким образом, приобщает молодежь к новым ценностям. В результате исторического процесса развивается духовная культура молодежи, и многовековой социальный и духовный опыт объединяется волевым путем.

4. Существует стремление молодых людей осваивать мир, приобретать общечеловеческие ценности на основе целостных духовных взаимоотношений, проникать во внутренние мотивационные источники социальной жизни в стремлении к своим целям. Стремление к этой цели будет возобновлено в ответ на потребность в общечеловеческих ценностях. Рассматривая духовную культуру как универсальную потребность, ценности включают субъективные и объективные аспекты изучения духовности в практическом плане. При анализе этой взаимосвязи субъективные и объективные взаимосвязи увеличивают условия и возможности для реализации потребности в общечеловеческих ценностях. Духовное устремление, условия, необходимые для достижения универсальности, обогащают процесс духовного воспитания в форме ценностей и служат развитию общечеловеческих ценностей.

Государство создало широкие возможности для усиления подхода молодежи к развитию духовной культуры в обществе на основе единства философского и инновационного мышления. Это укрепит интерес каждого молодого поколения к свободным и независимым культурным процессам и поможет развивать основы национальной государственности в соответствии с наследием их предков.

В целом изучение духовной культуры молодежи как объекта философского исследования предоставляет широкие возможности для углубленного изучения теоретически значимых социокультурных процессов. Важность духовной культуры для человека и общества отражается в формах общественного сознания. В то же время молодые люди не ограничиваются достижениями своей практической работы, а стремятся улучшить, приукрасить и превратить их в более современную реальность.

Естественные и культурные потребности, желания и склонности человечества как биосоциального существа не всегда фиксированы в одном месте, но проявляются светским образом, обновляясь достижениями цивилизации и в гармонии с национальными ценностями. Именно в ходе этого процесса молодые люди, благодаря своим философским наблюдениям за реальностью, вносят коллективные изменения в духовные ценности общества. В любом обществе молодые люди прежде всего насыщают свое общественное сознание на основе существующих культурных процессов и постепенно обновляют его в процессе усвоения ценностей в духе современности в соответствии со своими пожеланиями, благодаря чему система научных и философских знаний о реальности будет обновляться. В заключение, роль сегодняшней молодежи в обогащении нового Казахстана высокими духовными и духовно-культурными достижениями и передаче их будущим поколениям имеет особое значение. Основываясь на их светских знаниях, в нашей стране развиваются вопросы национального мышления и философского осмысления. Было изучено, что понятия духовности и культуры, формировавшиеся веками в процессе развития общества, были впитаны в философское мышление молодежи в соответствии со временем. В нем основное внимание уделяется аксиологическим аспектам преданности наследию предков, которые сегодня служат воспитанию казахской молодежи в духе национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей. В результате изучения понятия духовной культуры как категории в системе социальной философии в качестве объекта изучения были рассмотрены взгляды философов, культурологов, спиритуалистов. Научно изучены исследования казахских и зарубежных ученых в области духовной культуры, их взгляды на духовную культуру, которая неразрывно связана с судьбой каждого народа.

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Art History

Primitive Painting Art and Red Color

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Abstrakt:

In this study, the primitive painting of the ancient period and the importance of red paint, which is used extensively, have been refined. The conference material was prepared based on the research of the first part of the study "The use of red color in the art of painting from ancient times to the present" using qualitative research methods. Humans have been affected by the colors in nature in every period, and have used them in every period of their life, loading meanings into colors to express their emotions and thoughts. Troglodytes, prehistoric cave paintings, magic rituals, hunting scenes, emotions and thoughts were depicted using shades of red. Throughout history, red has been an indispensable element in painting, thus coloring the most important works of art.

Key words: Troglodyte, color, red color, primitive artist

Material evidences made and used by ancient civilizations, discovered during archeological excavations, show us the use of colored earth for the purpose of paint from the earliest times. The history of the first use of red soil dates back to 350,000 BC. In the Lower Paleolithic period, colored gold (red) earth, living and dead (bones painted red with paint) were used to decorate human bodies (Delamare and Guineau, 2017: 16).

During the conducted studies, the first use of red paint in the art of painting can be seen in colorful animal paintings on the walls of caves from the Stone Age. Examples of these images are found in the Lascaux cave in southwestern France. Hunting scenes and colorful animal figures are depicted on the cave walls. Along with white lime, black manganese oxide, and yellow clay sand, it is observed that red sand is used in a large part of the images. At the same time, there is a concept of ornament consisting of strong color and rhythmic elements in the early painted painting samples found in the Caves. It is no coincidence that the first embryos of colored ornaments are found in Paleolithic caves (Boztunalı, 2016: 97).

In the cave of Altamira, the power of red color is observed in animal figures. This color is derived from the large crystalline hematite minerals that are abundant in the soil. The Les Trois Freres cave in France is particularly distinctive in terms of color and pattern (Delamare and Guineau, 2017: 17). The man who created the images on the cave walls (an artist in the words of our time) used animal fats, vegetable juices and milk. The reason for using red color more than wheat is that it is effective on human psychology and this color is naturally abundant in the soil. On the other hand, the reason why green and blue colors are not a coincidence in cave paintings is because these colors are not easily found in nature (Per, 2012b: 104).

Ancient people, paying attention to the relation of light and shade in the paintings they drew on the cave walls, used the indentations existing on the rock and tried to give a realistic image to the painting. In each of the paintings, it was observed that the successive moments of the movements of the figures were detected and described. In this regard, it is known that people who create images have strong observation skills.

On the other hand, along with animal figures, there are also caves with human figures. The Cueva del Civil cave in Spain is the best example of this information. However, these paintings belong to times closer to our time. In these paintings, human and animal figures are depicted together in a composition (Çömen, 2010: 22).

Figure 1. Altamira Cave, Spain
Source: Kiyar, 2012: 142.

We all know that during the Paleolithic period, the troglodyte lived in a cave and hunted. At the same time, primitive people do not understand natural phenomena and cannot fight with them. As a result, the primitive artists created the paintings they created on the cave walls for the purpose of witchcraft and spells and thought that they got power from them. Caves were considered sacred because they thought they had a protective effect derived from those paintings. Caves have become cult meeting places as well as temples. Primitive artists working on rock walls carved the contour lines of the image with blunt tools or scratched with other methods, and applied the paint by hand by crushing and mixing the previously obtained dyes with oils, vegetable juices and milk. In addition, they used the spraying method as a technique to fill the inside of the bone fragments with the obtained paint mixtures. (Tansuğ, 1999: 21).

Figure 2. Lascaux Cave, France
Source: G.Beyaz, 2017: 3322.

The color red has been used throughout history, starting with the Altamira and Lascaux cave paintings. And it is possible to see that this color occupies an important place in each of the ancient paintings. Primitive artists, from the earliest times, applied to different materials in nature, such as plants, animals and minerals, to obtain this color.

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GREEN CHEMISTRY IN SOUTH KAZAKHSTAN PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY NAMED AFTER O.ZHANIBEKOV

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Abstract. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, green chemistry is becoming an increasingly priority topic at universities. Educational institutions, including South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University named after O.Zhanibekov, strive to incorporate the principles of green chemistry into their programmes and research to ensure sustainable development and environmental protection. In this article we conducted a questionnaire with undergraduates and students.

Keywords: Green chemistry education, questionnaire, role-playing, GBL

Introduction

Although the principles and practices of green and sustainable chemistry were formulated more than 20 years ago, they have yet to be systematically incorporated into the bachelor's degree programme in chemistry.

Currently, an ecological approach to teaching chemistry based on the ideas of "green chemistry" is one of the most relevant topics in modern science and education around the world. The introduction of "green chemistry" in the educational process has been very successful. A number of articles were written on various aspects of the introduction of "green chemistry" in the curriculum.[1]

There is a recognized need that green chemistry must be included at all levels of education, from the first introduction to science in middle school and high school through university training and beyond to practicing chemists in academia and industry. [2]

Due attention should be paid to environmental education of the younger generation in schools and universities. Environmental action "Birge - taza Qazaqstan" designed to strengthen environmental values in society should be carried out on a systematic basis. In the medium term, growth should become increasingly "green". The groundwork for deep decarbonization must therefore be laid now. I instruct the Government, in cooperation with the scientific society and the private sector, to develop a package of proposals for "green growth", - said Kassym-Zhomart Tokayev.[3]

He also says "In general we all need to strengthen ecological education and inculcate in the younger generation a careful attitude to green plantings. Some plantations, particularly in Turkey, have laws that strictly prohibit the cutting of trees and the destruction of greenery. I think we should use useful foreign experience." [4]

Methods

South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University named after O.Zhanibekov conducted a questionnaire among chemists undergraduates of first and second courses and bachelors of chemistry. The questionnaire was conducted in Google form. Google form had 11 questions. These questions were prepared to learn how much undergraduates and bachelors know about Green Chemistry, and what would they suggest to learn the subject well?

Results and discussion

The purpose of the questionnaire was to study "green chemistry" as part of the training programme. There were 11 questions in the questionnaire. The survey was conducted with 4 students and 23 undergraduates in chemistry of the South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University named after O.Zhanibekov showed that students and undergraduates. The main objective of the survey was the introduction of green chemistry as an elective course for undergraduate students at the Department of Chemistry of the South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University named after O.Zhanibekov.

The following questions were asked for the survey:

Table 1. Questionnaire questions.

1. Your degree	7. How to arouse interest in green chemistry?
2. Are you familiar with the concept of green chemistry?	8. What additional subject could you include in teaching green chemistry?
3. What do you mean by green chemistry?	9. Do you think that green chemistry should be taught at a university?
4. Is there a difference between green chemistry and environmental chemistry?	10. Do you want to expand your knowledge of green chemistry?
5. How many principles of green chemistry are there?	11. What do you think is the best way to teach green chemistry?
6. What do you think you need to improve your knowledge of green chemistry?	

Now let us see the students and undergraduates answer. Among the participants, the majority [85.2%] of undergraduates and we checked their initial knowledge of Green Chemistry.

On question 2, we found out if the participants were familiar with the concepts of green chemistry and from the answers given, it was clear that most of the participants [96,3%] knew each other. [Figure 2]

Are you familiar with the concept of green chemistry ?

27 responses

Figure 2.

In question 3, the answers of most participants to, "what you mean by green chemistry?" were divided by questions such as using chemistry without compromising nature and creating and processing eco-products.

To question 4, "Is there a difference between green chemistry and environmental chemistry?" While 74.1% of the participants said that Green Chemistry and Ecology were

interlinked disciplines, 18.5% said there was no link between green chemistry and ecology, and the remaining 7.4% said they did not know if there was a link between these subjects. [Figure 3]

Is there a difference between green chemistry and environmental chemistry ?

27 responses

Figure 3.

With regard to question 5: 70.4%, the response showed that the participants were aware of the 12 principles of green chemistry, while the other participants [29,6%] were not aware of the 12 principles. [Figure 4]

How many principles of green chemistry are there ?

27 responses

Figure 4

Question 6: "What do you think is needed to deepen your knowledge of green chemistry? to the question: "you need to get more knowledge, learn from real specialists, in our territory there are not enough books and translations in green chemistry, at production and conferences to see, experiment, work in the laboratory," - said the participants.

On question 7, "How do you get an interest in green chemistry?" - participants of the question: "with the help of illustrations, games, technologies, explanation of the essence of the phenomena of everyday life, multiplication of experiment, vision of processes and increasing the responsibility of the student for the protection of the environment.

On question 8, "What would you suggest in teaching green chemistry? »- They replied, Introduction to universities and educational institutions; visited factories, checked what waste is thrown into nature and studied it.

In response to question 9, 81.5% of participants said that the university should study green chemistry, 11.1% said no, and 7.4 % said they did not know. [Figure 5]

Do you think that green chemistry should be taught at a university ?

27 responses

Figure 5.

In response to question 10, they want to [81,5%] expand their knowledge and the question 11 participants answered, 51,9% as a separate subject, 18,5% of participants want to integrate into other chemical disciplines and others want to study as an optional lesson. [Figure 6, 7]

Do you want to expand your knowledge of green chemistry ?

27 responses

Figure 6.

What do you think is the best way to teach green chemistry ?

27 responses

Figure 7.

In addition, it was found that most students were unfamiliar with development goals.

As a result of a survey conducted among undergraduates and graduate students, I tested the students' knowledge of green chemistry and the results showed that it is necessary to provide

students with opportunities for study, to better understand these topics and their implications for the curriculum in green chemistry.

Conclusion

In summary, I tested the initial knowledge of the participants as a result of the survey and their results are shown above.

Green chemistry is an important and topical direction of education in pedagogical universities in Kazakhstan, which helps to form environmental literacy of future teachers and contributes to solving environmental problems in society. And I propose that the undergraduate students of the chemistry department join as an elective subject in green chemistry, while taking the green chemistry class in the labs, to provide full-fledged equipment, I think they should contribute to solving this problem by seeing it with their own eyes. I hope only then that in the future we will be able to train real specialists.

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